

Exploring Photoionised Outflowing Winds in Active Galactic Nuclei

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I, Samuel Grafton-Waters, confirm that the work presented in this thesis is my own. Where information has been derived from other sources, I confirm that this has been indicated in the work.

Abstract

In this Thesis I present a study of the ionised outflowing winds within four active galactic nuclei (AGN): NGC 7469 (Seyfert type 1), NGC 1068 and NGC 5643 (both type 2), and NGC 3227 (type 1 during obscuration). The aim of this work, based on high-resolution X-ray spectroscopy using the XMM-Newton Reflection Grating Spectrometer (RGS), is to understand the ionisation state and kinematics of the outflowing winds and determine their locations with respect to the central supermassive black hole (SMBH).

The emission line region within NGC 7469 is found to be made up of two narrow components and a possible broad component. The distances of these ionised plasma phases from the SMBH depend strongly on the volume filling factor, which is currently unknown. The 0.3 – 10 keV spectrum of NGC 1068 is analysed by simultaneously modelling the XMM-Newton RGS and EPIC-PN data, comparing observations taken in 2000 and 2014. I find that four photoionised components are required to explain the emission features in both epochs. I also find strong evidence for collisionally ionised emission. NGC 5643 is the target of an XMM-Newton AO20 proposal which I submitted and was accepted, with the aim of studying the possible X-ray outflow-induced star formation as seen in the optical band. Analysis of archival observations and preliminary modelling by simulating data with larger exposure times than previously available are presented here. Finally, NGC 3227 was observed to undergo an obscuration event at the end of 2019. I study the EPIC-PN spectrum in order to investigate what drives the observed variability.

My analysis of the outflowing winds in AGN show that the kinematics

and ionisation states are similar in different types of objects, suggesting that similar plasma clouds inhabit type 1 and type 2 AGN, thus giving support to the standard model of AGN.

Impact Statement

Astrophysics has impacted the world around us from imaging and scanning techniques used in medicine, to CCD technology that has been implemented into phones and cameras.

My Thesis results show similarities between different types of emitting and absorbing winds, suggesting that they are part of the same regions in AGN outflowing winds. This contributes to the scientific community in understanding the origins and locations of these winds to investigate their impact on the host galaxies, and thus gives support to the standard model of AGN. Studying the properties of these winds, seen along different lines of sight, can help shed light on the connection between the AGN and host galaxy through feedback mechanisms, answering questions outside of the field that my Thesis is focused on.

My work on AGN was the foundation for an outreach project for high school students, with the aim of influencing young scientists to take up STEM subjects in the future. I taught the key concepts within black hole astrophysics and data analysis techniques, harnessed in my own researching, giving the students the opportunity to create their own scientific analysis of data which has led to a published paper. Through the project, they learned skills such as coding and critical thinking but also, public speaking and confidence, which are valuable regardless of future career. My Thesis work was fundamental to this project and therefore has impacted the young scientists of the future.

I am proud that the impact of my work informs not only the scientific community studying AGN but has impacted and inspired future scientists

who may go on to contribute to this community as well.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Active galactic nuclei (AGN) are some of the most energetic and luminous objects in the Universe, found at the centre of galaxies. These extreme environments are powered through the process of accretion which radiates energy across the electromagnetic spectrum, and consequently launches gas and dust away into the host galaxy in the form of an outflowing wind, which is subsequently ionised by the UV and X-ray radiation. The coupling of the outflowing matter from the central supermassive black hole (SMBH) with the surrounding galaxy is known as feedback, and is thought to be responsible for the coevolution of the SMBH and its host galaxy (e.g. [Di Matteo et al., 2005](#); [Hopkins & Elvis, 2010](#); [Soker & Meiron, 2011](#); [Heckman & Best, 2014](#); [Yuan & Narayan, 2014](#)). The black hole mass (M_{BH}) correlates exceptionally well with the velocity dispersion (σ) of the stars in the galaxy bulge, where $M_{BH} \propto \sigma^{4.8}$ is known as the $M - \sigma$ relation ([Ferrarese & Merritt, 2000](#); [Gebhardt et al., 2000](#)).

The overall motivation in AGN research is to understand how black holes and galaxies coevolve through this feedback mechanism (seen through the $M - \sigma$ relation). However, in order to answer these questions, and gain any insight into the relation between the central AGN and galaxy, small scale studies are required. In this Thesis I investigate the gaseous environment surrounding the SMBH within the AGN centre, to analyse the nature of the outflowing wind, determining its ionisation state, kinematics, geometry, chemical composition,

densities, and location from the SMBH. The overall aim from studying the physical properties of these winds is to establish whether the plasma wind regions seen in different types of AGN are the same, and hence we observe the emission and absorption features based on our line-of-sight viewing angle. From here, the questions as to whether the wind energies are significant enough to lead to star formation or quench it, in addition to supernovae and collimated relativistic jets, can be answered.

Multiwavelength observations of AGN allow us to obtain the full dynamic and temporal picture of these winds, as well as to observe changes in the ionising continuum originating from close to the SMBH. Observations in the X-ray band are paramount in AGN research in order to investigate the regions closest to the SMBH. However, because the nucleus of the AGN cannot be resolved, spectroscopic and reverberation techniques are used to study the outflowing winds and accretion processes. In this Thesis I focus on the spectroscopic techniques, using data from XMM-Newton to obtain high resolution X-ray spectra of these extremely luminous sources, where I investigate the emission and absorption features produced by the outflowing winds. Photoionisation modelling is a fundamental tool to analyse these spectral features, in order to understand the properties and structure of the AGN environment.

The outline of this Thesis is as follows. Chapter 1 introduces AGN, their constituent components and the different types of outflowing wind. In Chapter 2, I discuss the ionisation processes that produce the observed spectral features, as well as explaining how the data are modelled. Chapter 3 gives insight into the X-ray observatories, in particular XMM-Newton. My analysis and findings of four individual AGN are then presented: NGC 7469 (Chapter 4), NGC 1068 (Chapter 5), NGC 5643 (Chapter 6), and NGC 3227 (Chapter 7). Finally, I bring the Thesis together into a concluding chapter (Chapter 8), before looking ahead into the future.

Figure 1.1: A schematic to illustrate the various kinds of active galactic nuclei (AGN). AGN are initially split into two categories: radio-loud (top) and radio-quiet (bottom). The presence of a jet is observed in radio-loud AGN, caused by synchrotron radiation. From this, the line-of-sight viewing angle determines what type of AGN is being observed - type 1 or type 2 - this is known as the unification theory of AGN (Antonucci & Miller, 1985). These AGN regions and their acronyms are all explained in Section 1.2. (Image taken from Beckmann & Shrader, 2012b). Also labelled in this schematic are the different AGN components (bottom right), such as the narrow and broad line regions, that are clouds of ionised plasma. Figure 1.2 displays a closer view of these components.

1.1 Active Galactic Nuclei: What are they?

Figure 1.1 shows a schematic of the different types of AGN we observe. AGN are initially sub-classed as either radio-quiet (RQ) or radio-loud (RL): around 90% of AGN are RQ and do not produce radio jets (Beckmann & Shrader, 2012a). The AGN environment is complex, made up of multiple components. Figure 1.2 shows a zoomed in version of Figure 1.1, outlining the main constituents of an AGN. An overview of the different morphological types of AGN are given in this Section, while the AGN constituents are discussed in Section 1.2.

AGN are further subclassed based on the spectral features we observe. To explain why some optical spectra show both narrow and broad emission lines, whilst others only show narrow lines (see left side of Figure 1.3) comes down to how we view AGN. Type 1 AGN are seen ‘face-on’ (from above or below in Figure 1.2), meaning we observe both the broad and narrow line regions (BLR and NLR, respectively; see Section 1.3.1), and hence why both emission features are present in the spectra (top spectrum in Figure 1.3, blue line). Type 2 AGN are viewed ‘side-on’, meaning our line-of-sight to the central engine is blocked by the dusty torus; we can only see material from the NLR, located above or below the torus. Therefore the spectra of type 2 AGN only have narrow emission lines (bottom spectrum in Figure 1.3, red line). From this, the viewing angle and line-of-sight obstruction (Figure 1.2) determines the spectral properties that we can see (Figure 1.3), characterising AGN further (Netzer, 2013). This is known as the unification theory of AGN (Miller & Antonucci, 1983; Antonucci & Miller, 1985).

1.1.1 Radio quiet Galaxies

1.1.1.1 Seyfert Galaxies

Seyfert galaxies are RQ AGN, first reported by Carl Seyfert in 1943 (Seyfert, 1943), with SMBH masses of $10^6 - 10^{10} M_{\odot}$ and core luminosities $L_{bol} = 10^{34} - 10^{38} \text{ W}$ (Beckmann & Shrader, 2012a), comparable to the host galaxy.

Figure 1.2: A schematic focusing on the central region of the AGN (zoomed in region of Figure 1.1) to illustrate the different components. The central black hole is encircled by the accretion disc; the hot electron corona is situated near the SMBH [Sunyaev & Titarchuk \(1980\)](#), but its geometry is not known (added above the SMBH for illustration purposes; [Reynolds & Nowak, 2003](#)). The broad line region (BLR) lies within the dusty torus and the narrow line region is located further out. The line-of-sight viewing angle categorises the AGN galaxies into type 1 or type 2. Type 1 AGN galaxies are seen “face on”, looking down through the torus from either above or below, such that the optical spectra contain both narrow and broad emission lines (blue spectrum in Figure 1.3, left). Type 2 AGN, however, only contain narrow emission line spectra because the BLR is obscured by the torus when seen “side on” (red spectrum in Figure 1.3, left).

Seyfert AGN make up 5 - 16 % of the number of all galaxies, with four times as many type 2 compared to type 1 ([Maiolino & Rieke, 1995](#)). Individual Seyfert galaxies are studied in this Thesis because they are bright, nearby and contain different types of outflowing winds (Section 1.3), making them excellent laboratories for X-ray spectroscopy analysis and investigating the feedback processes. In addition, these AGN test different regions of the AGN outflow parameter space, as I study both type 1 and type 2 nuclei.

Figure 1.3: *Left:* Comparing the optical spectra of type 1 and 2 AGN. The top spectrum (blue) contains both narrow and broad emission lines, implying a type 1 AGN. The bottom spectrum (red) contains only narrow emission lines, and is therefore from a type 2 AGN. (Figure from [Hickox & Alexander, 2018](#)). *Right:* Spectral comparison between a Seyfert AGN, NGC 1358 (top), and a LINER galaxy, NGC 1052 (bottom). (Figure adapted from [Ho, 2008](#)).

1.1.1.2 NLS1 Galaxies

A particular sub-class of Seyfert galaxies are represented by narrow line Seyfert type 1 (NLS1) AGN. The spectra of NLS1 Seyferts contain narrow $H\beta$ and broad $H\alpha$ emission lines, but the UV lines are narrower in NLS1 galaxies compared to Seyferts ([Beckmann & Shrader, 2012a](#)). They have a steeper X-ray continuum slope with respect to Seyfert 1 galaxies and show rapid variability in the soft X-ray band ([Boller et al., 1996](#)), but the variability is very weak in the UV ([Beckmann & Shrader, 2012a](#)). On average, the black holes within these galaxies are less massive than the central engines in Seyferts, $M_{NLS1} \sim 10^5 - 10^7 M_\odot$, but the bolometric luminosities are comparable ([Beckmann & Shrader, 2012a](#)), implying these galaxies have very high accretion rates.

1.1.1.3 LINERS

Some SMBH, like Sgr A* at the centre of our Milky Way Galaxy, are not very active and are therefore not luminous ($L_{bol, Sgr A^*} = 10^{30}$ W; [Beckmann &](#)

Shrader, 2012a). This is either due to low mass accretion rates or inefficacy at converting the accreted matter into radiation. However, some AGN have been seen with bolometric luminosities $10^{33} \leq L_{bol} \leq 10^{34}$, which suggests that there are AGN types in between quiescent and active states. One such type are called low ionising nuclear emission regions (LINERs). LINERs have low luminosities compared to Seyferts, but emit strong, narrow emission lines from the surrounding ionised gas and produce strong forbidden lines; they possess similar properties to Seyfert 2 AGN (Beckmann & Shrader, 2012a). The right side of Figure 1.3 compares the spectrum of a LINER (NGC 1052, bottom) to a Seyfert galaxy (NGC 1538, top).

1.1.2 Radio-Loud AGN

RL AGN produce bright radio emission, usually due to the synchrotron radiation in non-thermal jets (Beckmann & Shrader, 2012a); see top half of Figure 1.1. What determines whether or not a galaxy is classified as RL depends on the ratio between the radio and optical fluxes, given by

$$R = \frac{F_{radio}}{F_{optical}}, \quad (1.1)$$

where the flux in the radio band is measured at 5 GHz and the optical band flux is at 2500 Å (Beckmann & Shrader, 2012a). Typically, a ratio larger than 10 implies the galaxy is RL.

RL AGN can be split into further categories depending on the intensity of the radio source - named after Fanaroff and Riley (FR; Fanaroff & Riley, 1974): low luminosity (FR-I) and high luminosity (FR-II). FR-I sources have diffuse lobes with radio emission originating from close to the nucleus, while FR-II are dominated by bright and extended radio lobes that appear to be more luminous far out from the SMBH (top left and top in Figure 1.1, respectively; Beckmann & Shrader, 2012a).

1.1.2.1 Quasars

Through radio surveys, the first quasi-stellar radio sources or Quasars were discovered, which optically appear blue and contain strong emission lines (Beckmann & Shrader, 2012a). Quasars are the most luminous and distant AGN. The furthest one to date is at a redshift of $z = 7.64$, with a SMBH mass of $M_{BH} = 1.6 \times 10^9 M_{\odot}$ and bolometric luminosity of $L_{bol} = 1.38 \times 10^{40}$ W (Wang et al., 2021).

Like all other AGN, RL Quasars are also categorised based on viewing orientation (Figure 1.1). One type of Quasar is called a Blazar, where the relativistic jets are pointed directly towards the observer, and outshine the emission from the host galaxy. Blazars are further classified into BL Lacertae (BL Lac) objects if FR-I, and flat spectrum radio quasars (FSRQs) if FR-II (Netzer, 2013). BL Lac objects do not show X-ray absorption, broad and narrow Balmer emission lines, or the FeK α line in their spectra¹, but they do emit γ -rays. FSRQs emit γ -rays, while narrow and broad Balmer lines, and the FeK α line, are present in their spectra (Beckmann & Shrader, 2012a).

1.1.3 Starburst Galaxies

Starburst galaxies are galaxies that contain regions of star formation, where supernovae and stellar driven winds are the energy sources (Netzer, 2013). Compared to plasmas in Seyfert galaxies, where the temperatures are much lower as the ions are excited by photoionisation and recombination, starburst galaxies are heated by collisionally excited gas, to temperatures of around 10^7 K. Charge exchange has also been seen in star forming galaxies as the hot starburst gas meets the cold interstellar medium (ISM) (Liu & Mao, 2015).

1.2 What makes up an AGN?

1.2.1 The Black Hole

The SMBHs within AGN have two main properties: mass and luminosity - albeit the latter is not measured directly (see Section 1.2.2). AGN have

¹See Chapter 2 for details about absorption and emission.

SMBH masses between $M_{BH} = 10^5 - 10^{10} M_{\odot}$, and luminosities ranging from $L_{bol} = 10^{34} - 10^{41}$ W (Beckmann & Shrader, 2012a), where $L_{bol} = 10^{38}$ W is the threshold between Seyferts and Quasars (Netzer, 2013).

The angular momentum of a black hole is used to determine the maximum energy output during accretion (Netzer, 2013), as well as the radius of its event horizon. The radius of a SMBH can be determined from

$$R_{BH} = \left(1 + \sqrt{1 - \alpha^2}\right) \frac{GM_{BH}}{c^2}, \quad (1.2)$$

where α is the specific angular momentum of the black hole, G is the gravitational constant, and c is the speed of light (Netzer, 2013). For a non-rotating black hole $\alpha = 0$ and $R_{BH} = \frac{2GM_{BH}}{c^2}$, known as the Schwartzchild radius (R_S). For example, a non-rotating SMBH with mass $M_{BH} = 10^8 M_{\odot}$ would have a radius $R_{BH} = 2.96 \times 10^{11}$ m ~ 2 AU. For a Kerr black hole (maximum rotating black hole), $\alpha \simeq 1$, so the black hole radius becomes $R_{BH} = \frac{GM_{BH}}{c^2}$.

1.2.2 The Accretion Disk

The central SMBH is encircled by an optically thick, geometrically thin accretion disk (Shakura & Sunyaev, 1973), made up of dust and gas from the host galaxy's ISM. Within the disk, the gas and dust particles collide with each other converting kinetic energy into thermal energy, via frictional forces through viscosity, heating up the disk. This results in the material losing angular momentum causing it to fall inwards, and thus the speed of the material in the orbit increases. However, to conserve the total angular momentum of the disk, this loss in angular momentum from the collisions between particles is transported to the outer edge of the disk. Although this process is currently not fully understood, magnetic fields within accretion disks are believed to be essential at producing turbulence and transporting angular momentum (Proga, 2007). As the disk material gets close to the SMBH, the gas compresses to a dense plasma and the disk temperature gets higher. This thermal energy, leading to temperatures of 10^6 K (Carroll & Ostlie, 2006), is then released as

radiation, in the form of optical/UV photons. Close to the black hole, the speed of the gas is supersonic (approaching the speed of light), achieved when the gravitational potential energy exceeds the kinetic energy, allowing for the material to accrete onto the SMBH (Frank et al., 2002).

The size of the accretion disk can vary from the innermost stable circular orbit (ISCO) to a few 1000 R_g (where $R_g = R_S/2$ is the gravitational radius; Netzer, 2013). ISCO is the theoretical inner edge of the disk where the particles in the accretion disk lose their stability in the orbit and fall onto the black hole. The location of ISCO is dependent on the angular momentum of the SMBH relative to the angular momentum of the accretion disk. For example, ISCO corresponds to 1 R_g for a spinning black hole and 6 R_g for a Schwarzschild black hole. For a retrograde black hole, $R_{ISCO} = 9R_g$.

1.2.2.1 The Eddington Luminosity

Accretion onto the SMBH releases the gravitational binding energy through vast amounts of radiation (Netzer, 2013). It is this process that determines many properties of an AGN, such as the luminosity and the mass accretion rate, which are both related to the Eddington luminosity (L_{Edd}). L_{Edd} is the maximum luminosity that can be generated through accretion by a SMBH with mass M_{BH} (Netzer, 2013).

L_{Edd} is derived by taking a cloud of fully ionised gas in the accretion disk, of mass $M = Nm_p$, at a distance of r from the SMBH of mass M_{BH} . The cloud will feel both a gravitational force $F_g = \frac{GM_{BH}Nm_p}{r^2}$ and a radiation pressure force $F_{rad} = \frac{L\sigma_T N}{4\pi r^2 c}$. Here, m_p is the proton mass, N is the number of protons in the cloud, L is the luminosity, c is the speed of light and σ_T is the Thompson cross-section. When the force of radiation equals the force of gravity, the Eddington limit is given by

$$L_{Edd} = \frac{4\pi GM_{BH}m_p c}{\sigma_T}. \quad (1.3)$$

If the radiation pressure gradient force dominates the gravitational force,

the luminosity of the AGN becomes larger than L_{Edd} , driving an outflow; matter is still able to accrete onto the black hole under the influence of gravity, but the rate has decreased (e.g. King, 2003). In most cases, it is assumed that the accretion process has an efficiency of $\eta \sim 0.1$, which means that 10% of the rest-mass energy from material accreted is radiated away and hence why AGN are so bright. The remaining 90 % of matter from the disk is accreted onto the black hole.

1.2.3 The Electron Corona

The accretion disk is not hot enough ($T = 10^6$ K) to emit X-ray photons. So, where do the X-rays originate from? The best model to explain the X-ray origin involves a hot electron corona² (e.g. Sunyaev & Titarchuk, 1980), where the temperatures can reach $T = 10^8$ K (Netzer, 2013). However, the location, geometry and heating mechanism of the corona are currently unknown, although it is thought to be heated by magnetic fields (Reynolds & Nowak, 2003). In the optically thin, hot corona, X-rays are produced through inverse-Compton processes whereby optical/UV photons from the accretion disk are up-scattered, gaining energy from collisions with the electrons. These processes create the X-ray power-law - see Section 2.3.1.1 in Chapter 2 for details.

1.2.4 The Dusty Torus

X-ray spectra of some type 2 Seyferts show strong absorption below 10 keV. This is due to optically thick material ($N_H > 10^{28}$ m⁻²), making up the dusty torus, obstructing the intrinsic continuum from reaching the detector. We call this type of AGN ‘Compton-thick’. The torus is a large structure, made of cold dust and gas, that surrounds the central nucleus at 0.1 - 10 pc (Netzer, 2013).

The original dusty torus model was used to explain the viewing angle dependence of type 1 and type 2 AGN (see Figure 1.2; Antonucci & Miller, 1985). However, the geometry and structure were arbitrary. Recently an alternative torus model has come about, that describes the mass distribution,

²In reality, the corona is a quasi-neutral plasma with electrons and protons. However, the photon interactions occur with the electrons only.

kinematics, and structure as shown in the top panel of Figure 1.4 (Hönig, 2019; Ricci et al., 2017; Ramos Almeida & Ricci, 2017). Recent observations of nearby AGN have suggested that the torus is multiphased and multidynamic, rather than a continuous structure (Hönig, 2019). The complexity of the clumpy structures suggests a variety and range of column densities which, in some cases, have been found to change on short timescales (producing the so called changing-look AGN), such as in NGC 7674 (Bianchi et al., 2005), NGC 6300 (Matt et al., 2003), NGC 4151 (Beuchert et al., 2017), and NGC 1068 (Marinucci et al., 2016).

In order to identify the obscuring structure and components, IR and submm observations are used to analyse the dust and molecular gas that surrounds the AGN. The updated torus model is, at first, simply made up of a polar region (cone structure; red arrow in Figure 1.4) and a geometrically thick H₂ disk (blue arrow in Figure 1.4), emitting in the mid-infrared (MIR) and near-infrared (NIR) bands, respectively (Hönig, 2019). In addition, there is a geometrically thin disk seen in the sub-mm (green arrow in Figure 1.4). Although this is enough to explain the observed obscuration and attenuated type 2 spectra, these components are a little more complicated than this, influenced by disk turbulence and radiation pressure (Hönig, 2019). A cold outer component ($T \sim 10$ K) is located between 5 - 10 pc from the SMBH and is thought to be a reservoir that links the host galaxy to the accretion structure. A hot inner structure is located near the sublimation radius ($T_{dust} \sim 1500 - 2000$ K) which is shown by the pink arrow in Figure 1.4. Because the hot dust in the disk is optically thick and re-emits the X-ray and UV radiation from the AGN in the infrared (IR) band, radiation pressure in the NIR causes the material in the inner disk to puff up. As a result, AGN radiation drives hot material away and creates a hollow cone structure with the dust confined to the edges (orange arrow); the ionised outflowing plasma is able to flow within. This self-consistent model also implies a possible origin of the outflowing wind due to the radiation pressure of the AGN. This dusty, hollow cone, seen in the

MIR, is optically thick enough, $N_H \sim 10^{26} - 10^{27} \text{ m}^{-2}$, to contribute to AGN obscuration, depending on the line-of-sight viewing angle (see e.g. Ricci et al., 2017; Ramos Almeida & Ricci, 2017).

Not only is the obscuration due to the line-of-sight viewing angle, but it also depends on the covering fraction of the dusty disk (in addition to the hollow cone). This is shown in the bottom panel of Figure 1.4, which zooms in on the central torus disk region (yellow structure in the top panel). The covering fraction, which is linked to the column density of the material, determines the probability that a photon will escape, and whether the AGN is obscured (Ramos Almeida & Ricci, 2017). From clumpy torus models, the covering fraction of type 1 AGN (bottom left of Figure 1.4) is less than the value of type 2 (bottom right of Figure 1.4), meaning the observed differences between type 1 and type 2 AGN are not only dependent on the line-of-sight orientation ('side-on' or 'face-on'), but also on the covering fraction (Ramos Almeida & Ricci, 2017).

1.3 Gaseous Environment of the SMBH

As is evident from Section 1.2, AGN are very complex, built up of lots of components. In this Section, I describe the four main types of outflowing wind in AGN; three of which are studied in great detail in this Thesis. I also explain the ionisation cone model.

1.3.1 The Broad and Narrow Line Regions

The emission line region (ELR) in AGN can be divided into broad and narrow line regions (BLR and NLR, as seen in Figure 1.2), which were first characterised from the optical spectra of AGN (see Figure 1.3). The BLR, is a region populated by highly dense, optically thick, and fast moving clouds that produce broad spectral emission lines with broadening velocities corresponding to 1000 to 10,000 km s^{-1} (e.g. Peterson, 1997; Krolik, 1999; Netzer, 2015). The broadness of the lines is caused by the gravitational influence of the black hole (Netzer, 2015). Situated at around 0.01 - 1 pc (Netzer, 2015) within

Figure 1.4: *Top:* Updated torus model showing a multidynamic, multiphased and self consistent structure. This model is made up of a geometrically thick H₂ disk (blue arrow) and a geometrically thin CO/HCN disk structure (green arrow), with an ionisation cone (red and orange arrows). Close to the SMBH (black arrow), the radiation can cause the inner radius of the disk (pink arrow) to puff up; this could be the origin of the outflowing wind. (Figure adapted from [Hönig, 2019](#)). *Bottom:* Zooming in on the dusty disk (depicted by the blue and green arrows in the top panel) we can see that its size - i.e. its covering fraction - determines the probability of a photon escaping. The larger the column density, or the clumpier the material, the lower the escape probability and the AGN is obscured. Obscuration is also dependent on our line-of-sight viewing angle. R_o and R_d are the outer and dust sublimation radii for the torus, respectively, i is the inclination angle, τ_v is the optical depth, N_o is the number of clumps, and σ angular width. (Figure taken from [Ramos Almeida & Ricci, 2017](#)).

the dusty torus (see Figure 1.2), the densities of the clouds within the BLR can exceed 10^{15} m^{-3} , with temperatures of $T \sim 10^4 \text{ K}$ (Beckmann & Shrader, 2012a). Studies of the BLR's geometry has led to describe it as a set of clouds through to a distribution of continuous gas (see Costantini et al., 2016, and references within), with possible origins including a failed wind from the disk (e.g. Czerny & Hryniewicz, 2011; Czerny et al., 2017).

The boundary between the BLR and torus is known as the sublimation radius (R_{sub}) which is the distance from the SMBH where the temperatures are high enough for the dust to sublimate ($T > 1200 - 1900 \text{ K}$; see e.g. Czerny & Hryniewicz, 2011; Czerny et al., 2017). Here, the dust cannot survive and the material becomes a plasma. The sublimation radius is proportional to the square root of the AGN luminosity ($R_{sub} \propto L^{1/2}$; e.g. Ashton et al., 2006).

The NLR, on the other hand is situated outside the torus, (Figure 1.2), located between to 0.1 and 3 kpc, and can even extend towards larger distances (Netzer, 2013, 2015). The emitting clouds have broadening velocities of a few 100 - 1000 km s^{-1} (e.g. Beckmann & Shrader, 2012a), seen in the optical spectra, with densities of $10^9 - 10^{12} \text{ m}^{-3}$ (e.g. Netzer, 1990; Xu et al., 2007). The narrow emission lines are produced in colder and less ionised gas than the BLR clouds, and as they are found further from the black hole, they have smaller velocities too. The NLR is a multiphased plasma with different ionisations such that both soft X-ray and optical [O III] emissions can come from the same ELR (Bianchi et al., 2006). The line ratios and widths of the forbidden lines are similar in both type 1 and type 2 AGN, suggesting that the physics of the narrow line regions is the same (Netzer, 2013).

The ELR of individual the AGN NGC 7469, NGC 1068, and NGC 5643 are studied in Chapters 4, 5, and 6, respectively.

1.3.2 The Warm Absorber

The next type of outflowing wind is known as the warm absorber (WA). The WA is made up of multiple regions, or components, that have a wide range of velocities, column densities and ionisations - they are multi-phased and have

multiple temperatures (Krolik & Kriss, 2001). First discovered by Halpern (1984), they were used to explain the variable absorption within the AGN spectra, modelled originally with strong O VII and O VIII absorption edges (e.g. George et al., 1998b). WAs can be found in about half of Seyfert 1 galaxies (e.g. Reynolds & Fabian, 1995).

Since the launch of XMM-Newton and Chandra (Chapter 3), high resolution spectra of AGN have shown WAs to be characterised by a multitude of strong, narrow absorption lines in the soft X-ray band, as displayed in Figure 1.5 (Kaastra et al., 2000, 2002). Diagnostics of the AGN spectra show that these WAs have a variety of ionisation states ($\log \xi = -1$ to 3; e.g. Blustin et al., 2005) and are blueshifted with velocities of a few 100 - 1000 km s⁻¹. Furthermore, the column densities within these clouds of ionised gas range from $10^{24} - 10^{28}$ m⁻², with temperatures of $10^4 - 10^6$ K (see e.g. Krolik & Kriss, 2001; Blustin et al., 2005; Mehdipour et al., 2015a). The location of the WA is still not fully understood, but the range is likely to be between the BLR and >10pc, consistent with the NLR; this is a question investigated in this Thesis. In addition, the geometry of the WA is currently unknown - whether the wind is a spherical shell, a continuous stream (Steenbrugge et al., 2003, 2005), or clouds with their lengths comparable to their thickness (Zhang et al., 2015).

The WA in NGC 7469 is studied in Chapter 4.

1.3.3 Ionisation Cone Model

Some type 1 AGN spectra have been found to contain both absorption and emission features (e.g. NGC 7469 - Chapter 4), while type 2 AGN spectra (e.g. NGC 1068 - Chapter 5) only show narrow emission lines in the soft X-ray band. The ionisation cone model proposed by Kinkhabwala et al. (2002) suggests that the outflowing wind, which absorbs so much of the nuclear X-ray flux seen in Seyfert 1 AGN, re-emits the X-rays perpendicular to the direction of outflow, producing the emission features seen in the spectra of Seyfert 2 AGN, as shown in Figure 1.6. In other words, the emission seen in Seyfert 2 AGN is the re-emission of the plasma radiation from the warm absorber (WA)

Figure 1.5: First high resolution X-ray spectrum of the Seyfert AGN NGC 5548, taken with Chandra-LETGS, showing a multitude of strong and narrow absorption lines. Through spectral and photoionisation modelling, the absorption lines were found to be blueshifted by a few hundred km s^{-1} , similar to the UV absorption lines (Image taken from [Kaastra et al., 2000](#)).

wind in Seyfert 1 AGN (e.g. [Kaastra et al., 2002, 2012](#); [Behar et al., 2017](#); [Mehdipour et al., 2018](#)), from evidence that the ionic column densities of the emission lines in NGC 1068 were consistent with the values of the WAs in Seyfert 1 AGN ([Kinkhabwala et al., 2002](#)).

The model suggests that the WA and NLR could be part of the same regions in the outflowing wind. However, it does not, to some degree, give insight into the geometry and locations of the plasma regions, but rather just explains the observed differences in type 1 and type 2 AGN, in terms of the emission and absorption features. In this Thesis, I aim to answer this by studying both emitting and absorbing plasma regions (NLR and WA, respectively), comparing the parameters obtained from the spectral modelling. From there, the distances with respect to the SMBH can be inferred to gain insight into

Figure 1.6: Ionisation cone model of the outflowing wind in AGN. Seen in Seyfert 1 AGN the nuclear X-ray flux is absorbed, whereas in Seyfert 2 AGN, we see the re-emission of the X-ray flux in a direction perpendicular to that of outflow, producing the emission features seen in the spectra. This suggests that the WA and ELR are the same structure within the outflowing wind, seen at different lines of sight. (Image taken from [Kinkhabwala et al., 2002](#)).

whether they are located co-spatially in the ionisation cone, or not.

1.3.4 UFOs

There has been evidence to suggest that some Seyfert AGN (34%; [Tombesi et al., 2013](#)) contain ultra-fast outflows (UFOs; e.g. [Cappi et al., 2006](#); [Tombesi et al., 2010](#)) which are different to the WA winds. UFOs are identified by their highly blueshifted absorption lines in the 6 - 10 keV band, corresponding to speeds of up to $0.4c$, produced by Fe XXV and Fe XXVI K shell absorption (as shown in the top panel of [Figure 1.7](#); [Risaliti et al., 2005](#)). The bottom two panels of [Figure 1.7](#) illustrate that the UFO and WA parameter values are on opposite ends of the parameter space, suggesting that these winds are different

Figure 1.7: *Top:* Four highly blueshifted absorption lines between 6.7 - 8.3 keV in NGC 1365. (Figure taken from [Risaliti et al., 2005](#)). The lines are produced by FeXXV and Fe XXVI $K\alpha$ and $K\beta$ absorption, which could be important characteristics of UFO winds. The plot shows the residuals as a change in χ^2 against energy over four different observations. The vertical lines show the rest frame energies of these four absorbing ions, and the depth of the troughs show the significance of each line. *Bottom:* Comparing the kinematics with the ionisation parameter (*left*) and column density (*right*) of WAs (red circles) and UFOs (blue circles); the green triangles are non-UFOs that have velocities lower than 10,000 km s $^{-1}$. (Figures adapted from [Tombesi et al., 2013](#)).

regions of a large scale outflow, found at various distances from the nuclear SMBH; 67% of Seyferts that contain UFOs also contain a WA wind (Tombesi et al., 2013). The UFO winds are thought to originate at the accretion disk (Risaliti et al., 2005; Cappi et al., 2006; Tombesi et al., 2010, 2012), while the WA winds stem from the torus (Blustin et al., 2005).

UFOs have also been found in the high redshift ($z = 1.695$) quasar, Q2237+030 (known as the Einstein cross), with an outflow velocity of $v_{out} \sim 0.1c$ (Bertola et al., 2020). In addition, there is some evidence that there is a secondary wind component with $v_{out} \sim 0.5c$, but these spectral features were not completely modelled. In the local neighbourhood, UFOs are well understood, but not at higher redshifts, such as $z = 1 - 3$. Therefore this study by Bertola et al. (2020) gives good insight into quasar outflows, but further investigations of UFOs at a higher redshift are required.

1.3.5 Obscuring Winds

Recently, it has been found that some AGN have undergone strong absorption events, whereby the X-ray fluxes were observed to be weaker compared to previous observations. For example, the soft X-ray flux in NGC 5548 was 25 times weaker in 2013 (Kaastra et al., 2014) compared to 2002 (Kaastra et al., 2002) (left side of Figure 1.8). During the multiwavelength campaign of NGC 5548 in 2013/14, a clumpy stream of weakly ionised gas was identified - called an obscuring wind. This stream caused heavy absorption in the line-of-sight, obscuring the nucleus (Kaastra et al., 2014). The geometry of NGC 5548, with the obscurer, is shown in the left side of Figure 1.9, along with the constant AGN components. Comparing the spectra in the left side of Figure 1.8 illustrates the loss in flux and absence in absorption features caused by the obscuring wind. However, the obscuration event allowed for detailed studies of the NLR features (Figure 1.10; Whewell et al., 2015), implying the obscurer did not cover the line-of-sight of the X-ray source to the NLR (Kaastra et al., 2014).

In 2016, NGC 3783 was found to have an obscuring cloud which heavily

absorbed the soft X-ray and UV lines (see right side of Figure 1.8; Mehdipour et al., 2017). The obscurer was found to be highly variable and at a distance of 10 light-days, between the BLR and WA (Mehdipour et al., 2017). The strength of the continuum absorption meant there were no absorption features detected in the soft X-rays (Mehdipour et al., 2017), however, the emission features were very strong, with the narrow components staying consistent between the 2000/01 (unobscured) and 2016 (obscured) observations (Mao et al., 2019). Furthermore, Mao et al. (2019) found that a broad emission component significantly improved the fit in the 2000/01 observations (e.g. Kaspi et al., 2000; Blustin et al., 2002), but was much weaker in the 2016 observations, further confirming the geometry proposed by Mehdipour et al. (2017), shown in the right side of Figure 1.9.

Both obscurers in NGC 5548 and NGC 3783 contained two components, although the former was thought to be a stream of cold gas, and the latter a hotter, short lasting cloud closer to the black hole. The event lasted for 32 days in NGC 3783, but is still ongoing for NGC 5548 at the time of writing this Thesis. The inhomogeneous and clumpy obscurer in NGC 3783 was more ionised but slower ($\log \xi = 1.8$, $v_{out} = -1900 \text{ km s}^{-1}$; Mehdipour et al., 2017) compared to NGC 5548 (almost neutral, $v_{out} = -5000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$; Kaastra et al., 2014), but covered less of the central source. The column densities of the two obscuring wind components in both AGN were $N_H = 10^{26} - 10^{27} \text{ m}^{-2}$. It is possible that many AGN have undergone obscuration at some point in their lifetime and these events are more common than first thought (Kaastra et al., 2018). For example, multiple obscuration events were seen in NGC 3783 between 1993 and 2016 (Kaastra et al., 2018), in addition to the December 2016 event lasting 32 days (Mehdipour et al., 2017). Another obscuration event was seen in NGC 3227 at the end of 2019 - the X-ray variability is investigated in Chapter 7.

Figure 1.8: Comparing AGN spectra during obscured and unobscured states. *Left:* The 2013 RGS spectrum (red line) of NGC 5548 is 25 times lower in flux compared to the 2002 Chandra spectrum (black line) - a result of an obscuring wind. The flux increases at higher energies suggesting the obscurer only absorbs the soft X-rays. (Figure taken from [Kaastra et al., 2014](#)). *Right:* The 2016 XMM-Newton spectra (red and blue lines) of NGC 3783 have lower fluxes compared to the archive 2000 data (black line), with absorption only affecting the soft X-ray band. (Figure taken from [Mehdipour et al., 2017](#)).

1.4 Physical Properties of the Outflowing Wind

In Section 1.3, I described the four main outflowing wind components. Here I explain how their distances with respect to the SMBH are derived, as well as the energetics to determine whether these outflows can influence their host galaxies.

1.4.1 Calculating Distances of the Outflowing Wind

To fully understand the photoionised outflowing wind, an accurate estimation of the geometry and location is required ([Kaastra et al., 2011](#)). There are a few techniques that allow us to determine the distances of the outflowing wind.

1.4.1.1 Recombination Timescale Method

Variability techniques use time-dependent photoionisation modelling to measure how long it takes for the plasma to respond to changes in the ionisation

Figure 1.9: Schematics illustrating the obscuring wind geometry in the vicinity of the black hole in NGC 5548 (left; based on the image from Kaastra et al., 2014) and NGC 3783 (right; taken from Mao et al., 2019). For the right panel: NEL and BEL are short for narrow and broad emission line; WAX is short for warm absorber in X-rays; ABS and EM stand for absorption and emission. The fast moving obscurers in both AGN block out the ionising X-ray source from reaching the WA clouds, meaning no absorption features were present in the spectra. The fact that the obscured spectrum of NGC 5548 (Figure 1.10) and NGC 3783 had strong emission features implies that both the NLRs received the full X-ray radiation from the nuclear source.

continuum using the ionisation parameter (ξ). This is defined as

$$\xi = \frac{L_{ion}}{n_H r^2}, \quad (1.4)$$

where L_{ion} is the ionisation luminosity measured between 13.6 eV and 13.6 keV (1 - 1000 Ryd), r is the distance of the plasma to the central source, and n_H is the hydrogen number density. The higher the plasma density, the faster the plasma can respond to changes in the ionising continuum to reach a new ionisation equilibrium (e.g. Kaastra et al., 2012). The ionisation parameter (through photoionisation modelling) and the luminosity (via spectral energy distribution modelling), can both be measured (see Chapter 2 for details). However, n_H and r are degenerate with respect to each other, preventing a direct derivation of the distance.

Figure 1.10: Obscured RGS spectrum of NGC 5548, taken from [Whewell et al. \(2015\)](#). Due to the obscuration event, the intrinsic X-ray continuum became very low and no absorption features were present in the soft X-ray spectrum. However, strong, narrow emission lines appeared such that the NLR could be studied in greater detail than before.

Therefore, to obtain the distances, changes in the ionising continuum, which causes variations in the ionisation parameter of the plasma, need to be studied. If these changes occur over large enough time frames, constraints on the densities, and therefore distances, can be made. Limits on the distance can be found using the recombination timescale, which is a function of the plasma density n_H (e.g. [Mehdipour et al., 2018](#)), given by

$$t_{rec}n_H = n_H^*\tau, \quad (1.5)$$

where t_{rec} is recombination timescale (the time it takes for an ion in the $i + 1$ state to recombine to the i state), n_H is the hydrogen number density in the plasma (this can be measured in PION; see Section 2.3.2), τ is the time

between the observed changes, and n_H^* is the hydrogen number density of the plasma needed for the changes to happen in time τ . Therefore, by using Eq. 1.4, the upper limit of the distance can be found (n_H^* here is the lower density limit if t_{rec} is a known upper limit; e.g. [Ebrero et al., 2016](#)).

1.4.1.2 Non-variable Methods

When there is no variability in the source, alternative ways to estimate the distances of the WA are required. For example, to calculate the lower distance limit of the outflowing wind, it is assumed that the outflow gas has a velocity (v_{out}) greater than or equal to the escape velocity

$$R_{min} \geq \frac{2GM_{BH}}{v_{out}^2}, \quad (1.6)$$

where M_{BH} is the black hole mass ([Blustin et al., 2005](#)). For the upper distance limit, it is assumed that the outflowing wind is a thin shell, with a thickness (Δr) much smaller than its distance to the black hole (R). Substituting the absorbing column density, given as $N_H \sim n_H f_v \Delta r$, where f_v is the volume filling factor, into Eq. 1.4 (such that $N_H = \frac{L_{ion} f_v \Delta r}{\xi R^2}$), and applying the condition $R \geq \Delta r$, the upper limit distance is given by ([Blustin et al., 2005](#))

$$R_{max} \leq \frac{L_{ion} f_v}{\xi N_H}. \quad (1.7)$$

The volume filling factor f_v is the fraction of volume taken up by each wind component ($f_v \leq 1$); when $f_v = 1$, the wind component fully fills the volume in our line-of-sight. If we assume that the outflow wind is continuous, and not a shell, the inequality for R_{max} becomes an equality (e.g. [Ashton et al., 2006](#)). These estimates were used for the WA winds in type 1 AGN ([Blustin et al., 2005, 2007](#)), and are used in this Thesis.

1.4.1.3 Location of the Emission Line Regions

Alternatively, the distances of the NLR can be estimated through

$$N_H = \int_{r_{min}}^{r_{max}} f_v n_H dr = \int_{r_{min}}^{r_{max}} \frac{L_{ion} f_v}{\xi r^2} dr, \quad (1.8)$$

where n_H is substituted using Eq. 1.4. For a single ionisation component, the integral on the right hand side of Eq. 1.8 yields

$$N_H = \frac{L_{ion} f_v}{\xi} \left(\frac{1}{r_{min}} - \frac{1}{r_{max}} \right). \quad (1.9)$$

Assuming that the outflowing wind is a large, almost continuous cloud, then $r_{max} \gg r_{min}$, which means the lower distance limit becomes

$$r_{min} = \frac{L_{ion} f_v}{\xi N_H}. \quad (1.10)$$

This derivation was used to measure the distance of the emission line region in NGC 5548 (Whewell et al., 2015).

In order to directly substitute the ionisation parameter equation (Eq. 1.4) into the left side of Eq. 1.8, in terms of n_H , I assume a continuous wind travelling at constant velocity. Therefore, the density falls off as r^{-2} . As a result of this, I assume the hydrogen number density is small at distances larger than r_{min} , allowing the direct substitution from the left side of Eq. 1.8 to the right. Furthermore, if $n_H = \frac{k}{r^2}$, where k is the constant of proportionality, is substituted into the ionisation parameter equation, the distances cancel, meaning the ionisation parameter ξ has no dependence on the distance r , so is constant throughout the plasma.

This method (Eq. 1.10) is similar to the WA distance method (Eq. 1.7), but the limits are different. Both derivations use the definitions of ξ and N_H , but the assumption on the size of the wind is important. In other words, the distance from the SMBH depends on whether the cloud is a shell (Eq. 1.7) or continuous (Eq. 1.10). Either way, these distances are not as accurate com-

pared to using variability arguments and the recombination timescale method (Section 1.4.1.1).

1.4.2 Energetics and Luminosities

In order to have an impact on the host galaxy, the outflowing winds must have significant energy. The two quantities discussed here are the mass outflow rate (\dot{M}_{out}) and kinetic luminosity (L_K) which demonstrate how powerful the winds are and what fraction of the total AGN output they make up (Blustin et al., 2005). Both \dot{M}_{out} and L_K depend on the surrounding environment of the AGN nucleus, and therefore the location and origin of the wind (Kaastra et al., 2013).

The mass outflow rate (derived in Appendix B.1; Blustin et al., 2005), is given by

$$\frac{dM}{dt} = \dot{M}_{out} = \frac{1.23 m_p v f_v \Omega L_{ion}}{\xi} \quad (1.11)$$

where Ω is the solid angle, m_p is the proton mass, f_v is the volume filling factor, L_{ion} is the ionising luminosity, v is the outflow velocity of the gas, and ξ is the ionisation parameter. Furthermore, the kinetic luminosity can be found using

$$L_K = \frac{1}{2} \dot{M}_{out} v^2 = \frac{1.23}{2} \frac{m_p v^3 f_v \Omega L_{ion}}{\xi}, \quad (1.12)$$

which is the kinetic energy carried by the wind per unit time. The kinetic luminosity of the WAs in NGC 7469 were responsible for less than 1% of the bolometric luminosity (L_{bol}) and therefore were unlikely to have an impact on the galaxy (Blustin et al., 2007). However, over the lifetime of the AGN the wind can be significant enough to affect the host galaxy (Blustin et al., 2005). Despite this however, compared to the UV wind, the X-ray WA has been found to dominate the mass and kinematic energy outputs of the absorbing gas in NGC 7469 by 90 % and 95 %, respectively (Blustin et al., 2007). On the other hand, L_K of UFOs make up a significant fraction of L_{bol} (Tombesi et al., 2013).

1.5 AGN Across the Electromagnetic Spectrum

AGN and galaxies can be hard to separate with just one waveband and as a result, observations using multiple wavelengths are needed. For example, as quasars are so far away, they appear to be point like sources which makes it very difficult to distinguish between them and stars or other galaxies (Beckmann & Shrader, 2012a). Therefore, we require many observations and energy bands to resolve different components within the AGN, in order to achieve a full picture.

The spectral energy distribution (SED) is a fundamental property of AGN and a useful tool in interpreting the multiwavelength spectrum, in order to determine the origin and nature of outflowing winds (Mehdipour et al., 2018). Ranging from IR (or radio) up to X-rays/ γ -rays for RQ (or RL) AGN, SEDs are used to examine which energy bands give rise to which spectral features, as shown in Figure 1.11. The SED describes the overall properties of the AGN continuum (Netzer, 2013).

IR radiation is a major contribution to the bolometric luminosity, either coming from starburst activity and star formation, or from dust within the torus heated by the AGN radiation (Figure 1.4). The latter can be seen in obscured AGN (Beckmann & Shrader, 2012a), whereby most of the NIR (0.8 - 1.4 μm) and far-IR (FIR) emission comes from the dust grains heated by AGN radiation. Thermal FIR emission is thought to come from colder dust heated by star formation and young stars (Netzer, 2013). In AGN, IR emission originates from two main components in the torus: a disk-like structure seen in NIR and a hollow cone structure seen in the MIR (Hönig, 2019); see Section 1.2.4 for details.

The ultraviolet (UV) waveband spans the range of 100 - 4000 Å but, like with X-rays, the photons are absorbed by the Earth's atmosphere. Furthermore, the extreme UV (EUV) range (100 - 1210 Å) is difficult to observe even with space-based telescopes due to being absorbed by the Galaxy's ISM. This

Figure 1.11: Full energy range spectral energy distribution (SED) of Seyfert (black-solid line), RQ (grey-dashed line) and RL (black-dotted line) galaxies. SED plots are used to examine which energy band gives rise to which spectral features: the IR bump is caused by thermal emission from dust; the big blue bump is a result of thermal radiation from the multi-temperature accretion disk; and the Compton hump is caused by a cooling mechanism whereby the photons lose energy to the ions via Compton scattering. The gap between the big blue bump and soft X-ray band is due to extreme UV photons being absorbed by the Galaxy's ISM. (Figure adapted from [Koratkar & Blaes, 1999](#)).

is the gap in Figure 1.11, between the *big blue bump* (BBB) and the soft X-ray excess. Despite this, UV spectra are rich in atomic lines, with plasma temperatures between $T = 10^4 - 10^5$ K, making them easy to study through UV line/continuum diagnostics. UV spectroscopy gives precise measurements of the gas dynamics and can resolve many outflowing components. Similar to the WA, strong absorption features of bright AGN seen in UV spectra show multi-ionised material flowing away from the black hole, tying them with the X-ray plasmas.

However, UV radiation is extremely sensitive to dust extinction and therefore appears redder (Beckmann & Shrader, 2012a). Scattering and absorption of photons within a dusty environment causes reddening of optical/UV photons due to a large absorbing cross section, removing shorter wavelengths and therefore the true wavelength will be very different from what is observed. This is known as extinction. Absorption occurs if the dust particle size is larger than the photon wavelength, while scattering occurs when both wavelength and particle size are approximate.

The most distinctive UV feature in the SED is the BBB (at around 10 eV or 1100 Å in Figure 1.11), which produces a large fraction of the AGN bolometric luminosity (e.g. Nandra et al., 2000). Therefore, the BBB is a significant element that has a strong influence on the wind’s thermal and ionised states (Mehdipour et al., 2018). It is thought to come from thermal radiation in a multi-temperature accretion disk (Reynolds & Nowak, 2003), where the high energy UV/optical photons originate close to the black hole. The disk is built up of multiple blackbody-like spectra, due to a range of temperatures, where the hottest temperature is $T \sim 10^4 - 10^5$ K (Beckmann & Shrader, 2012a). In addition, there is a “Small Blue Bump”, a blend of Fe and Balmer lines between 2000 - 4000 Å (Shang et al., 2005).

Correlations in the UV and X-ray bands have been found between the fluxes and continuum slopes/shapes (Nandra et al., 2000). These correlations are explained via Comptonisation processes in the hot electron corona where

Figure 1.12: The soft X-ray excess is a result of the intrinsic power-law (with slope Γ) under-predicting the spectrum at lower energies (below 2 keV). The soft excess suggests that the soft X-rays originate from a separate continuum component than the hard X-rays, also linked to the UV/optical photons through Comptonisation up-scattering processes. (Image of the NGC 5548 EPIC-PN spectrum, taken from [Mehdipour et al., 2015a](#)).

UV/optical photons are upscattered to form the hard X-rays. Some of these X-rays are then reflected off the disk. However, the extrapolation of the X-ray power-law into the EUV and the BBB can under-fit the X-ray spectrum at soft X-rays, below 2 keV (see [Mehdipour et al., 2015a](#), and references within). This is shown in Figure 1.12, and is known as the soft X-ray excess, found in over half of AGN spectra ([Bianchi et al., 2009](#)). It is not fully understood where the soft excess originates from, or what causes it, but some ideas include a two component thermal Comptonisation model (e.g. [Petrucci et al., 2018](#)), a relativistically blurred disk reflection model ([Crummy et al., 2006](#)), or a second power-law (e.g. [Bianchi et al., 2009](#)).

The Compton hump is another feature in the SED, peaking at around 30

keV, which comes from a combination of reflection and absorption in Compton thick material, which has a column density of $N_H > \frac{1}{\sigma_T} = 1.5 \times 10^{28} \text{ m}^{-2}$, where $\sigma_T = 6.65246 \times 10^{-29} \text{ m}^2$ is the Thompson scattering cross section (Netzer, 2013). Above 10 keV scattering dominates and reflection from the the material adds to the continuum flux, producing the hump. However, as the photon energy increases beyond the peak, the hump decreases because the photons give their energy to the electrons. Below 10 keV, the photons get absorbed by Compton-thick material, while scattering dominates above this energy.

Observing AGN across the electromagnetic spectrum gives an overall picture of these complex objects, that just one waveband cannot see. Fitting a broadband model (IR-optical-UV-X-ray) to all the data means better constraints on the parameters can be imposed. From this, more precise and accurate models can be used to explain everything that we see. Details of how to construct the multiwavelength SED model for photoionisation analysis is described in Section 2.3.1 of Chapter 2.

1.6 Launching Mechanisms

The origin and launching mechanisms of the outflowing winds are, to date, not fully known; the two most favoured ideas are that they originate either from the accretion disk or from the torus. There are three main launching mechanism theories for the outflowing winds in the literature and they are described here. The citations in this Section come from Krolik & Kriss (2001) and Proga (2007) for thermally-driven winds; Proga et al. (2000) and Proga (2007) for radiatively-driven winds; and Proga (2007) and Fukumura et al. (2010a,b, 2015) for magnetically-driven winds; unless stated otherwise.

1.6.1 Thermally-driven Winds

Thermally driven winds are associated with material being evaporated off the inner edge of the torus, which is determined by a combination of dust sublimation and photoionisation. The accretion disk loses mass if it is heated by irradiation on the cooler/outer disk from the inner/hotter disk radiation.

Figure 1.13: Schematic to show the possible origin of the BLR, taken from Czerny et al. (2015). The X-rays ionise the outer accretion disk to higher temperatures. When $T \simeq 1000\text{ K}$, the sublimation temperature is reached and the dust becomes a plasma. This radiation pressure acts on the plasma in the accretion disk atmosphere and launches the outflow, but sometimes the material falls back down as a failed wind.

Within the torus, the optical depth is large enough to protect and keep the gas cool ($T \leq 10^3\text{ K}$). However, as more gas is heated, the opacity drops and more gas is exposed, which is then added to the hot phase. This can happen as long as thermal and ionisation equilibrium times are shorter than the flow time, and until the matter reaches a high temperature ($T > 10^6\text{ K}$). X-rays then heat the low density gas up to temperatures greater than $T_c = 10^7\text{ K}$ through Compton heating, causing the disk to either puff up (forming a corona) or produce a thermal wind, depending on whether it has a large enough velocity to escape (v_{esc}). This process is effective at large distances where v_{esc} is small. However, if $T < T_c$ then radiation forces dominate and thermal driving is less important. This launching mechanism explains the origins of the WA wind, expected to originate from the torus.

1.6.2 Radiatively-driven Winds

Radiatively-driven winds are produced when momentum is transferred from the photons to the disk through the absorption of spectral line emission. This depends on the number of lines available for absorption, in addition to the optical thickness of the absorbing material; the ratio between optically thick and optically thin lines give rise to the total line acceleration (e.g. [Kudritzki & Puls, 2000](#)). When there is a small increase in velocity, the material is then exposed to a greater amount of radiation (same for O-type stars), making these winds very unstable ([Runacres & Owocki, 2002](#)). Assuming the disk is moderately ionised, the line force is significant and can overcome gravity, as long as the gas opacity is large enough. The larger the outflow velocity, the stronger the line driving, and therefore the broader the absorption lines. The wind becomes faster at larger radii due to the acceleration from line driving; the wind is slower closer to the black hole ([Mizumoto et al., 2021](#)). However, the X-ray radiation over ionises the wind, resulting in a drop in opacity and causing line driving to become negligible - the material falls back down onto the disk as a failed wind. If, on the other hand, the column density close to the disk is large enough, then it will shield the disk at larger radii, which means material further out can be accelerated by line driving, causing a wind. This X-ray shielding is important in order for UV line driving to occur and to explain the observed UV absorption lines.

Furthermore, radiative driving could explain the origins of the low ionised BLR, whereby local radiation pressure acts on the dust in the accretion disk atmosphere and launches the outflow (shown in [Figure 1.13](#)). However, high above the disk, the radiation evaporates the dust, such that the material falls back down, producing a failed wind. This depends on the type of AGN, and the effective temperature at which the dust would sublimate ($T_{eff} \sim 1000$ K), corresponding to the location of the BLR (See e.g. [Czerny & Hryniewicz, 2011](#); [Czerny et al., 2017](#)).

1.6.3 Magnetically-driven Winds

Magnetic fields corotate with the accretion disk and provide a reasonable explanation for the transfer of angular momentum between the inner, fast moving and outer, slow moving disk regions. These magnetic fields also play an important role in collimating the wind at larger distances. When material is launched from the disk with small velocities (likely from radiative driving), the magnetic fields drag and pull the plasma with it as it rotates with the disk. The strong centrifugal force and magnetic pressure accelerate the disk material, causing highly ionised winds to be ejected from different parts of the disk; the magnetic energy is converted into kinetic energy of the plasma wind. As the magnetic field increases the wind becomes faster and dominates the mass outflow rate, producing broader lines, which can affect the line absorption. Magnetically driven winds do not require radiation pressure gradient, are independent on the luminosity, and are not affected by over ionised gas. This launching mechanism explains the UFO outflow winds, with a range of ionisation state $\log \xi = 5 - 6$, column density $N_H \sim 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, and velocities of 0.1 - 0.4 c (Tombesi et al., 2013). Magnetically driven winds play a crucial role in the mass outflow rate, and if UFOs are important in feedback, then it suggests that the magnetic properties of disk can affect the host galaxy (Kraemer et al., 2018).

Chapter 2

AGN Spectra

AGN spectra in the X-ray band are abundant with emission and absorption features that directly present the properties and characteristics of the black hole environment, in particular of the outflowing winds photoionised by the nuclear radiation. Through spectral analysis and modelling, the kinematics, column densities and ionisation states of photoionised (PI) plasmas can be measured, in addition to the temperature and emission measure of collisionally ionised (CI) plasmas. Further to this, accurate measurements of the abundances and ionic species within the outflowing gas give vital information about the evolution of the outflowing wind and ISM of the host galaxy (Steenbrugge et al., 2011; Behar et al., 2017).

Since the advent of XMM-Newton and Chandra (Chapter 3), high resolution X-ray spectra have allowed for more sensitive and detailed AGN research than possible beforehand, indispensable in understanding the properties of the warm absorber (WA; e.g. Kaastra et al., 2000; Kaastra, 2003) and emission line regions (ELR; e.g. Kinkhabwala et al., 2002). Figure 2.1 illustrates some of the different AGN spectral features in the X-ray band, which are described and explained in this Chapter. The red continuum is over imposed by many narrow absorption lines (from the WA) as well as some strong emission features such as the FeK α (~ 2 Å) and O VII forbidden (~ 20 Å) lines. The power law continuum (blue line in Figure 2.1) does not fit the X-ray spectrum well anywhere, therefore other components are required to explain the observed

Figure 2.1: Example of the spectral features within an AGN (red line): strong narrow absorption lines from the WA wind, emission features from the emission line region ($> 10 \text{ \AA}$) and the $\text{FeK}\alpha$ emission line in the high energy regime due to reflection of neutral material such as the accretion disk or torus. The power-law (blue line) is the underlying continuum and does not fit the spectrum well, in particular at lower energies where the soft excess is present. (Figure adapted from [Kaastra, 2003](#)).

spectral features, in addition to continuum models for the soft X-ray excess and high energy reflection.

In this Chapter, I introduce the `SPEX` analysis code, used to model the data, before describing the many spectral features that give rise to the characteristics of the outflowing winds investigated in this Thesis. Finally, I explain the thermal state of the plasma and the physical processes that give rise to the heating and cooling mechanisms. This Chapter addresses how photoionisation modelling is critical in explaining the properties of the ionised wind and how the spectral features are produced in the plasmas. Modelling with the spectral energy distribution (SED) is also discussed, which is paramount in investigating the central source as it ionises the surrounding environment.

Figure 2.2: Comparing the model transmissions for the X-ray spectra of a PIE plasma with ionisation parameter $\log \xi = 2$, column density $N_H = 10^{26} \text{ m}^{-2}$, and turbulent velocity $v_{turb} = 200 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. The three codes are SPEX (red), XSTAR (green), and Cloudy (blue) - there are slight differences in continuum shape and absorption lines between each one. (Figure taken from Mehdipour et al., 2016b).

2.1 Spectral Fitting in SPEX

The analysis of high resolution spectra through photoionisation modelling is a very effective way to investigate AGN outflows. The models applied in this Thesis are implemented via the SPEX¹ code (Kaastra et al., 1996), which is a specialist analysis software for high resolution X-ray and UV spectra. SPEX contains many plasma models², including photoionised equilibrium (PIE) and collisional ionised equilibrium (CIE) models. The main models used in this Thesis are explained in Sections 2.3.2 and 2.3.3.

¹<https://www.sron.nl/astrophysics-spex>

²<https://www.sron.nl/astrophysics-spex/manual>

In comparison to most analysis codes, such as XSPEC (Arnaud, 1996), Cloudy (Ferland et al., 2013), and XSTAR (Kallman & Bautista, 2001), SPEX has its advantages and disadvantages. For example, an advantage of SPEX is that it minimises the number of calculations, but still produces fast and accurate results (Kaastra et al., 2017). SPEX also allows for the use of a self-consistent PIE model that does not require a pre-calculated ionisation grid (Mehdipour et al., 2016b) - this is explained in more detail in Section 2.3.

Mehdipour et al. (2016b) modelled the ionisation balance, thermal stability, and ionic abundances of AGN plasma using three different photoionisation codes and compared them together. In all cases the fitting outcomes differed, albeit slightly, which is a result of small deviations in the atomic data, heating/cooling processes, and ionisation balance calculations. This can be seen, as an example, in Figure 2.2, where there are modest differences in the continuum shape and the lines present when comparing SPEX with XSTAR and Cloudy. Therefore, these discrepancies are recognised and taken into account when comparing AGN results from different codes.

SPEX has two goodness-of-fit tests for spectral fitting: χ^2 and the Cash statistic (C-statistic hereafter; Cash, 1979). The χ^2 statistic is expressed as

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(N_i - S_i)^2}{\sigma_i^2}, \quad (2.1)$$

where N_i is the observed number of counts in bin i , S_i is the expected number of counts, and σ_i is the standard deviation of N_i , for n number of bins. However, AGN X-ray spectra often contain a low number of counts per bin, due to, for example, Galactic and intrinsic absorption, their distance from Earth, intrinsically low luminosity, and small contributions to the total L_{bol} compared to other wavebands, which can lead to inaccurate and biased results (Kaastra, 2017).

Therefore, in this Thesis, the C-statistic is the statistical analysis tool used for a goodness-of-fit test between the data and the fitted model. Unlike

χ^2 tests, the C-statistic method is valid at low count rates, and is given by

$$C = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n S_i - N_i + N_i \ln \left(\frac{N_i}{S_i} \right). \quad (2.2)$$

The derivation of the C-statistic is shown in Appendix B.2. SPEX also gives the expected C-statistic to check if the spectral fit is acceptable. On the other hand, there needs to be a thorough understanding of the applicability of the fitted models, and a correct physical interpretation of the AGN environment is sometimes more important than the best minimised statistic (Blustin et al., 2002).

SPEX, like many other spectral fitting codes, uses the Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) method to compute and solve the non-linear minimisation problem, whilst fitting the model to the data. It does this through least squares fitting. Here, LM uses a sequence of parameter updates, iteratively reducing the sum of the squares between the model and the data (Gavin, 2011).

2.2 X-ray Spectral Features

There are two main types of plasma studied in this Thesis, where the rate of ionisation equals the rate of recombination: photoionised equilibrium (PIE) and collisionally ionised equilibrium (CIE). CIE plasmas occur when free, high energy electrons collide with ions. As CIE plasmas are very hot and can be found in star forming regions, it is generally assumed that CIE plasmas which contribute to X-ray emission from galaxies are optically thin so that radiation can pass through (Porquet et al., 2010). PIE plasmas, by contrast, are ionised by high energy photons, where the difference in the photon energy and ionisation energy is then transferred to the kinetic energy of the free electron. Due to this, PIE plasmas have a much lower electron temperature compared to CIE plasmas (Porquet et al., 2010; Kahn et al., 2002). The electron densities and temperatures determine the plasma type, while the ionic abundances and energies determine which ions are present. Although the source of ionisation is

Figure 2.3: Simplified Grotrian diagrams displaying the absorption and emission process in PIE and CIE plasmas. The recombination processes are the same in both plasma types, but the way they are ionised is different. *Top:* Photoexcitation and radiative decay (blue box); *Bottom:* Photoionisation and radiative recombination/cascades (red box). Dashed lines are photons and solid lines are the electron (dots) transitions. (Taken and adapted from [Kinkhabwala et al., 2003](#))

different in CIE and PIE plasmas, they both emit X-rays from direct recombination and radiative cascades ([Kahn et al., 2002](#)) as the electrons transition to the ground state. These processes are shown in Figure 2.3, where photoexcitation and radiative decay, and photoionisation and recombination are displayed in the blue and red boxes, respectively.

In this Section I shall describe and explain the different spectral features that come about from the emission and absorption processes within PIE or CIE plasmas.

2.2.1 Absorption Features

Absorption features are present in AGN spectra if the plasma is covering some of the ionising continuum within our line-of-sight (LOS). Essentially, the X-rays

are blocked by the plasma. The WA plasma imprints its signature absorption lines on the soft X-ray spectra due to multiple ionic transitions from, e.g. C, N, O, Mg, Ne, S and Fe ions (e.g. [Kaastra et al., 2002](#); [Behar et al., 2017](#)). Spectral lines are produced from transition between discrete energy levels, and therefore have discrete energies. This process is shown in the top left panel of [Figure 2.3](#). Absorption depends on the photoionisation cross section σ_{ph} which becomes larger for an increase in the atomic number (Z), meaning more energy is required to ionise the atom ([Morrison & McCammon, 1983](#)).

In addition to absorption lines, another spectral feature is the absorption edge. Absorption K-edges, occur when the photon energy (in the case of PIE plasma) is larger than or equal to the ionised threshold energy $E_{ph} = h\nu \geq \chi$ of the inner most shell, and hence the absorption edge features are broad. For example, the O VII and O VIII absorption edges occur at 0.74 keV and 0.87 keV, respectively. The main difference here compared to spectral lines is that edges are caused by photoionisation, whereby the ion absorbs a photon and causes an electron to be ejected. This process is shown in the bottom left panel of [Figure 2.3](#).

2.2.2 Radiative Recombination Continua

In CIE plasmas, the electron temperature is close to the ionisation potential (χ) of the ion, allowing for electron collisions to ionise the gas. However, for PIE plasmas, work is done by the photons, so the electron temperature is lower ([Kahn et al., 2002](#)). A useful spectral feature to determine if a plasma is in CIE or PIE, based on the electron distribution, is the width of the radiative recombination continua (RRC), as illustrated in [Figure 2.4](#).

RRCs occur when electrons, with a Maxwellian energy distribution, recombine into the energy levels of the ion ([Kahn et al., 2002](#)). If the electron has an energy equal to the ionisation threshold energy (χ), they can recombine with the ion. At this energy, the photon emission is at its most intense (peak in [Figure 2.4](#)), before falling off to higher energies ([Kahn et al., 2002](#)), caused by a range in electron energies. The electrons in the plasma have an initial thermal

energy $E_i = kT$, where T is the electron temperature and k is the Boltzmann constant. The broadness of an RRC feature is approximately equal to kT and the photon released has energy $E = \chi + kT$, equal to ionisation energy plus the extra kinetic energy. For CIE plasma, as the electron temperature is very high, the RRC peak is broad, but also very weak. In PIE plasmas, the threshold energy is much greater than the RRC line width $\chi \gg kT$, so the peak is narrow and strong (Kahn et al., 2002). This is because the electrons in the CIE plasmas have more kinetic energy (on average) to add to the photon, whereas PIE plasmas are not as hot so electrons have less kinetic energy compared to χ . Usually the electrons recombine to any shell, however, the RRCs seen in the X-ray spectra (e.g. NGC 1068; Kinkhabwala et al., 2002) are at the K-edge absorption edge energies - therefore these processes are the opposite.

This spectroscopic analysis of the RRC is paramount in photoionisation modelling of the outflowing winds, measuring the plasma temperature and the emission measure (EM) of each ion. EM is the measure of the volume of material that is emitting, and is defined by

$$EM = \int n_e n_H dV, \quad (2.3)$$

where n_e and n_H are the number densities for electrons and hydrogen ions, respectively, for a given volume V . A change in EM implies a change in the plasma density.

2.2.3 He-like Triplets and H-like Doublets

Many X-ray spectra show features of He-like triplets (e.g. Whewell et al., 2015; Behar et al., 2017; Mao et al., 2019) consisting of a resonance (w or r) line, an intercombination line (made up of two lines: x + y or i) and a forbidden line (z or f). The transitions for the resonance, intercombination and forbidden lines are $1s2p \ ^1P_1 \rightarrow 1s^2 \ ^1S_0$; $1s2p \ ^3P_2 \rightarrow 1s^2 \ ^1S_0$ (x) and $1s2p \ ^3P_1 \rightarrow 1s^2 \ ^1S_0$ (y); and $1s2s \ ^3S_1 \rightarrow 1s^2 \ ^1S_0$, respectively (Porquet & Dubau, 2000). The electron transitions for these four lines are displayed in Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.4: Radiative recombination continua are fundamental tools for understanding plasmas in AGN environments. The broadness of the lines are correlated to the plasma temperature and therefore the ionisation process. As shown in the diagram (adapted from [Kahn et al., 2002](#)), the lower the plasma temperature, the narrower and more intense the peak: PIE plasma. As the temperature increases, the peak becomes broader and less intense: CIE plasma. The peak of the line is at the same wavelength for a given ionic species, irrespective of the ionisation process and despite the temperature increase.

The He-like triplet lines come about through spin orbit coupling (e.g. [Tipler & Mosca, 2008](#)), where two electrons are present in the ion. This is the coupling between the spin angular momentum (S) and orbital angular momentum (L) of the electrons in their bound states, which are summed together to get the total angular momentum ($J = |L + S| \dots |L - S|$). These three quantities are related via the spectroscopic configuration $^{2S+1}L_J$. For two electrons in the ground state, in order not to violate the Pauli exclusion principle, the electron spins must be anti-parallel, so the spin magnetic moment is $m_s = \pm \frac{1}{2}$. If one of these electrons is excited to a higher energy state, then the electron spins can be either parallel ($1\uparrow$) or anti-parallel ($1\downarrow$), meaning $S = 1$ for the parallel spin configuration, called a triplet, and 0 for the anti-parallel configu-

Figure 2.5: Energy level diagram showing the electron transitions that produce the resonance (w) line in a singlet state (left of dashed blue line), and intercombination ($x + y$) and forbidden (z) lines in a triplet state (right side of dashed line). These spectral features are called He-like triplet lines. For photoionised plasma, the electron density is low, so the forbidden line dominates as more electrons are in the lower energy state (3S_1). As the density increases, such as in collisionally ionised plasma, the electrons are in higher energy levels so the intercombination and resonance lines become more intense (${}^3P_{1,2}$ and 1P_1 , respectively). The energy levels (red arrows) are denoted by $n = 1$ and $n = 2$ for the ground state and first energy level, respectively.

ration, called a singlet. Therefore, for a triplet, with $S = (1/2 + 1/2) = 1$, the total angular momentum, J , of each triplet energy level is $J = L + 1, L, L - 1$. If L is in the first excited state, or P state ($L = 1$), then $J = 2, 1$ or 0 and the spectroscopic configuration is ${}^3P_{0,1,2}$, corresponding to the triplet energy levels seen in Figure 2.5 (right side of dashed blue line). This produces the intercombination and forbidden lines. For the resonance line, the transition is a singlet ($S = 0, L = 1$ and therefore $J = 1$), shown on the left side of the dashed blue line in Figure 2.5.

For low density gas, the $n = 2$ shell is filled from recombination (or radiative cascades) from higher levels (Dubau & Porquet, 2002). From here, the

electron in the $n = 2$ shell can decay to the ground state, emitting a photon. In the PIE plasma, the forbidden line is the most dominant line due to transitions from higher energy levels down to the lowest $1s2s\ ^3S_1$ energy level, which in turn radiatively decays into the ground state (z transition in Figure 2.5; Kahn et al., 2002).

However, as the electron density of the gas increases, the electrons in the lower states are collisionally excited to higher energy levels (Dubau & Porquet, 2002). This means that the intercombination line strength increases as there are now more electrons in the $1s2p\ ^3P_{1,2}$ level, resulting in a higher probability of transitions from this energy state to the ground state (x and y transitions in Figure 2.5). Increasing the density further causes the resonance line to become important (w transition in Figure 2.5; Dubau & Porquet, 2002).

The forbidden line is not actually “forbidden”, rather it is very unlikely for the transition to happen. Due to a particular selection rule, the electron is unlikely to be excited from the ground state to the 3S_1 energy level. This is why in high density plasma, the forbidden line becomes weaker as the free electrons can excite the bound electrons to the $1s2p\ ^3P_{1,2}$ and $1s2p\ ^1P_1$ levels (intercombination and resonance transitions, respectively).

The ratios between the three triplet lines are important at identifying certain properties of the ionised gas, such as the temperature and electron density. The ratio R between the forbidden line and the intercombination line can give a measure of the electron density n_e

$$R(n_e) = \frac{f}{i}; \quad (2.4)$$

whereas a ratio G between the sum of the forbidden and intercombination lines and the resonance line is used to determine the temperature T of the gas

$$G(T) = \frac{f+i}{r}. \quad (2.5)$$

In PIE plasma, the forbidden line is strongest so $G > 4$, whereas for CIE plasma

Figure 2.6: This schematic indicates the paths in which the X-rays travel before reaching the detector in a type 1 AGN. The primary X-ray source (red arrows) comes from the corona and is observed directly (same for the UV/optical photons from the accretion disc). However, some of the X-rays are reflected off either the disk (green arrows), the BLR (purple arrows), or the torus (blue arrows).

the resonance line is dominant so $G \sim 1$ (Dubau & Porquet, 2002).

Further to He-like triplets, H-like doublets are also prominent in X-ray spectra (Kahn et al., 2002). The H-like states of, for example, C, N and O are found in the Lyman series within the X-ray band. These bright resonance lines are used to determine abundances and velocities of the plasma, but are limited in diagnosing temperatures and densities (Kahn et al., 2002). For H-like ions the spectral feature results in a doublet, also a consequence of spin orbit coupling. This occurs because there is only one electron present in the ion, which means the spin magnetic moment in an energy level can either be $m_s = +\frac{1}{2}$ or $m_s = -\frac{1}{2}$, and therefore the total spin is $S = \frac{1}{2}$. If the orbital angular momentum $L = 1$ (P state), then the total angular momentum is $J = \frac{3}{2}, \frac{1}{2}$, and the spectroscopic configuration is ${}^2P_{\frac{3}{2}, \frac{1}{2}}$, giving rise to the doublet line.

2.2.4 The FeK α Line

The most prominent emission line feature in the hard X-ray band is the FeK α line, at around 6.4 keV (Netzer, 2013). This feature is produced when X-rays from the nuclear region interact with and reflect off the surrounding environment (see Figure 2.6). The FeK α line originates from material with $N_H \sim 10^{25} - 10^{27} \text{ m}^{-2}$, but, it is not fully understood where these features come from - accretion disk, BLR, torus, or all three (Ramos Almeida & Ricci, 2017). However, an AGN survey from Gandhi et al. (2015) found the narrow FeK α line originates from within the dust sublimation radius, likely the BLR.

The FeK α line is present in many AGN; a result of its high cosmic abundance (e.g Lodders et al., 2009). It is a result of X-ray fluorescence, whereby the X-ray photons ionise the atom, causing the inner shell electrons (the K band) to be ejected from each atom. This is then followed by an electron, in a higher energy shell, transitioning down to fill the vacant shell, emitting a photon (Kaastra et al., 2008). Electrons are more likely to transition from the $n = 2$ (L) shell to $n = 1$ (K) shell, causing the K α line, than they are to fill the vacancy from $n = 3$ (M) to $n = 1$, called the K β transition. But many AGN spectra have a corresponding, albeit weaker, FeK β line as well.

2.2.5 Photoionised and Collisionally Ionised Plasmas

Combined

In a few AGN, a starburst region and photoionised gas are both present, emitting photons from CIE and PIE plasmas. For example, in NGC 1365 two optically thin CIE plasmas had temperatures of 300 and 640 keV, respectively, caused by collisional excitation and shock heating (Guainazzi et al., 2009), and three PIE gas phases, with ionisation parameters of $\log \xi = 1.1, 1.5$ and 2.5 , were located between 0.5 and 270 pc from the SMBH (Whewell et al., 2016). NGC 7469 (Chapter 4; e.g. Behar et al., 2017; Mehdipour et al., 2018), NGC 1068 (Chapter 5; e.g. Grafton-Waters et al., 2021b), and NGC 5643 (Chapter 6) are the three AGN studied in this Thesis that show evidence for X-ray emission from both photoionised gas and the starburst region.

Figure 2.7: Comparing spectra from an AGN only (left) and a AGN with a starburst region (right). The top panels show the spectra produced by photoionised (PI) plasma, while the middle panels illustrate the effects of photoexcitation (PE; left) and CIE plasma (right) in the spectra. The bottom panels show the total spectrum when the top and middle panels are added together. The triplet in AGN only (PI + PE) can have the same line ratios as an AGN with a starburst region (PI + CIE). This implies that the triplet alone cannot be used to decipher between the plasma types in AGN and AGN+starburst spectra. Instead, RRCs and other emission features, such as PE processes, must be used to tell the difference. (Image taken from [Kinkhabwala et al., 2002](#)).

Figure 2.8: Model emission lines for Fe XVI - Fe XIX in a CIE plasma (left) and in a PIE plasma (right). *Left:* Fe XVII line at 15 Å is dominant in CIE plasma compared to PIE; *Right:* Fe XVII line at 17 Å is more dominant in PIE plasma. (Figure adapted from Liedahl et al., 1990).

However, caution is required when analysing these types of spectra. Figure 2.7 compares the spectra of an AGN only and an AGN with a starburst region (Kinkhabwala et al., 2002). For the AGN only scenario, photoionised and photoexcitation (PE) processes are involved (left side of Figure 2.7). For the AGN and starburst region scenario, both PIE and CIE plasma emission are present (right side of Figure 2.7). The bottom panels of Figure 2.7 show the combined spectra for either scenario: PIE + PE (left) and PIE + CIE (right). The line ratios of the O VII triplet lines ($\sim 21.5\text{\AA}$) are very similar in both panels, even though the plasma processes are completely different. This means that this feature cannot be solely used to decipher between plasma types in AGN only and AGN with starburst regions. Instead, the radiative recombination continua and photoexcitation features below 19 Å are required to illustrate the difference (Kinkhabwala et al., 2002).

Furthermore, the Fe XVII lines at 15 and 17 Å present in many high resolution spectra of AGN (e.g. NGC 7469; Behar et al., 2017) posed a problem when studying NGC 1068 (Chapter 5 and Grafton-Waters et al. 2021b). In SPEX a PIE plasma does not account for these RGS features, but they are fitted well with a CIE model, which is generally assumed to originate from the starburst region, or more likely in the case of NGC 1068, an extended,

Figure 2.9: Possible accretion disk and corona geometry for AGN. The hard X-rays are produced in the hot electron corona located between R_{isco} and R_{in} ; these photons irradiate the disk, producing the warmer layer above or below the disk. This warm layer produces the soft X-ray photons and explains the soft X-ray excess. The middle of the accretion disk (and likely outer disk) produces the blackbody spectrum from UV and optical photons. (Image taken from [Petrucci et al., 2013](#), used to model the broadband spectrum of Mrk 509).

secondary region (e.g. [Brinkman et al., 2002](#)). In terms of the Fe-L lines themselves, the Fe XVII line at 17 \AA is populated by recombination rather than direct excitation, so PIE plasma should dominate this line. As for the resonance Fe XVII line at 15 \AA , the 3d shell is highly populated if the plasma density is high, suggesting that CIE plasma can account for this. [Figure 2.8](#) ([Liedahl et al., 1990](#)) shows that the 15 \AA line is emitted in CIE plasma (left side), whereas the Fe XVII at 17 \AA should be accounted for by PIE plasma (right side), reiterating the arguments above. However, photoexcitation was not considered by [Liedahl et al. \(1990\)](#), which could explain the 15 \AA resonance line ([Sako et al., 2000](#); [Kinkhabwala et al., 2002](#)). In this case the explanation for the lack of PIE emission in the model at 17 \AA is, however, unknown (see [Chapter 5](#) for the study on NGC 1068).

2.3 Photoionisation Modelling

In this Thesis, the main SPEX model used to explain and analyse the nature and properties of the photoionised plasmas in AGN winds is PION (Mehdipour et al., 2016b); see Section 2.3.2. For photoionisation modelling, it is assumed that the gas is in photoionisation equilibrium, whereby the rate of ionisation is equal to the rate of recombination. The outflowing wind (WA, NLR) is photoionised by the continuum radiation, affecting the ionisation and thermal states of the plasma (see Section 2.4.2). Modelling photoionised plasma is very complex due to the various interacting processes within the plasma winds, in addition to line transitions and energy balance calculations (see e.g. Mehdipour et al., 2016b). Conveniently, on the other hand, the ionisation and thermal states of the photoionised plasma can be quantified as a single parameter - the ionisation parameter ξ (Eq. 1.4 from Chapter 1). Before modelling the X-ray spectrum, however, the spectral energy distribution (SED) needs to be obtained.

2.3.1 The SED

Intrinsic continuum emission from AGN is argued to come from three main regions: the optically thick accretion disk which emits a multi-temperature blackbody (BB) spectrum; a hot thermal plasma region, known as the hot electron corona ($T_e \sim 100$ keV and $\tau \sim 1$; Sunyaev & Titarchuk, 1980); and a EUV/soft X-ray component with an electron temperature $T_e \sim 0.2 - 0.3$ keV and a large optical depth (e.g. Magdziarz et al., 1998). Although the disk and corona emission are well explained (albeit the origin of the corona is unknown), there are still debates as to the origin of the soft X-ray component (Gierliński & Done, 2004; Done et al., 2012). As the disk temperature is too low to explain the origin of the soft X-rays (Magdziarz et al., 1998), the large consensus for the soft X-ray excess is that it is produced in a second region. This second region has a lower temperature ($kT \sim 0.2$ keV) but higher optical depth ($\tau = 20 - 30$) compared to the electron corona, whereby seed photons are also up-scattered through inverse-Compton processes, but to a lower energy than the power-law

(Magdziarz et al., 1998; Petrucci et al., 2013; Mehdipour et al., 2011; Middei et al., 2018).

The geometry of this two Comptonisation component system is unknown; they could be separated either radially or vertically (e.g. Done et al., 2012). Figure 2.9 models the electron corona as being located between the inner disk (R_{isco}) out to some distance (R_{in}); alternatively, other ways to model the corona are above the black hole (e.g. Keck et al., 2015), similar to Figure 1.2. Petrucci et al. (2000) investigated different types of geometry and found similar electron and seed photon temperatures in a slab or hemispherical geometry, both of which were good fits to their data. In SPEX, a disk (or slab of material) geometry for the Comptonisation component (see Section 2.3.1.2) is the default setting whereby different photon energies are produced from different areas on the accretion disk (e.g. Petrucci et al., 2013; Mehdipour et al., 2015a; Gardner & Done, 2017; Mahmoud & Done, 2020); a spherical geometry can also be selected in SPEX. For a disk-like geometry (Figure 2.9), the soft X-ray photons are then produced in a Comptonisation component above/below the disk in a warm layer that up-scatters the optical/UV seed photons from the middle of the disk into soft X-ray photons - this is the Comptonisation plasma. The BB radiation is produced in the cooler disk either between the warm layers or at significantly larger distances. A further problem regarding the soft X-ray excess and Comptonisation component, in addition to the geometry, is that the emission is in the EUV part of the spectrum, which is absorbed by the Galaxy ISM.

It is the broadband continuum SED shape that is important in the modelling, which is dependent on the AGN. The SED is obtained from multiwavelength observations (Mehdipour et al., 2016b) and created using optical-UV-X-ray data (Kaastra, 2017). Below I describe the three main SPEX SED model components used throughout this Thesis to model the optical-UV-X-ray ionising continuum over a large energy range. The SED of NGC 5548 is shown in Figure 2.10 as an example (Mehdipour et al., 2015a).

Figure 2.10: *Top:* Full optical-UV-X-ray SED of NGC 5548 (green line), where the black dashed line is the Comptonisation component (COMT) and the dotted lines are for the power-law (POW) and reflection components (REFL). The red circles and black squares are data points from UV/optical instruments. *Bottom:* Residuals between the data and model: RGS in light blue, EPIC-PN in black, NuSTAR in pink, and INTEGRAL in dark blue. (Figure edited from [Mehdipour et al., 2015a](#)).

2.3.1.1 Power-law (POW)

The power-law (POW) models the hard X-ray emission produced when optical/UV disk photons are upscattered in a hot electron corona ([Sunyaev & Titarchuk, 1980](#)). For a non-relativistic, thermal energy distribution of electrons with temperature T_e , the average change in photon energy for a single scatter is (e.g. [Reynolds & Nowak, 2003](#); [Rybicki & Lightman, 1986](#))

$$\frac{\Delta E}{E_i} = \frac{E_T - E_{ph}}{E_e}, \quad (2.6)$$

where $E_T = 4kT_e$ is the thermal energy of the electrons, E_{ph} is the photon energy, $E_e = m_e c^2$ is the electron rest mass energy, and E_i is the initial seed photon energy. For N interactions between the photons and electrons the photons can gain or lose energy from the electrons, depending if $E_{ph} < E_e$ or $E_{ph} > E_e$, respectively (Done, 2010). This creates a distribution of photon energies after N interactions and scatters, known as the power-law. If $E_{ph} > 4kT_e$, then the photons do not gain energy from the electrons, but if $E_{ph} \ll 4kT_e$, photons do gain energy from each scatter, given by

$$\frac{\Delta E}{E} = \frac{4kT_e}{m_e c^2}. \quad (2.7)$$

After N scatters between the electrons and photons, the final photon energy E_f will be

$$E_f = E_i \exp N \frac{4kT_e}{m_e c^2}. \quad (2.8)$$

Here, the exponent is equivalent to the Compton parameter (y), which equals the average fraction of energy per scatter, multiplied by the number of scatters: $y = N \times \frac{4kT_e}{m_e c^2}$. This implies that multiple scatters becomes exponentially unlikely, but multiple scatters lead to an exponential increase in the photon energy. When the rate of energy gained is balanced with the rate of energy lost, the power-law is produced. The power-law is given by $F = AE^{-\Gamma}$, where F is the photon flux per unit of energy E , and A is a normalisation (e.g. Reynolds & Nowak, 2003; Rybicki & Lightman, 1986).

2.3.1.2 Comptonisation Component (COMT)

To explain the UV/optical emission from the accretion disk and account for the soft X-ray excess (e.g. Petrucci et al., 2013; Middei et al., 2018), a Comptonisation component (COMT; Titarchuk, 1994) is used. COMT models the up-scattering of soft photons in a warm, optically thick medium, which is shown above and below the accretion disk in Figure 2.9. This mechanism is similar to the one that produces the power-law in a hot electron corona, but here the photons are upscattered to soft X-ray energies.

2.3.1.3 Reflection Component (REFL)

The reflection component (REFL; Magdziarz & Zdziarski, 1995) models the reflection and scattering of the X-ray power-law off neutral or almost neutral material such as the accretion disk and the obscuring torus. This gives rise to the fluorescent FeK α line at about 6.4 keV and the Compton hump. Figure 2.6 displays the multiple ways in which the power-law can be reflected off material within the AGN environment.

2.3.1.4 Energy Cut-offs (ETAU)

Finally, to the power-law in each SED, upper and lower cut-off energies (ETAU) are applied. The lower cut-off energy is fixed at the accretion disk temperature to stop the power-law energies becoming lower than the disk photon energies. The high energy cut-off is the maximum electron energy that can produce X-ray photons before the photons give energy to the electrons from each scatter; i.e. the maximum electron energy in the corona.

2.3.2 The PION Model (PION)

In this Thesis, I use the photoionisation model PION in SPEX. PION is a sophisticated, physically self-consistent photoionisation model that accounts for both absorption and emission of a slab of material in a PIE plasma. PION is the only model currently available that computes explicitly all the absorption and emission lines in the spectrum, using the ionising continuum (SED) to calculate both the spectrum and ionisation balance of the plasma simultaneously. It solves the ionisation and energy balance equations, resulting in the electron temperature and plasma abundances, quantified by ξ (Mehdipour et al., 2016b). The biggest advantage of PION over other models and codes is that if the continuum changes, the ionisation balance and the spectrum are recalculated on the fly (see Section 2.3.1; Mehdipour et al., 2018), and therefore there is no need of a pre-determined ionisation grid (e.g. Di Gesu et al., 2013; Whewell et al., 2015).

The main PION model parameters to describe the plasma are the equiv-

alent column density N_H , the ionisation parameter ξ , and the outflow and turbulent velocities (v_{out} and v_{turb} , respectively). For modelling emission, I also fit the covering factor $C_{cov} = \frac{\Omega}{4\pi}$, where Ω is the solid angle. Details for each parameter are described below.

- **Column density.** N_H is the total number of hydrogen in either ionic and atomic forms and is independent of the ionisation state in the plasma. For the WA, N_H refers to the column of gas within the LOS to the X-ray source. For the NLR, emission can come from any region, therefore N_H refers to the total amount of gas in all regions that cause line emission. Overall, the total volume of emitting clouds is larger compared to the amount of gas in our LOS, so the column densities are larger in the ELR. In terms of spectral fitting, N_H determines the line strength in the spectrum - the larger the column, the stronger the absorption or emission lines.
- **Ionisation parameter.** The ionisation parameter is defined as $\xi = \frac{L_{ion}}{n_H r^2}$ (see Section 1.4.1.1) and is the measure of how ionised the material is, therefore the higher the ionisation state, the more absorption and emission lines are observed at higher energies. ξ is also related to the thermal state of the plasma (see Section 2.4.2). Changes in ξ are caused by variations in the ionising continuum and can be used to infer the distance from the SMBH (Section 1.4.1.1).
- **Kinematics.** The observed positions of the lines relative to the rest wavelengths determines the outflow velocity v_{out} of the photoionised plasma, measured within our LOS only. The turbulent velocity v_{turb} in the model is the velocity dispersion of the plasma. v_{turb} affects the line widths, determining, along with N_H , the strengths of the features and which lines are saturated.
- **Covering fraction.** Finally, the C_{cov} is the fraction of the solid angle over the full sky which is occupied by the emitting plasma, as seen by the black hole. The larger the covering fraction, the more extended

the emission component. C_{cov} , like N_H , acts as a sort of normalisation parameter, scaling the spectral features up or down. However, the important difference is that N_H is calculated from line ratios while C_{cov} is not, and therefore **SPEX** finds the best combination of the two parameters to fit the spectrum.

2.3.3 Other SPEX Models

In this Thesis, I have used a number of models to fit the X-ray spectra, which I describe here; red are absorption models, blue are emission models, and black for correcting instrumental effects.

Model	Description
HOT	Calculates the absorption of neutral Galaxy plasma (i.e. ISM) in CIE with cosmic abundances. For neutral gas, the temperature is set to 0.5 eV.
SLAB	Models the transmission through a slab of photoionised material without prior knowledge of the ionisation balance; column densities can be chosen independently.
XABS	Calculates the transmission through a slab with the column densities linked via the ionisation parameter (ξ). More advantageous than the SLAB model because it takes into account relative abundances of the ions, as well as the kinematic properties of the gas.
CIE	Calculates firstly the ionisation balance, then the X-ray spectrum, for a plasma in CIE. The temperature of the plasma refers to the electron temperature which determines the continuum shape and line emissivity.
RRC	Calculates the continuum emission corresponding to radiative recombination of electrons in the ion. It determines the emission measure (EM) for each ion of interest and the temperature of the plasma. This model does not account for line radiation and therefore only accounts for edge emission (Section 2.2.1).
KNAK	A piecewise broken power-law model that splits the spectrum into continuous segments to describe the instrumental effects and test calibration issues. In each segment, the model is multiplied by a correction factor T_N at a given wavelength (λ_N), where N is the segment number (the maximum is nine per KNAK component). The correction factor is based on normalising two separate spectra to the model.

Figure 2.11: *Left:* Plasma temperature against ionisation state (ξ ; *top*) and pressure form of the ionisation state (Ξ ; *bottom*) for NGC 7469 (taken from Mehdipour et al., 2018). Half of the WA components were thermally stable, and the other half lie on the curve with a negative gradient. *Right:* Thermal stability plot for Mrk 509 (taken from Ebrero et al., 2011). Warm absorber components (red squares) 2 and 3 had overlapping Ξ values, implying they were part of the same outflowing wind.

2.4 Plasma Processes

When modelling the X-ray spectra of AGN winds, it is assumed that photoionisation and thermal equilibria are achieved. In order for this to occur, heating and cooling processes are present such that if there is a change in temperature, equilibrium can still be reached by overcoming this change. However, if the plasma is not stable, then it may not reach equilibrium again. In this Section, I explain the heating and cooling processes and the thermal state of PIE plasma in AGN winds. These are important in order to understand and translate the ionisation and energy balance equations that are calculated in the spectral fitting using the ionising SED and PION model.

2.4.1 Heating and Cooling

The process of ionisation and recombination not only depends on a balance between free and bound electrons, but also on the heating and cooling processes. Essentially, heating means giving energy to the electrons, and cooling means taking energy away. Therefore, it is this electron energy that is responsible for the temperature in the plasma. In PION the total heating and cooling rates of different processes can be calculated. Some examples of heating and cooling processes are described in Sections 2.4.1.1 and 2.4.1.2 (information from e.g. [Kaastra et al., 2008](#)).

2.4.1.1 Heating Processes

Heating Process	Description
Photoelectrons	Electrons are removed from ions during photoionisation, heating the plasma environment through free electron collisions and increasing the kinetic energy of the gas.
Compton Scattering	Free electrons gain energy from high energy photons
Auger Electron	Similar to X-ray fluorescence, autoionisation is the process whereby a core electron is transferred to a higher energy shell, causing another outer shell electron to fall into the low energy vacancy, releasing a photon. However, in some cases, the energy in the ion is transferred to an outer electron, which is ejected from the atom - this is the Auger electron.
Compton Electron	Incident photon interacts with an ion, but is not absorbed. Instead, it scatters off and causes a bound electron to escape the atom.

2.4.1.2 Cooling Processes

Cooling Process	Description
Collisional Excitation	An atom or ion is hit by a free electron that loses energy in the collision, causing excitation.
Bremsstrahlung Emission	Free electron is decelerated as it is deflected by the Coulomb field of an ion; the lost kinetic energy is converted into radiation.
Recombination	Free electron recombines with ion. The binding energy and free electron kinetic energy are radiated away in the photon.
Inverse Comptonisation	Photon gains energy from high energy free electrons. This process happens in the hot electron corona within AGN where the UV/optical photons gain energy from the electrons, creating X-ray photons (Section 2.3.1.1)

2.4.2 Thermal Stability Curves

In order to fully understand the energy balance and thermal equilibrium of the plasma, we need to comprehend its thermal stability - i.e. is the plasma in thermal equilibrium? To do this, the pressure form of the ionisation parameter (Ξ ; Krolik et al., 1981) is used, given by

$$\Xi = \frac{F}{n_H c k T} = \frac{L}{4\pi n_H r^2 c k T} = \frac{\xi}{4\pi c k T}, \quad (2.9)$$

where $\xi = L/n_H r^2$ is the ionisation parameter, $F = L/4\pi r^2$ is the source flux, c is the speed of light, k is the Boltzmann constant, n_H is the hydrogen number density, and T is the plasma temperature. Plots of temperature versus ionisation parameter, called stability curves (Figure 2.11), are used to examine how thermally stable or unstable the wind components are (e.g. Mehdipour et al., 2015a, 2018), or if the components are in pressure equilibrium (e.g. Ebrero et al., 2011).

On the stability curve ($T - \Xi$ plot), the heating rate equals the cooling rate, while to the left, cooling dominates over heating, and to the right heating dominates over cooling. From the $T - \Xi$ plots, if the curve has a positive gradient ($dT/d\Xi > 0$), the gas is thermally stable against isobaric thermal perturbations, and is in thermal equilibrium. If, on the other hand, the gradient is negative ($dT/d\Xi < 0$), the gas is thermally unstable and not in thermal equilibrium. Therefore any changes in the heating or cooling processes imply that the gas is unable to reach an equilibrium again, at least on short time-scales. However, when the gradient is negative, cold dense gas can exist in pressure equilibrium with hot sparse gas (Krolik et al., 1981). If $dT/d\Xi = 0$, the equilibrium curve rises in T for no change in Ξ , and is best described as having marginal stability - thermal fluctuations do not grow/decay exponentially. From spectral modelling, a range of components will have differing ionisation states, such that if they coexist at the same distance, then they would share the same pressure (Krolik & Kriss, 2001).

For NGC 7469, four WA components were found, with a range in ionisation states which increased for a change in temperature (top left of Figure 2.11; Mehdipour et al., 2018). By taking the pressure form of the ionisation parameter, Mehdipour et al. (2018) found that two of these components were thermally unstable, located on a negative gradient (bottom left of Figure 2.11). For all four WA components, they were able to obtain the upper distance limits using the recombination timescale (13 years) to put limits on the number density (see Section 1.4.1.1). However, for the two thermally unstable components, they argued that the cooling time should be greater than 13 years, which allowed them to obtain upper limits on n_H and therefore lower limits on r . Hence, for the two unstable components, upper and lower distance limits were obtained.

The right side of Figure 2.11 shows the thermal stability curve for Mrk 509, where three WA components ($\log \xi = 1.06, 2.26$ and 3.15) were found by Ebrero et al. (2011), shown by the red squares. They were all thermally stable (on

positive gradients), but component 1 did not have the same ionisation pressure (Ξ) as components 2 and 3 (which do within their error bars). [Ebrero et al. \(2011\)](#) estimated the distances to be 6 kpc, 300 pc and 50 pc for components 1, 2 and 3, respectively. From this, and using [Figure 2.11](#), they concluded that component 1 was not an outflow feature, rather it was part of the ISM.

Chapter 3

X-ray Observatories

X-rays are absorbed by the Earth's atmosphere, meaning that X-ray telescopes must be sent into space in order to observe the Universe. Past X-ray observatories include Einstein (1978-1981), ROSAT (1990-1999), ASCA (1993-2001) and BeppoSax (1996-2003). Since the turn of the millennium, XMM-Newton and Chandra have allowed for high spectral and spatial resolution images and spectra, that have pushed the frontier of X-ray research. In this Chapter, I describe the XMM-Newton observatory, which provided the data used in this Thesis, before giving an overview of future missions, particularly dedicated to spectroscopy, which are under development.

3.1 XMM-Newton

The X-ray Multi-Mirror Newton (XMM-Newton) observatory was launched at the end of 1999 by the European Space Agency (ESA) - their largest scientific satellite in the Horizon 2000 programme ([Jansen et al., 2001](#)) - and is still operational today. The mission objectives were to investigate the unknowns in the cosmos, from black holes to the origin of the Universe. This 10 meter long spacecraft contains three X-ray telescopes, each with 58 nested Wolter 1 mirrors, and three European Photon Imaging Camera (EPIC) detectors positioned at the focal points. The total effective area of XMM-Newton's mirrors is about 4500 cm^2 at 1 keV (1500 cm^2 each) which is around 2.5 times larger than Chandra. The EPIC-PN camera sits at the 7.5 m focal point of

Figure 3.1: The RGS instrument on board XMM-Newton. **3.1a** depicts the X-ray path of photons interacting with the reflection gratings or passing straight through to the EPIC-MOS camera. **3.1b** displays the reflection gratings and how the X-rays reflect off the surface, to be collected by the RGS focal camera. The incident angle (α) is related to the reflection angle (β) via the dispersion relation (Eq. 3.1). **3.1c** shows the CCD bench, with side on and face on views, which intercepts the X-ray photons and allows the X-ray energy, from the position on the detector, to be determined. **3.1a** and **3.1b** were taken from den Herder et al. (2001), and **3.1c** was adapted from Brinkman et al. (1998).

one telescope receiving all of the X-ray photons; two EPIC-MOS (metal-oxide semiconductors) are situated at the focal points of the other two telescopes. Under each mirror module of the EPIC-MOS telescopes are mounted reflection grating arrays which deflect half the X-ray photons to a secondary focus where the Reflection Grating Spectrometer camera is located. The other half are detected by the EPIC-MOS cameras (see Figure 3.1).

3.1.1 Reflection Grating Spectrometer

The Reflection Grating Spectrometer (RGS; den Herder et al., 2001) is an instrument incorporating two reflection grating arrays. RGS works by having

the collimated X-ray photons in the exit of each mirror module being deflected off the grating surface (Figure 3.1b) to the RGS focal cameras situated off axis to the primary focus (as seen in Figure 3.1a). Each RGS array is made up of 182 stacked gratings. Due to the converging X-ray beam, each grating is oriented so that the X-ray incident angle α is the same for each grating in the array (Brinkman et al., 1998). Each grating is very flat and thin to reduce any degradation in the resolution, whilst minimising any obstruction (den Herder et al., 2001). After being reflected, the photons are detected by the CCDs in the RGS focal cameras (RFC). The wavelength range of RGS is 6 - 38 Å (0.3 - 2.5 keV).

The RFCs are made up of 9 back-illuminated CCDs (Figure 3.1c), that are $\sim 30\mu\text{m}$ thick (Brinkman et al., 1998). Back illumination means that these CCDs are more efficient at detecting soft X-rays because they are not absorbed when passing through the electrodes; a thin layer helps the detection of soft X-rays¹. The RFCs are kept at a temperature of -80°C to reduce dark currents, using a two stage passive radiator (den Herder et al., 2001). Each CCD is composed of an image and storage section (384×1024 pixels), with the size of each pixel being $27 \times 27\mu\text{m}^2$. The aperture of RGS is 30' in the dispersion direction (i.e. along the length of the CCD bench), covering the full field of view of the mirrors. In the cross dispersion direction, the RGS aperture is 5', equal to the width of a CCD.

The absorption of the X-ray on the CCD pixels produces an electron-hole pair, creating an accumulation of charge, proportional to the energy of the photon. Individual photons are read out separately and quickly to avoid pileup which is caused when multiple photon energies are added. The pixels get read out one line at a time through read-out registers on the sides (den Herder et al., 2001). The X-ray CCDs are able to obtain the position and energy of each photon. For optimal performance, an image is accumulated in half of the CCD, which contains the spectrum, before being transferred to the

¹See e.g. <https://www.teledyneimaging.com/>

other half for storage, doubling the speed of the readout (den Herder et al., 2001).

The position of the photon on the CCD is determined by the dispersion relation:

$$m\lambda = d(\cos\beta - \cos\alpha), \quad (3.1)$$

where λ is the X-ray wavelength, d is the groove separation, α is the incident angle, β is the deflected angle (Figure 3.1b), and m is the spectral order. As $\beta > \alpha$, $m < 0$ so the light is diffracted to the position shown in Figure 3.1a. The dispersion relation states that if the photon path difference (right hand side of Eq. 3.1) equals an integer value multiplied by the X-ray wavelength, then constructive interference occurs at the spectral order m . Therefore, at any integer m , maximum brightness occurs. This means that, given the position of the X-ray on the CCD, the photon energy or wavelength can be determined; the energy of the X-ray photon is dependent on the deflection angle β . In other words, the higher the X-ray energy, the less it is deflected and therefore hits the CCD detector on the left hand side of the RFC (Figure 3.1c), whereas a low energy photon is deflected more and hits the CCD towards the right of bench. Although the first and second order spectra overlap on the CCDs, because the different X-ray energies will hit the same position ($E_1 = 1/2E_2$ if E_2 is second order), the energy resolution of the CCDs can easily separate the spectral orders (den Herder et al., 2001). These spectral order separations are shown clearly in the ‘banana plots’ in Figure 3.2.

RGS has a resolving power of $\frac{\lambda}{\Delta\lambda} = 100 - 500$ and a peak effective area (EA) of 120 cm^2 at 15 \AA for both RGS chains combined (den Herder et al., 2001). Figure 3.3 shows the EA of RGS 1 (blue) and RGS 2 (red), for two spectral orders ($m = -1$ and -2), over the RGS wavelength range. The first order spectrum covers the full wavelength range with a large effective area, compared to the second spectral order. The broad and deep troughs at 11 \AA and around 22 \AA in Figure 3.3, for RGS 2, are due to CCD 4 failing, caused by a malfunction of an electronic component (den Herder et al., 2001). Similarly,

Figure 3.2: ‘Banana plots’ show the order separation within the CCDs for the RGS instruments, these are labelled as $m=-1$, $m=-2$ and even $m=-3$ for first, second and third orders, respectively. The bright areas in the light blue and yellow boxes show the calibration sources from $\text{AlK}\alpha$ and $\text{FK}\alpha$, respectively. The CCDs are in descending order from CCD9 on the left to CCD1 on the right.

CCD 7 on RGS 1 failed in the 10.5 - 14 Å range; this was sometime later than CCD4 on RGS2, and hence is not shown in Figure 3.3 (but this can be seen in Figure 3.2). Due to these failures, the EA in the wavelength ranges covered have dropped by a factor of two (den Herder et al., 2001).

3.1.2 EPIC Cameras

At the primary foci of XMM’s three X-ray telescopes sit the three EPIC imaging and spectroscopic cameras (Jansen et al., 2001). Each EPIC-MOS camera (Turner et al., 2001) is made up of seven CCDs, each $2.5 \times 2.5 \text{ cm}^2$ in size, arranged in a stepping pattern towards the mirror to follow the curvature of the focal plane, as shown in the top left of Figure 3.4. This gives the telescope a field of view of $30'$, with each CCD measuring the energy and position of the photons.

The EPIC-PN camera (Strüder et al., 2001) is located at the focus of the remaining telescope where it collects all the X-ray photons that pass through the mirror module unimpeded by the RGS gratings. The EPIC-PN camera

Figure 3.3: Comparisons in the effective area (EA) of the two RGS instrument chains and the spectral orders (m): RGS 1 is shown in blue and RGS 2 in red. The large trough between 20 - 24 Å for $m = -1$ and at 11 Å for the $m = -2$, is due to an electronic component in CCD 4 of RGS 2 failing. (Image taken from [den Herder et al., 2001](#)).

contains twelve CCDs, in a layout of four quadrants of three CCD subunits, each $1 \times 3 \text{ cm}^2$ in size, as shown in the top right side of Figure 3.4. *CCD0* of quadrant 1 contains the focal point of the detector ([Strüder et al., 2001](#)) and is labelled as the red box in the right side of Figure 3.4.

The bottom panel in Figure 3.4 shows the combined EA for EPIC-PN and EPIC-MOS, depending on the filter that is being used², which is larger than 1000 cm^2 between 0.5 and 8 keV for all three filters. Figure 3.5 shows the quantum efficiencies (QE) of the EPIC-PN and EPIC-MOS cameras as a function of energy. The QE is the measure of how many photons that reach the pixels are actually detected, usually as a percentage. The EPIC-PN (left side of Figure 3.5) has a high QE (above 90%) between 0.3 and 10 keV, whereas the QE drops to greater than 60% outside of this energy range. The drop at 528

²The filters reduce the contamination from optical light.

Figure 3.4: Comparing EPIC camera layouts and effective areas. *Top left:* CCD layout for EPIC-MOS, made up of seven CCDs, each $2.5 \times 2.5 \text{ cm}^2$ in size, equivalent to 10.9×10.9 arcminutes. *Top right:* CCD layout for EPIC-PN: twelve CCDs, each $1 \times 3 \text{ cm}^2$ in size, equivalent to 4.4×13.6 arcminutes, in a layout of four quadrants of three CCD subunits (denoted from Q0 to Q3). The red CCD shows the EPIC-PN focal point, located in CCD0 of quadrant 1 (Q1). In both images, the circles represent a $30'$ field of view. *Bottom:* Combined effective area for EPIC-MOS and EPIC-PN, assuming the cameras are operating with the same filters (see figure key). (Image from [ESA/Cosmos](#).)

Figure 3.5: Comparing the quantum efficiencies (QE) of the EPIC-PN (left) and EPIC-MOS (right) cameras. *Left:* The QE of the EPIC-PN camera is high over the full X-ray range. The drop at 528 eV is due to absorption from SiO_2 , and the one at 1.84 keV (the enlarged insert) is the SiK absorption edge. (Figure taken from [Strüder et al., 2001](#)). *Right:* The QE for EPIC-MOS is lower compared to EPIC-PN, peaking between 1 and 6 keV. The drops in QE at around 0.5 and 2 keV are due to the absorption edges of oxygen and silicon, respectively. (Figure taken from [Turner et al., 2001](#)).

eV in the left side of Figure 3.5 is due to absorption from SiO_2 , and at 1.84 keV (the enlarged insert) is from the SiK absorption edge ([Strüder et al., 2001](#)). EPIC-MOS (right side of Figure 3.5) has a lower QE compared to EPIC-PN - greater than 50% between 1 and 6 keV, and lower outside this range. The drops in QE at around 0.5 and 2 keV are due to the absorption edges of oxygen and silicon, respectively ([Turner et al., 2001](#)).

The low QE for MOS at low and high energies, compared to EPIC-PN (Figure 3.5), is because EPIC-PN is back illuminated, so is more efficient at detecting photons over a larger energy range. In addition, EPIC-PN has a stronger response for all X-ray energies as it receives all the photons that travel down the telescope, whereas the MOS cameras have RGS modules in the way so do not detect the full beam of X-rays. Despite this, MOS has a better energy resolution compared to PN, as shown in Figure 3.6.

Figure 3.6: EPIC camera energy resolutions as a function of energy. *Left:* EPIC-PN energy resolution for single (blue line) and double events (green line), close to the readout node. *Right:* MOS energy resolution for single events (blue line) and double events (black line). At lower energies, EPIC-MOS has a better energy resolution, but EPIC-PN has a lower FWHM at higher energies. (Images edited from [XMM-Newton Users Handbook](#).)

3.1.3 The Optical/UV Monitor Telescope

The Optical/UV Monitor Telescope (OM; [Mason et al., 2001](#)) on board XMM-Newton is a stand alone instrument, mounted on the mirror support structure, with a better sensitivity compared to ground based telescopes. The OM mirror has a diameter of 30 cm and focal length of 3.8 m. OM contains a filter wheel with eleven different apertures: six broad band filters for UV and optical wavelengths (the wavelength range of OM is 170 - 650 nm); a white light filter which transmits over the whole wavelength band; two gratings (one for UV and the other for optical) and a magnifier for high spatial resolution. The final aperture is taken up by the shutter which is used with targets so optically bright that they may endanger the instrument.

Figure 3.7: Comparing the Fe XXV He-like triplet lines of the Perseus cluster from Hitomi (red) to the simulated data of Athena X-IFU (blue; Section 3.3.1). With the large EA and spectral resolution of Athena, this iron triplet is stronger compared to Hitomi for the same 230 ks observation length. (Image taken from [D. Barret et al. 2019](#)).

3.2 Chandra

The Chandra X-ray mission was launched in July 1999 by NASA. On board Chandra, there are 4 instruments³: the advanced CCD imaging spectrometer (ACIS), which has the ability to simultaneously measure the X-ray energies as it takes images; the high resolution camera (HRC) which has a spatial resolution of half an arcsecond; and the two high resolution spectrometers. Both the HRC and ACIS cameras are at the focal point of the telescope.

The two spectrometers on board Chandra are the high energy transmission grating (HETGS; [Canizares et al., 2005](#)) and low energy transmission grating (LETGS; [Brinkman et al., 2000](#)) spectrometers. Unlike XMM-Newton, however, the photons are transmitted towards ACIS or HRC, rather than being reflected. The LETGS and HETGS gratings are mounted on the side of the

³Information taken from http://chandra.harvard.edu/about/science_instruments.html, unless stated otherwise

Figure 3.8: *Left:* The Athena silicon pore optics are made of individual petals that are assembled together to form a circle. Within each pore, the X-ray photons are scattered to the focal point; these pores act as individual tiny mirrors. Given the number of pores, the effective area is very large and the mirror is very light. (Image taken from Willingale et al., 2013). *Right:* Comparing the effective areas for each of the four high resolution spectrometers, across the X-ray energy band. XMM-Newton/RGS (green line) has a good effective area over the soft band, and Chandra (blue line) over the harder energies. Although Astro-H (also known as Hitomi) had a relatively good effective area across the whole energy range (red line), Athena (black line) will have the largest effective area over the full X-ray band of any X-ray observatory when it is eventually launched in the early 2030s. (Image taken from Barret et al., 2016).

mirrors and are moved in position behind them when required. The LETGS has a wavelength band of 5 - 175 Å (0.07 - 2.5 keV) and a resolving power of $\frac{E}{\Delta E} \sim 1000$ at 50 - 160 Å. The HETGS observes in the 0.4 - 10 keV energy band, and is made up of two types of gratings: the medium energy grating (MEG) and high energy grating (HEG); the resolving powers of the two are $\frac{E}{\Delta E} \sim 660$ at 0.83 keV and $\frac{E}{\Delta E} \sim 1000$ at 1 keV, respectively. By having the HEG and MEG gratings, optimum performance in both efficiency and resolution is achieved (Canizares et al., 2005). Together, they have an effective area of 60 cm² at 1 keV for the first spectral order, and 200 cm² at 1.5 keV with ACIS too.

Figure 3.9: *Left:* Comparing Athena’s X-IFU 50 ks simulated spectrum (red) to XMM-Newton/EPIC-PN (green) and Hitomi (blue) of a $z = 1$ galaxy group with $kT = 3$ keV and $L_X = 1 \times 10^{37}$ W. Across the full X-ray band, Athena will show strong, resolved emission lines and absorption features compared to the other two instruments. *Right:* 100 ks simulated X-IFU spectrum showing strong, narrow absorption lines from an UFO wind seen above 6 keV in the spectrum of PDS456 ($z = 0.184$). (Images taken from Barret et al. 2016 and D. Barret et al. 2019).

3.3 Future Missions

Despite these two amazing spacecraft described above, even more advanced telescopes are required. These future missions will contain more powerful telescopes and cameras for higher spectral resolution and sensitivity to delve deeper into AGN X-ray properties (amongst other phenomena in the Universe), as well to observe more distant objects (Kaastra, 2016).

The Japanese satellite, Hitomi (also known as Astro-H), was launched in February 2016, but was lost a month later. On board was the first X-ray calorimeter, from NASA, that had a resolving power of 5 eV between 0.5 - 12 keV (Hitomi Collaboration et al., 2016), resolving the Fe-K band 30 - 40 times better than a CCD (Kaastra et al., 2017). A calorimeter works by measuring the temperature change caused by a X-ray photon being absorbed by the detector: an increase in temperature is proportional to the X-ray photon energy ($\Delta T \propto E_{X-ray}$; den Herder et al., 2012). Hitomi operated at 0.05 K in order to detect these very small temperature changes. Hitomi’s only major

Table 3.1: A comparison of the specifications of the two instruments on board Athena.

Parameter	WFI	X-IFU
Energy Range	0.1 - 15 keV	0.3 - 12 keV
Resolution	< 150 eV @ 6 keV	2.5 eV @ 6 keV
Field of View	40' (diameter)	5' × 5'
Quantum Efficiency	97 % @ 10 keV	> 80 % @ 7 keV
Effective Area	1.7 m ² @ 1 keV	1.5 m ² @ 1 keV

observation was that of the Perseus cluster, which after a 230 ks exposure, was able to resolve the He-like triplet of Fe XXV between 6.5 and 6.6 keV for the first time (see red line in Figure 3.7). The follow up mission to Hitomi is XRISM (X-ray Imaging and Spectroscopy Mission), which is set to be launched around 2022. XRISM will have two instruments: *Xtend* - a soft X-ray imager (0.4 - 13 keV); and *Resolve* - a soft X-ray spectrometer (micro-calorimeter) with a resolving power less than 7 eV over 0.3 - 12 keV (Kaastra et al., 2017; Tashiro et al., 2018).

A possible next generation X-ray mission was Arcus (Smith et al., 2016), but in February 2019 it was not selected to go forward to implementation. The science goals for Arcus were to understand how black holes and accretion discs form and influence their surroundings, as well as looking at how matter cycles through galaxies (Smith et al., 2016). The Arcus mission required an EA of 500 cm² and a resolving power of $\frac{\lambda}{\Delta\lambda} \gtrsim 2500$ at the OVII bandpass (21.6 - 28 Å; Smith et al., 2016). Although the former is not as good as Athena (Arcus would fit in between Athena and Hitomi in the right side of Figure 3.8), comparatively the spectral resolution is better ($\frac{\lambda}{\Delta\lambda} \gtrsim 2000$ at 6 keV; den Herder et al., 2012). These requirements are a big improvement compared to RGS in terms of resolving power ($\frac{\lambda}{\Delta\lambda} \sim 500$ for RGS; den Herder et al., 2001) and EA (see green line in Figure 3.8, right side).

Table 3.2: Comparing the energy resolution of RGS and EPIC CCDs to the predicted values for X-IFU on board Athena.

	RGS	EPIC	X-IFU
Energy Range (keV)	0.3 - 2.5	0.15 - 15	0.2 - 12
Energy Resolution (eV)	2 - 6	70 - 180	2.5 (≤ 7.5 keV)

Figure 3.10: *Left:* Image of the X-IFU micro-calorimeter observation of a simulated cluster of galaxies. *Right:* Simulated mosaic of seven different X-IFU pointings, each 100 ks in length, for a cluster of galaxies. The colour scale is in number of photons per X-IFU pixel. (Images taken from X-IFU team, e.g. [Cucchetti et al., 2018](#)).

3.3.1 Athena

The advanced telescope for high energy astrophysics, or Athena, is set to launch in the early 2030s by ESA ([Nandra et al., 2013](#)), an X-ray telescope with a focal length of 12 m and a proposed effective area of 2 m^2 at 1 keV (e.g. [Barret et al., 2016](#)). The mirror is based on silicon pore optic (SPO) technology ([Willingale et al., 2013](#)), giving impressive performance with its large collecting area but low mass (see left side of [Figure 3.8](#)).

The right side of [Figure 3.8](#) shows the EA of Athena compared to XMM-Newton, Chandra and Hitomi (ASTRO-H), for their respective high resolution spectrometers. Athena's incredibly large EA (resulting from the SPO technology) means that it will be able to detect AGN and galaxies at even higher redshifts, and will require shorter exposure times to achieve the same measurement accuracy of closer targets as current X-ray observatories. An example

of Athena’s potential power is the simulated spectrum of the Perseus cluster (Nandra et al., 2013), shown in Figure 3.7: Hitomi in red and the Athena X-IFU simulation in blue. With the same observation time (230ks) Athena will be able to achieve greater spectral resolution and obtain stronger line signals compared to any other mission before it. This is also seen in, for example, the spectrum of a $z = 1$ galaxy group (left panel in Figure 3.9), whereby across the full X-ray band, Athena will show stronger, resolved emission lines and absorption features compared to XMM-Newton (green line) and Hitomi (red line; Barret et al., 2016). The right panel of Figure 3.9 shows that Athena X-IFU will obtain high resolution spectra at harder X-ray energies, meaning further studies of, for example, UFO winds can be done.

The science goals for Athena are to understand how black holes grow and shape the Universe and the mechanism behind large scale structures being formed from ordinary matter (Nandra et al., 2013; Barcons et al., 2015). These questions will be answered by investigating the evolution of galaxy clusters through kinematics, thermodynamics and abundances of the hot gas. In addition, Athena will allow us to study the X-rays of high redshift AGN ($z = 1 - 4$) to understand black hole and galaxy coevolution through feedback (Nandra et al., 2013), and will probe jet, accretion disk and outflowing wind physics through time resolved spectroscopy.

Athena will carry two main instruments: the wide field imager (WFI) camera and the X-ray integral field unit (X-IFU). The specifications for these instruments (Barret et al., 2013, 2016; Nandra et al., 2013; Barcons et al., 2015) are shown in Table 3.1. The X-IFU will consist of an X-ray micro-calorimeter spectrometer (XMS), cooled below 0.05 K (den Herder et al., 2012). Cooling the XMS down to such low temperatures means that a better energy resolution can be obtained as there is less noise in the measurement of each photon energy. Figure 3.10 shows simulated images from the X-IFU micro-calorimeter, while Table 3.2 compares the energy resolution between XMM-Newton and Athena X-IFU.

Figure 3.11: *Left:* Radiation absorber, coupled to a cold bath and a thermometer (the TES) to measure the temperature change due to the absorption of the photon. When a X-ray photon (purple wave) is absorbed, it increases the temperature of the TES detector. This increase in temperature is measured as the change in electronic resistance, and is proportional to the photon energy. *Right:* Increase in temperature (or resistance) over time in each TES detector. The fast rise is due to the strong link between absorber and TES, while the slow decay is caused by the weak link with the 50 mK thermal bath. (Images taken from [D’Andrea, 2019](#)).

The X-IFU calorimeter on board Athena is made up of an array of 3840 transition-edge sensors (TES), arranged in a hexagonal shape (left side of [Figure 3.10](#)). Due to the unique shape of the X-IFU detector, different observations can be put together like a mosaic, as shown in the right side of [Figure 3.10](#). Each element of the TES array is linked to an X-ray absorber, such that when an X-ray photon hits the absorber the temperature increases sharply by a few mK. TES measures this change in temperature as a change in electrical resistance, which is then read out as a current through a low noise amplifier called a SQUID (superconducting quantum interference device; [D’Andrea, 2019](#)). The schematic of the different TES components is shown in the left side of [Figure 3.11](#), whereby the signal is read out of each TES pixel individually. The right side of [Figure 3.11](#) shows the change in temperature (or resistance) over time caused by the absorption of an X-ray photon; the temperature is proportional to the X-ray energy. X-IFU is capable of obtaining detailed images (over a 5’ field of view) and high resolution spectra simultaneously, measuring both the

arrival time and photon energy ([Ravera et al., 2014](#); [D'Andrea, 2019](#)). Athena will have an energy resolution of less than 3 eV below 7 keV ([den Herder et al., 2012](#)) because it is cooled to such low temperatures ($T \sim 0.05$ K).

On the other hand, X-IFU cannot tell the difference between a photon and high energy background particle. Therefore, under each TES pixel is a second detector, called a Cryogenic AntiCoincidence (CryoAC) detector, such that if a particle is detected in both TES and CryoAC, then the double event is removed ([D'Andrea, 2019](#)).

Chapter 4

A study of the emission line regions and the warm absorber in NGC 7469

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Abstract

NGC 7469 is a bright and nearby type 1 Seyfert galaxy, with strong warm absorber (WA) spectral features that are characteristic of an outflowing wind. Interestingly, NGC 7469 has a black hole mass ten times lower than the type 1 AGN Mrk 509, but has the same bolometric luminosity. Therefore, based on this comparison, after their extensive study of the variable outflowing wind in Mrk 509, my collaborators proposed to observe NGC 7469. NGC 7469 was observed in 2015/16 with XMM-Newton, Chandra, HST, and NuSTAR, in order to study this AGN in great detail through a multiwavelength campaign. Although the initial aim was to investigate the spectral variability between each of the seven XMM-Newton observations, no such changes were observed. However, this did allow for an in depth study of the 640 ks RGS spectrum which I report in this Chapter. The aim of my work, which contributed to this multiwavelength campaign of NGC 7469, was to analyse the WA wind

and the emission line region (ELR). Through photoionisation modelling of the different plasma components, I estimated their locations with respect to the central black hole. For the first time, the distance of the ELR was determined in NGC 7469 through this work.

4.1 Introduction

NGC 7469 is a type 1 Seyfert AGN, at a redshift of $z = 0.016268$ (Springob et al., 2005) and with a SMBH of mass $M_{BH} = 1 \times 10^7 M_{\odot}$ (Peterson et al., 2014). NGC 7469 also contains a starburst ring, which surrounds the nucleus (e.g Wilson et al., 1991; Mehdipour et al., 2018). Active galaxies with both photoionised plasma and a starburst region are not uncommon. For example, NGC 1365 had been found to contain two collisionally ionised, and three photoionised emission components (Guainazzi et al., 2009; Whewell et al., 2016).

NGC 7469 has the same high bolometric luminosity as Mrk 509 with $L_{bol} = 10^{38}$ W, but has a black hole mass ten times smaller; it is one of the brightest Seyfert 1 AGN in the X-ray band ($F_{0.3-10keV} = 4 - 5 \times 10^{-15}$ W m⁻²) with an Eddington ratio of $\frac{L}{L_{Edd}} = 0.3$ (Behar et al., 2017). This type 1 AGN has been observed many times since the launch of XMM-Newton and Chandra (Chapter 3) across a range of energy bands. Table 4.1 displays the instruments, dates and exposure times of all the observations discussed and compared to in this Chapter, along with the references to the literature.

From mid 2015 to early 2016, a multiwavelength campaign of NGC 7469, using XMM-Newton, Chandra, HST, Swift, and NuSTAR, was undertaken (Behar et al., 2017). NGC 7469 was chosen for its unique features described above. As with previous observing campaigns such as those on Mrk 509 and NGC 5548, this was based on a collaboration by the RGS co-investigators, led by Kaastra et al. (2011, 2014). My work on NGC 7469 in this Chapter contributed to this multi-wavelength campaign and built upon previous research on this AGN.

The investigation of the ionised AGN outflow in NGC 7469 observed in

2015 started with the analysis of the 640 ks RGS spectrum obtained by Behar et al. (2017). They modelled the warm absorber (WA) with six different components - a range of column densities and ionisation parameters were found, categorised into three velocity phases (see top of Table 4.2). Comparatively, Mehdipour et al. (2018) found four photoionised WA components in NGC 7469 using Chandra’s HETGS instrument, in their analysis of the 2015 and archived 2002 data (bottom of Table 4.2). These also had a range of column densities and ionisation parameters, but the outflow velocities were somewhat smaller than the RGS results.

Like many other AGN, NGC 7469 showed evidence of a soft X-ray excess (see Sections 1.5 and 2.3). In Mrk 509 (Mehdipour et al., 2011) and NGC 5548 (Mehdipour et al., 2015a), a two-corona model was applied to fit the soft excess where a blackbody or a second power-law model were insufficient. This two-corona model was implemented into the analysis of NGC 7469 by Middei et al. (2018). They found that it consisted of a power law, with a high exponential cut-off ($E_{cut} = 170$ keV; see Section 2.3.1.4) produced in a hot corona ($T_{e, hot} = 45_{-12}^{+15}$ keV, $\tau = 2.6 \pm 0.9$), and the emission from a warm, optically thick corona ($\tau = 9.2 \pm 0.2$), with a temperature of $T_{e, warm} = 0.67 \pm 0.03$ keV. Compton upscattering of the hot corona explained the high energy X-ray continuum, with a photon index of $\Gamma = 1.78$, consistent with the AGN average (Ricci et al., 2011).

In an earlier observation (2004 archived data), the 164 ks RGS spectrum comprised a three component WA with ionisation phases $\log \xi = 0.8, 2.7$ and 3.6 and two velocity regimes at -580 to -720 , and -2300 km s⁻¹ (Blustin et al., 2007). The outflow velocities found in 2004 were consistent with those found with RGS in the 2015 campaign (Behar et al., 2017), while the large column densities showed similarities with HETGS data (Mehdipour et al., 2018). In the UV regime, two absorption components were found in NGC 7469 between 1999 and 2004, with kinematic properties of -570 and -1900 km s⁻¹ (Kriss et al., 2003; Scott et al., 2005), with the former component

Table 4.1: Instruments, dates, and exposure times for all NGC 7469 observations referred to in this Chapter. The data used in this Chapter comes from the 2015 XMM-Newton observation.

Instrument	Date	Exposure (ks)	Reference
FUSE	Dec 1999	38	Kriss et al. (2003)
	Dec 2002	74	Scott et al. (2005)
Chandra/ACIS	Dec 2002	150	Scott et al. (2005)
	Dec 2015	111	Mehdipour et al. (2018)
	Jan 2016	125	
XMM-Newton	Dec 2000	40	Blustin et al. (2003)
	Nov/Dec 2004	164	Blustin et al. (2007)
	June 2015	90	Behar et al. (2017)
	Nov 2015	86	
	Dec 2015	464	
HST/STIS	Dec 2002	13	Scott et al. (2005)
	June 2004	23	
HST/COS	June 2015	2	Arav et al. (2020)
	Nov 2015	2	
	Dec 2015	34	

Figure 4.1: NGC 7469 taken with HST in 2002 showing the inner starburst ring at 1 - 3'' around the extremely luminous nucleus. There is also an outer starburst ring at about 8 - 10'', but is not seen here. (Image amended and taken from [Mehdipour et al., 2018](#)).

having a velocity comparable to the high ionisation X-ray component found with Chandra in the same epoch (Scott et al., 2005). In the 2015 campaign, three UV components were found at -530 , -1420 , and -1900 km s $^{-1}$, where the distances of components 1 and 3 were found at 6 and between 60 - 150 pc, respectively (Arav et al., 2020).

In both the 2015 RGS and HETGS spectra there were multiple narrow emission features, modelled with two photoionisation components (Behar et al., 2017; Mehdipour et al., 2018). The emission components could have originated from the same outflow that produced the absorption components due to all the lines being blueshifted (Behar et al., 2017), and similarities with the ionisation states (Mehdipour et al., 2018). For the star formation region in NGC 7469 (Figure 4.1) the outflow velocity was -250 km s $^{-1}$, with a collisional gas temperature of approximately 0.35 keV (Behar et al., 2017; Mehdipour et al., 2018).

The aperture of RGS is 30' in the dispersion direction and 5' in the cross dispersion direction. NGC 7469 has an angular size of $1.38' \times 1.15'$ ¹, meaning that the whole galaxy is in the field of view (FOV) of RGS.

In this Chapter, I describe and explain the modelling processes applied to the RGS spectrum of NGC 7469, using SPEX v3.04.00. In the first part (Section 4.2), I discuss my preliminary work using XABS to model the absorption lines of the WA components, with Gaussian components to fit the emission features. The second part of the Chapter (Section 4.3) contains the bulk of my first, large research project (Grafton-Waters et al., 2020), where I used PION to model both photoionised absorption and emission plasmas, and CIE for the collisionally ionised plasma in the starburst region. The X-ray continuum was modelled using an appropriate spectral energy distribution (SED; see Section 4.3.1.1) from Mehdipour et al. (2018). To evaluate the quality of the fits, the C-statistic was used (see Section 2.1), with errors given at 1σ confidence level. Solar-abundances of Lodders et al. (2009) were assumed.

¹See <http://simbad.u-strasbg.fr/simbad/sim-id?Ident=NGC++7469>.

Table 4.2: *Top:* Warm absorber parameter values for the six components found in the RGS spectrum by Behar et al. (2017). These were the initial values I used for modelling the data. *Bottom:* Warm absorber parameter values found from the analysis of the Chandra-HETGS spectrum by Mehdipour et al. (2018).

Comp No.	N_{H} (10^{24} m^{-2})	$\log \xi$ ($\times 10^{-9} \text{ Wm}$)	v_{turb} (km s^{-1})	v_{out} (km s^{-1})	ΔC
Behar et al. (2017)					
1	0.2 ± 0.1	-0.6 ± 0.2	70 ± 10	-650 ± 50	33
2	1.0 ± 0.3	1.4 ± 0.1	70 ± 10	-650 ± 50	221
3	5.5 ± 1.0	2.0 ± 0.1	70 ± 10	-650 ± 50	1027
4	22 ± 10	2.7 ± 0.2	35 ± 20	-950^{+50}_{-100}	383
5	1.1 ± 0.3	2.0 ± 0.3	60 ± 30	-2050^{+50}_{-160}	82
6	0.1 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.2	60 ± 30	-2050^{+50}_{-160}	48
Mehdipour et al. (2018)					
1	7 ± 1	1.90 ± 0.05	42 ± 10	-540 ± 40	303
2	18 ± 2	2.40 ± 0.03	42 ± 10	-460 ± 10	584
3	17 ± 2	2.79 ± 0.03	42 ± 10	-1200 ± 100	291
4	23 ± 7	3.28 ± 0.04	42 ± 10	-370 ± 30	49

4.2 Preliminary Work

In this preliminary work, the photoionised plasma of the WA in NGC 7469 was modelled using absorption model XABS (Section 2.3.3), while the emission features were modelled with RRC and Gaussian components. To do this analysis, I modelled the 640 ks stacked RGS spectrum from 2015, plotted in Figure 4.2 using SPEX (v3.04.00 Kaastra et al., 1996) between 7 and 38 Å and binned by a factor of 2. Due to a decrease in sensitivity at shorter wavelengths, the errors become large, so the data below 7 Å were ignored. The stacked RGS spectrum consists of seven observations, each an average of 90 ks, from both RGS 1 and RGS 2.

Firstly, I modelled the continuum with a power-law (POW) component which was then redshifted ($z = 0.016268$) and absorbed by the Galaxy interstellar medium (ISM). The Galaxy absorption component (HOT) had a fixed temperature (T) and column density of 0.5 eV and $5.5 \times 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-2}$, respectively

(see Behar et al., 2017). The turbulent velocity of the H0T component was fixed at the default value of 100 km s⁻¹.

I fitted the normalisation (N) and photon index (Γ) of POW, achieving an initial C-statistic value of 7209 (for 1548 degrees of freedom; d.o.f hereafter). The resulting spectrum, with the continuum best fit (red line), is shown in Figure 4.2 with the data and model residuals plotted in the bottom panel.

4.2.1 Modelling the Warm Absorber

4.2.1.1 Six WA Components

Behar et al. (2017) found six different WA components with a range of ionisation phases (Table 4.2). Fixing the continuum parameters, I fitted six XABS components one at a time to the spectrum, in order of decreasing C-statistic (i.e. components 3, 4, 2, 5, 6, 1). Here, the column density (N_H), ionisation parameter (ξ), outflow (v_{out}) and turbulent (v_{turb}) velocities of each XABS component were fitted. The results are recorded in Table 4.3, which also displays the change in C-statistic (ΔC) showing the significance of each component to the best fit.

For components 3 ($\Delta C = 0$) and 6 ($\Delta C = 3$) the column densities are very small compared to the other four components (each with significant ΔC values). To investigate whether these components were significant, transmission models were plotted to compare the amount of X-ray flux, as a function of wavelength, being absorbed by each WA component. The results of three components (2, 3 & 6), and Galaxy absorption only, are shown in Figure 4.3.

From Figure 4.3, it is clear that the X-ray absorption by components 3 and 6 (panels A and B, respectively) is negligible. These plots are similar to that of the Galaxy absorption (Figure 4.3 C) as the N_H values are too low for other absorption lines to be visible. Comparatively, Figure 4.3 D shows the model plot of component 2 which has the largest column density and ionisation parameter, and as a result, many absorption lines are visible. This is a good comparison to components 3 and 6. Therefore from the lack of observed lines seen in Figures 4.3 A and B, components 3 and 6 were ignored, allowing for

Table 4.3: Best fit values for each of the six warm absorber components, using the initial values from Behar et al. (2017). The final C-statistic was 4559 for 1524 d.o.f.

Comp No.	N_{H} (10^{24} m^{-2})	$\log \xi$ ($\times 10^{-9} \text{ Wm}$)	v_{turb} (km s^{-1})	v_{out} (km s^{-1})	ΔC	Behar et al. Comp
1	9.91	1.9	3	-807	1747	3
2	45.60	2.8	61	-923	302	4
3	0.01	1.5	272	-1497	0	2
4	2.02	0.5	6	-2383	222	5
5	2.92	1.0	0	-1952	137	6
6	0.09	-0.4	326	-481	3	1

Figure 4.2: RGS spectrum of NGC 7469 plotted in the observed frame with the X-ray continuum overposed (red line) consisting of a power-law component that is absorbed by the Galactic material. The absorption lines at 23.5 \AA (O I) and 31.3 \AA (N I) are due to the Galaxy absorption.

Figure 4.3: Comparing absorption components 3 (A) and 6 (B) to the Galaxy absorption only (C), after fitting six XABS components. This was to investigate why components 3 and 6 have such low column densities. (D) shows the model plot of component 2, which has the highest ionisation and column density (from Table 4.3) and is rich in absorption lines.

four components to be used further in this investigation.

4.2.1.2 Four WA Components

After removing components 3 and 6, I re-fitted the remaining four WA components. This time they were fitted in order of decreasing ΔC (components 1, 2, 4, 5) from Table 4.3. These new XABS components correspond to components A - D, respectively, in Table 4.4.

Once all four WA components were fitted, I then freed all the parameters of interest (along with Γ and N from POW) and allowed the model to fit again. This improved the fit by a further $\Delta C = 201$. The best fit parameters for the four WA components are shown in Table 4.4, in addition to the power-law parameter values. The best fit was $C = 4535$ for 1532 d.o.f and is shown in the final row of Table 4.4. Although the column density (and ΔC) for component D is fairly small relative to components A, B, and C, its N_H value is still larger by an order of magnitude compared to components 3 and 6 in Section 4.2.1.1,

Table 4.4: Four warm absorber XABS components and their best fit parameter values. The power-law parameters and C-statistic are also shown.

Comp No.	N_{H} (10^{24} m^{-2})	$\log \xi$ ($\times 10^{-9} \text{ W m}$)	v_{turb} (km s^{-1})	v_{out} (km s^{-1})	ΔC
A	10.6	1.8	4	-807	1826
B	46.1	2.9	55	-942	453
C	4.2	0.7	7	-2298	189
D	0.2	1.9	13	-1822	2
	Norm ^a	Γ	C-stat	ΔC^b	d.o.f
	7.53	2.41	4535	2674	1532

^a in units of $10^{51} \text{ ph s}^{-1} \text{ keV}^{-1}$; ^b ΔC is the difference between the C-statistic values from fitting only the Galaxy model and fitting the XABS components with all parameters free.

so component D was kept in further fits.

4.2.2 Modelling the Emission Lines

After the initial WA properties had been found, I froze the POW, XABS and HOT parameters and added an RRC component (RRC). Behar et al. (2017) found five different RRC components at 32.1, 25.7, 22.8, 17.0 and 14.4 Å, corresponding to C V, C VI, N VI, O VII and O VIII, respectively. The emission measures (EM) values of the five RRC ions, and the plasma temperature, were fitted with this component, improving the fit by $\Delta C = 279$.

Finally, multiple Gaussian components (GAUS) were used to fit the remaining emission lines. For each emission feature in Figure 4.4, I fitted the wavelength, FWHM, and normalisation of a Gaussian component, one at a time. Once I had accounted for all the emission lines, I fitted all of the Gaussian parameters together, improving the fit by $\Delta C = 1360$, and achieving a new best fit of $C = 2893$ (for 1481 d.o.f).

4.2.3 Abundances and Galaxy Absorption

After accounting for the emission lines and fixing all the GAUS and RRC parameters, I went back to the abundances of the XABS components, which were currently fixed at their solar values. The WA ion abundances of interest were

Figure 4.4: Best fit model (red) fitted over the RGS spectrum (grey crosses). The blue ion names show the absorption features from the four XABS components, and the purple ones indicate the emission features from the RRC and GAUS components. O I and N I from the Galaxy absorption are also presented in orange.

Figure 4.5: Comparing the absorption model plots of the four WA components, indicating which components are absorbing which ions. To compare with the Galaxy absorption only, see Figure 4.3 (C). Table 4.6 displays the final best fit parameters of each of these components.

C, N, Ne, Mg, S and Fe (Behar et al., 2017), fitted relative to O. The abundances were only fitted in component A (the first WA component) and the abundances of the other three components were coupled to them. I assumed that the ion abundances were the same for all the components in the AGN inner regions. This improved the statistic by $\Delta C = 554$ to a C-statistic of 2339 (for 1543 d.o.f).

Finally, Behar et al. (2017) found the Galaxy absorption column density was smaller than the nominal value ($N_H = 5.5 \times 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-2}$) during their fitting. Therefore I also fitted the column density of the H0T component. Furthermore, as the Galactic turbulence was too large (100 km s^{-1}) for a neutral plasma, the v_{turb}^{Gal} parameter was also allowed to fit. Here, the C-statistic was improved by $\Delta C = 33$ to a new value of $C = 2305$.

4.2.4 Results and Discussion

Once all the components were fitted to the spectrum, I went back through and refitted each of them one at a time. Initially, I refitted the continuum and WA components together (POW, HOT, XABS), improving the fit by $\Delta C = 223$. I then fixed these parameters before fitting the RRC ($\Delta C = 17$), and the GAUS components ($\Delta C = 111$). Finally I refitted the power-law again to obtain a final best fit of $C = 1933$ for 1548 d.o.f. Due to the number of Gaussian components (16) I did not simultaneously fit all the parameters in the model together. The results for the WA and emission lines are discussed below. Figure 4.4 illustrates the final best fit model and spectrum of this preliminary work, with the two Galaxy absorption lines for O I and N I shown in orange at 23.5 and 31.4 Å, respectively.

4.2.4.1 The Warm Absorber Results

Table 4.5 shows the best fit parameters from the power-law and the Galaxy absorption, while Table 4.6 displays the best fit parameter values for the four WA components and the ion abundances. Component B in Table 4.6 has the largest column density out of the four WA components, followed by component A; they both have similar outflow velocities. The large column and warm ionisation states of components A and B are evident in Figure 4.5 (panels A and B) where the strong absorption lines are concentrated at higher energies. Comparatively, components C and D have fairly small N_H values, with component C being the least ionised. However, their outflow velocities are much larger compared to Components A and B.

Despite component D being the most ionised, the absorption lines in Figure 4.5 (D) are weaker than those of component C because the column density is too small to observe such a high- ξ plasma. This links to the observation bias where a large column density is required to see lines in a highly ionised plasma (Blustin et al., 2005). Even though component C has a smaller value of N_H it has the smallest ionisation parameter, so the absorption lines are visible in the RGS band compared to component D (Figure 4.5 (C)). The ini-

Table 4.5: Final best fit parameter values of the power-law continuum and the Galaxy absorption.

Power-law	Norm ^a 7.11 ^{+0.04} _{-0.01}	Γ 2.32 ^{+0.01} _{-0.02}
Galaxy Absorption	N_H^{Gal} (10^{24} m ⁻²) 4.92 ^{+0.06} _{-0.15}	v_{turb}^{Gal} (km s ⁻¹) 21 ⁺⁸ ₋₁₁

^a in units of 10^{51} ph s⁻¹ keV⁻¹ at 1 keV.

Table 4.6: Final best fit parameter values for the four WA components and the ion abundances, relative to oxygen.

Comp.	N_H (10^{24} m ⁻²)	$\log \xi$ ($\times 10^{-9}$ Wm)	v_{turb} (km s ⁻¹)	v_{out} (km s ⁻¹)		
A	10.4 ^{+0.5} _{-0.4}	2.28 ^{+0.07} _{-0.09}	28 ⁺¹² ₋₆	-812 ⁺⁶⁶ ₋₃₀		
B	68.6 ^{+26.6} _{-28.2}	2.92 ^{+0.10} _{-0.07}	26 ⁺¹⁰ ₋₁₄	-858 ⁺⁴⁷ ₋₂₄		
C	4.4 ^{+0.3} _{-1.1}	1.00 \pm 0.04	< 2	-2107 ⁺¹⁵ ₋₆₉		
D	5.9 ^{+3.8} _{-4.3}	3.06 ^{+0.23} _{-0.26}	< 84	-2046 ⁺⁷² ₋₁₂₁		
Ionic Abundances						
	C	N	Ne	Mg	S	Fe
	1.5 \pm 1.0	2.6 ^{+1.0} _{-0.2}	0.8 ^{+0.6} _{-0.2}	0.5 ^{+0.7} _{-0.2}	1.8 ^{+1.2} _{-0.4}	0.8 ^{+0.5} _{-0.1}

tial fit for component D (Table 4.4) contributes very little to changing the C-statistic ($\Delta C = 2$), which shows that adding this component did not significantly improve the model. Furthermore, from Figure 4.5 (D), it does not look like component D fits any new lines that components A - C have not already accounted for. Therefore, I conclude that component D is not part of the WA wind.

4.2.4.2 The Emission Line Region Results

Table 4.7 shows the best fit parameter values for the RRC component. The temperature to produce the RRC features was 12.7 eV, consistent with photoionised plasma. The strongest RRC feature was C V as shown by its EM value.

Table 4.8 displays the emitted wavelength, normalisation, line energy and

Table 4.7: Final best fit RRC values.

Ion	Wavelength (Å)	Emission Measure (10^{64} m^{-3})
C V	32.1	$2.6_{-1.0}^{+0.7} \times 10^4$
C VI	25.7	< 5639
N VI	22.8	< 1919
O VII	17.0	< 632
CVIII	14.4	< 201
Temp (eV)		12.7 ± 0.4

FWHM of the 16 emission lines. The outflow velocities v_{out} for each ion were calculated using the Doppler shift between the emitted wavelength $\lambda_{emitted}$ (fitted) in the reference frame of NGC 7469, and the rest wavelength λ_{rest} , given by

$$\frac{v_{out}}{c} = \frac{\lambda_{emitted} - \lambda_{rest}}{\lambda_{rest}}, \quad (4.1)$$

where c is the speed of light. From Table 4.8, it is clear that not all of the velocities are blue-shifted towards us. Similar to NGC 5548 (Whewell et al., 2015), the O VII triplet lines all have different outflow velocities, with the resonance and intercombination lines being almost negligible. The N VI triplet lines, on the other hand, appear to all be redshifted, with the forbidden line having a very large upper uncertainty. Other emission features with very large uncertainties include the Fe XVII, S XIV and C VI Ly α lines, with the latter having a low velocity. These large outflow velocity errors could be due to uncertainties in the broadness (FWHM) or the normalisation of the lines too. The remaining lines in Table 4.8 have blueshifted velocities.

In some places of Figure 4.4, the model does not completely fit the spectrum. For example, at around 20.8 Å (observed frame), there seems to be an emission and absorption feature at almost the same wavelength in the spectrum. This is due to CCD gaps and residuals from combining the spectra (Behar et al., 2017), but does not affect the overall fitting. At 32.6 and 33.4 Å there are some features which were not explained by Behar et al. (2017), but here I did fit one Gaussian component to the emission line at 32.6 Å and

Table 4.8: Emission lines with their respective GAUSS best fit parameter values. The ion outflow velocities (v_{out}) were calculated using the Doppler shift (Eq. 4.1) between the emitted wavelength in the reference frame of NGC 7469 and rest wavelengths taken from the SPEX line list.

Gaus No.	$\lambda_{Emitted}^a$ (Å)	λ_{Rest}^b (Å)	Norm ($\times 10^{49}$ ph s $^{-1}$)	E (keV)	FWHM (Å)	Ion Name	v_{out} (km s $^{-1}$)
1	9.75 ± 0.04	9.81	$0.5^{+4.0}_{-0.1}$	1.27	< 1.02	Fe XXI	-1835 ± 1230
2	13.69 ± 0.02	13.7	0.7 ± 0.1	0.91	< 0.02	Ne IX (f)	-219 ± 438
3	13.93 ± 0.02	14.0	0.5 ± 0.2	0.89	0.08 ± 0.05	Fe XXI	-1287 ± 431
4	$15.38^{+0.04}_{-0.44}$	15.5	$1.2^{+1.2}_{-0.3}$	0.81	< 1.16	Fe XVII	-1552^{+780}_{-8600}
5	$17.09^{+0.03}_{-0.04}$	17.1	$0.8^{+0.4}_{-0.3}$	0.73	< 0.47	Fe XVII	-175^{+527}_{-702}
6	18.97 ± 0.02	19.0	$0.9^{+0.3}_{-0.1}$	0.65	< 0.10	O VIII Ly α	-474 ± 316
7	21.60 ± 0.02	21.6	1.1 ± 0.7	0.57	< 1.11	O VII (r)	$+27 \pm 278$
9	$21.81^{+0.05}_{-0.04}$	21.8	$2.6^{+1.4}_{-0.9}$	0.57	$0.21^{+0.16}_{-0.12}$	O VII (i)	$+41^{+688}_{-580}$
9	22.06 ± 0.01	22.1	$3.2^{+0.6}_{-0.2}$	0.56	< 0.07	O VII (f)	-557 ± 136
10	$23.20^{+0.14}_{-0.04}$	23.05	$4.6^{+2.0}_{-0.3}$	0.53	$0.57^{+0.41}_{-0.06}$	S XIV	$+1952^{+1810}_{-517}$
11	28.98 ± 0.08	28.8	$3.2^{+2.7}_{-0.3}$	0.43	$0.63^{+0.57}_{-0.13}$	N VI (r)	$+1875 \pm 828$
12	$29.49^{+0.04}_{-0.06}$	29.1	$0.9^{+0.7}_{-0.2}$	0.42	< 1.012	N VI (i)	$+4021^{+407}_{-610}$
13	$29.68^{+3.24}_{-0.02}$	29.5	$1.1^{+2.0}_{-0.2}$	0.42	$0.18^{+0.11}_{-0.08}$	N VI (f)	$+1524^{+11000}_{-202}$
14	$32.52^{+0.24}_{-0.12}$	32.6	$22.3^{+7.0}_{-4.0}$	0.38	$1.62^{+0.59}_{-0.12}$	S XIV	-276^{+2214}_{-1167}
15	$33.74^{+0.13}_{-0.07}$	33.7	$2.8^{+4.3}_{-2.1}$	0.37	< 0.58	C VI Ly α	$+89^{+1156}_{-622}$
16	35.24 ± 0.02	35.6	$2.5^{+0.8}_{-1.8}$	0.35	$0.12^{+0.05}_{-0.12}$	S XII	-3117 ± 170

^a Wavelength emitted in NGC 7469 reference frame.

^b Wavelength taken from the SPEX line list

(https://personal.sron.nl/~kaastra/leiden2020/line_new.pdf).

identified it as S XIV. However, the large errors in the velocity suggest there is an uncertainty with this feature, hence why Behar et al. (2017) could not fit it.

4.2.4.3 Summary

In this preliminary work, I have fitted a model to the RGS spectrum of NGC 7469, containing a power-law X-ray continuum, four XABS components, 16 Gaussian lines, five RRC ions, and absorption from our Galaxy. Four WA components were initially fitted and showed that the WA is multi-phased.

Components A and B have similar outflow velocities, but the column densities and ionisation parameters vary between the two. Components C and D both have similar column densities, but the ionisation parameter in Component D is too large to be able to observe any of the lines with its column density. Given such a small improvement in the fit statistic ($\Delta C = 2$) as well, I concluded that component D is not part of the WA. The emission lines have a mixture of blueshifted and redshifted velocities, but some of the measured wavelengths have large errors (Table 4.8), implying that there are uncertainties associated with the identification of some of these lines. The temperature ($T = 12.7$ eV) from the RRC model is consistent with a PIE plasma.

Following on from this preliminary work, I went on to use the sophisticated photoionisation model, PION, to account for both the warm absorber and emission line regions in NGC 7469, self-consistently. I also accounted for the starburst region using the CIE model in SPEX.

4.3 Modelling NGC 7469 using PION

This work builds upon the preliminary analyses of the WA and emission line region (ELR) within the nucleus of NGC 7469, reported in the previous Section (4.2). Here, I use a physically motivated model to study the photoionised wind that produces the observed features seen in the 640 ks RGS spectrum, as opposed to the phenomenological model that I fitted before. In this work, I use the SED continuum model from Mehdipour et al. (2018) (Section 4.3.1.1), which is fed through the advanced fitting software PION, to simultaneously fit the continuum and the ionising radiation to calculate both the spectrum and ionisation balance of the plasma, self-consistently (see Section 2.3.2 for details; Mehdipour et al., 2016b). Because of this, the modelling approach carried out in this Chapter is also a major improvement on the phenomenological model applied to the same RGS spectrum by Behar et al. (2017).

In PION, the column density (N_H) and ionisation parameter (ξ) were fitted, as were the turbulent and outflow velocities (v_{turb} and v_{out} , respectively), for both absorption and emission. In order to differentiate between absorption or emission, PION uses different covering factors: for absorption, the absorption covering factor (f_{cov}) was set at unity and fixed; for emission, the emission covering factor ($C_{cov} = \Omega/4\pi$, where Ω is the solid angle) was free and able to vary between 0 and 1 ($f_{cov} = 0$ for emission).

4.3.1 Spectral Modelling

The RGS spectrum is rich in narrow absorption and emission lines. After modelling the underlying optical-UV-X-ray continuum (SED) and Galaxy absorption (Sections 4.3.1.1 and 4.3.1.2), the spectral features were modelled (Sections 4.3.1.3 and 4.3.1.4). I also included a CIE component to model the collisionally ionised plasma produced in the starburst region. The ELR in Seyfert 1 AGN have been investigated in great detail in NGC 5548 (Whewell et al., 2015; Mao et al., 2018) and more recently in NGC 3783 (Mao et al., 2019). Later in this Chapter, I will measure, for the first time, the location of the ELR with respect to the central black hole.

Figure 4.6: The spectral energy distribution of NGC 7469 using the data from [Mehdipour et al. \(2018\)](#) and [Middei et al. \(2018\)](#). The red line shows the broad-band continuum (optical-UV-X-ray) made up of three components. The blue line illustrates the power-law with a photon index $\Gamma = 1.78$ and a high energy cut off of 170 keV ([Middei et al., 2018](#)). The black dashed line is the Comptonisation component that models the soft excess and UV/optical disk photons. The green dotted line shows the reflection component that produces the Fe $K\alpha$ line due to the reflection of X-rays off neutral material surrounding the SMBH. The reflection component is on the higher-energy side of the SED and is not part of the intrinsic continuum. Instead, it is caused by the high energy X-rays from the corona interacting with the surrounding medium (e.g. accretion disk or torus). If the column density is large enough, the X-rays with sufficient energy ($E > 10$ keV) can inverse-Compton scatter off free electrons which results in a reflected spectrum.

4.3.1.1 The Spectral Energy Distribution

The broad band ionising continuum (optical-UV-X-ray), which I have adopted to fit the RGS spectrum, was modelled using the SED derived in [Mehdipour et al. \(2018\)](#), and is displayed in Figure 4.6. Table 4.9 displays the parameter values used in the modelling. The hard X-ray continuum was modelled by a power-law (POW), produced when the photons from the disk are Compton up-scattered in the hot electron corona. A high energy cut-off of $E_{cut} = 170_{-40}^{+60}$ keV ([Middei et al., 2018](#)) was applied to the power law. A warm optically thick medium was found to best fit the soft X-ray excess and explain the UV and optical photons from the disk ([Middei et al., 2018](#)), so I modelled this with a warm Comptonisation component (COMT; [Titarchuk, 1994](#)), as described by [Mehdipour et al. \(2015a, 2018\)](#). Finally, the FeK α line and Compton hump were modelled with a reflection component (REFL; [Magdziarz & Zdziarski, 1995](#)). The reflection component is on the higher-energy side of the SED in Figure 4.6 and is not part of the intrinsic continuum. Instead, it is caused by the high energy X-rays from the corona interacting with the surrounding medium (e.g. accretion disk or torus). If the column density is large enough, the X-rays with sufficient energy ($E > 10$ keV) can inverse-Compton scatter off free electrons and hence we see a reflected spectrum at higher energies. Although the REFL and high energy cut-off are outside the RGS energy range, PION uses the full broad band SED ionising continuum to achieve a more accurate photoionisation result ([Mehdipour et al., 2016b](#)).

The parameters for these three SED components were initially set to the values found by [Mehdipour et al. \(2018\)](#) (see Table 4.9). However, the normalisation (N_{pow}) and photon index (Γ) of POW, and the normalisation (N_{comt}) and electron temperature (T_e) of COMT were let free to fit to the RGS spectrum. As the RGS spectrum does not contain any data from the optical/UV wavebands, the disk temperature (T) was fixed to the value of 1.4 eV, found by [Mehdipour et al. \(2018\)](#). The initial C-statistic, without any WA and soft X-ray emission line models, was $C = 5212$ (for 1546 d.o.f).

Table 4.9: SED model parameter values for NGC 7469 derived by [Mehdipour et al. \(2018\)](#). The SED is displayed in [Figure 4.6](#).

Model Component	Parameter	Value
POW	N_{pow}^a	7.1
	Γ	1.9
COMT	N_{comt}^b	5.7
	T_s (eV)	1.4 (f)
	T_e (keV)	0.14
	τ	21 (f)
REFL	N_{refl}^a	10 (f)
	Γ	1.9 (c)
	s	0.3 (f)
	E_{cut} (keV) ^c	170 (f)

^a $\times 10^{51}$ ph s⁻¹ keV⁻¹ at 1 keV; ^b $\times 10^{55}$ ph s⁻¹ keV⁻¹;

^c high energy cutoff also applied to the power-law.

SED values with (f) are fixed throughout the modelling;

(c) means the parameter is coupled.

4.3.1.2 Galaxy Absorption

The absorption through the Galaxy was taken into account throughout the spectral fitting using the HOT component in SPEX. Initially I set the Galactic column density to $N_H^{Gal} = 5.5 \times 10^{24}$ m⁻² ([Wakker, 2006](#); [Wakker et al., 2011](#)), which I fitted at the same time as the WA components. A best fit Galaxy column density $N_H^{Gal} = 3.66_{-0.02}^{+0.03} \times 10^{24}$ m⁻² was achieved, which is lower compared to the initial value; this was also found by [Behar et al. \(2017\)](#), with $N_H^{Gal} = 3.4 \times 10^{24}$ m⁻². The temperature for neutral gas was fixed at $T_{Gal} = 0.5$ eV and the turbulent velocity was fixed at $v_{turb}^{Gal} = 5.64 \pm 0.96$ km s⁻¹ (see [Appendix C](#) for details of obtaining this velocity value; no significant ΔC is achieved for a zero-turbulent velocity). The C-statistic, after fitting the SED with the addition of Galaxy absorption, was $C = 3631$ (for 1545 d.o.f).

4.3.1.3 Absorption

The WA components were applied one at a time to the spectrum, with initial values from [Table 4.2](#), in order of decreasing contribution to ΔC . I found that

three PION components fitted the absorption features in the RGS spectrum, with each fit giving a significant change in the C-statistic value (see Table 4.11). The C-statistic after all three WA components were initially fitted was $C = 2780$ (for 1538 d.o.f). A fourth component had no statistical significance on the best fit and had a ξ value similar to component 3; a fourth WA component was therefore not included. In the spectral fitting, I required three WA components to describe the absorption features in the RGS spectrum, instead of the six found by Behar et al. (2017). The model discrepancies between these two studies are not beyond what is expected from different analysis codes (see Figure 2.2; Mehdipour et al., 2016b); Behar et al. (2017) used the photoionised plasma code XSTAR in their XSPEC fits.

The ionisation parameters of all three WA components were constrained to fit between $0 \leq \log \xi \leq 3$, to reduce the possibility that SPEX tries to find a best fit which cannot be constrained by the RGS operational range. From fitting these components, I found that WA component 2 always shifted towards the upper limit of the set range. Therefore, I fixed the ionisation parameter value at $\log \xi = 3$ for component 2, which also reduced the number of free parameters.

Before fitting all the emission components, I freed all the parameters of interest (the three WA components, the column density for neutral Galactic absorption (N_H^{Gal}) and the four SED parameters - N_{pow} , Γ , N_{comt} and T_e) and fitted them all together. This improved the C-statistic further ($\Delta C = 43$) to a new best fit value of $C = 2737$ for 1533 d.o.f.

4.3.1.4 Emission

The emission features in the RGS spectrum were fitted in much the same way as the WA components, with the addition of the emission covering factor (C_{cov}) being a free parameter. Two narrow emission components (EM1 and EM2) were fitted one at a time, improving the C-statistic by $\Delta C_{EM1} = 230$ and $\Delta C_{EM2} = 34$ ($C = 2473$ for 1541 d.o.f). A third narrow component did not have an effect on the statistical best fit.

After fitting the two narrow emission components together, I detected an excess fit residual in the O VII triplet at 22 Å, which required an additional component. A broad emission component was found to significantly improve the fit to the spectra of NGC 5548 (Mao et al., 2018) and NGC 3783 (Mao et al., 2019). Therefore, a third PION emission component (EM3), coupled with a Gaussian velocity broadening component VGAU (represented by the parameter v_b), was also fitted. This VGAU component broadens the emission lines from the motion of the plasma region around the central black hole, rather than from the motion of the ions internally. (The internal turbulent velocity was fixed at the default value of $v_{turb} = 100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$.) The broad component improved the fit by $\Delta C = 23$, reducing the residuals at 22 Å ($C = 2450$ for 1545 d.o.f).

4.3.1.5 Nuclear Starburst Ring

Further to the photoionised emission, emission from collisionally ionised equilibrium (CIE) plasma, within the starburst region, was modelled using the CIE component in SPEX. The electron temperature (T_e), emission measure (EM) and outflow velocity (v_{out}) were the fitted parameters. The CIE component improved the global C-statistic by $\Delta C = 9$. This does not seem very significant, compared to the other components, but without this component, the starburst emission lines of Fe XVII at 15.3 and 17.4 Å (Behar et al., 2017) would not be accounted for; hence, I included this component in the best fit nevertheless.

4.3.1.6 Abundances

After refitting all the PION emission and CIE components together (improving the statistical fit only by $\Delta C = 11$), I let the abundances of C, N, Ne, Mg, S and Fe free in WA component 1. The abundances were calculated with respect to oxygen as no hydrogen lines were present in the RGS spectrum (Behar et al., 2017). The abundances of the remaining absorption and emission components (both PION and CIE) were coupled to WA component 1. This is because I assumed that the chemical enrichment was the same throughout the AGN nucleus and starburst region. I fitted the abundances in WA component 1 and

the C-statistic decreased by $\Delta C = 54$ ($C = 2376$ for 1544 d.o.f). The best fit values are displayed in Table 4.11 and are consistent with the values from Behar et al. (2017), within errors, except the abundance of S is three times larger in this analysis.

Behar et al. (2017) found the abundances of C, N, Ne and Fe to be super-solar, whereas Mg and S were sub-solar. In Table 4.11, the abundances of C, Ne and S are all super-solar, while Mg is sub-solar (with large errors), and N and Fe are consistent with solar within their uncertainties. Similarly, in the preliminary study (Table 4.6) the abundances of N and S were super-solar, but the other abundances were consistent with solar values, within uncertainties. Significant over- or under-abundances were explained when multiple photoionisation components with varying densities were used (see e.g Bauer et al., 2015, and references within), like in this case. Therefore, the reason why the majority of abundances are consistent with solar values in the preliminary work (Table 4.6) is likely to be that only three components were coupled together, while in this more advanced model six PION components have their abundances coupled to the same component.

Comparatively, Blustin et al. (2007) found sub/super-solar abundances in the 2007 observation of NGC 7469 with XMM-Newton/RGS. However, when taking into account the uncertainties of C, N, O, and Mg, the values were consistent with solar. Si and S, on the other hand, had extremely large values (11_{-8}^{+9} and 6_{-5}^{+10} , respectively), while Ne had a value of 3_{-1}^{+2} . Alternatively, Mehdipour et al. (2018) fixed the abundances to their solar values for the 2015/16 Chandra data as fitting them had no overall effect on the best fit model.

Therefore, from the comparison of the abundances in Tables 4.6 and 4.11, and the findings from Blustin et al. (2007) and Behar et al. (2017) (using RGS data), and Mehdipour et al. (2018) (using Chandra data), one explanation for the abundance discrepancy could be related to the FOV and spatial resolution of these two observatories. There is no way of separating AGN and host

Table 4.10: Final best fit parameter values for the observed continuum (POW and COMT) and the Galaxy absorption (HOT) components.

Component	Parameter	Value
POW	N_{pow}^a	6.70 ± 0.01
	Γ	2.07 ± 0.01
COMT	N_{comt}^b	$8.81_{-0.35}^{+0.12}$
	T_e (keV)	0.118 ± 0.001
HOT	$N_H^{Gal\ c}$	$3.66_{-0.02}^{+0.03}$
	$v_{turb}^{Gal\ d}$ (km s ⁻¹)	5.64 ± 0.96

$a \times 10^{51}$ photons s⁻¹ keV⁻¹ at 1 keV; $b \times 10^{57}$ photons s⁻¹ keV⁻¹; $c \times 10^{24}$ m⁻²; d fixed, see Appendix C for details.

galaxy in the RGS spectra, unlike with EPIC-PN/MOS and with Chandra. As a result of this, all the X-rays from the AGN and host galaxy of NGC 7469 are detected by RGS. This means that the spectra also contain emission and absorption lines from plasmas in the extended regions of the galaxy, not just from the outflowing wind. However, the spectrum of a small section of the galaxy, in this case the AGN, can be extracted using Chandra. Therefore, if, together with the AGN, the plasma clouds within the host galaxy, such as the star forming regions, are being observed in RGS, then the abundances are likely to be very different compared to solar. As a result of this, it is likely that the non-solar abundances of the outflowing wind from this RGS study are caused by contamination from other regions within the host galaxy, rather than an enrichment process from AGN activity and accretion.

4.3.2 Spectral Fitting Results

The RGS spectrum and best fit model are displayed in Figures 4.7 and 4.8, with significant absorption and emission features labelled with their respective ions; all wavelengths are in the observed reference frame. Table 4.10 displays the best fit parameter values from the POW and COMT components, in addition to the parameters of the neutral HOT component.

The final model best fit C-statistic value is a fairly acceptable 2252 for 1512 d.o.f, obtained by fitting all parameters together. However, the expected C-

Figure 4.7: RGS spectrum of NGC 7469 in the observed frame with the best fit model (red line) over plotted. The significant absorption and emission features are labelled with their corresponding ions (blue and purple, respectively). Galactic absorption features are indicated in orange.

Figure 4.8: Figure 4.7 Continued.

statistic, calculated by SPEX (Kaastra, 2017) is 1551 ± 56 . The large difference could be due to the unaccounted features in the spectrum (Figure 4.8). For example, the absorption feature at 28.5 \AA and emission features at 32.6 and 33.4 \AA are not fitted with the current best fit model; Behar et al. (2017) found no physical explanation for these emission lines in terms of ionic species.

4.3.2.1 The Photoionised Wind

The best fit WA parameters and ionic abundances of the six ions are displayed in Table 4.11. The total equivalent column density of the WA is

Table 4.11: Best fit parameter values for the three warm absorber components. The turbulent velocity of component 2 is coupled to that of component 1 as they had the same values when they were both set free. The ΔC values indicate the change in statistical fits produced by each component when introduced to the model. Also shown are the ionic abundances of the photoionised and collisionally ionised plasmas throughout the nucleus of NGC 7469, fitted to WA component 1 (see Section 4.3.1.6).

Absorption Comp.	N_H (10^{24} m^{-2})	$\log \xi$ (10^{-9} Wm)	v_{turb} (km s^{-1})	v_{out} (km s^{-1})	ΔC
1	$10.0^{+0.5}_{-0.4}$	2.32 ± 0.01	35 ± 2	-630 ± 20	592
2	52.0 ± 2.2	3.00 (f)	- ^a	-910^{+50}_{-30}	105
3	2.3 ± 0.1	1.57 ± 0.04	11 ± 3	-1960 ± 20	155
Abundances ^b					
C	N	Ne	Mg	S	Fe
$2.03^{+0.17}_{-0.08}$	$1.11^{+0.20}_{-0.15}$	2.04 ± 0.20	$0.56^{+0.41}_{-0.13}$	2.80 ± 0.40	1.01 ± 0.04

^a Coupled to WA component 1. ^b Abundances relative to oxygen.

The $\log \xi$ parameter of WA component 2 is followed by a (f) because this value is fixed.

$N_H^{Tot} = 64 \times 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-2}$, consistent with the HETGS results (Mehdipour et al., 2018), but approximately two times larger than the total equivalent hydrogen column density found by Behar et al. (2017). These WA components have three ionisation phases of $\log \xi = 1.6, 2.3$ and 3.0 , and three kinematic phases, consistent with the X-ray kinematics from Table 4.2 (Behar et al., 2017) and UV velocities (Kriss et al., 2003; Scott et al., 2005; Arav et al., 2020). Figure 4.9 illustrates the transmission models for each absorption component comparing the strengths of the X-ray absorption lines produced at each ionisation state of the WA. The Galactic absorption model (orange line) shows how much of the continuum is absorbed by the Galaxy, especially at longer wavelengths.

Component 1 ($\log \xi = 2.32$) is responsible for the H-like and He-like ions of Ne IX, Ne X and O VII, as well as the absorption lines of C V - C VI, S XII - S XV and F XIII - F XVIII. Component 2 ($\log \xi = 3.00$) accounts for the H-like and He-like ions of Mg XI, Mg XII, Ne IX and Ne X, along with the F XV - F XVIII absorption lines. Component 3 is the least ionised component

Table 4.12: Best fit parameters, including the emission measure (EM), for the three emission components. The ΔC values indicate the change in C-stat when each component was introduced to the model.

Emission Comp.	N_H (1)	$\log \xi$ (2)	v_{turb} (3)	v_{out} (3)	C_{cov} (4)	EM (5)	ΔC
EM1	641 ± 50	$0.35^{+0.09}_{-0.01}$	50^{+140}_{-50}	-660^{+110}_{-20}	2.1 ± 0.2	13	230
EM2	42^{+7}_{-6}	1.55 ± 0.08	50^{+180}_{-30}	0 (f) ^a	21 ± 3	1	34
EM3	787^{+130}_{-110}	$0.18^{+0.01}_{-0.07}$	^b 1360^{+340}_{-270}	-4460^{+200}_{-110}	1.4 ± 0.2	15	23

The parameter units are: (1) 10^{25} m^{-2} ; (2) 10^{-9} W m ; (3) km s^{-1} ; (4) $\Omega/4\pi$ (10^{-4}); (5) 10^{70} m^{-3} . ^a(f) shows that this value is fixed; ^bBroadening velocity (v_b) from the VGAU component which is coupled to the broad PION component.

with $\log \xi = 1.57$, but has the fastest outflow velocity $v_{out} = -1960 \pm 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and is responsible for the H-like and He-like C VI and O VII. In addition, component 3 produces the unresolved transition array (UTA; Behar et al., 2001) between 16 and 17 Å, which can be seen in the bottom panel of Figure 4.9.

The H- and He-like absorption lines from C VI, N VII, O VII, O VIII, Ne IX and Ne X are fitted by all three absorption components. Components 1 and 2, with different outflow velocities, fit the lower energy part of the absorption lines, and due to its high blueshift velocity, component 3 either produces a second trough in the absorption lines on the high energy side, or broadens the line. This can be seen in the absorption profile of the C VI Ly α line, in top panel of Figure 4.10, where each trough (or peak) signifies at what velocity the absorption (or emission) line is produced, corresponding to a certain component. Due to the resolution of the RGS spectrum at lower energies it is clear that the C VI Ly α absorption line contains two troughs from the three different WA components.

4.3.2.2 Emission Line Region

The emission lines in the spectrum are described by three PION components, with the best fit parameter values shown in Table 4.12. The first emission component (EM1) fits the O VII forbidden line at 22.4 Å, the most dominant

Figure 4.9: PION absorption transmission models for each warm absorber component (1 - 3 from top to bottom). These plots help demonstrate what the model looks like with the parameter values from Table 4.11: large ξ means absorption at higher energies; large N_H means stronger absorption lines. The Galaxy absorption transmission is overlaid in orange for a comparison which affects the continuum emission, especially at longer wavelengths, causing the transmission to decrease. As a consequence of the RGS resolution, weak narrow lines are not evident in Figures 4.7 and 4.8 due to the low equivalent width, but can be seen in these models.

Figure 4.10: Velocity profile plots of the C VI Ly α line (top panel) and the O VII (f) line (bottom panel). Red line is the best fit model fitted to the data (black crosses). *Top:* The blue dashed lines indicate the velocities of the three WA components ($v_{out} = -631, -912$ and -1964 km s⁻¹) and their contributions to the absorption. The C VI Ly α emission line is produced at 0 km s⁻¹, which corresponds to EM2 (purple dashed line). *Bottom:* The O VII forbidden line is produced by EM1 and EM2 at -657 and 0 km s⁻¹, respectively, as illustrated by the purple dashed lines showing the outflow velocities of the emission components. EM3 falls at the position of the intercombination line because the forbidden line is blueshifted to higher energies ($v_{out} = 4460$ km s⁻¹; Table 4.12). I note that the widths of the emission lines in these two panels are determined fully by the resolution of the RGS instrument ($FWHM \sim 600$ km s⁻¹ at 34 Å and $FWHM \sim 800$ km s⁻¹ at 22 Å, for top and bottom panels respectively), and not by the turbulent velocities (v_{turb}) in Table 4.12.

line in the RGS spectrum. EM1 also produces the N VI forbidden line (30.0 Å) and the C VI Ly α line (34.4 Å), in addition to the RRCs of C V (32.1 Å), C VI (25.7 Å), N VI (22.8 Å), and O VII (17.0 Å), with C V being the strongest RRC feature in the spectrum.

The emission features produced by the second narrow emission component (EM2) are the C VI Ly α and O VIII Ly α (19.4 Å) lines, along with the O VII and Ne IX (13.8 Å) triplet lines. EM2 gives rise weakly to the Ne X (12.3 Å) and N VII Ly α (25.2 Å) lines and the O VII (17 Å), O VIII (14.4 Å), and C VI RRCs. I find that these emission features are emitted by EM2 at rest (this was also found by [Mehdipour et al., 2018](#)).

The third, broad, emission component (EM3) appears only to produce blueshifted forbidden lines of the O VII and N VI triplets, however the latter is not very evident in the spectrum. EM3 also produces a blueshifted C V RRC. Due to the high blueshift velocity of the broad component, $v_{out} = -4460_{-110}^{+200}$ km s $^{-1}$, the peak of the O VII forbidden line (in the observed frame), is shifted towards shorter wavelengths, as visible in the bottom panel of Figure 4.10 (see also the purple line in Figure 4.11). This is discussed further in Sections 4.3.3.2 and 4.3.3.3.

The bottom panel of Figure 4.10 shows the velocity profile of the O VII forbidden line with the emission components indicated by the purple dashed lines. The top panel shows the emission feature of the C VI Ly α , produced at zero km s $^{-1}$, with the position of the absorption components illustrated by the blue dashed lines.

Finally, for each ELR component, I calculated the emission measure (EM) to determine, from the contribution of each component, the line luminosities. The EM is given by

$$EM = \frac{n_e}{n_H} 4\pi C_{cov} \frac{L_{ion} N_H}{\xi} \quad (4.2)$$

(see e.g. [Mao et al., 2018](#); [Psaradaki et al., 2018](#)), where n_H and n_e are the hydrogen and electron number densities, respectively, and the other parameters are calculated from the spectral modelling (Table 4.12). The calculated EM

Table 4.13: Collisionally ionised plasma properties from the nuclear starburst region of NGC 7469.

EM ($\times 10^{69} \text{ m}^{-3}$)	T (keV)	v_{out} (km s^{-1})	ΔC
4.0 ± 0.3	0.32 ± 0.02	-280^{+80}_{-70}	9

values, assuming $n_e = 1.2n_H$ for fully ionised plasma, are displayed in Table 4.12.

4.3.2.3 Nuclear Starburst Ring

The starburst region in NGC 7469 is found to have a CIE plasma temperature of 0.32 ± 0.02 keV, with an outflow velocity of -280^{+80}_{-70} km s^{-1} (Table 4.13), consistent with previous results in this campaign (Behar et al., 2017; Mehdipour et al., 2018). In addition to the Fe XVII emission lines at 15.3 and 17.4 Å, the starburst region also emits the O VIII Ly α line at around 19 Å and the Ne IX forbidden line at 13.9 Å. The CIE component may also produce the O VIII Ly β and Ne X Ly α lines.

4.3.3 Characterising the Emission Line Region

In this section, I discuss the physical locations of the ELR components, based on the results in Section 4.3.2 and Table 4.12. I then investigate the O VII triplet, the most prominent feature in the RGS spectrum.

4.3.3.1 Location of the Emission Line Region

I estimate the distance of the ELR within NGC 7469, assuming there is no further absorption by the WA components (if I apply absorption from the WA components to each of the emission components I find no significant statistical improvement), using

$$r_{min} = \frac{L_{ion} f_v}{\xi N_H}, \quad (4.3)$$

where N_H is the column density, ξ is the ionisation parameter, both obtained from Table 4.12, and $L_{ion} = 1.39^{+0.02}_{-0.06} \times 10^{37}$ W is the ionising luminosity (measured between 13.6 eV and 13.6 keV), calculated from the SED. The volume filling factor, f_v , is the fraction of the total volume taken up by each PION

Table 4.14: Lower bound distance measurements of the emission line region components. EM1 and EM2 distances were calculated using $f_v = 0.1$; EM3 distance was calculated with $f_v = 0.001$.

Emission Comp.	R (pc)
EM1	$2.62^{+0.31}_{-0.73}$
EM2	$2.52^{+1.05}_{-0.81}$
EM3	0.03 ± 0.01

component; for both the WA and ELR. For the derivation of this distance equation, see Section 1.4.1.3 in Chapter 1.

Here, I consider a volume filling factor such that each emission component only takes up a fraction of the total volume within NGC 7469. There is, however, very little information in the literature regarding the volume filling factor of the ELRs, although the f_v of the BLR is quoted between 0.001 and 0.01 (e.g. Osterbrock, 1991; Snedden & Gaskell, 1999). For EM3, I set the filling factor at $f_v = 0.001$ as I assume the broad line region is made up of multiple cloudlets (see e.g. Snedden & Gaskell, 1999, and references within).

In order for the NLR to be further out from the central ionising source than the WA (assuming no absorption of the emission regions by the WA), I set f_v to equal 0.1 for EM1 and EM2. I note that the uncertainties calculated in Table 4.14 do not include the large (and unknown) errors on the volume filling factor. Therefore, due to this, the uncertainties on the distance measurements are significantly greater than what is actually quoted.

Although the distances between the narrow and broad emission components (Table 4.14) are consistent with the overall picture of AGN, the distance of EM3 is still an order of magnitude larger compared to the distance of the optical BLR ($r_{BLR} = 0.004$ pc; Kollatschny & Zetzl, 2013). This is because the ionisation parameter of EM3 is very small ($\log \xi = 0.18$), so Eq. 4.3 places this emission component further out than expected. This shows an inconsistency: if EM3 is a cloud in the BLR, then it would be bombarded with a large amount of X-ray flux, ionising the plasma greatly.

By comparing the optical BLR to EM3, the kinematics are similar. The FWHM of the $H\beta$ line in the optical BLR is $2168 \pm 459 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (Kollatschny & Zetzl, 2013), similar to the broadening velocity $v_b = 1360^{+340}_{-270} \text{ km s}^{-1}$ of EM3 (an equivalent FWHM velocity of 3200 km s^{-1}). The radial velocity within the radius of the torus is -4521 km s^{-1} (Suganuma et al., 2006), which is consistent with the EM3 outflow velocity $v_{out} = -4460^{+200}_{-110} \text{ km s}^{-1}$. Setting the outflow velocity as the escape velocity, the distance of EM3 results to be $R = \frac{2GM}{v_{out}^2} = 0.004 \pm 0.001 \text{ pc}$. This value is closer to the black hole than the one found through the ionisation method (Eq. 4.3), and is consistent with the optical distance, measured using the $H\beta$ line, of 4.5 ld, equivalent to 0.004 pc (Kollatschny & Zetzl, 2013).

This distance discrepancy between the ionisation and kinematic methods are likely to be explained considering two main caveats. Firstly, there are large uncertainties associated with the volume filling factor, which may be different up to many orders of magnitude. As stated before, these uncertainties are unknown, so the errors on the distance estimates cannot be quantified accurately. Secondly, PION models the photoionised plasma as a geometrically and optically thin shell, which is true for the NLR. On the other hand, the BLR is dense and optically thick, meaning the values for EM3 have larger uncertainties associated with them, on top of the calculated errors. Therefore, due to this problem, the ionisation state ($\log \xi = 0.18$) of this broad component results to be very low, whereas EM3 has the largest the column density ($\log N_H = 27.9 \text{ m}^{-2}$) of all the emission components. Therefore, photoionisation modelling using Cloudy (Ferland et al., 2013) is required to model the BLR if comparing the X-ray BLR to the optical BLR. This is because Cloudy also deals with optically thick plasma, and thus allows the modelling of both the NLR and BLR.

4.3.3.2 The O VII Triplet

The oxygen He-like triplet is prominent in many AGN X-ray spectra (e.g. Whewell et al., 2015; Behar et al., 2017). The velocities of the emission lines

Figure 4.11: O VII He-like triplet in the observed frame of NGC 7469, with the three emission lines labelled in black (resonance, intercombination and forbidden for r, i and f, respectively). The spectrum (black crosses) is over imposed with the best fit model (red line). Two narrow components (EM1 and EM2) are shown by the blue and green lines, respectively, and a broad component (EM3) is plotted with the purple line. EM1 fits the forbidden line, EM2 fits the resonance line, as well as the forbidden line, and EM3 produces emission at the location of the intercombination line. However, this is actually a broadened forbidden line with a large blueshifted velocity (labelled with the purple ‘f’).

of the oxygen triplet were found to differ in NGC 5548, whereby the initial solution for this was that the emission lines were being absorbed by some of the WA components (Whewell et al., 2015). However, due to the contradictions in the implied geometry, Mao et al. (2018) considered multiple emission components, in much the same way that the WA is multiphased. Mao et al. (2018) found two narrow emission components explained this discrepancy as each had a different outflow velocity, with no influence on the geometry. In the case of NGC 3783, adding a broadened emission component significantly improved the fit by $\Delta C \sim 200$ (Mao et al., 2019). For this reason, I applied the same approach to NGC 7469.

Figure 4.11 displays the O VII triplet between 21.7 and 22.6 Å, with

Figure 4.12: Ionic concentration of O VII as a function of ionisation parameter ξ (blue line), calculated using PION. The red line shows the value of ξ found for EM3 through photoionisation modelling, which is much lower than the peak O VII ion concentration, indicating that this region is not ionised enough to produce a substantial forbidden line.

the best fit model (red line). The coloured lines show the contributions from each of the PION emission components. EM2 (green line) fits the forbidden line, albeit not as strongly compared to EM1 (blue line), and also accounts for some of the resonance line. In Figure 4.11, it is clear EM1 does not fit the resonance line. Initially, this was thought to be due to its large column density and optical depth, implying resonance scattering is significant enough to cause a lack of observed resonance emission. Taking into account the very small covering fraction of EM1, I tested to see if a smaller column density could be achieved, by increasing the covering fraction, allowing the resonance line to be fitted. Although increasing the covering fraction did decrease the column density, the resonance line was still not fitted by EM1, ruling out the possibility of resonant scattering. A degeneracy was found by Di Gesu et al. (2017) between the column density and covering factor in their PION analysis of the Seyfert 1 galaxy 1H 0419-577. Further to this, I refitted these two parameters (N_H and C_{cov}), and the best fit is again obtained for the parameters in Table 4.12. Even a local fit of just the O VII triplet (between

21.7 and 22.6 Å) required EM1 to have similar parameter values to those in Table 4.12; again the resonance line was unaccounted for.

Although both EM1 and EM2 fit the majority of the emission features in the rest of the spectrum, the intercombination line is not accounted for by either of them. This is where the broad emission component came in, as EM3 appears to fill in the intercombination line in the spectrum (see Figure 4.11, labelled with the purple f). However, due to the high blueshift velocity of this broad component, $v_{out} = -4460_{-110}^{+200}$ km s⁻¹, the peak of the forbidden line (in the observed frame) is shifted towards shorter wavelengths, so falls at the position where the intercombination line would be expected. This is also evident in the velocity profile of O VII (f) in the bottom panel of Figure 4.10. Instead, the intercombination line is actually filled in coincidentally. If EM3 is part of the BLR, then I would expect a strong resonance line to be emitted, due to the high density plasma in the BLR, blueshifted to higher energies. However, the forbidden line is the strongest feature produced by EM3, making the interpretation of the broad emission component doubtful. This is also supported by the small ionisation parameter (Table 4.12). Figure 4.12 displays the O VII concentration as a function of ξ for EM3 as derived using the PION code. The ionisation parameter value for EM3 ($\log \xi = 0.18$; red line in Figure 4.12) shows the ionisation level is far from the peak for the O VII ion, implying this region is not ionised enough to produce a substantial amount of this forbidden line. Therefore, EM3 only statistically improves the fit, and is likely to represent an unphysical, ad hoc solution.

4.3.3.3 The Missing O VII Intercombination Line

After ruling out the physical validity of EM3 to explain the residuals between 22.0 and 22.2 Å, where the O VII intercombination emission line is, I investigate why EM1 and EM2 do not produce the intercombination line. One reason why the intercombination line is weak (or non-existent), could be due to a low plasma density, which enhances the forbidden line. For high density plasma, the excitation from the upper level of the forbidden line occurs from

electron collisions, and this would therefore result in stronger intercombination and resonance lines; the former is not seen here. With the PION model, I tried to calculate the densities of the narrow emission components, however I was unable to constrain the values. Instead, upper limits to the densities in EM1 and EM2 were calculated using $\xi = \frac{L_{ion}}{nr^2}$, where the ionisation parameters are from Table 4.12, the lower limit distances are from Table 4.14, and $L_{ion} = 1.39 \times 10^{37}$ W. The density upper limits were found to be $n_1 \leq 1 \times 10^{12}$ m⁻³ for EM1 and $n_2 \leq 7 \times 10^{11}$ m⁻³ for EM2. These values are consistent with the densities found in the NLR ($n_{NLR} \sim 10^{12}$ m⁻³; e.g. Netzer, 1990), and therefore are associated with a strong forbidden line.

An alternative solution to the lack of intercombination emission could be due to Li-like absorption (Mehdipour et al., 2015b). This is where the O VI ion self-absorbs the intercombination emission line of the O VII triplet at around 22 Å (in our reference frame; Figures 4.8 and 4.11). To test this out, I used the SPEX model SLAB, which applies a single absorption phase. By keeping all the best fit parameters fixed, I multiplied a SLAB component by the two narrow emission line components and fitted the O VI column density, with initial value of $\log N_{OVI} = 22$ m⁻² (Mehdipour et al., 2015b). However, there was no significant change in the C-statistic, nor any absorption features in the spectrum that would be produced by O VI. One caveat is that SLAB models only the foreground absorption, and not the self-absorption in the plasma; the transmission calculations within the plasma are more complex. In conclusion, it is still unclear how to explain the presence of emission at the position of the O VII intercombination line given the emission components which best fit the rest of the spectrum of NGC 7469.

4.3.4 The WA Location

The location of the WAs in many AGN is still debated, and their origins are still unclear; most researches favour the launching site to be at the torus (e.g. Krolik & Kriss, 2001; Blustin et al., 2005). Estimates of the WA locations relative to the central engine usually require variability in the X-ray source

Table 4.15: Volume filling factor and distance measurements using the derivation from [Ashton et al. \(2006\)](#). See Section 4.3.4.1 for details.

Comp.	f_v	R ($\times 10^{16}$ m)	R (pc)
1	0.0056	3.73	1.21
2	0.1395	3.73	1.21
3	0.0002	3.73	1.21

for time-dependent photoionisation modelling (e.g. [Mehdipour et al., 2018](#)). However, the degeneracy of the distance r and hydrogen number density n_H , makes this very difficult (Section 1.4.1.1).

On the the other hand, there are alternative methods to estimate the WA distances (see Section 1.4.1.2 for details; [Blustin et al., 2005](#)). The lower distance limit is given by

$$R \geq \frac{2GM_{BH}}{v_{out}^2}, \quad (4.4)$$

where $M_{BH} = 10^7 M_\odot$ is the black hole mass ([Peterson et al., 2014](#)), assuming the outflow velocity is greater than or equal to the escape velocity from its gravitational potential, and the upper distance limit is

$$R \leq \frac{L_{ion} f_v}{\xi N_H}, \quad (4.5)$$

where f_v is the volume filling factor. If the volume filling factor is 1 then the WA fully fills the total volume, giving the maximum upper limit value for the distance. However, as f_v is dependent on the distance and geometry (gas could be clumpy, a continuous stream or be made up of filaments) of the WA, this value needs to be calculated based on other properties of the WA. I discuss two methods to estimate f_v below. From there, I was able to estimate the distances of the WA with respect to the central SMBH, from Eqs. 4.4 and 4.5, using best fit parameters of Table 4.11, and the ionising luminosity.

4.3.4.1 Volume Filling Factor: Method of Ashton et al. (2006)

[Ashton et al. \(2006\)](#) argued that if the WA is continuous, with constant veloc-

ity, the launching radius R_L is related to the column density by

$$N_H = n_H R_L f_v, \quad (4.6)$$

where n_H is the hydrogen number density and f_v is the volume filling factor. As n_H is unknown, I can use $\xi = \frac{L_{ion}}{n_H R_L^2}$ to get

$$L_{ion} = \frac{\xi N_H R_L}{f_v}. \quad (4.7)$$

This is the same relation found in [Blustin et al. \(2005\)](#), except here the WA is assumed to be continuous, rather than a thin shell, and R_L is the launching radius, not the location of the wind.

To calculate f_v , [Ashton et al. \(2006\)](#) assumed that if both n_H and ξ are constant, then $R \propto \sqrt{L_{ion}}$ (where R is now the distance of the WA from the ionising source, given by $R^2 = \frac{L_{ion}}{n_H \xi}$). This is similar to the relation between the ionising luminosity (L_{ion}) and the inner edge of the torus (R_{torus}) - also known as the sublimation radius - given by

$$R_{torus} \sim K \sqrt{L_{ion}}, \quad (4.8)$$

where $K = 10^{-2}$ is a constant. Eq. 4.8 is an amendment of Eq. 1 from [Ashton et al. \(2006\)](#) as Eq. 4.8 is in meters and Watts, rather than cm and erg s⁻¹. [Ashton et al. \(2006\)](#) reasoned that if the WA components originate from the torus (R_{torus}), then they must start with similar values for ξn , independent of L_{ion} . In other words, the product for ξn in one component must be equal to the product for a different component: $\xi_1 n_1 = \xi_2 n_2$, where 1 and 2 are different components. Therefore equating R_{torus} to R_L gives

$$\sqrt{L_{ion}} = \frac{\xi N_H K}{f_v}, \quad (4.9)$$

which allows f_v to be calculated independently of the distance.

Table 4.15 displays the volume filling factor values and distances of each component. Using Eq. 4.8, and $L_{ion} = 1.39_{-0.06}^{+0.02} \times 10^{37}$ W, the torus distance is $R_{torus} = 1.21_{-0.05}^{+0.02}$ pc, but this is the same value for the distances of each WA component (using Eq. 4.5). This is because of the cyclic nature of this method. As the launching distance equals the torus distance, a fair assumption (e.g. Blustin et al., 2005) when substituting Eq. 4.9 into Eq. 4.7, I get back to the relation in Eq. 4.8. Therefore, for a continuous outflowing wind, the origin of each WA component will always be at the torus, because f_v is calculated at the location of the launching radius, rather than where the outflow is currently. Furthermore, to calculate f_v , I have used the values of N_H and ξ from Table 4.11 which were measured from the location of the WA components now, rather than when they were at the location of the torus. Therefore, I do not use this method to estimate f_v and the WA distances.

4.3.4.2 Volume Filling Factor: Method of Blustin et al. (2005)

An alternative approach for calculating f_v was derived by Blustin et al. (2005), arguing that f_v is likely to be dependent on the distance. Blustin et al. (2005) started with the mass outflow rate (\dot{M}_{out} ; Eq. 4.14) of the WA wind, assuming radiatively accelerated outflow (see Section 1.4.2 and Appendix B.1). From this, they estimated f_v by equating the outflow momentum of the wind to the momentum of the radiation absorbed (P_{abs}), plus the momentum of the radiation scattered (P_{scat}), given by

$$\dot{M}_{out}v \sim \dot{P}_{abs} + \dot{P}_{scat}, \quad (4.10)$$

where v is the outflow velocity. Here

$$\dot{P}_{abs} = \frac{L_{abs}}{c}; \quad \dot{P}_{scat} = \frac{L_{ion}}{c}(1 - e^{-\tau_T}); \quad \tau_T = \sigma_T N_H, \quad (4.11)$$

where τ_T is the optical depth and σ_T is the Thompson scattering cross-section. These terms were calculated individually (see Table 4.16) and then substituted

into

$$f_v = \frac{(\dot{P}_{abs} + \dot{P}_{scat})\xi}{1.23m_p L_{ion} v^2 \Omega} \quad (4.12)$$

(equating Eq. 4.10 with Eq. 4.14), where $\Omega = 1.6$, generated by assuming a quarter of near AGN are type 1, with an outflow covering factor of at least 0.5 ($0.5 \times 0.25 \times 4\pi$; Blustin et al., 2005). L_{abs} in Eq. 4.11 is the amount of luminosity absorbed by the WA gas, where the ionising luminosity from the X-ray source is L_{ion} . This means that each WA component absorbs and blocks out a fraction of this ionising luminosity. To obtain the absorbed luminosities of the three WA components, I measured the flux through each of them individually (F_{WA}) and compared this value to the total flux without any absorption (F_{SED}). The amount of absorbed luminosity is therefore given by

$$L_{abs} = \frac{F_{SED} - F_{WA}}{F_{SED}} L_{ion}, \quad (4.13)$$

where the ratio is multiplied by the ionising luminosity to get it from flux units to luminosity units. To calculate L_{abs} , I assume each WA component is separate from each other and that there is no overlap between them in our line of sight to the central engine. However, this is unlikely to be the case, and when I measure L_{abs} for all three components combined, the absorbed luminosity is larger than the three individual values, implying there is some overlap. From this, \dot{P}_{abs} was calculated for the three components. \dot{P}_{scat} was an easier calculation to do as all the parameters came from the photoionisation modelling. Both \dot{P}_{abs} and \dot{P}_{scat} values are shown in Table 4.16.

The f_v values calculated with Eq. 4.12 are shown in Table 4.16, in addition to the upper and lower distance limits. The distances of all three components are consistent with the distance ranges from Blustin et al. (2007). Taking the torus distance (due to dust sublimation) to be $R_{torus} = 1.21_{-0.05}^{+0.02}$ pc, the escape velocity from the black hole is then ~ 189 km s⁻¹, which is far less than the outflow velocities of the three WA components (Table 4.11). Therefore, these WA components can originate, or be located, closer than the torus (similar to,

Table 4.16: Change of momentum (due to absorption and scattering), volume filling factor (f_v) and distance measurements of each WA component, along with mass outflow rates, kinetic luminosities and their fractions with respect to the bolometric luminosity ($L_{bol} = 2.5 \times 10^{37}$ W; [Petrucci et al., 2004](#)).

WA Comp.	\dot{P}_{abs} (Ws m ⁻¹)	\dot{P}_{scat} (Ws m ⁻¹)	f_v	R_{min} (pc) (Eq. 4.4)	R_{max} (pc) (Eq. 4.5)
1	7.3×10^{26}	3.1×10^{25}	0.0087	0.22 ± 0.01	$1.88^{+0.42}_{-0.21}$
2	9.3×10^{26}	1.6×10^{26}	0.0290	$0.10^{+0.01}_{-0.02}$	0.25 ± 0.02
3	5.3×10^{26}	7.0×10^{24}	0.0001	0.02 ± 0.01	$0.60^{+0.13}_{-0.16}$

WA Comp.	\dot{M} ($M_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1}$)	$\log L_K$ (W)	L_K/L_{bol} (%)
1	0.019	32.4	0.0010
2	0.019	32.8	0.0025
3	0.004	32.6	0.0016

e.g. NGC 3783, NGC 4593 and NGC 7469; [Blustin et al., 2005](#)).

4.3.5 Discussion

4.3.5.1 Mass Outflow Rate and Kinetic Luminosity

The mass outflow rate and kinematic luminosities of the WA can give insight into the amount of energy and matter carried out by the outflowing wind and whether it will significantly impact the host galaxy (see section 1.4.2). Here, the mass outflow rate (\dot{M}) and kinetic luminosity (L_K) ([Appendix B.1](#); [Blustin et al., 2005](#)) are calculated for each WA component, given by

$$\dot{M}_{out} = \frac{1.23m_p L_{ion} f_v v_{out} \Omega}{\xi}, \quad (4.14)$$

and

$$L_K = \frac{\dot{M}_{out} v_{out}^2}{2} = \frac{1.23m_p L_{ion} f_v v_{out}^3 \Omega}{2\xi}, \quad (4.15)$$

where m_p is the proton mass, $\Omega = 1.6$ is the solid angle, f_v is from [Table 4.16](#), and $L_{ion} = 1.39 \times 10^{37}$ W is the ionising luminosity from the central source.

The individual mass outflow rates and kinematic luminosities for the three

Figure 4.13: Possible locations of the WAs (green clouds) and ELRs (orange clouds) with respect to the central black hole. This schematic is not intended to show the exact locations of the photoionised plasma clouds, but can give insight into studying the physical scenarios. Next to each plasma cloud are the distance, ionisation and outflow velocity, depicted for an easy comparison. The distances for the ELRs are the lower limits, as obtained from Eq. 4.3. As a comparison to the X-ray broad emission component (EM3), the optical BLR is at a distance of 0.004 pc in NGC 7469 (Kollatschny & Zetzl, 2013).

WA components are displayed in Table 4.16. The total mass outflow rate is $0.042 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, which is somewhat less than the total of $0.052 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for the three components in archive data (Blustin et al., 2007).

The L_K values found here are consistent with previous studies ($\log L_K = 31.7$ to 32.7 W from Blustin et al., 2007). I also measure L_K as a fraction of the bolometric luminosity $L_{\text{bol}} = 2.5 \times 10^{37} \text{ W}$ (Petrucci et al., 2004). The values for this fraction are shown in Table 4.16 and are between 0.001 - 0.003 % of L_{bol} , also consistent with previous analysis (Blustin et al., 2007). The L_K of the UV outflowing material is negligible compared to the X-ray components (Arav et al., 2020), so does not need to be included here. The L_K/L_{bol} ratios here suggest that the outflowing wind has insufficient energy to significantly impact the host galaxy, which is the overall picture of WAs in AGN (Blustin et al., 2005).

4.3.5.2 Physical Structure of NGC 7469

After analysing the WA and ELR separately, it is now time to combine everything together to achieve an overall understanding of the nuclear region within NGC 7469. Figure 4.13 displays a schematic to demonstrate the structure and possible locations of the ELR and WA components with respect to each other, the torus, and the central engine.

The ionisation parameters of both EM2 and WA component 3 are $\log \xi = 1.6$, suggesting that they could be part of the same, extended photoionised plasma (e.g. Kinkhabwala et al., 2002; Blustin et al., 2003; Behar et al., 2003, 2017). However, there is not enough evidence to conclusively deduce this, as the location of EM2 is very different compared to WA component 3. In addition, the outflow velocity of EM2 is fixed at rest in the best fit model (Table 4.12), suggesting that it does not have any radial velocity (or it is at least small relative to the other emission line components) in our line of sight. Therefore, in Figure 4.13, EM2 is placed as close to the plane of the torus as possible, but such that it can still receive the full ionising continuum from the central source. Consequently, although these two components share the same ionisation parameter, it is unlikely that they are part of the same, extended wind, because of their varying outflow velocities and the location of EM2 with respect to the WA components. On the other hand, both EM1 and WA component 1 have similar outflow velocities, but different ionisation parameters. This is also seen when comparing the kinematics between the low-ionised UV components with the high-ionised X-ray components in NGC 7469 (e.g. Kriss et al., 2003; Scott et al., 2005; Blustin et al., 2007).

As a result of each WA and ELR component being independent of each other (as shown schematically in Figure 4.13), one probable mechanism for creating different components is that they were launched at different times throughout the history of the AGN. Furthermore, the differences in locations, ionisation parameters and outflow velocities suggest that each component was launched from a slightly different location of the torus/outer accretion disk.

If the launching mechanisms of the wind were due to thermal or radiative driving processes (see Section 1.6), then over the course of the AGN lifetime, the plasma could have been launched at different times, provided that there were variations in the activity of the AGN over its lifetime; for example changes in accretion and mass outflow rates. Otherwise, a continuous outflowing stream would be more likely.

From Figure 4.13, it looks like EM3 ($r = 0.03$ pc; $v_{out} \sim 4500$ km s⁻¹) could catch up with WA component 2 ($r_{min} = 0.1$; $v_{out} \sim 1000$ km s⁻¹) in just over 30 years. However, this is not a secure prediction for many reasons. Firstly, there is a difference (by an order of magnitude) between the calculated distances of EM3, depending on if I use the ionisation parameter (Eq. 4.3) or the kinematic distance (Eq. 4.4). Secondly, a large uncertainty in the volume filling factor means the distance could be very different to the value quoted in Table 4.14; in addition, a $f_v < 0.001$ could mean the ionisation distance is similar to the kinematic distance. Finally, the warm absorber distances calculated here are at least 10 times smaller than the distances from variability arguments (Figure 4.14; Mehdipour et al., 2018), meaning WA component 2 could be much further away from EM3, thus implying it is very unlikely that EM3 would catch up to WA component 2. Therefore, from the above arguments, I cannot conclusively determine whether the absorption and emission regions are part of the same outflowing clouds within the nucleus of NGC 7469, from this analysis. This is discussed further in Chapter 8.

Furthermore, the uncertainty regarding the plasma locations is shown in Figure 4.14, which compares the ELR and WA distances found here to the locations found by Mehdipour et al. (2018). Mehdipour et al. (2018) used the variability technique (Section 1.4.1.1) and a recombination timescale of 13 years to determine the locations of the WA components. The ability to constrain distance estimates from variability arguments naturally depends on the timescales covered by the data; given the long intervals between observations, the derived distances are generally upper limits. Here I try to find a way

to reconcile the results with the expectations based on the standard model of AGN by adjusting the f_v parameter. This is because I am only using data from 2015, and the spectrum does not show variability (Behar et al., 2017). Therefore, it is unsurprising that, using the thin shell method from Blustin et al. (2005), the distances found here are consistent with previous findings of the WAs within NGC 7469 (0.1 - 1.6 pc; 0.012 - 1.7 pc, Blustin et al., 2005, 2007, respectively), but are different compared to variability techniques (Mehdipour et al., 2018), as shown in Figure 4.14. From studying the RGS spectrum, the three WA distances are significantly closer to the black hole compared to the HETGS results.

For the ELR in this Chapter, I compare distances using volume filling factor values of $f_v = 1$ and $f_v = 0.1$ for EM1 and EM2 (see Table 4.14). If $f_v = 1$ for the narrow line region components then the maximum lower limit distances for EM1 and EM2 would become 25 and 26 pc, respectively, taking these distances to be at the same location as the HETGS WA components (see Figure 4.14). But this is unphysical as both plasma clouds cannot cover the full volume. For the broad emission component, EM3, the volume filling factor was set to $f_v = 0.001$, meaning the distance is consistent with WA component 1. As a comparison, I used the emission parameters from the Chandra data (Table 3 in Mehdipour et al., 2018), to calculate the minimum distances of the NLR components E ($\log \xi = 0.9$) and F ($\log \xi = 2.2$). The distances were found at 2.4 and 22.3 pc (with $f_v = 0.1$), respectively. Component F is consistent with WA component 2 and component E is consistent with the four WA components from HETGS. From Figure 4.14, there could be some evidence of the WA and ELR being part of the same outflow regions, but this is inconclusive and only true if we consider both RGS and HETGS results together, as well as all distance methods. However, if the filling factor is between the range of 0.1 and 1, then the discrepancy of the NLR distances, compared to the location of the WA, in NGC 7469 can be overcome.

Figure 4.14: Comparing the WA and ELR distances from this work to the analysis by [Mehdipour et al. \(2018\)](#). From studying the RGS spectrum, the three WA distances (red lines) are significantly closer to the black hole compared to the HETGS variability results (blue lines and arrows). For the ELR, I compare $f_v = 1$ to $f_v = 0.1$ for EM1 and EM2 (green circles and purple down-triangles, respectively), whereby using $f_v = 1$ places them at a similar distance as the WA components from the HETGS analysis. EM3 ($f_v = 0.001$; purple up-triangle) has a distance consistent with WA component 1. Finally, the orange down-triangles show the two ELR component distances, components E and F, from [Mehdipour et al. \(2018\)](#), using $f_v = 0.1$. Component F is consistent with WA component 2 and component E is consistent with the four WA components from HETGS. From this plot, there could be some evidence of the WA and ELR being from the same outflow, but this is inconclusive. For further comparison, the distances of the optical BLR (0.004 pc; from [Kollatschny & Zetzl, 2013](#)) and the torus (1.21 pc; Eq. 4.8) are shown by the magenta dashed and solid lines, respectively.

4.4 Conclusions

In this Chapter I report the investigation of the 640 ks RGS spectrum of NGC 7469 taken between 2015 and 2016. Using the spectral analysis code `SPEX`, the absorption features from the outflowing WA and emission lines from the NLR, and possibly BLR, were studied in great detail and compared to previous analysis of this bright AGN. For the first time in NGC 7469, limits on the distances of the narrow ELRs from the central black hole were estimated and a full picture of the outflowing wind was constructed.

In Section 4.2, the absorption lines were modelled with `XABS`. The preliminary results showed that the WA is made up of three components with a range of ionisation states ($\log \xi = 1 - 3$), kinematics ($v_{out} = -800$ to -2100 km s⁻¹) and column densities ($\log N_H = 24.6 - 25.8$ m⁻²). Components A and B had the largest column densities and ionisation parameters, but had the lowest outflow velocities; the opposite was found for component C. The emission lines were fitted with a `RRC` component, with a temperature consistent with that of PIE plasma ($T_e = 12.7 \pm 0.4$ keV), and and 16 Gaussian components. The `GAUS` components showed a mixture of blue and redshifted velocities, but some values were unconstrained with relatively large uncertainties. Interestingly, the O VII resonance and intercombination lines were found almost at rest, while the forbidden line was blueshifted by around -560 km s⁻¹. This was also found in NGC 5548 by [Whewell et al. \(2015\)](#), who put this down to absorption of the resonance line. For the N VI triplet, all lines were greatly redshifted. Overall, this preliminary work gives good insight into the properties of the outflowing WA wind, showing that it contains multiple components with a range of ionisation states and kinematics. However, a better approach was required to fully understand all the features present; this was done in the second part of this Chapter.

In Section 4.3 I investigated the RGS spectrum with a more physically motivated and self-consistent model to fully explain the ionised plasma in the black hole environment of NGC 7469. The SED, derived by [Mehdipour et al.](#)

(2018) (Table 4.9 and Figure 4.6 in Section 4.3.1.1), was used to represent the full broadband ionising continuum, which was fed through each PION component to simultaneously calculate the spectrum and ionisation states of the plasma regions. This method is physically motivated and represents an important improvement compared to the previous phenomenological fit by Behar et al. (2017).

Using PION, three WA components were found to explain the absorption features in the RGS spectrum, with ionisation states of $\log \xi = 2.3, 3.0,$ and 1.6 and kinematic phases of $v_{out} = -630, -910,$ and -1960 km s^{-1} , respectively; the highest outflow velocity is associated with the smallest ξ (similar to Blustin et al., 2003; Kriss et al., 2003; Blustin et al., 2007). The WA kinematics are also similar to the UV velocity components measured in this campaign (Arav et al., 2020) and from archive results (Kriss et al., 2003; Scott et al., 2005). I find that the total column density of the WA is $N_H^{Tot} = 64 \times 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-2}$, about twice as large as the total found by Behar et al. (2017). On the other hand, the WA ionisation parameter and outflow velocity values are consistent with the four components found by Mehdipour et al. (2018), in addition to the total column density. Interestingly, Behar et al. (2017) found six WA components, so the large difference in N_H may come down to the modelling approach carried out between the two investigations. However, the model discrepancies between these two methods are not beyond what is expected from different analysis codes (Figure 2.2; Mehdipour et al., 2016b).

The upper distances of the WA components were found to be 1.9, 0.3, and 0.6 pc for components 1 to 3, respectively, consistent with previous findings (Blustin et al., 2007). The WA volume filling factors f_v were estimated from Eq. 4.12 (Blustin et al., 2005) and the location of the torus was estimated at around 1.2 pc. In order to determine how much energy is associated with the WA and whether it will impact the host galaxy, I measured the mass outflow rate (\dot{M}_{out}) and kinematic luminosity (L_K) of each component. The total \dot{M}_{out} of all three WA components combined is $0.042 M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$, which is less

than the total of $0.052 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ found by [Blustin et al. \(2007\)](#). I measured the kinematic luminosities to be between $\log L_K = 32$ and $\log L_K = 33$ W, and the fraction of the kinematic luminosity compared to the bolometric luminosity ($L_{bol} = 2.5 \times 10^{37}$ W; [Petrucci et al., 2004](#)) is $\sim 0.001 - 0.003$ %. Both these results are consistent with [Blustin et al. \(2007\)](#). However, this indicates that the WA has insufficient energy to impact the host galaxy, similar to the WAs in other AGN ([Blustin et al., 2005](#)).

With PION, I was also able to model the photoionised plasma from the ELR. Here, two narrow components were required to fit the majority of the emission features, with ionisation states and column densities of $\log \xi = 0.35$ and 1.55 , and $\log N_H = 27.8$ and 26.6 , respectively. The ionisation range of the ELRs is consistent with that found by [Mehdipour et al. \(2018\)](#), who also found a component at rest. However, their total column density for the two narrow line components ($N_H = 1.46 \times 10^{27} \text{ m}^{-2}$) is significantly less than what I found here ($N_H = 6.83 \times 10^{27} \text{ m}^{-2}$), although the covering fractions are roughly an order of magnitude smaller in this analysis (there is a degeneracy between these two parameters; e.g. [Di Gesu et al., 2017](#)). Assuming a volume filling factor value of 0.1 , the two narrow components, EM1 and EM2, are found to be located at 2.6 and 2.5 pc away from the central source, respectively. This was the first time that the distances of the NLR in NGC 7469 were calculated. The RGS spectrum also shows emission features from collisionally ionised plasma, produced in the starburst region of NGC 7469. Here, the electron temperature was found to be 0.32 keV, with the plasma moving towards us at -282 km s^{-1} , consistent with [Behar et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Mehdipour et al. \(2018\)](#).

In addition, a broad emission component (EM3) was found to reproduce emission at the position of the intercombination line of the O VII triplet. EM3 was found to have an outflow velocity of $v_{out} = -4460 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and broadening velocity of $v_b = 1360 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (similar to the optical BLR values; [Suganuma et al., 2006](#); [Kollatschny & Zetzl, 2013](#)). However, the large blueshift implies that this broad component is actually the forbidden line, coincidentally filling

in the intercombination line. As a result, it was difficult to obtain a distance estimate for EM3. Assuming a volume filling factor value of 0.001, the distance was found to be 0.03 pc. However, this was further away from the black hole compared to the optical BLR (Kollatschny & Zetzl, 2013). Instead, if I used the outflow velocity of EM3 ($v_{out} = -4460 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) as the escape velocity, the distance was 0.004 pc; this is now consistent with the optical BLR. This discrepancy comes about from the fact that the ionisation state of EM3 ($\log \xi = 0.18$) is very low, lower than that of EM1 and EM2, but the column density ($\log N_H = 27.9 \text{ m}^{-2}$) is larger. This is likely to be due to the modelling assumptions of PION, which assumes the photoionised plasma is a thin shell that is optically thin, which is true for the NLR. On the other hand, the BLR is dense and optically thick, meaning the values for EM3 have larger uncertainties associated with them, on top of the calculated errors. Instead, photoionisation modelling using Cloudy (Ferland et al., 2013) is required to model the BLR if comparing the X-ray BLR to the optical BLR. Therefore, these caveats suggest that EM3 is not part of the ELR, but is instead an unphysical ad hoc solution to fit the intercombination line, statistically improving the fit.

Overall, I conclude that it is very unlikely that any of the plasma components in the nuclear region of NGC 7469 are made up of both emission and absorption regions (see Figure 4.14). This is due to the large uncertainties associated with the respective volume filling factors and different distance measurements of the WA components resulting from this work and from variability arguments by Mehdipour et al. (2018).

Chapter 5

Exploring the X-ray emission line regions within NGC1068

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Abstract

NGC 1068 is the archetype type 2 AGN, with an X-ray spectrum that displays strong, narrow emission lines on top of an almost negligible continuum. This is characteristic of the central engine being obscured by a dusty torus as the emission lines originate from plasma at a distance far from the black hole. The motivation for this Chapter is to determine whether the emission line region (ELR) properties changed between observations taken by XMM-Newton in 2000 and 2014. I simultaneously fitted the RGS and EPIC-PN spectra in each epoch to obtain an in-depth photoionisation modelling analysis. This highly detailed investigation, whereby two epochs were compared, had never been done before on NGC 1068.

From the photoionisation modelling, four plasma components are found in each epoch, fitting the majority of the emission lines within the full 0.35 - 10 keV energy range. The ionisation parameters (ξ) of each component are consistent between the two epochs, implying that we are observing the same plasma regions. Unfortunately, there is little variation between the two spec-

tra and ionisation parameters, meaning I could not obtain distance estimates through variability techniques. Instead, I compare different distance methods to estimate the locations of the ELR components with respect to the SMBH. Finally, I found evidence of emission from collisionally ionised plasma, as the photoionisation model did not account for the Fe XVII spectral features at 15 and 17 Å. The origin of this collisionally ionised plasma is unknown, although evidence suggests that it stems from the secondary region in NGC 1068, instead of the starburst region.

5.1 Introduction

NGC 1068 is a heavily studied type 2 Seyfert galaxy at a redshift of $z = 0.0038$ (Huchra et al., 1999), with a super massive black hole (SMBH) mass of $M_{BH} = 1.6 \times 10^7 M_{\odot}$ (e.g. Panessa et al., 2006). This archetype Compton thick (CT) AGN supports perfectly the unification (Antonucci & Miller, 1985) and the ionised cone (Kinkhabwala et al., 2002, Figure 1.6 in Section 1.3.3) models, as only narrow emission lines are observed in its soft X-ray spectra. Interestingly, although the nucleus of NGC 1068 is occulted by the torus blocking out the photons in our LOS, the host galaxy is face on to us.

The galaxy nucleus of NGC 1068 is made up of two main structures: the AGN and its surrounding environment, called the circumnuclear disk (CND), and the starburst ring (SBR), located 1.3 kpc from the AGN (García-Burillo et al., 2017). Figure 5.1 illustrates the continuum emission map of NGC 1068 obtained by the Atacama Large Millimeter Array (ALMA; García-Burillo et al., 2014), displaying the SBR and AGN within the CND. The outflow rate within the CND was found to be an order of magnitude larger than the star formation rate, suggesting the ionised gas outflow is AGN driven (García-Burillo et al., 2014). The SBR is colder and less dense than the CND (Viti et al., 2014) as it is much further out from the black hole ($r_{CND} < 200$ pc, $r_{SBR} \sim 1.3$ kpc, shown in Figure 5.1; García-Burillo et al., 2017). The torus, with gas mass $M_{gas}^{torus} \sim 1 \times 10^5 M_{\odot}$ and a distance of $R_{torus} \sim 3.5$ pc from the black hole, was

found to be inhomogeneous and non-circular in motion, possibly inclined at larger radii (García-Burillo et al., 2016).

The majority of the X-ray emission originates from the CND in NGC 1068. The very first high resolution X-ray spectra of NGC 1068 were taken in 2000 by XMM-Newton (Kinkhabwala et al., 2002) and Chandra (Brinkman et al., 2002; Ogle et al., 2003), both showing many narrow emission lines originating from photoionised plasma. Kraemer et al. (2015) reanalysed the 2000 RGS spectrum with a two component model, and found the emission lines were blueshifted by $\sim 160 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, consistent with the optical [O III] $\lambda 5007$ results (Crenshaw et al., 2010). Both Brinkman et al. (2002) and Kraemer et al. (2015) suggest that the optical and X-ray emission line regions are part of the same outflowing wind, having consistent velocities; this is a general property of type 2 Seyfert AGN (Bianchi et al., 2006).

Due to the higher spatial resolution of Chandra, Brinkman et al. (2002) and Ogle et al. (2003) were able to differentiate between two emission regions within the nucleus of NGC 1068, made up of a central, primary region, and an off-centre, secondary region (Figure 5.2). The secondary region is a bright X-ray source that coincides with intense radio and optical emission, indicating a correlation between the X-ray and optical regions, which may arise from old jet material (Wilson & Ulvestad, 1987; Young et al., 2001). It was found to have an ionic column density three times smaller compared to the primary region, and plasma diagnostics were unable to conclude if the emission was produced in photoionisation equilibrium (PIE) or collisionally ionised equilibrium (CIE) plasma (Brinkman et al., 2002).

From studying the XMM-Newton RGS spectra, Kinkhabwala et al. (2002) found that excess emission in the resonance lines was explained by photoexcitation, rather than emission from CIE plasma. They suggested that the addition of CIE plasma could explain the emission excess in the lower order resonance lines, but would enhance the other lines in the spectrum, in particular over predicting the intercombination and forbidden lines of the He-like triplets.

The hard (2 - 10 keV, and above) X-ray spectrum for NGC 1068 is also very complex (see e.g. [Guainazzi et al., 1999](#); [Bianchi et al., 2001](#)) whereby the emission features can be explained by multiple components (e.g. [Bianchi et al., 2001](#); [Matt, 2002](#); [Matt et al., 2004](#); [Pounds & Vaughan, 2006](#); [Bauer et al., 2015](#)). The high energy ($E > 4$ keV) spectrum was explained by a neutral reflection component (possibly part of a CT material) and a highly ionised component with a column density of $N_H \sim 10^{25} \text{ m}^{-2}$ ([Matt et al., 2004](#); [Pounds & Vaughan, 2006](#)). To further confirm the existence of a CT material ($N_H > 1.5 \times 10^{28} \text{ m}^{-2}$; e.g. torus), evidence of a Compton shoulder¹ ([Iwasawa et al., 1997](#); [Matt, 2002](#)) was found ([Matt et al., 2004](#); [Pounds & Vaughan, 2006](#)). This was further observed by NuSTAR, whereby three reflection components were necessary to model the Fe $K\alpha$ line and Compton hump with column densities of 1.5×10^{27} , 5×10^{28} , and 10^{29} m^{-2} ([Bauer et al., 2015](#)); this agreed with the three component model from [Bianchi et al. \(2001\)](#).

Infrared observations have shown hydrogen emission structures to in-fall towards the central SMBH. One molecular cloud was close enough (~ 1 pc) such that a tidally distributed, optically thick stream could have possibly made-up the outer part of a clumpy, dusty torus ([Müller Sánchez et al., 2009](#)). Evidence for this clumpy structure, in the high energy X-rays, was found during an unveiling event in August 2014 when a flux excess was observed above 20 keV, compared to December 2012 and February 2015 ([Marinucci et al., 2016](#)). This was the first observation of a torus unveiling event and was caused by a decrease in column density by about $\Delta N_H \sim 2.5 \times 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, which allowed [Marinucci et al. \(2016\)](#) to infer an intrinsic 2 - 10 keV luminosity of $L = 7 \times 10^{43} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$ for the central, normally obscured AGN.

The goal of this the work reported in this Chapter is to attain a self-consistent best fit photoionisation model for the 2000 and 2014 XMM-Newton observations of NGC 1068 in order to achieve an in depth understanding of the

¹The Compton shoulder is the small hump observed in the spectrum at 6.3 keV, caused by scattered line emission of the Fe $K\alpha$ line photons off optically thick material (e.g. dusty torus).

Figure 5.1: ALMA continuum image of NGC 1068, displaying the different regions: starburst ring (SBR), circumnuclear disk (CND) and AGN. Also shown is the secondary region (SR) $\sim 4''$ north-east of the central AGN. (Image adapted from [García-Burillo et al., 2014](#)).

Figure 5.2: *Left:* Zero-order LETGS image of NGC 1068, where the central region is very bright. *Right:* X-ray contours plotted on top of the optical [O III] HST image, showing a very good spatial correlation. The three diagonal lines indicate the primary (P, bottom) and secondary (S, top) regions. The secondary region can be seen in Figure 5.1. (Images taken from [Brinkman et al., 2002](#)).

emitting plasma regions within this AGN. I aim to determine if there are any changes in the emitting plasma between the epochs, and to then obtain other properties such as the location from the central black hole. In my preliminary work of NGC 1068, Reflection Grating Spectrometer (RGS, Section 3.1.1; den Herder et al., 2001) and European Photon Imaging Camera pn-CCD (EPIC-PN, Section 3.1.2; Strüder et al., 2001) spectra were modelled separately and compared in each epoch (Section 5.4). In the main part of this Chapter, both spectra were modelled simultaneously, over the full 0.35 - 10 keV energy band, for the 2000 and 2014 data (Sections 5.5 - 5.6). I modelled the spectra of NGC 1068 using SPEX (v 3.04.00; Kaastra et al., 1996), setting the redshift of this AGN to $z = 0.0038$ (Huchra et al., 1999) and assuming solar abundances from Lodders et al. (2009). I used the Cash statistic (C-statistic, hereafter; Cash, 1979; Kaastra, 2017) for statistical significance, with errors at a 1σ confidence.

5.2 Data reduction

NGC 1068 was observed twice in 2000 and four times in 2014 with XMM-Newton. I reduced the RGS and EPIC-PN data from each observation of NGC 1068 via the SAS (v 17.0.0) pipeline; the observation log is displayed in Table 5.1. The RGS data were reduced with RGSPROC and the EPIC-PN data were reduced using the EPPROC command. The 2000 observations were taken during the same XMM-Newton orbit so I stacked both the RGS and EPIC-PN spectra (separately) using RGSCOMBINE and EPICSPECCOMBINE, respectively. For the 2014 observations, separated by different time scales (see Table 5.1), there was little variability in the RGS spectra, so all four observations were combined. However, due to multiple background flares (too close together to filter out) in the final 2014 campaign observation (February 2015) I was only able to use and combine the first three (July/August 2014) EPIC-PN spectra; only the RGS data for the 2015 observation were used (see Table 5.1).

The total angular size of NGC 1068 extends to $6.9' \times 6.0'$, but the optical and X-ray emission is brightest from within roughly $3' \times 3'$ ². This means

²See <http://simbad.u-strasbg.fr/simbad/sim-id?Ident=NGC+1068>, and the image

Table 5.1: Observation log for NGC 1068 showing the observation ID, start date, duration, and the instruments used in this investigation.

Observing Campaign	Obs ID	Start Date	Duration (ks)	Instrument Used
2000	0111200101	2000/07/29	42	PN, RGS
	0111200201	2000/07/30	46	PN, RGS
2014	0740060201	2014/07/10	64	PN, RGS
	0740060301	2014/07/18	58	PN, RGS
	0740060401	2014/08/19	54	PN, RGS
	0740060501	2015/02/03	55	RGS

that NGC 1068 is easily detected by RGS, which collects all of the photons from the AGN and extended regions.

5.2.1 PN Energy Shift

At visual inspection, the Fe $K\alpha$ and higher energy emission lines in the 2014 EPIC-PN spectrum appear to be shifted with respect to the 2000 observation (top panel of Figure 5.3, as well to the Chandra and MOS spectra; see Figure 5.4). The top panel of Figure 5.3 compares the 2000 data (red crosses) with the 2014 data (blue crosses) for the Fe $K\alpha$ line (at around 6.4 keV), where there is an energy difference of $\Delta E = 50$ eV between the observed line peaks. This blueshift (and broadening; $\sigma(E) \sim 20$ eV relative to Chandra observations from 2012) of the Fe $K\alpha$ line was also found in NGC 5548, where the problem was attributed to uncertainties in the long-term charge transfer inefficiency and instrumental gain correction of the EPIC-PN CCDs, causing modest but significant variations (see Cappi et al., 2016, and references within). Similar to Cappi et al. (2016), to check if this is an instrumental issue, rather than a physical property of the AGN, I compared the 2014 EPIC-PN data with the 2000 and 2014 MOS spectra, as well as to some 2012 Chandra observations (see Figure 5.4). I found that all Fe $K\alpha$ lines had energies consistent with 6.4 keV, except for the 2014 EPIC-PN Fe $K\alpha$ line. Therefore, this blueshifted iron line is not a new and interesting result, but rather an artefact of the long life of the EPIC-PN camera.

on the right hand side.

To account for this energy shift between the 2000 and 2014 data in the preliminary work (Section 5.4.4) I coupled the observed REFL component (see Section 5.3.1, below) with a second REDS component, like Cappi et al. (2016), in SPEX, setting the *flag* parameter value to a velocity rather than the cosmological redshift³. However, in the simultaneous fit (Sections 5.5 - 5.6) I manually changed the gain correction of the EPIC-PN instrument for the 2014 observations rather than just shift the model. This is more advantageous because all the data in the spectrum are shifted by the same amount, whereas using REDS requires an additional model correction with some uncertainties. It also means that multiple corrections (REDS) for each component are not needed, nor is one correction assumed, which could cause problems if the correction for one component is not the same for another (see Section 5.4.4 for an example.). Taking the event list files for each of the three observations in 2014 (the 2015 observation was not used due to background flaring), I multiplied the energy (PI) column by 0.993, before restacking the spectra. The value of 0.993 came from taking the ratio $\frac{E_{2000}}{E_{2014}}$, where E_{2000} and E_{2014} are the energies of the data points from 2000 and 2014 spectra, respectively, at different energies in the FeK range (6 - 7 keV; Figure 5.3). I then averaged the ratios to obtain $PI = 0.993$. I also checked the energies outside this range: the lower energies were less effected by the original shift, but this correction did not cause a problem; and the higher energies also agreed when this PI value was used. This procedure corrected the emission line energies in the 2014 EPIC-PN data to be consistent with the 2000 data (see bottom panel of Figure 5.3).

³The REDS component in SPEX has two parameters: redshift (z) and *flag*. If *flag* = 0 then a cosmological redshift is used such that the value z is that of the redshift of the observed source, for example $z = 0.0038$ for NGC 1068. If *flag* = 1 on the other hand, then a velocity redshift is set up such that the value z is a physical velocity shift (once multiplied by the speed of light). For example, if *flag* = 1 and $z = -0.0001$, then the component or source is blueshifted by 30 km s^{-1} .

Figure 5.3: Comparing the Fe $K\alpha$ line in 2000 (red crosses) and 2014 (blue crosses). *Top:* There is a clear shift in the Fe $K\alpha$ line between these two epochs, denoted by the red and blue dashed vertical lines at the peak energies of the observed data. The magenta arrow signifies this energy shift between the observations, equivalent to $\Delta E = 50 eV$. This shift is due to uncertainties in the long-term charge transfer inefficiency and instrumental gain (Cappi et al., 2016). *Bottom:* I account for this shift manually by multiplying the energies (PI) of the event lists in each 2014 observation by 0.993 for the simultaneous fit. Now the 2014 EPIC-PN data are consistent with the 2000 data and the correction is sufficient for modelling.

Table 5.2: The parameter values (fixed) for the ionising SED initially adopted from the broad band ionising continuum of NGC 7469 (Mehdipour et al., 2018, see Section 5.3.1 for details). To modify the SED in order to match with NGC 1068, some of the parameters are changed to observational results found in the literature, shown in the reference column. I assume the ionising reflection is the same as the observed reflection, so I fit only the normalisation of the REFL component.

Component	Parameter	Value	Reference
POW ^a	Norm ^b	7.1×10^{51}	1
	Γ_{pow}	2.1	2, 3, 4
COMT	Norm ^c	5.7×10^{55}	
	T_{disk} (eV)	1.4	1
	T_e (keV)	0.14	
	τ	21	
REFL	Γ_{refl} ^d	2.1	2, 3, 4
	A_{Fe}	2.45 ^e	2, 3
	E_c (keV)	500	3
	θ_{inc}	60°	3
	Reflection scale	0.5	-
	σ_v (km s ⁻¹)	~ 3000	1

^a I apply an upper and lower cut-off energy to the power-law: the lower cut-off energy (E_L) is equal to the disk temperature (T_{disk}) and the upper cut-off energy is $E_C = 500$ keV (Bauer et al., 2015). The units for the normalisations are:

^b ph s⁻¹ keV⁻¹ at 1 keV; and ^c ph s⁻¹ keV⁻¹. ^d Coupled to POW.

^e This value has been adjusted from Matt et al. (2004); Pounds & Vaughan (2006), who measured $A_{Fe} = 2.4$, to the abundance of Lodders et al. (2009).

References: (1) Mehdipour et al. (2018); (2) Matt et al. (2004); (3) Bauer et al. (2015); (4) Pounds & Vaughan (2006).

Figure 5.4: *Top Left:* Comparing the 2014 EPIC-PN data (blue crosses) with the 2000 EPIC-PN data (red crosses) between 6 and 7 keV. It is clear that there is an energy shift between the epochs. *Top Right:* The 2014 EPIC-PN data compared to Chandra (HEG) data from 2008 (+1 and -1 orders; see legend for data point colours). Here, the EPIC-PN data is also shifted with respect to the Chandra data. *Bottom Left:* Comparing the EPIC-PN 2000 spectrum (red crosses) with the MOS 2000 (orange circles) and MOS 2014 (purple diamonds) spectra. The peak of the Fe $K\alpha$ lines in all three spectra are at the same energy. *Bottom Right:* Comparing the 2014 EPIC-PN spectrum (blue crosses) with the 2000 and 2014 MOS spectra (orange circles and purple diamonds, respectively). It is clear that the Fe $K\alpha$ in the EPIC-PN spectrum is shifted compared to the two MOS spectra.

5.3 Spectral energy distributions

5.3.1 Ionising Continuum

Due to the nature of NGC 1068, the line of sight (LOS) obscuration from the torus means we are unable to observe the central ionising source directly. Therefore, as I cannot directly observe the ionising continuum I had to assume a broadband continuum model, which was fixed throughout the spectral fitting. It is the shape of the ionising spectral energy distribution (SED) that is important, not the normalisation (Mehdipour et al., 2016b), so it is not unreasonable to use a SED from a type 1 Seyfert galaxy. In this case, I adopted

the SED of NGC 7469 derived by [Mehdipour et al. \(2018\)](#) (and used in Chapter 4), as it is a bright and unobscured Seyfert 1 AGN, but adjusted some of the parameters to match the observed values found for NGC 1068 in the literature (e.g. [Bauer et al., 2015](#)). The SED shape of NGC 7469 is a good representation of a typical AGN SED when the actual ionising SED of NGC 1068 is unknown, and is a step better than a simple power-law. [Mehdipour et al. \(2016b\)](#) compared photoionisation results using the SEDs of NGC 5548 (both unobscured and obscured) and a power-law SED. I compared the SEDs and thermal stability S-curves of NGC 5548 ([Mehdipour et al., 2016b](#)) and NGC 7469 ([Mehdipour et al., 2018](#)), and found that within the X-ray ionisation region where I am probing ($\log \xi = 1 - 4$), the S-curves (Section 2.4.2) do not appear to be significantly different. From this, I am confident that the differences between typical SEDs of the same type (like NGC 7469 and NGC 5548) would not significantly affect the results here. Therefore, NGC 7469 is a reasonable SED to use when modelling the ionising continuum of NGC 1068.

The three main components that contribute to the ionising SED (see Section 2.3.1 in Chapter 2 for further details) are displayed in Table 5.2; they are as follows:

1. Firstly, a power-law (POW) is used to model the hard X-ray emission produced when optical/UV disk photons are upscattered in a hot electron corona. To this power-law I applied upper and lower cut-off energies. The lower cut-off energy is fixed at the disk temperature, adopted from NGC 7469 ([Mehdipour et al., 2018](#)), to stop the power-law energies becoming lower than the disk photon energies; the high energy cut-off is fixed at 500 keV ([Bauer et al., 2015](#)).
2. The next SED component is a reflection component (REFL; [Magdziarz & Zdziarski, 1995](#)) which models the Fe K α line and Compton hump. The inclination ($\theta_{inc} = 60^\circ$) and photon index ($\Gamma = 2.1$, coupled to the photon index of POW) are fixed at the values found from previous observations of NGC 1068 (e.g. [Matt et al., 2004](#); [Pounds & Vaughan, 2006](#); [Bauer](#)

et al., 2015). In addition, I use the iron abundance value of $A_{Fe} = 2.45$, which applies to the reflecting material within the AGN environment and was derived from the fitted parameter value of 2.40 (Matt et al., 2004; Bauer et al., 2015). The reason for this correction is that XSPEC (used by Matt et al. 2004 and Bauer et al. 2015) uses solar values from Anders & Grevesse (1989), while SPEX implements the abundances from Lodders et al. (2009). To make the correction, I used the Fe solar value from Anders & Grevesse (1989) of 7.67 and the Fe value from Lodders et al. (2009) of 7.51, and derived the abundance for this model in SPEX as $(7.67/7.51) \times 2.40 = 2.45$. The Fe abundance was fixed in the reflection component throughout the fitting process, and this value does not apply to the photoionised plasma abundance of iron in the outflowing wind of NGC 1068. Here I assumed that the X-rays observed (after being reflected) are the same reflected X-rays that ionise the emitting plasma. This means that there is only one REFL component that accounts for both ionising and observed X-ray reflection, so I fitted the normalisation parameter of REFL (N_{refl}) in the model. This is the only fitted parameter in the SED, all other parameters are fixed to the values in Table 5.2.

3. Finally, I model the soft X-ray excess and the UV/optical emission from the accretion disk (e.g. Petrucci et al., 2013; Middei et al., 2018) with the Comptonisation component (COMT; Titarchuk, 1994). All the values for COMT are adopted and fixed from the ionising SED in NGC 7469 (Mehdipour et al., 2018).

5.3.2 Observed Continuum

The X-ray spectrum seen is the result of the ionising continuum reflecting off the circumnuclear material within or surrounding the nucleus of NGC 1068 (e.g. the dusty torus or scattering off free electrons; Antonucci & Miller, 1985), interacting and ionising the outflowing plasma wind. This observed continuum is modelled with a reflection component (same REFL as the ionising SED; see

above) for the hard X-rays (PN data), with an addition of a simple power-law component for the soft X-ray band (RGS data), for completeness. As I am only interested in the photoionised emission lines within NGC 1068, an ad hoc continuum, in the form of a simple observed power-law plus reflection, is justified. Therefore I fit N_{pow} , Γ_{pow} , and N_{refl} of the observed continuum.

The SED set-up in Sections 5.3.1 and 5.3.2 are used in both the preliminary work (Section 5.4) and the simultaneous fitting (Sections 5.5 - 5.6.4).

5.3.3 Galaxy Absorption

In addition to the SED being the same in all the models, the Galaxy absorption is also unchanged throughout this Chapter. The Galaxy absorption was modelled with the H0T component, setting the total hydrogen column density to $N_H^{Gal} = 3.34 \times 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-2}$, made up from both HI (Kalberla et al., 2005a) and H₂ (Wakker, 2006). For a neutral Galactic gas, I fixed the temperature and turbulent velocity to $T_{Gal} = 0.5 \text{ eV}$ and $v_{turb}^{Gal} = 5.62 \pm 3.19 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (for details of obtaining this turbulent velocity result, see Appendix C), respectively. All fitted components are redshifted ($z = 0.0038$; Huchra et al., 1999) and then absorbed by the Galaxy medium in this model.

5.4 Preliminary Modelling

In this Section, I study the RGS and EPIC-PN spectra separately from the 2000 (Sections 5.4.1 and 5.4.2) and 2014 (Sections 5.4.3 and 5.4.4) observations, respectively. This is the preliminary work before fitting both RGS and EPIC-PN spectra simultaneously in Sections 5.5 - 5.6. In this Section, the EPIC-PN data were binned by a factor of 3, the same as the RGS spectra, while the data shown in Figure 5.5 is binned for the simultaneous fitting. Figure 5.5 displays the RGS (top) and EPIC-PN (bottom) spectra of NGC 1068, in the observed reference frame, comparing both epochs, where the main emission lines are labelled with their respective ions. The spectra in Figure 5.5 show very little to no variability between the two observations (as noted by Marinucci et al., 2016).

Figure 5.5: Comparing the RGS (top) and EPIC-PN (bottom) spectra of NGC 1068 from 2000 (red) and 2014 (blue), in the observed reference frame. All spectra show a striking similarity in shape, emission features and flux, suggesting no change between the two epochs. The EPIC-PN data, shown in the bottom panel, was binned for the simultaneous fit, whereas the spectrum for the preliminary work is shown in Figure 5.8, binned the same as the RGS spectrum (top).

5.4.1 2000 Observation: RGS Modelling

The initial C-statistic from fitting the observed power-law (N_{pow} and Γ_{pow} ; Section 5.3.2) to the 2000 RGS spectrum was $C = 56376$ for 1560 degrees of freedom (d.o.f, hereafter). As the C-statistic is significantly higher compared to the d.o.f, I note the change in C-statistic (ΔC) for the change in d.o.f ($\Delta d.o.f$).

5.4.1.1 Emission Line Regions

I modelled the photoionised emission lines in NGC 1068 using the self-consistent photoionisation model PION (Mehdipour et al., 2016b) in SPEX (for details, see Section 2.3.2 in Chapter 2). I fitted one component at a time, fixing the previous component before adding the next, until no further improvement on the overall fit statistic was achieved. In all PION components, I fitted the column density (N_H), ionisation parameter (ξ), outflow and turbulent velocities (v_{out} and v_{turb} , respectively) and the covering fraction ($C_{cov} = \Omega/4\pi$). The first and second PION components (EM1 and EM2) improved the fit by $\Delta C = 35449$ and $\Delta C = 2982$, respectively (with $\Delta d.o.f = 5$ for both). I then refitted the two components, together with the continuum (POW parameters) improving the fit by $\Delta C = 1460$ (for $\Delta d.o.f = 12$). A third PION component had no statistical improvement on the fit, nor was the column density large enough to produce any emission lines.

5.4.1.2 Abundances

Next I fitted for the abundances of C, N, Ne, Mg, and Fe, relative to oxygen as the O VII triplet is the most dominant feature (this was also done by Kraemer et al., 2015, for the same reason). I coupled these five abundances of EM2 to the respective ions in EM1 and fitted them in EM1, significantly improving the fit by $\Delta C = 2571$ ($\Delta d.o.f = 5$).

5.4.1.3 Collisionally Ionised Plasma

After fitting the PION components, and the abundances, I still found residuals in some of the emission features (mostly in the region $< 18 \text{ \AA}$). Although the

large consensus regarding CIE plasma is that it is not the dominant source for X-ray emission in the nucleus of NGC 1068 (e.g. [Young et al., 2001](#); [Ogle et al., 2003](#); [Kinkhabwala et al., 2002](#)), there is evidence of a star formation ring (see [Figure 5.1](#); e.g. [García-Burillo et al., 2014](#)). Therefore, I did add a CIE component to the model. This is not to model the resonance lines ([Kinkhabwala et al., 2002](#)), as PION takes these into account, but rather to fit the residuals in the emission spectrum between 8 and 17 Å, which are not explained through photoionisation modelling (also found in [Kraemer et al., 2015](#)). In NGC 7469, [Behar et al. \(2017\)](#) found residuals in the RGS spectrum at 15.3 and 17.4 Å (Fe XVII) which were actually due to emission in CIE plasma from the starburst region.

Therefore, I introduced a CIE component in SPEX (CI1, hereafter). Fitting for the electron temperature (T_e), emission measure (EM) and outflow velocity (v_{out}), this component improved the fit by $\Delta C = 4800$ ($\Delta d.o.f = 3$). A second CIE component did not statistically improve the fit. After fitting all the parameters together (including POW and PION) to the RGS spectrum, I obtained a C-statistic of $C = 5658$ for 1542 d.o.f.

5.4.1.4 Fitting between 8 and 20 Å

There were, however, still some residuals in the fit between 8 and 17 Å, which was also found by [Kraemer et al. \(2015\)](#). The residuals were due to the over prediction of, for example, the O VIII RRC (14.4 Å) and the Fe XVIII line (14 Å). In addition, there is an under prediction of the model to the data between 10 and 12 Å (and even down to 8 Å), even after taking into account both CIE and PIE plasmas (see [Figure 5.6](#)). To try and explain this under prediction, I wanted to test whether the abundances had an effect on the emission features. Therefore, using the current RGS best fit model, I fitted it to the 8 to 20 Å region (ignoring any data points below or above this range) in two ways: (i) with the abundances in each component coupled, and (ii) decoupling the abundances in the CIE component and fitting them separately. The initial C-statistic within this wavelength range was $C = 2131$ (401 d.o.f).

In both models I fitted the parameters in EM1 first, with the power-law free. As EM2 does not account for any emission features in this wavelength range I fixed its parameters. I then fitted the CIE component in both models, before fitting the abundances, either (i) coupled to those in EM1 or (ii) separately in the CIE component, initially with the values fixed at solar. Finally, I freed all the parameters together to obtain a best fit in the 8 to 20 Å range of $C = 1750$ (386 d.o.f) for (i), and $C = 1690$ (381 d.o.f) for (ii). Although these are fairly good fits, there were still residuals throughout the wavelength range.

Figure 5.6 shows the RGS spectrum between 8 and 20 Å fitted with the different models (i) and (ii). Comparatively, there is little difference in the spectral fitting between these two models; the only major difference is at 16.8 Å where model (ii) (blue line in Figure 5.6) still over predicts the O VII RRC compared to model (i) (red line). As there is no significant difference between the models and parameter values, I assume that the chemical abundances are the same throughout the PIE and CIE regions within the nucleus of NGC 1068. Therefore, I coupled the five abundances of all model components to those in EM1 in all the following analysis.

The final test I tried was fitting the turbulence of the CIE plasma, with the parameter v_t . Freeing this parameter improved the fit by $\Delta C = 450$. Unfortunately, however, the continuum between 10 and 12 Å is still very much under predicted, possibly due to a blend of iron and nickel lines that the model cannot fully account for. In addition, the O VIII RRC (14.4 Å) and the line at 15.5 Å are not fitted well with the model, this could be because the latter feature is a blend of O VIII γ and Fe XVII. This mismatch was initially put down to incomplete atomic data for the emission line ions in Kraemer et al. (2015), however, the current version of SPEX uses the most up to date atomic models (Gu et al., 2019), so there may be some other underlying factor prevents this region from being modelled well (e.g. the continuum is not well fitted or rather there is too much line blending and no significant emission features in this 10 to 12 Å region). Another factor may be down to the underlying ionis-

Figure 5.6: Comparing the difference between coupling the abundances in CI1 to those in EM1 (red line) and fitting the abundances in CI1 separately (blue line), within the 8 to 20 Å range of the 2000 RGS spectrum. It is clear that there is very little difference in the two scenarios, implying that it does not matter how the abundances are fitted. From here, I assume that the abundances are the same throughout the nucleus of NGC 1068, and couple the CI1 abundances to those in EM1.

ing continuum that I have assumed here (adopted from NGC 7469). However, all analysis of the RGS and Chandra data have found an under prediction between the model and the data in this region (e.g. [Kinkhabwala et al., 2002](#); [Brinkman et al., 2002](#); [Kraemer et al., 2015](#)).

5.4.1.5 Refitting the Full RGS Spectrum

Finally, after fitting the model in the 8 - 20 Å range, I went back to the full RGS range (7 to 38 Å). From the current best fit model ($C = 5658$ for 1542 d.o.f, made up from Sections 5.4.1.1 - 5.4.1.3), and with the abundances in all emission components coupled, I freed the turbulent velocity parameter (v_t) in CIE, improving the fit by $\Delta C = 558$, with all parameters free (EM1, EM2, CI1 and the power-law). The final best fit model was $C = 5100$ for 1541 d.o.f; the best fit parameters are shown in Tables 5.3, 5.4 and 5.5, and the spectrum is shown in Figure 5.7 (left).

Table 5.3: Best fit parameter values for the photoionised emission lines in the RGS spectra of NGC 1068. Both 2000 (top) and 2014 (bottom) models required two photoionisation components to fit the emission lines. For each observation, the normalisation and photon index of the power-law (POW), which make up the observed continuum, are also presented.

Emission Component	N_H (10^{25} m^{-2})	$\log \xi$ (10^{-9} Wm)	v_{turb} (km s^{-1})	v_{out} (km s^{-1})	$C_{cov} = \Omega/4\pi$ *	ΔC
2000 RGS						
EM1	$4.83^{+0.07}_{-0.23}$	1.38 ± 0.01	610 ± 10	-230 ± 10	3.30 ± 0.10	35449
EM2	14.26 ± 0.30	0.29 ± 0.02	337 ± 15	-292^{+10}_{-20}	0.86 ± 0.02	2982
POW: Norm ^a = $5.56^{+0.08}_{-0.09} \times 10^4$			$\Gamma = 5.40 \pm 0.02$			
2014 RGS						
EMA	6.32 ± 0.05	1.28 ± 0.01	556 ± 10	-226 ± 10	3.03 ± 0.02	79491
EMB	$29.64^{+0.02}_{-0.08}$	0.14 ± 0.01	424 ± 15	-420 ± 10	0.38 ± 0.01	6110
POW: Norm ^a = $2.88 \pm 0.03 \times 10^4$			$\Gamma = 6.11 \pm 0.01$			

^a $\times 10^{44} \text{ Ph keV}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 1 keV. * $\times 10^{-2}$

Table 5.4: Abundances of the first emission components in the 2000 (EM1, top) and 2014 (EMA, bottom) RGS observations. I coupled any other emission components to these values, as I assumed the same chemical enrichment throughout the nucleus of NGC 1068.

Obs.	C	N	Ne	Mg	Fe	ΔC
EM1 (2000)	1.60 ± 0.05	4.00 ± 0.10	1.50 ± 0.05	1.60 ± 0.10	0.50 ± 0.05	2571
EMA (2014)	1.46 ± 0.01	$3.81^{+0.06}_{-0.01}$	1.30 ± 0.02	1.39 ± 0.03	0.41 ± 0.01	842

Table 5.5: Best fit parameter values for collisionally ionised plasma in the 2000 (top) and 2014 (bottom) RGS observations.

CIE (Obs.)	EM ($\times 10^{70} \text{ m}^{-3}$)	T (keV)	v_{out} (km s^{-1})	v_t (km s^{-1})	ΔC
CI1 (2000)	1.15 ± 0.01	0.75 ± 0.01	-55^{+15}_{-40}	1240^{+45}_{-36}	4800
CIA (2014)	1.31 ± 0.01	0.75 ± 0.01	-230 ± 20	1420 ± 30	10647

Figure 5.7: RGS spectra (grey crosses) for 2000 (left; Section 5.4.1) and 2014 (right; Section 5.4.3), with the best fit models over plotted in red. The coloured lines show the contributions to each emission feature from each emission component: EM1 and EMA (blue lines), EM2 and EMB (green lines), and CI1 and CIA (orange lines). The bottom slice of each panel displays the residuals between the best fit model and the data, giving a good indication to which features are not modelled well.

5.4.2 2000 Observation: EPIC-PN Modelling

The reflection spectrum in the hard (2 - 10 keV) X-ray energy band of NGC 1068 has many emission lines (Matt et al., 2004; Pounds & Vaughan, 2006). Matt et al. (2004) and Pounds & Vaughan (2006) modelled these features with Gaussian components from 6.8 to 8.8 keV. Although they give an indication on the line strength and energy shift (to determine velocity), Gaussian components do not give any insight about the properties of the plasma itself, such as its ionisation or column density. Therefore, to model these emission lines, I

Table 5.6: Best fit parameters for the continuum fitted to the 2000 and 2014 EPIC-PN spectra.

Component	Parameter	Value
2000		
POW	Norm ^a	$2.63^{+0.06}_{-0.04}$
REFL	Norm ^b	1.15 ± 0.02
	σ (km s ⁻¹)	2440 ± 300
2014		
POW	Norm ^a	$2.60^{+0.02}_{-0.05}$
REFL	Norm ^b	1.19 ± 0.01
	σ (km s ⁻¹)	1870^{+210}_{-240}
REDS	v_{shift} (km s ⁻¹)	$-3.60^{+0.12}_{-0.07} \times 10^3$

^a $\times 10^{49}$ ph s⁻¹ keV⁻¹ at 1 keV;

^b $\times 10^{51}$ ph s⁻¹ keV⁻¹.

used the PION component in the same way as Section 5.4.1.1.

The EPIC-PN continuum was modelled with two components, using the same observed continuum (POW and REFL) from Section 5.3.2. The normalisations of both these continuum components were fitted to the 2-10 keV spectrum, yielding a C-statistic of $C = 2128$ for 531 d.o.f. I then fitted two PION components, freeing the same five parameters in Section 5.4.1.1 (N_H , ξ , v_{out} , v_{turb} , and C_{cov}). The first component improved the fit to $C = 1099$ ($\Delta C = 1029$ and $\Delta d.o.f = 7$). I then fitted a second PION component, improving the fit to $C = 971$ ($\Delta C = 128$ and $\Delta d.o.f = 7$). The abundances of Si, S, Ar, Ca, and Ni, with respect to Fe, were fitted, improving the fit by $\Delta C = 25$ ($\Delta d.o.f = 5$). Both the PION components were then freed, giving a best fit of $C = 802$ (for 518 d.o.f).

Finally, I coupled the REFL component with a VGAU component to determine the velocity broadness (σ) of the material that produces the Fe K α line. Fitting all the parameters together achieved a final best fit of $C = 726$ for 517 d.o.f. The best fit model is displayed in Figure 5.8; Table 5.6 shows the best fit continuum results, Table 5.7 presents the best fit PION parameter values of this model, and Table 5.8 displays the abundances.

Figure 5.8: Best fit model to the 2000 EPIC-PN spectrum (red line), with the different components shown in the different colours. The continuum is made up of a power-law (orange line) and a reflection component (purple line). The emission lines are modelled with two PION components EM3 (blue line) and EM4 (green line). The bottom panel shows the residuals between the model and the data. The model fits the data well, except at 7.4 keV, where the Ni $K\alpha$ emission line is.

Table 5.7: Best fit PION parameter values of the models fitted to the 2000 (top) and 2014 (bottom) EPIC-PN spectra.

Emission Comp.	N_H (1)	$\log \xi$ (2)	v_{turb} (3)	v_{out} (3)	$C_{cov} = \Omega/4\pi$ *	ΔC
2000 PN						
EM3	49.0 ± 2.0	3.88 ± 0.02	2700 ± 300	-1290^{+260}_{-160}	0.22 ± 0.01	1029
EM4	$22.4^{+3.5}_{-1.0}$	2.14 ± 0.05	7440 ± 1000	-2100 ± 850	$0.16^{+0.05}_{-0.01}$	128
2014 PN						
EMC	28 ± 1	3.84 ± 0.01	1430^{+340}_{-360}	-94^{+160}_{-130}	$0.37^{+0.01}_{-0.02}$	3290
EMD	193 ± 10	1.90 ± 0.04	7610^{+520}_{-550}	-210^{+190}_{-150}	$0.06^{+0.02}_{-0.01}$	612

The units of the PION parameters are: (1) 10^{25} m^{-2} ; (2) 10^{-9} Wm ; (3) km s^{-1}
* $\times 10^{-3}$

Table 5.8: Best fit abundances fitted in the first PION component within the EPIC-PN spectra of the two epochs. All abundances are relative to iron. Parameter values set at 1 (f) are fixed at their solar values as fitting them had no significant impact on the C-statistic.

Obs.	Si	S	Ar	Ca	Ni
EM3 (2000)	0.01 ± 0.01	$0.28^{+0.02}_{-0.05}$	$0.20^{+0.13}_{-0.10}$	1 (f)	1 (f)
EMC (2014)	< 0.002	$0.18^{+0.05}_{-0.01}$	$0.28^{+0.04}_{-0.01}$	$0.85^{+0.15}_{-0.13}$	$1.33^{+0.28}_{-0.24}$

5.4.3 2014 Observation: RGS Modelling

For the 2014 observation, the C-statistic from fitting the RGS spectrum with just the power-law was $C = 118033$ for 1540 d.o.f. In a similar fashion to the 2000 RGS spectrum, I fitted the photoionised emission features in the 2014 spectrum with one PION component at a time, freeing the same five parameters (N_H , ξ , v_{turb} , v_{out} , and C_{cov}). Again, two PION components (EMA and EMB) accounted for the photoionised emission features in the 2014 RGS spectrum of NGC 1068, with $\Delta C_{EMA} = 79491$ and $\Delta C_{EMB} = 6110$ ($\Delta d.o.f = 5$ for both), respectively. A third PION component did not improve the fit, but fitting both EMA and EMB together reduced the C-statistic further by $\Delta C = 2120$ for $\Delta d.o.f = 11$.

I then fitted the C, N, Ne, Mg, and Fe abundances, relative to the solar value of O. These abundances were fitted in EMA (EMB had the abundance values coupled to EMA), significantly improving the fit by $\Delta C = 842$ ($\Delta d.o.f = 5$). I refitted together the two PION components, along with N_{pow} and Γ_{pow} , which substantially improved the fit again by $\Delta C = 4717$ for $\Delta d.o.f = 17$.

Similar to fitting the 2000 spectrum, there were still many unaccounted for emission lines after fitting the two PION components and the abundances. A third PION component did not improve the C-statistic, so I introduced a CIE component (CIA, hereafter), with both PION components were fixed. CIA, with abundances coupled to those in EMA (assuming the same chemical composition throughout the nucleus and starburst region of NGC 1068; see Section 5.4.1.4), improved the statistical fit significantly by $\Delta C = 10647$ for $\Delta d.o.f = 5$.

All the components were fitted together to get a best fit of $C = 10210$ for

1519 d.o.f ($\Delta C = 3396$). I then freed the turbulent velocity parameter (v_t) in CIA which significantly improved the fit by $\Delta C = 1926$. Similar to the 2000 observation, fitting v_t decreased the over prediction of most of these emission lines between 8 and 16 Å, except for the O VII RRC (at 14 Å) and the Ne X α line (at 12 Å). In addition, the RGS region between 10 and 12 Å was also under predicted in the 2014 spectrum (see right side of Figure 5.7).

The final best fit model for the 2014 RGS spectrum gave a C-statistic of $C = 8273$ (for 1537 d.o.f). Figure 5.7 (right side) displays the best fit model to the emission line features in the RGS spectrum. The best fit photoionisation emission components are shown in Table 5.3, the abundances fitted in EM3 are shown in Table 5.4, and Table 5.5 displays the parameters from the CIE component.

5.4.4 2014 Observation: EPIC-PN Modelling

I modelled the 2014 EPIC-PN spectrum with a reflection continuum in the same way as for the 2000 observation, using a power-law (POW) and reflection component (REFL). However, the 2014 EPIC-PN spectrum is a little more difficult to model due to the Fe K α line being slightly blueshifted relative to its expected energy. Therefore in this preliminary work I account for this energy shift by coupling the observed REFL component with a second REDS component in SPEX. See Section 5.2.1, and Figures 5.3 and 5.4 for details.

With this additional velocity shift of REFL, the C-statistic was $C = 5609$ (for 530 d.o.f), compared to $C = 8367$ (for 531 d.o.f) without this adjustment. I therefore used the velocity shifted reflection model when fitting for the emission lines, coupling this REDS component to each PION component to account for the energy shift.

The emission lines in the 2014 EPIC-PN spectrum were fitted with PION components, freeing the same five parameters in Section 5.4.3. The first PION component (EMC) improved the fit by $\Delta C = 3289$ ($\Delta d.o.f = 7$), which accounted for the iron emission lines very well. A second PION component (EMD) improved the C-statistic by $\Delta C = 612$ ($\Delta d.o.f = 7$), removing the residuals at

lower energies. Refitting both PION components together improved the fit by $\Delta C = 36$.

Finally, I fitted the abundances of Ni, Si, S Ar, and Ca, relative to Fe, in EMC (EMD abundances were coupled to EMC), improving the fit by a respectable $\Delta C = 50$ ($C = 1491$ for 516 d.o.f). Coupling REFL with a VGAU component to obtain the velocity broadness of the Fe $K\alpha$ line improved the fit by $\Delta C = 34$. The final best fit for the 2014 EPIC-PN spectrum is $C = 1400$ for d.o.f = 514, with all the parameters fitted together. The best fit continuum, emission lines, and abundance values are shown in Tables 5.6, 5.7 and 5.8, respectively. I note here that the outflow velocities of EMC and EMD in 2014 are significantly lower compared to the 2000 component velocities. This is most likely because I have used the same REDS component that is coupled to the REFL model.

5.4.5 Preliminary Summary

From this preliminary work, I have shown that both RGS and EPIC-PN spectra required two photoionised emission components to explain the emission line features found in both 2000 and 2014. In addition, a CIE component is required to account for some of the RGS features that photoionised plasma could not explain.

For the photoionised plasma, the ionisation parameters of these emission components in 2000 and 2014 range between $\log \xi = 0.1$ and 1.4 in the RGS spectrum (see Table 5.3) and between $\log \xi = 2$ and 4 in the EPIC-PN spectrum (see Table 5.7). Both the turbulent velocity and column density of the RGS components are, at least, an order of magnitude smaller than the values found in the EPIC-PN spectrum; the covering factors between the two instruments differ by a factor of 10 to 100. I also found the outflow velocities of the RGS spectrum components to be smaller ($v_{out}^{RGS} = -230$ to -420 km s⁻¹) compared to the EPIC-PN components ($v_{out}^{PN} = -100$ to -2000 km s⁻¹). The lower values for the 2014 EPIC-PN velocities are due to the PION components being coupled to the same REDS component as REFL.

From these results, I can get an indication on the distances from the SMBH, if I assume the outflow velocity (v_{out}) is the escape velocity. From this, EM3 and EM4 are situated at $r_{EM3} = 0.08$ and $r_{EM4} = 0.03$ pc from the central black hole (using the velocities from Table 5.7). As a comparison, the distances of the emission line components found in the RGS spectrum are $r_{EM1} = 2.6$ and $r_{EM2} = 1.6$ pc for EM1 and EM2 (using the outflow velocities in Table 5.3). From the 2014 results, $r_{EMC} = 15.7$ and $r_{EMD} = 3.1$ pc, which are significantly further away from the SMBH compared to EMA ($r_{EMA} = 2.7$ pc) and EMB ($r_{EMB} = 0.8$ pc). The most likely reason why the v_{out} parameters are much lower in 2014 compared to 2000 (Table 5.7) is because the PION components are coupled to the same REDS component that corrects for the EPIC-PN energy shift for the 2014 observation. If a different correction (REDS) component was used for the PION model, the v_{out} values may be more consistent with the 2000 results. Furthermore, RGS has many more lines and a better resolution compared to EPIC-PN, therefore accurate wavelength shifts and outflow velocities can be obtained. The narrow components in the RGS spectrum are likely to originate from the NLR, while there is some discrepancy between the two broader components found in the EPIC-PN spectra from each epoch.

The broadening velocities of EM4/EMD ($\sim 7400 - 7600$ km s⁻¹) are significantly larger compared to the values for EM3/EMC ($\sim 1500 - 3000$ km s⁻¹), as shown in Table 5.7. This very large broadening velocity for EM4/EMD is likely to be a result of multiple radial velocities which is seen as a very broad feature in the spectrum, e.g. at 2.5 keV in Figure 5.8. This means that it is unlikely that the line broadening is a result of the natural motion of the ions in the plasma causing the observed turbulence, but rather a combination of many radial velocities. This could suggest these high- ξ components come from the BLR, as the typical broadening velocities are between 1000 and 10,000 km s⁻¹ for the BLR in Seyfert 1 AGN (e.g. Netzer, 2013, 2015).

On the other hand, as the nucleus of NGC 1068 is obscured, we are only

able to directly observe the photoionised emission from the NLR. Although the arguments on the distances, broadening velocity, and ionisation states suggest that EM3/EMC and EM4/EMD could come from the BLR (or at least from close to the black hole) after being reflected off the circumnuclear material, we cannot see the BLR due to the LOS obscuration. Therefore, I conclude that EM3/EMC and EM4/EMD are more likely to come from the NLR. This may mean that both models in the RGS and EPIC-PN spectra are fitting the same component separately (high energy in the RGS, but lower energy in the PN, for example EM1 and EM4, respectively). To conclusively determine this, I need to fit the RGS and EPIC-PN spectra simultaneously (see Section 5.5).

5.5 Modelling RGS and EPIC-PN Data Simultaneously

Modelling the RGS and EPIC-PN spectra separately of NGC 1068 in 2000 and 2014 has unveiled a plethora of information regarding the environment around the central AGN (Section 5.4). In order to conclusively determine the emission feature properties and their locations in NGC 1068 across the 0.35 - 10 keV energy range, I fitted both RGS and EPIC-PN spectra simultaneously in each epoch (see Figure 5.9), thus allowing me to obtain better continuum constraints compared to using just RGS or EPIC-PN data individually. In this Section, I describe the analysis of fitting the RGS and EPIC-PN spectra simultaneously in 2000 and 2014.

As the same continuum model goes through both RGS and EPIC-PN data points, covering the whole X-ray band (0.35 - 10 keV, shown in Figure 5.9), it is acceptable to have no or little overlap between RGS and EPIC-PN data. I wanted the high-resolution spectral features to be fitted well with RGS and the fitting not be affected by the statistically dominant EPIC-PN data. Therefore, to reduce the weighted fitting bias of the EPIC-PN continuum, which has higher flux counts at lower energies compared to the RGS spectrum, I ignore the EPIC-PN data below 1.7 keV. This has been done in previous works whereby the EPIC-PN data are excluded in the RGS range (see e.g. [Kaastra et al., 2014](#); [Mehdipour et al., 2017](#)). Therefore, the RGS spectrum covers the energy range between 0.35 - 1.7 keV ($\sim 7 - 37 \text{ \AA}$) and the EPIC-PN spectrum accounts for the 1.7 - 10 keV range (Figure 5.9). I binned the EPIC-PN data using the optimal method as described by [Kaastra & Bleeker \(2016\)](#), whereas the RGS data are binned by a factor of 3 (see Figure 5.5). This corresponds to an average bin size of 0.04 \AA , which still over-samples the RGS resolution element of $\sim 0.07 \text{ \AA}$ FWHM.

5.5.1 Data Analysis

In both 2000 and 2014 spectra, I modelled the full 0.35 - 10 keV observed X-ray continuum by fixing both the POW and REFL parameters to the values in Table 5.2. However, I did fit the normalisation parameters of both POW (N_{pow}) and REFL (N_{refl} ; same as the ionising reflection component described in Section 5.3.1), and the photon index (Γ_{pow}) for the power-law, which was initially set to 2.1 (Matt et al., 2004; Pounds & Vaughan, 2006; Bauer et al., 2015); Γ_{refl} in REFL was fixed at 2.1 throughout the modelling. I also coupled a VGAU component to REFL to obtain a measurement for the velocity broadness (σ) of the Fe K α line. From modelling both EPIC-PN and RGS spectra together, I am able to constrain the reflection continuum in this energy range as well as the X-ray emission line region. I modelled the two epochs in the same way, as follows.

The ionising SED was taken from Section 5.3 and Table 5.2, adopted from NGC 7469. This ionising SED is fed into each PION component, to model the photoionised emission lines in the spectrum. The Galaxy absorption was modelled with the HOT component in the same way as Section 5.3.3.

To model the emission features in both spectra, I fitted PION components, freeing the column density (N_H), ionisation parameter (ξ), covering fraction (C_{cov}), and outflow and turbulent velocities (v_{out} and v_{turb} , respectively). During the modelling, I fitted one component at a time, fixing the previous component before adding the next, until no further improvement on the overall fit statistic was achieved.

After fitting the PION components, I still found residuals in some of the emission features, mostly in the region between 14 - 18 Å (see the preliminary work, Section 5.4.1.4 for details). Therefore, I introduced a CIE component, fitting the electron temperature (T_e), emission measure (EM), and outflow (v_{out}) and turbulent (v_t) velocities. Figure 5.10 shows that some of the emission lines in the 2000 RGS spectrum could not be explained by PIE plasma (blue line), but were accounted for when I fitted for CIE plasma (orange line).

Figure 5.9: Combined RGS and EPIC-PN spectra for the 2000 (blue and red) and 2014 (green and purple) observations, in the observed reference frame. I simultaneously fit both RGS and EPIC-PN spectra for each epoch to model all emission features and the observed continuum over the full 0.35 - 10 keV energy range.

The elemental abundances fitted in this model were for C, N, O, Ne, Mg, Si, S, Ar, Ca and Ni, all with respect to Fe (relative to solar; fixed at $A_{Fe} = 1$), as Fe emission lines are found in both RGS and EPIC-PN spectra (oxygen is the strongest feature only in the RGS energy band). However, as C, N, O, Ne and Mg are only found in the RGS energy range, and Si, S, Ar, Ca and Ni are only present in the EPIC-PN spectrum, I split the abundances up into two PION components when fitting. The first PION component accounting for the high energy emission lines, fitted the five higher Z elements and the second PION component (RGS band) accounted for the five lower Z elements. The remaining PION and CIE components had their abundance values coupled to these two PION components. This meant that the model fitted the abundances for all the lines from each component, but with each element free only once. In order to do this, I assumed that the chemical enrichment is the same in all emitting plasma regions (PIE or CIE) throughout the AGN nucleus and starburst region of NGC 1068.

Table 5.9: Observed continuum best fit parameter values for the 2000 (top) and 2014 (bottom) observations; σ corresponds to the velocity width of the Fe K α line.

Obs.	Component	Parameter	Value
2000	POW	Norm ^a	$2.27^{+0.12}_{-0.05}$
		Γ_{pow}	2.24 ± 0.02
	REFL	Norm ^b	$9.47^{+0.23}_{-0.24}$
		σ (km s ⁻¹)	2120^{+270}_{-360}
2014	POW	Norm ^a	$2.06^{+0.03}_{-0.08}$
		Γ_{pow}	$2.18^{+0.02}_{-0.04}$
	REFL	Norm ^b	$8.86^{+0.15}_{-0.26}$
		σ (km s ⁻¹)	< 1800

^a $\times 10^{49}$ ph s⁻¹ keV⁻¹ at 1 keV; ^b $\times 10^{52}$ ph s⁻¹ keV⁻¹ at 1 keV.

5.5.2 Spectral results

In Figure 5.9, the combined RGS and EPIC-PN spectra show many complex features, a result of a mixture of many emission lines, some of which are blended, and an obscured continuum that is not easily modelled. This meant that acquiring a statistically significant best fit, represented by the C-statistic, was very challenging. Therefore, in both epochs, I used the change in C-statistic (ΔC) to signify the improvement on the best fit from each fitted component. Despite this however, ΔC can still be very large due to the complexity of the spectrum and its statistical quality. The change in C-statistic was with respect to the previous component, that I fixed when introducing the next component, unless stated otherwise.

5.5.2.1 2000 Best fit

The initial fitting of the observed continuum (POW and REFL), to the 2000 data, gave a C-statistic of $C = 58486$ (for 1075 d.o.f). Throughout the emission component fitting (PION and CIE), the continuum parameters were free to vary.

The first PION emission component (EM1) was required to fit the high energy emission lines in the EPIC-PN spectrum ($E > 6.4$ keV). This highly

Figure 5.10: RGS spectrum (grey points) between 8 and 20 Å of the 2000 observation for NGC 1068. The red line shows the best fit model and the blue line displays the photoionisation model made up of two PION components, fitting the majority of the emission lines in the RGS spectrum, except for the features at 15 and 17 Å. I therefore introduced a collisionally ionised component (CIE; orange line) to account for these emission lines from Fe XVII.

ionised ($\log \xi = 3.91$) component improved the fit with a fairly modest $\Delta C = 2200$. The second PION component (EM2; $\log \xi = 0.63$) accounted for many of the narrow emission lines in the RGS spectrum, improving the quality of the fit by $\Delta C = 35600$. When I fitted both EM1 and EM2 together, the fit improved by $\Delta C = 270$. A third PION component (EM3; $\log \xi = 1.84$) fitted lines in both RGS and EPIC-PN spectra, updating the fit by $\Delta C = 4700$. Again, I freed all (three) PION components, improving the fit by $\Delta C = 1600$. A fourth component (EM4; $\log \xi = 3.02$) further improved the fit, albeit not as significantly as the other three components, by $\Delta C = 220$. All four PION components were then fitted together, improving the model by a further $\Delta C = 240$.

The CIE component (CI1) improved the fit by $\Delta C = 1440$ (after fixing all the PION components), accounting for all the emission lines not produced by

photoionised plasma, with large enough statistical significance. I then freed and refitted all four PION components with the CIE component to obtain $\Delta C = 840$.

Finally, I fitted the abundances of the ten elements in the spectrum, with respect to iron. Firstly, I fixed all the parameters in the PION and CIE components, in order not to fit too many parameters at the same time, which could cause a degenerate result for the parameter values for the same ΔC . I fitted the abundances of the elements in EM2 for the RGS spectrum (C, N, O, Ne and Mg) followed by the high energy elements (Si, S, Ar, Ca and Ni) in EM1, improving the C-statistic by $\Delta C = 4900$ and $\Delta C = 330$, respectively. From this, I sequentially fitted the emission components, firstly EM1 and EM2 ($\Delta C = 220$) followed by EM3 and EM4 ($\Delta C = 500$), and then CI1 ($\Delta C = 500$), with all abundances left free throughout these last few steps. Here, all parameters were fitted to obtain a new global C-statistic minimum of $C = 4970$ for 1040 d.o.f.

Despite obtaining a relatively good fit so far, there was still an emission feature not accounted for. This line, belonging to the neutral Ni $K\alpha$ (7.4 keV), originates from neutral material, similar to the Fe $K\alpha$ line. As REFL in SPEX only accounts for neutral Fe, I fitted this line with a Gaussian (GAUS) for simplicity, freeing the normalisation, energy and line broadening, which improved the fit by $\Delta C = 130$. A similar approach was taken by [Semena et al. \(2019\)](#) for NGC 5643.

After fitting all the parameters together ($C = 4530$ for 1037 d.o.f), there were still many residuals where neither PION nor CIE had fitted the data well, in particular in the region between 32 and 36 Å. Therefore, I introduced some Gaussian components (GAUS) to the RGS data only. Four GAUS components were fitted to the lines at 35.6, 34.9, 34.3 and 32.2 Å, while keeping the other model parameters fixed, improving the best fit in the 2000 model by $\Delta C = 48, 219, 106, \text{ and } 66$, respectively. I note that there are no likely identifications with ion species for the lines fitted in the 32 to 36 Å wavelength range. There

was also a large residual at 8.4 Å, corresponding to the Mg XII Ly α line, that the PION components only half fitted. I therefore added another GAUS component for this line, improving the fit by $\Delta C = 56$. As these Gaussians do not add to the photoionisation modelling and have no physical meaning, but are introduced instead to achieve a statistical improvement in the fitted model, I kept the GAUS parameters fixed (after the initial fits). I also note that these Gaussian lines do not affect the overall parameter values of the photoionisation modelling. I then refitted all the parameters together and obtained final best fit C-statistic values of $C = 3790$ (for 1037 d.o.f). Unfortunately, in 2000 the model was still statistically poor: $\frac{C}{dof} = 3.65$. However, due to the complexity of such a rich spectrum, I was unable to improve the fit any further. The spectrum and final best fit model are shown in Figure 5.11, while the best fit parameter values are displayed in Tables 5.9, 5.10, 5.11, 5.12, and 5.13; all parameter errors were obtained with all fitted parameters free.

5.5.2.2 2014 Best Fit

For the 2014 data, I fitted first the continuum model (POW and REFL) to the combined spectrum where the initial global fit statistic was $C = 125643$ (for 1065 d.o.f). All continuum parameters were freed when fitting the emission lines.

For the 2014 spectrum, I also fitted four PION emission components. The first two components, EMA ($\log \xi = 3.96$) and EMB ($\log \xi = 0.67$), improved the fit by $\Delta C_{EMA} = 8600$ and $\Delta C_{EMB} = 76100$, respectively. Fitting these two components together gave a $\Delta C = 2700$. I then fitted a third component (EMC; $\log \xi = 1.91$) which yielded $\Delta C = 5740$. A further $\Delta C = 4670$ was achieved when I freed the parameters in EMA and EMB together with EMC. The fourth, and final, component (EMD; $\log \xi = 3.02$) improved the fit by $\Delta C = 1000$. When I fitted all four PION components together, I achieved a further improvement in the fit with $\Delta C = 540$.

Similarly to the 2000 spectrum, not all the emission lines were fitted with PION components, so I added a CIE component (CIA). CIA significantly im-

Table 5.10: Best fit parameter values for the PION components fitted to the 2000 (top) and 2014 (bottom) spectra.

Obs.	PION Comp.	N_H (1)	$\log\xi$ (2)	v_{turb} (3)	v_{out} (3)	$C_{cov} = \Omega/4\pi$	EM (4)	ΔC
2000	EM1	50^{+1}_{-2}	3.91 ± 0.02	2910^{+280}_{-260}	-610^{+200}_{-330}	0.19 ± 0.01	$2.7^{+0.1}_{-0.2}$	2200
	EM2	41 ± 2	0.63 ± 0.01	370 ± 10	-260 ± 10	0.03 ± 0.01	670^{+270}_{-240}	35600
	EM3	22 ± 1	1.84 ± 0.01	890 ± 20	-110 ± 10	0.04 ± 0.01	30^{+9}_{-8}	4700
	EM4	18 ± 1	$3.02^{+0.02}_{-0.01}$	960^{+120}_{-110}	-200^{+150}_{-70}	0.02 ± 0.01	$0.8^{+0.5}_{-0.4}$	220
2014	EMA	33^{+1}_{-2}	$3.96^{+0.02}_{-0.01}$	2910^{+420}_{-370}	-230^{+30}_{-90}	$0.32^{+0.03}_{-0.04}$	$2.7^{+0.2}_{-0.5}$	8600
	EMB	51 ± 1	0.67 ± 0.01	410 ± 10	-300 ± 10	0.02 ± 0.01	510 ± 260	76100
	EMC	29^{+2}_{-1}	1.91 ± 0.01	920 ± 20	-230 ± 10	0.04 ± 0.01	33 ± 10	5740
	EMD	37^{+3}_{-2}	$3.02^{+0.03}_{-0.02}$	1630^{+200}_{-160}	-530^{+150}_{-370}	0.01 ± 0.01	< 1.7	1000

The units of the PION parameters are: (1) 10^{25} m^{-2} ; (2) 10^{-9} W m ; (3) km s^{-1} ; (4) 10^{69} m^{-3} .

Figure 5.11: Best fit model to the 2000 spectrum of NGC 1068. I plot the soft X-ray (RGS) band in wavelength units and the hard X-ray (EPIC-PN) band in energy units for display purposes. The red line shows the best fit model to the data points (grey crosses) and the other coloured lines (labelled in the legends) represent each emission component in the model. The bottom panels display the residuals between the best fit model and the observed data points.

proved the fit by $\Delta C = 1960$. Refitting the four PION components with the CIE component further improved the fit by $\Delta C = 760$.

Next I fitted the abundances, subsequently to fixing all PION and CIE components. The five lower Z elements (C, N, O, Ne, Mg) were fitted in EMB (accounting for the RGS lines) obtaining $\Delta C = 10440$, while the five higher Z elements (Si, S, Ar, Ca, Ni) fitted in EMA improved the fit by $\Delta C = 420$. I then fitted the parameters in each component together, with the abundances free, starting with EMA and EMB, followed by EMC and EMD, giving changes in the C-statistic of $\Delta C = 790$ and $\Delta C = 2100$, respectively. I then freed the CIA parameters too and obtained a new best fit with a decrease in C-statistic of $\Delta C = 800$.

Finally, I accounted for the neutral Ni $K\alpha$ line at 7.4 keV with a Gaussian component (GAUS), fitting the normalisation, energy and broadening velocity.

Figure 5.12: Best fit model to the 2014 spectrum of NGC 1068. I plot the soft X-ray (RGS) band in wavelength units and the hard X-ray (EPIC-PN) band in energy units for display purposes. The red line shows the best fit model to the data points (grey crosses) and the other coloured lines (labelled in the legends) represent each emission component in the model. The bottom panels display the residuals between the best fit model and the observed data points.

Adding this line to the model improved the best fit by $\Delta C = 440$. However, I was unable to constrain these parameters so I fixed them to their initially fitted values in the subsequent fits and error searches (Table 5.13).

All the parameters were fitted together again to obtain a best fit of $C = 8510$ for 1027 d.o.f, but there were still residuals, like in 2000. In the 2014 data, adding the same four GAUSS components to the lines at 35.6, 34.9, 34.3 and 32.2 Å, with the other parameters fixed, improved the fit by $\Delta C = 105$, 466, 169, and 80, respectively, while the GAUSS component used to model the Mg XII Ly α line at 8.4 Å improved the fit by $\Delta C = 180$. I then refitted all the parameters together (except the GAUSS components) and obtained final best fit C-statistic values of $C = 7252$ (1027 d.o.f). Unfortunately, the model was still statistically poor: $\frac{C}{dof} = 7.06$, but as with the 2000 data, I was unable to improve the fit any further. The spectrum and final best fit model are shown

Table 5.11: Best fit collisionally ionised emission (CIE) component parameters, fitted to the 2000 (top) and 2014 (bottom) spectra.

Obs.	EM (10^{69} m^{-3})	T_e (keV)	v_{out} (km s^{-1})	v_t (km s^{-1})	ΔC
2000 (CI1)	$2.72^{+0.08}_{-0.06}$	0.57 ± 0.01	-40^{+30}_{-40}	1220^{+50}_{-70}	1440
2014 (CIA)	$2.19^{+0.06}_{-0.04}$	0.58 ± 0.01	-165 ± 30	1290^{+40}_{-50}	1960

in Figure 5.12, and the best fit parameter values are displayed in Tables 5.9 - 5.13.

5.5.2.3 Caveats and Model Complexities

The complex spectrum of NGC 1068, including line blending (e.g. the O VII forbidden line with the N VI RRC between 22 and 23 Å) and unresolved emission lines (e.g. Mg XI triplet at 9 Å), means I am unable to fit all the lines well. For many lines, in particular the He-like triplets, the model underpredicts these features, such that I obtain line ratios that are inconsistent with pure photoionised plasma. This comes down to the line-emitting regions in NGC 1068 being more complex than the model can completely match. The geometry and variations in the density and ionisation state of the gas, such as clumpy or stratified gas, all affect the overall line spectrum. Nevertheless, this PION model still gives a more useful insight than an empirical model with Gaussian line fitting.

In the modelling, the poor fit in both epochs may be a result of the assumed geometry of PION, which takes a slab of material and produces forward emission facing us. This simple geometry works very well with type 1 Seyfert AGN because we are observing the AGN and plasma from face on. However, for type 2 AGN, where we see the plasma from side on, the modelling becomes more complex, especially if the outflowing wind is emitting in an ionising cone (Kinkhabwala et al., 2002). Therefore, a simple slab geometry may break down here as the geometry is fundamental for radiation transfer issues, where resonance lines are sensitive to the column density and can vary depending on the line of sight. This being said, PION is an excellent tool at analysing

photoionised plasma self consistently, calculating the photoionisation balance on the fly and computing explicitly the photoionisation properties (ξ and N_H) of all the emission lines in the spectrum. However, if the underlying AGN environment is far more complex than assumed by PION, such as an outflowing cone seen in type 2 AGN, then the fitting of the spectra will be simplistic to some extent, explaining why I cannot fit some of the emission lines very well.

On the other hand, this is a common result with this CT AGN, as previous models have not been able to fully explain the Chandra or RGS spectra of NGC 1068, showing strong residuals. For example, [Kinkhabwala et al. \(2002\)](#) were unable to model many emission lines between 10 and 16 Å or above 34 Å (see their Figure 11); [Brinkman et al. \(2002\)](#) were able to fit the Chandra spectrum above 20 Å, but many of the emission lines below 16 Å were not fitted well (in their Figure 7); [Kraemer et al. \(2015\)](#) could not fit the emission lines below 17 Å and above 31 Å (see their Figures 1 and 4); while [Kallman et al. \(2014\)](#) were unable to model some of the strongest lines such as the O VII and Ne IX triplets.

Moreover, none of these modelling attempts accounted for the Fe XVII lines at 15 and 17 Å, which I model with a CIE component. This suggests either previous models did not account for photoexcitation, or CIE is a valid explanation. However, [Kinkhabwala et al. \(2002\)](#) did take these Fe XVII lines into account via photoexcitation, although the lines are not fitted in their plot (Figure 11), whereas [Brinkman et al. \(2002\)](#) say their model did not include the Fe-L transitions. [Gu et al. \(2019\)](#) tested the contributions to the population of levels by different processes within the Fe XVII ions, but did not consider photoexcitation. Further tests and comparisons are required in SPEX to fully understand these lines to reduce the limitations in the photoionisation codes, and to allow PION to treat photoexcitation properly. Although a CIE component here is able to account for the Fe XVII lines at 15 and 17 Å, photoexcitation is just as physically viable. Therefore both of these processes should be considered as possibilities in NGC 1068.

As a result, given the complexity of this spectrum, the models fitted (by [Kinkhabwala et al., 2002](#); [Brinkman et al., 2002](#); [Kallman et al., 2014](#); [Kraemer et al., 2015](#), and here) are unable to account for every feature. This means that in all the models the statistical fit is poor and there are many residuals. Only in this analysis do I quantify and compare the C-statistic of each component and its contribution to the final model.

As a further comparison, the type 1.5 AGN, NGC 4151, has a significantly similar RGS spectrum to that of NGC 1068, with many of the same emission features. The modelling of the soft X-ray spectra of NGC 4151 also shows strong under prediction of the continuum and some emission features (see Figure 3 and Figure 15 in [Schurch et al. 2004a](#) and [Beuchert et al. 2017](#), respectively), implying that it is difficult to obtain an acceptable model statistic, whilst fitting all the emission features in these obscured AGN.

5.5.2.4 Spectral Line Features

I display the complex spectra from the 2000 and 2014 observations in Figures [5.11](#) and [5.12](#), respectively. The best fit model is shown by the red lines, while the components are represented by different colours (see the legends in each figure). Four PION components were required to fit the majority of the emission lines, with similar ξ values in each epoch accounting for the same emission features. For example, EM1 and EMA (green lines) fit the same high energy features, whereas EM2 and EMB (purple lines) fit the same lower energy RGS features, in their respective epochs. This is the same for the CIE components.

Components EM1 and EMA fit the high energy Fe XXVI Ly α and Ly β , and Fe XXV resonance lines, present in the EPIC-PN spectrum. EM2 and EMB fit emission lines in the RGS band, such as the O VII and N VI triplets, O VII, N VI, C VI and C V RRCs, and C V and N VI H- and He-like species lines. EM3 and EMC fit the Mg XI triplet lines, Ne IX RRC, and the Ne IX He-like lines, in addition to the O VIII Ly α and Ly β , Si XII and S XIII lines, in both the RGS and EPIC-PN spectra. EM4 and EMD account for the Fe

XVII and Fe XX lines in the RGS spectrum, and the Fe XXV forbidden lines at 6.5 keV. The CIE component is required to explain the Fe XVII lines at 15.3 and 17.4 Å (see Figure 5.10).

I find that some emission features are accounted for by many components at the same time. These include Ne X, N VII and C VI Ly α lines, Si XIII and S XV lines, and the Ne IX triplet. In addition, some of the emission features (in the RGS band) are over predicted due to multiple components fitting them. These include the O VIII and N VI RRCs, the Mg XI forbidden line, and Fe XVIII and Fe XIX lines around 14 Å. On the other hand, I do account reasonably well for the features between 10 and 12 Å which were very underpredicted by Kraemer et al. (2015), who suggested that this was because the model had incomplete atomic data. However, there are still some residuals between 9 and 10 Å, but this may be a result of multiple lines being blended together.

5.5.2.5 Luminosities

I take the ionising luminosity (1 - 1000 Ryd or 13.6 eV - 13.6 keV) for both epochs to be $L_{ion} = 1.54 \pm 0.04 \times 10^{37}$ W, calculated from the assumed ionising SED; I use this value for further calculations (Section 5.6.1). In addition, I calculated the observed 2 - 10 keV luminosity (using POW and REFL parameters in Table 5.9) from the best fit model, where I obtain $L_{2-10}^{2000} = 1.07_{-0.04}^{+0.06} \times 10^{34}$ W and $L_{2-10}^{2014} = 1.04_{-0.03}^{+0.04} \times 10^{34}$ W, for the 2000 and 2014 observations respectively. The intrinsic 2 - 10 keV luminosity unveiled during a temporary decrease in absorption was $L_{obs, 2-10} = 7_{-4}^{+7} \times 10^{36}$ W (Marinucci et al., 2016). By taking the ratio between my observed 2 - 10 keV luminosities and the intrinsic luminosity, I find that roughly 0.15 per cent of the intrinsic X-ray source is reflected and scattered into our LOS.

5.5.3 Comparing Epochs

After fitting the simultaneous RGS and EPIC-PN spectra of NGC 1068 from 2000 and 2014, here I compare and discuss my overall findings and results from

Table 5.12: Best fit abundances with respect to iron. *Top:* abundances fitted to the 2000 observation. EM2 accounts for the elements in the RGS energy range while EM1 fits those in the EPIC-PN range. *Bottom:* abundances fitted to EMB for the RGS spectrum and EMA for EPIC-PN energies in the 2014 spectrum. The other components are coupled to these values such that all the lines are fitted by the ions in each component; I assume that the chemical enrichment is the same throughout the nucleus of NGC 1068.

2000	EM2 (RGS)	C	N	O	Ne	Mg	ΔC
		0.31 ± 0.01	0.67 ± 0.01	0.15 ± 0.01	0.32 ± 0.01	$0.38^{+0.01}_{-0.02}$	5200
	EM1 (PN)	Si	S	Ar	Ca	Ni	ΔC
		0.47 ± 0.01	0.58 ± 0.02	$0.83^{+0.06}_{-0.05}$	< 0.04	< 0.01	70
2014	EMB (RGS)	C	N	O	Ne	Mg	ΔC
		0.27 ± 0.01	$0.59^{+0.05}_{-0.06}$	0.13 ± 0.01	0.30 ± 0.01	0.36 ± 0.01	10600
	EMA (PN)	Si	S	Ar	Ca	Ni	ΔC
		0.42 ± 0.01	$0.63^{+0.02}_{-0.01}$	$0.67^{+0.04}_{-0.03}$	< 0.01	< 0.01	350

the photoionisation modelling.

5.5.3.1 Observed Continuum

Starting with the observed continuum (Table 5.9), both the power-law and reflection components differ between epochs. The photon index is flatter in 2014, while there is a decrease in normalisation for both POW and REFL components compared to 2000; they are not consistent within the uncertainties. I was able to constrain the line width (σ) of the neutral Fe K α line in 2000, but obtained an upper limit for 2014.

5.5.3.2 Photoionised plasma components

For the four PION components, I found very little difference in the ionisation parameters between the two observations. This suggests that the components with the same ionisation parameter in each epoch are the same plasma region. On the other hand, I did find the total equivalent column density increased from $N_H^{2000} = 131_{-6}^{+5} \times 10^{25} \text{ m}^{-2}$ in 2000 to $N_H^{2014} = 150_{-6}^{+7} \times 10^{25} \text{ m}^{-2}$ in 2014. This change of $\Delta N_H = 19 \times 10^{25} \text{ m}^{-2}$ is fairly significant, with an average of $\Delta C \sim 3900$, when substituting the N_H values from one epoch into the model of the other. Below I describe some possible reasons for this increase in the total equivalent column density.

A degeneracy was found between N_H and C_{cov} by Di Gesu et al. (2017) in their analysis of the Seyfert 1 AGN 1H 0419-577, using PION. This may explain the decrease in column density ($\Delta N_H = -17 \times 10^{25} \text{ m}^{-2}$) between EM1 and EMA, where there is an increase in covering fraction ($\Delta C_{cov} = 0.13$). For EM4 and EMD, the change in column density ($\Delta N_H = +19 \times 10^{25} \text{ m}^{-2}$) between the two epochs may actually be due to a degeneracy between N_H and v_{turb} . In this case there is a small change in covering fraction ($\Delta C_{cov} = 0.01$), but the turbulent velocity has increased by $\Delta v_{turb} = 670 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (the uncertainties in the parameters are smaller than this difference). This may be due to the large turbulent velocities being driven by line ratios, rather than line widths, causing changes in N_H between components and epochs. For EM2 and EMB, and EM3 and EMC, the changes in column density are $\Delta N_H = +10 \times 10^{25} \text{ m}^{-2}$

and $+7 \times 10^{25} \text{ m}^{-2}$, respectively. The change in C_{cov} is negligible, but the v_{turb} values increased by 40 and 30 km s^{-1} , respectively for EM2/B and EM3/C; this difference is larger than the uncertainties on the parameters for EM2/B. The varying N_H values between the two epochs are unlikely to be real, however, as there is very little spectral change between the two epochs (Figures 5.5 and 5.9). Therefore, the line column densities cannot vary as greatly as suggested here by the fit, and the most probable explanation for the increase in total N_H from 2000 and 2014 is model degeneracy with v_{turb} and C_{cov} .

The C_{cov} values for EM1 and EMA are significantly larger than the other three components, suggesting they are more extended as seen by the SMBH, and are therefore closer to it than the other components (see Eq. 5.5). These components also have broadening velocities (v_{turb} in Table 5.10) that are similar to the broadening velocity of the Balmer lines measured at $\sigma_{Balmer} \sim 3200 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (Antonucci & Miller, 1985), and with the line broadening velocities for BLRs found in type 1 AGN (e.g. Kollatschny & Zetzl, 2013). The v_{turb} measurements imply that these highly ionised components are close to the central SMBH, possibly consistent with the BLR, although we cannot observe the BLR directly due to obscuration from the torus. So for now, I assume all plasma regions are part of the NLR. A more likely explanation for the large broadening velocities of the high energy components is because we are observing this AGN from side on. As a result of our viewing angle to NGC 1068, a range of radial velocities are being observed that are not directly in our LOS, and as a result appear to be related to a highly broadened component. This is explained in more detail in Chapter 8, Section 8.1.1.

In addition, the emission measures (EM) of each PION component were calculated (see Table 5.10). The definition of the EM is given by $\int n_e n_H dV$, but as the number densities of electrons (n_e) and ions (n_H), respectively, are unknown, I use the following equation (e.g. Mao et al., 2019; Grafton-Waters et al., 2020)

$$EM = \frac{n_e}{n_H} \frac{4\pi N_H C_{cov} L_{ion}}{\xi}, \quad (5.1)$$

Table 5.13: Best fit Ni K α parameter values for 2000 (left) and 2014 (right) spectra. The 2014 parameter values could not be constrained, so I fixed (f) them to their initial fitted values.

Parameter	2000	2014
N (10^{47} ph s $^{-1}$)	2450^{+310}_{-550}	3600 (f)
E (keV)	$7.50^{+0.01}_{-0.22}$	7.47 (f)
σ (km s $^{-1}$)	4040^{+1070}_{-2170}	7000 (f)
ΔC	130	440

where $n_e/n_H \sim 1.2$ for fully ionised plasma and $L_{ion} = 1.54 \times 10^{37}$ W is the ionising SED luminosity (between 13.6 eV and 13.6 keV). For each PION component, if I assume a constant L_{ion} and C_{cov} , then EM depends on N_H and in particular ξ . If ξ is small, then the number density in the plasma is larger (for a fixed distance), which means EM (from the definition) increases, and this explains why the lower ionised plasmas have the highest EM values. The EM, ξ and N_H values for these four components in each epoch (Table 5.10) are consistent with the model components from Kallman et al. (2014).

5.5.3.3 Collisionally ionised plasma

The electron temperatures (T_e) and line widths (v_t) for each CIE component have not changed (within errors) between the two epochs, but the EM and v_{out} values are not consistent within the uncertainties (see Table 5.11). However, much like with the PION components, it is the outflow velocities that differ the most. In 2000, the outflow velocity is negligible with $v_{out} = -40^{+30}_{-40}$ km s $^{-1}$, whereas in 2014 the CIE plasma appears to be travelling at -165 ± 30 km s $^{-1}$.

Although the CIE components in each epoch account for the Fe XVII lines that PION did not fit, this is not an overall convincing conclusion. One argument against CIE is that the RGS spectra show strong, narrow RRC features, implying the X-ray emission is only from PIE plasma, making CIE unlikely in NGC 1068. However, RRC emission could come from outflowing PIE plasma closer to the black hole, while the CIE emission originates from further out, such as the secondary region or starburst region. In terms of the Fe-L lines themselves, the Fe XVII line at 17 Å is populated by recombination

rather than direct excitation, so PIE plasma should dominate this line. As for the Fe XVII resonance line at 15 Å, the 3d shell is highly populated if the plasma density is high (in a similar way the resonance line in He-like triplets is more dominant over the forbidden line if the density is large), suggesting that CIE plasma can account for this. Figure 2.8 (Liedahl et al., 1990) in Chapter 2 shows that the Fe XVII at 17 Å should be accounted for by PIE plasma, whereas the 15 Å line is emitted in CIE plasma, reiterating the arguments above. However, photoexcitation was not considered by Liedahl et al. (1990), and would explain the 15 Å resonance line (Sako et al., 2000; Kinkhabwala et al., 2002); in this case the explanation for the lack of PIE emission at 17 Å is, however, unknown. Therefore, the under-prediction of these lines by PION suggests the full picture is missing, and although CIE plasma can produce these Fe XVII lines (Figure 5.10), photoexcitation is a more natural process in the outflowing wind (Kinkhabwala et al., 2002). In spite of fitting a CIE component to each epoch to account for the Fe XVII lines, photoexcitation in PIE plasma cannot be dismissed.

5.5.4 Abundances

Table 5.12 displays the best fit values for the abundances fitted in this model; all abundances are sub-solar. As a comparison, the abundances fitted to the RGS data only in both epochs (Table 5.4) showed significantly super-solar values for C, N, Ne and Mg, while Fe was sub-solar. This could be due to RGS observing the whole galaxy in its FOV (similar to NGC 7469, as discussed in Section 4.3.1.6), which means that due to contamination from, for example, star forming regions in the host galaxy (see e.g. Bauer et al., 2015, and references within) there is a significant difference in abundances compared to solar values. In other words, the abundances measured here are not just from the outflowing wind plasma. On the other hand, the abundances fitted to the EPIC-PN spectra only (Table 5.8) show values that are significantly sub-solar (Si), slightly sub-solar (S, Ar and Ca), or slightly super-solar (Ni). This discrepancy from solar values is likely the result of EPIC-PN spectra having far

fewer emission features compared to RGS. As a result, the column densities and abundances are not as accurately measured via spectral fitting. Therefore, when I simultaneously fit the RGS and EPIC-PN spectra in each epoch, and couple the abundances together for the full X-ray range, the super-solar abundances from RGS and sub-solar abundances from EPIC-PN somewhat level out with each other. However, all the values in Table 5.12 are well below 1.

In previous studies of NGC 1068, the abundances of the photoionised gas were found to be non-solar, and attributed to, for example, shocks, supernovae, star forming regions (see e.g. [Bauer et al., 2015](#), and references within), and the result of multiple photoionisation models with various densities ([Kraemer et al., 2015](#)). Compared to other studies of NGC 1068, [Brinkman et al. \(2002\)](#) found the abundances were consistent with solar, while [Ogle et al. \(2003\)](#) found them to be within 50% of solar; the only outlier was the O abundance being four times lower in the nuclear region. Both [Brinkman et al. \(2002\)](#) and [Ogle et al. \(2003\)](#) studied NGC 1068 with Chandra data. Comparatively, [Kinkhabwala et al. \(2002\)](#) found the abundances to be consistent with solar from their study of the 2000 RGS data, except the value for nitrogen was three times larger than its solar value. In addition, [Kraemer et al. \(2015\)](#) (who also studied the 2000 RGS spectrum) found N and C to be six and three times solar, respectively, while the other elements were 1.5 times larger. [Kraemer et al. \(2015\)](#) put this down to early period star formation causing an excess of carbon, which would be converted into nitrogen. This suggests that the intrinsic abundances of the outflowing wind are not being measured with RGS as there is some alteration caused by contamination from other regions in NGC 1068. On the other hand, Chandra observations show the abundances are more consistent with solar because the spectra can be extracted from specific regions of the galaxy (e.g. the AGN), which cannot be done with RGS. Therefore, the primary and secondary regions can be separately studied in detail, where the abundances are found to be consistent with solar.

In summary, similar to NGC 7469 (Section 4.3.1.6), the non-solar abun-

dance values found in this Chapter (Tables 5.12, 5.8, and 5.4) are likely to be due to contamination from extended regions of the host galaxy. This means that the abundances are not intrinsic to the outflowing wind only.

5.6 Discussion

In this section, I discuss the results from the spectral modelling of NGC 1068 in 2000 and 2014, using the data to infer and determine properties of the emitting plasma that surrounds the nucleus in this AGN. Here I investigate the distances of each photoionised component from the SMBH (Section 5.6.1), determine the thermal stability of the plasma regions (Section 5.6.2), obtain the wind kinematics (Section 5.6.3), and study the validity of the CIE emission (Section 5.6.4).

5.6.1 Photoionised Plasma Distances

After determining the best fit photoionisation models to NGC 1068 spectra in both epochs, I now want to establish the locations of the emitting plasma regions, with respect to the central SMBH. Unfortunately, as seen in Figure 5.5 and Table 5.10, there is little variability between the two epochs, either in terms of the spectral features or the ionisation state of the plasma components. This suggests that the emitting plasma has not changed over the 14 year period between observations. As a consequence, I am unable to obtain distance measurements from variability arguments where a change in the ionisation parameter is due to a change in the SED shape (see Sections 1.4.1.1 and 4.3.1.1, and e.g. Mehdipour et al., 2018, for the application on NGC 7469). Therefore, I have investigated alternative ways to calculate the distances of the plasma regions, discussing the physicality, as well as the advantages and negatives, of each method. These measurements depend on the geometry and our LOS view of NGC 1068, which adds complexity in comparison to Seyfert 1 AGN.

The uncertainties on the distance estimates here are obtained from the parameters and errors of my best fit modelling using PION (Table 5.10). The

hydrogen number densities for each component, and their respective uncertainties, are shown in Table 5.14. Ideally, the plasma density should be constrained through the recombination timescale using the variability between observations (Section 1.4.1.1), but as this is not the case here, I have used the calculated densities from PION⁴.

5.6.1.1 Ionisation Parameter Distances

I start by estimating the locations of these emission components using the definition of the ionisation parameter (ξ)

$$\xi = \frac{L_{ion}}{n_H R^2}, \quad (5.2)$$

where n_H is the hydrogen number density, L_{ion} is the ionising luminosity (measured between 1 - 1000 Ryd), R is the distance of the plasma from the black hole, and n_H is the hydrogen number density from the PION model (displayed in Table 5.14).

Using the ionising luminosity of $L_{ion} = 1.54 \times 10^{37}$ W (for both epochs) and the ionisation parameters from Table 5.10, I can estimate the distances for each component using Eq. 5.2. Alternatively, I can obtain a similar answer using the following equation (Mao et al., 2018)

$$R^2 = \frac{EM}{4\pi n_H C_{cov} N_H}, \quad (5.3)$$

where N_H and C_{cov} are values from Table 5.10. By substituting EM from Eq. 5.1 into Eq. 5.3, it cancels down to Eq. 5.2, but with a factor of 1.2 difference between n_e and n_H .

Unfortunately, in both these methods (and the method below in Section 5.6.1.2), the number density values of EM1 and EMA are not accurately determined. Therefore the distance estimates could not be obtained for these two components. For EM4 and EMD, I was unable to constrain the values

⁴PION calculates the hydrogen density by fitting the line ratios of all density-sensitive lines in the spectrum (taking into account processes like resonant scattering).

and instead achieve a density upper limit value. The resulting distances (R_ξ and R_{EM} , respectively) are listed in Table 5.14.

5.6.1.2 Using the Size of the Component

The second method considers the size of each component estimated from the ratio between the column density (N_H) and hydrogen number density (n_H). I then use the relation between the covering fraction (C_{cov}) and the solid angle to find the area A of each component as seen from the black hole, given by

$$C_{cov} = \frac{\Omega}{4\pi} = \frac{A}{4\pi R^2} \quad (5.4)$$

where Ω is the solid angle, and R is the distance from the black hole. Here, I assume that each emitting component is spherical and the black hole sees only half of the sphere with area $A = 2\pi r^2$, where r is the radius of the component. However, the diameter of each sphere, which is its characteristic thickness, is $\Delta d \approx \frac{N_H}{n_H}$, and therefore $\Delta r \approx \frac{N_H}{2n_H}$, such that $A = \pi \Delta r^2$.

Substituting A into Eq. 5.4 and rearranging for R gives the distance from the black hole, given the size of each component

$$R^2 \approx \frac{\Delta r^2}{4C_{cov}}. \quad (5.5)$$

With this method it is fairly easy to obtain distance measurements based on the geometry between the black hole and plasma region. In addition, Eq. 5.5 does not depend directly on the SED, although N_H and n_H are measured with PION which does require the correct SED input. The N_H/n_H ratio gives an approximation for the thickness of a slab of emitting plasma, whereas I assume each component is spherical. This assumption is a crude one, and an over simplification of the plasma geometry that does not relate easily to the thickness. Maybe a more appropriate geometry for the plasma is a cube, with dimensions equal to the thickness N_H/n_H . This model relies heavily on the size and geometry of each plasma component, which is difficult to calculate with certainty, especially when viewed from side on. Distance estimates obtained

with this method ($R_{\Delta r}$) are shown in Table 5.14, except for EM1 and EMA due to inaccurate n_H values.

5.6.1.3 Escape Velocity Distances

Next I consider the escape velocity of each component, and assume the outflow velocities from Table 5.10 are large enough to allow the plasma components to escape the gravitational potential of the black hole. Therefore, setting $v_{out} = v_{esc}$ I can obtain distances from

$$R = \frac{2GM_{BH}}{v_{out}^2}, \quad (5.6)$$

where G is the gravitational constant and $M_{BH} = 1.6 \times 10^7 M_{\odot}$ is the black hole mass (Panessa et al., 2006).

This method is independent of the SED. However, the outflow velocity is along our LOS and therefore depends on the viewing angle relative to a face on view (type 1) AGN. Although the outflowing wind makes a cone-like shape, the v_{out} I measure is not the net outflow velocity, but rather a radial component of its true outflow velocity. In addition, while Eq. 5.6 was used by Blustin et al. (2005) to obtain minimum distance limits on the WA components in AGN, the $R_{v_{out}}$ values I derive are not the lowest distance measurements for each component in Table 5.14.

5.6.1.4 Estimated Volume Filling Factor Distances

In NGC 7469, both the WA and emission line region (ELR; Chapter 4) distances were estimated using the volume filling factor (f_v). The f_v values were calculated for the WA components, but the values for the ELR components had to be fixed at some arbitrary values for the NLR and BLR (Chapter 4). Ideally, I would want to calculate the f_v values for each individual emission component within NGC 1068.

There are two methods that can be used to obtain distance estimates using the volume filling factor (see Sections 1.4.1.2 and 1.4.1.3). Both methods start with $N_H = n_H f_v \Delta r$ and $\xi = L_{ion}/n_H R^2$, where n_H is the electron

number density, Δr is the thickness of the plasma region and R is the plasma distance from black hole; L_{ion} , ξ , and N_H are from the modelling. The first derivation (Section 1.4.1.2), from Blustin et al. (2005) and used in Chapter 4 of this Thesis, assumes a thin layer (of thickness Δr) for each plasma component that contains most of the mass, with an ionisation ξ . This method obtains a maximum distance limit because Blustin et al. (2005) assumed $\Delta r \leq R$. Alternatively, in Section 1.4.1.3 (e.g. Behar et al., 2003; Whewell et al., 2015) the distance estimate can be derived by integrating n_H (substituting for $n_H = \frac{L_{ion}}{\xi R^2}$; Eq. 5.2) over the thickness of the plasma region such that $N_H = \int \frac{L_{ion} f_v}{\xi R^2} dR$. Here, I assume the plasma outer distance is further from the black hole than the inner distance. Therefore, this second method measures a minimum distance value. The values calculated with these two methods are the same, it just depends on the assumptions made as to whether an upper distance limit or a minimum distance is achieved. Therefore, for ease, I shall assume this equation gives the locations of the emission components,

$$R = \frac{L_{ion} f_v}{\xi N_H}. \quad (5.7)$$

For NGC 7469, in Chapter 4, I set $f_v = 0.1$ for the two NLR components, and therefore, do the same here for all of the PION components (however, I note that Kallman et al. 2014 suggested a volume filling factor of 0.01). Consequently, there are very large uncertainties associated with f_v , which may be up to some orders of magnitude in difference, meaning the errors on the distances obtained from this method are significantly greater than what is derived from the fitting and what is quoted in Table 5.14. Furthermore, Eq 5.7 requires two PION parameters (N_H and ξ) as well as the ionising luminosity, none of which are secure because I do not know the true shape of the SED, adding to the uncertainties on the distance values. Distance estimates obtained from this method (R_{f_v}) are shown in Table 5.14.

5.6.1.5 Comparing distance estimates

Figure 5.13 illustrates the estimated distances from the central SMBH, as a function of ionisation parameter of each component, while Table 5.14 displays them quantitatively. The distances vary because the parameters and assumptions used in each method are different. Although I am unable to constrain the distances shown in Figure 5.13, and a range of estimated values for each component is found, these findings are very useful, with some components being within the same distance ranges as each other, suggesting they are part of the same emitting region (as found by Kallman et al., 2014). Overall, the distances for each component are consistent with the expectations based on the values in Table 5.10.

Figure 5.13 shows that the most ionised components, EM1 and EMA ($\log \xi \sim 4$), and EM4 and EMD ($\log \xi \sim 3$) are closest to the black hole, compared to the low ionised components. For EM1 and EMA, due to unconstrained number densities, I only have two distance estimates. The larger column density and outflow velocity of EM1 puts it closer to the black hole compared to EMA. EM4 and EMD have the largest range in distance estimates, mostly due to the upper limits of the number density, and therefore lower distance limits. The method using the plasma size ($R_{\Delta r}$) places EM4 and EMD close to the black hole, with the number density upper limit consistent with the BLR ($n_{BLR} \sim 10^{15} \text{ m}^{-3}$). However, this location is probably unphysical as the high density limit is a result of EM4 and EMD not fitting many emission lines (Figures 5.11 and 5.12) and statistically improving the C-statistic the least. The consistencies in distances between high ionisation components, EM1 and EM4, and EMA and EMD, suggest that they are at similar locations. In both epochs, the distances are within the torus radius, suggesting that they could be part of the BLR. However, as discussed previously, this is unlikely.

For the low ionised components in each epoch, EM2 and EMB are the furthest from the black hole, and they have a large range of distance estimates, placing them either side of the torus, depending on the method used. For

example, the large outflow velocity (compared to the other components) places EM2/EMB close to the black hole, while the low ionisation state indicates that they are further away. EM3 and EMC, on the other hand, have the most constrained distance estimates, placing the plasma region consistent with the torus distance ($R_{torus} = 3.5$ pc; [García-Burillo et al., 2016](#)). These components have the lowest outflow velocities in each epoch, along with a low column density for a moderate ionisation state of $\log \xi \sim 2$. In addition, I can constrain the number density of EM3 and EMC.

None of the components are found at the location of the secondary region of X-ray emission at 290 pc, which extends to about 400 - 500 pc from the central black hole ([Brinkman et al., 2002](#); [Ogle et al., 2003](#); [García-Burillo et al., 2017](#)). In addition, the secondary region has a column density three times smaller compared to the primary region ([Brinkman et al., 2002](#); [Ogle et al., 2003](#)), but there is no evidence of N_H being a third of the size of any other component (Table 5.10). This suggests that none of these components, in either epoch, are situated outside the circumnuclear disk.

5.6.2 Thermal stability of the plasma

From PION, I am able to extract the temperature of the plasma components⁵. Figure 5.14 displays the thermal stability of the emitting plasma, shown as a plot of electron temperature (T_e) as a function of either the ionisation parameter (ξ ; top panel) or the pressure form of the ionisation parameter (Ξ ; bottom panel), within NGC 1068 (see Chapter 2, Section 2.4.2 for details). The labelled circles show the locations of the four PION components from lowest ionisation (EM2 or EMB) to the highest (EM1 or EMA) for 2000 (red) and 2014 (blue), respectively. In the top panel of Figure 5.14, T_e increases with an increase in ξ (same for both epochs), which is to be expected as the higher the plasma ionisation, the more energy the electrons within it have, and therefore the hotter the gas is.

⁵PION, assuming photoionisation and thermal equilibrium, for each ionisation state, can calculate the ionisation and thermal balance equations as it iterates over a range in ionisation parameters ([Mehdipour et al., 2016b](#))

Figure 5.13: Comparing distances for each plasma component from the different methods in Section 5.6.1, at the respective ionisation parameters for 2000 (top) and 2014 (bottom). The point shapes are shown in the legend, as are the colours for each component. The dashed line in each plot represents the location of the torus, $r_{torus} = 3.5$ pc (García-Burillo et al., 2016), while the dotted line is at $1000 R_g$, corresponding to a typical outer disk radius (Netzer, 2013).

Table 5.14: Distance values calculated from the various methods in Section 5.6.1. I also note the hydrogen number density (n_H) and component size (Δr) required to calculate some distances. These values are plotted in Figure 5.13.

Obs	Comp.	n_H (10^{10} m^{-3})	R_ξ (pc)	R_{EM} (pc)	Δr (pc)	$R_{\Delta r}$ (pc)	$R_{0,out}$ (pc)	$R_{f_v}^\dagger$ (pc)
2000	EM1	*	-	-	-	-	$0.37^{+0.45}_{-0.22}$	$0.010^{+0.004}_{-0.003}$
	EM2	$2.17^{+1.80}_{-0.76}$	$13.21^{+3.76}_{-2.70}$	$14.48^{+3.84}_{-1.74}$	$0.61^{+0.33}_{-0.15}$	$1.77^{+1.13}_{-0.42}$	$1.01^{+1.20}_{-0.89}$	$23.75^{+2.28}_{-4.06}$
	EM3	$0.51^{+0.48}_{-0.25}$	$6.76^{+2.23}_{-2.10}$	$7.41^{+2.44}_{-1.69}$	$1.40^{+0.77}_{-0.71}$	$3.49^{+2.32}_{-1.22}$	$11.43^{+2.40}_{-1.83}$	$2.73^{+0.03}_{-0.04}$
	EM4	< 2830	> 0.021	> 0.024	> 0.0002	> 0.0006	$3.46^{+51.87}_{-1.56}$	$0.22^{+0.08}_{-0.06}$
2014	EMA	*	-	-	-	-	$2.62^{+0.84}_{-1.26}$	0.014 ± 0.001
	EMB	$2.06^{+0.78}_{-0.58}$	$12.93^{+2.00}_{-2.47}$	$14.23^{+2.17}_{-2.57}$	$0.80^{+0.21}_{-0.29}$	$2.83^{+1.12}_{-2.64}$	$1.54^{+0.11}_{-0.10}$	$17.41^{+0.62}_{-0.64}$
	EMC	$0.84^{+0.8}_{-0.56}$	$4.87^{+0.02}_{-1.12}$	$5.33^{+0.05}_{-1.04}$	$1.12^{+0.09}_{-0.49}$	$2.81^{+0.10}_{-1.84}$	$2.62^{+0.24}_{-0.21}$	$1.76^{+0.14}_{-0.09}$
	EMD	< 14400	> 0.010	> 0.015	> 0.0001	> 0.0003	$0.49^{+0.47}_{-0.32}$	0.11 ± 0.01
Section		5.6.1.1		5.6.1.2		5.6.1.3	5.6.1.4	

* Unable to accurately measure density, so the distances that use n_e cannot be calculated.

† $f_v = 0.1$

The bottom panel of Figure 5.14 shows the thermal stability curve, an effective tool to determine which plasma regions are thermally stable or unstable, depending on the gas being in thermal equilibrium. On the thermal stability curve (black line in Figure 5.14, bottom panel) the rate of heating equals the rate of cooling; to the left, cooling dominates over heating, and to the right heating dictates over cooling. Over-plotted onto the curve are the temperatures of the four PION components from each epoch (red for 2000 and blue for 2014), at their respective Ξ values (from Eq. 2.9 in Section 2.4.2). EM2, EM3 and EM4 (in 2000) and EMB, EMC and EMD (in 2014) lie on the curve where the gradient is positive. This means that these components are thermally stable and can reach thermal equilibrium: should a small change in temperature occur, then the gas will move towards a heating or cooling process to balance out this change. EM1 (2000) and EMA (2014), however, lie on the curve where there is a negative gradient, although at the point where the curve starts to turn towards a positive gradient. This means that these two components are thermally unstable and a little perturbation is enough to move the gas away from equilibrium.

Components EM1 and EMA and EM4 and EMD have similar Ξ values, suggesting they may be part of the same region within the outflowing wind and are far from the locations of the lower ionised components. This is also shown in Figure 5.13, where the distances of EM1, EM4, EMA, and EMD are similar to each other. The other two components in each epoch are possibly discrete phases, rather than belonging to a continuous distribution of ξ , as they lie on different stable parts of the curve (Ebrero et al., 2011). Hence, EM1 and EMA cannot be in equilibrium with EM2 and EMB as ξ (and therefore Ξ) are very different and thus they are located at different distances in the wind.

Bianchi et al. (2019) proposed an alternative scenario for obscured AGN where radiation pressure compression (RPC) in the outflowing gas leads to a well defined ionisation distribution and differential emission measure (DEM), although a constant gas pressure multi-phase scenario, as adopted here, is not

Figure 5.14: *Top panel:* Electron temperature (T_e) of the plasma as a function of ionisation parameter (ξ). The labelled circles correspond to the four PION components for each epoch (red for 2000 and blue for 2014) at their respective ionisation parameter values from Table 5.10. *Bottom panel:* Thermal stability curve of electron temperature (T_e) as a function of the pressure form of the ionisation parameter (Ξ). The labelled circles correspond to the Ξ values of the four PION components for each epoch: red for 2000 and blue for 2014. See Section 5.6.2 for details.

excluded by their results. The alternative scenario comes from the evidence that gas surrounding the AGN is photoionised by the continuum, producing soft X-ray and optical emission from the same plasma region in the AGN, suggesting high and low density gas can coexist together (Bianchi et al., 2006). The AGN continuum ionises and heats up the plasma, compressing the gas and causing a gradient gas pressure. Therefore, a DEM distribution is required to explain and model the emission of a RPC gas, meaning we see X-ray emission from high- ξ and low-density gas, and optical emission from low- ξ and high-density gas, further away from the ionising continuum, in the same cloud (Bianchi et al., 2019).

In Figure 5.15, I plot the emission measure (EM) of each PION component against $\log \xi$. I then plot the 12 ions (purple squares) from Figure 3 in Bianchi et al. (2019), adapted for the EM axis by multiplying the DEM values by the width of each $\log \xi$ bin. Finally, the DEM distribution (brown line) predicted for RPC gas is overlaid on top to test whether PIE plasma within a RPC gas is a solution. The overall trend shows a decreasing EM for an increase in $\log \xi$, i.e. the same behaviour as a DEM $\left(\frac{d(EM)}{d(\log \xi)}\right)$ in RPC (Bianchi et al., 2019). Both the distribution and overall trend suggest that the plasma is in RPC, which represents a natural solution. Here, however, the highest ξ component does not fit the RPC trend, because it comes from the region that is almost transparent (almost fully ionized), so adding more high ξ gas makes very little difference for the RPC solution.

In a similar way to calculating the temperatures of each component, PION can also calculate the rates of the various heating and cooling mechanisms, for a given ionisation parameter. Figure 5.16 displays the total heating rate (top panel) and total cooling rate (bottom panel) within the PIE plasmas in NGC 1068; the 2000 and 2014 PION components are overplotted as red and blue circles, respectively. I also display the individual processes that make up these heating and cooling rates. The main heating processes are: Compton scattering (CS), Auger electrons (AE) and photoelectrons (PE) (see Table

2.4.1.1 for details). In Figure 5.16, the largest contribution to heating the plasma comes from photoelectrons up to about $\log \xi = 3.5$, where Compton scattering starts to dominate. This is due to X-ray ionisation increasing the number of photoelectrons in the plasma with $\log \xi < 3.5$, while above this value the free electrons interact and gain energy from the X-rays. The main cooling processes are: inverse-Compton scattering (ICS), Bremsstrahlung (FF - free-free), collisional excitation (CE) and recombination (RE) (see Table 2.4.1.2 for details). The dominant cooling processes are collisional excitation for $\log \xi < 2.5$ and Bremsstrahlung for $\log \xi > 2.5$. The latter comes about because the ions in the highly ionised plasma have lost all their outer shell electrons, such that when a free electron passes by, the large charge difference causes the electron to be deflected greatly, losing its kinetic energy to radiation and therefore cooling the gas. These results are consistent with the heating and cooling processes for various SEDs (Mehdipour et al., 2016b).

5.6.3 Kinematics of the outflowing wind

Similar to NGC 7469 in Chapter 4, I now estimate the mass outflow rate and kinematic luminosity of the outflowing wind between the two epochs. Here, I use

$$\dot{M}_{out} = \frac{1.23 m_p L_{ion} f v_{out} \Omega}{\xi}, \quad (5.8)$$

and

$$L_K = \frac{\dot{M}_{out} v_{out}^2}{2}, \quad (5.9)$$

where m_p is the proton mass, $L_{ion} = 1.54 \times 10^{37}$ W is the ionising radiation between 13.6 eV and 13.6 keV, $f = 0.1$ is the volume filling factor (Chapter 4), v_{out} is the outflow velocity, ξ is the ionisation parameter, and $\Omega = 1.6$ sr is the solid angle (assuming 25% of the AGN population are CT, with an average 50% covering fraction; see references within Blustin et al., 2005). A caveat here, however, is that v_{out} is in our LOS, so I do not know the velocity in the direction of outflow - i.e. perpendicular to us. The calculated \dot{M}_{out} and L_K values are shown in Table 5.15, including the summed totals for each epoch. There is an

Figure 5.15: Emission measures (EM) of the four PION components in each epoch versus their respective ionisation parameter ($\log \xi$). The purple squares are the ions from Figure 3 in [Bianchi et al. \(2019\)](#), whereby the EM values decrease for increasing $\log \xi$, consistent with the PION components (same colours and point styles from Figure 5.13). I also plot the expected radiative pressure compression (RPC) curve (brown line) that follows the trend of both the ions (purple squares) and PION components suggesting that the photoionised plasma within NGC 1068 is consistent with RPC gas.

increase in both the mass outflow rates and kinetic luminosities from 2000 to 2014, by $\Delta \dot{M} = 0.372 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and $\Delta \log L_K = 33.70 \text{ W}$, respectively. However, the uncertainties on the total values are large and overlap with each other, suggesting that the changes in \dot{M}_{out} and L_K are insignificant between epochs. This, however, is no surprise given the results from Table 5.10 and Figure 5.5.

To see if these plasma components, have significant energy, I take the ratio between the total L_K of each epoch and the bolometric luminosity of NGC 1068; I use the average value of $L_{bol} = 2.55 \times 10^{38} \text{ W}$ (see [Gravity Collaboration et al., 2020](#), and references within). The ratios L_K/L_{bol} are found to be 0.004 % and 0.006 % for 2000 and 2014, respectively. This shows that the outflowing wind is not playing a major role in the system and has insignificant energies with which to impact the host galaxy, at least over short timescales relative to

Table 5.15: Mass outflow rate (\dot{M}_{out}) and kinetic luminosity (L_K) values for each photoionisation component from 2000 (top) and 2014 (bottom). Also listed are the ionisation states (ξ) and outflow velocities (v_{out}) of each component needed to calculate the wind energies. The total \dot{M}_{out} and L_K values for each epoch are also displayed.

Epoch	Comp.	$\log \xi$ (10^{-9} W m)	v_{out} (km s $^{-1}$)	\dot{M} (M_{\odot} yr $^{-1}$)	$\log L_K$ (W)
2000	EM1	3.91 ± 0.02	-610^{+200}_{-330}	$0.006^{+0.002}_{-0.004}$	$31.85^{+0.15}_{-0.55}$
	EM2	0.63 ± 0.01	-260 ± 10	$4.870^{+0.294}_{-0.305}$	$34.02^{+0.84}_{-0.25}$
	EM3	1.84 ± 0.01	-110 ± 10	0.127 ± 0.015	$31.69^{+0.58}_{-0.49}$
	EM4	$3.02^{+0.02}_{-0.01}$	-200^{+150}_{-70}	$0.015^{+0.011}_{-0.006}$	$31.29^{+0.01}_{-0.18}$
			Total:	$5.021^{+4.530}_{-3.958}$	$34.02^{+1.06}_{-0.85}$
2014	EMA	$3.96^{+0.02}_{-0.01}$	-230^{+30}_{-90}	0.002 ± 0.001	$30.53^{+0.43}_{-0.24}$
	EMB	0.67 ± 0.01	-300 ± 10	$5.125^{+0.284}_{-1.454}$	$33.66^{+0.43}_{-0.76}$
	EMC	1.91 ± 0.01	-230 ± 10	$0.261^{+0.050}_{-0.020}$	$32.58^{+0.84}_{-0.79}$
	EMD	$3.02^{+0.03}_{-0.02}$	-530^{+150}_{-370}	$0.040^{+0.013}_{-0.032}$	$32.56^{+0.19}_{-0.39}$
			Total:	$5.393^{+3.389}_{-5.329}$	$34.19^{+1.11}_{-1.23}$

the lifetime of the AGN (similar to the WA components of AGN; [Blustin et al., 2005](#)). A reason for this could be that we observe NGC 1068 from side on, so we are not measuring the outflow velocity in the direction of outflow, but instead the edge of the ionisation cone that is travelling towards us. Alternatively, it could be due to the assumed geometry from PION that breaks down for type 2 AGN. However, as measured in Chapter 4, the L_K/L_{bol} ratios for the WA (Table 4.16) are between 0.001 and 0.003 %, which are lower than the values measured for NGC 1068.

5.6.4 Origin of collisionally ionised plasma

Finally, if CIE plasma is the origin of the 15 and 17 Å lines (not considering photoexcitation), then I need to know where this emission originates from. The most likely origin is from the starburst ring (SBR), situated up to 1.3 kpc ([García-Burillo et al., 2017](#)) from the central black hole, which appears to be made up of two arcs, that together form a misshapen ring (Figure 5.1). The

SBR (and CND) appears to be a dynamic structure, where the east of the SBR is blueshifted down to -180 km s^{-1} , while the west is redshifted up to $+180 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (see Figure 10 in [García-Burillo et al., 2014](#)). These are consistent with the CIE velocity values from Table 5.11. The RGS instrument has an aperture of $\sim 5'$, large enough to cover the full SBR which is $0.8'$ ($\sim 50''$) in diameter, meaning I can observe the full SBR and therefore emission from the blue and redshifted sides.

Chandra LETGS images of NGC 1068 show bright X-ray emission at the nucleus (including the secondary region), but only diffuse emission further out ([Brinkman et al., 2002](#)). On the other hand, Chandra HETGS images show X-ray emission that corresponds to the SBR of the host galaxy, south east of the nucleus, in the energy range between 0.8 - 1.3 keV ([Ogle et al., 2003](#)). In addition, ACIS images show X-ray emission between 0.25 - 2 keV as far out as the SBR, in both north-west and south-east directions ([Young et al., 2001](#)). The X-ray energy ranges in which emission from the SBR is observed are consistent with the RGS band where I model the CIE plasma, suggesting that the SBR is a good candidate for the origin of CIE emission, although direct detection is yet to be confirmed (e.g. [Ogle et al., 2003](#)).

To confirm the legitimacy of this CIE component, more so than just by statistical significance in the model, I compare the calculated CIE luminosity (L_{CIE}) with the X-ray luminosity inferred from the far infrared (FIR) luminosity of the SBR in NGC 1068. The star formation rate (SFR) in NGC 1068 was estimated between $0.4 - 0.7 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ ([García-Burillo et al., 2014](#)). From here, I can estimate the FIR luminosity from the SFR using $L_{FIR} = \frac{SFR}{4.5 \times 10^{-44}} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$ ([Kennicutt, 1998](#)): I find the FIR luminosity to be between $L_{FIR}[0.4] = 8.9 \times 10^{35}$ and $L_{FIR}[0.7] = 1.6 \times 10^{36} \text{ W}$. I then use the relation $\log \left[\frac{L_X}{L_{IR}} \right] > -4.3$ ([Symeonidis et al., 2014](#)), where L_{IR} is the infrared luminosity and L_X is the soft X-ray (0.5 - 2 keV) luminosity (as CIE emission is only seen in the RGS band) to infer an X-ray luminosity based on the IR luminosity. I therefore estimate a lower limit for the X-ray luminosity to be within

the range $L_X > 4.46 \times 10^{31} - 7.82 \times 10^{31}$ W. The measured (0.5 - 2 keV) luminosities of the CIE components in 2000 and 2014 are $L_{CIE}^{2000} = 4.89_{-0.11}^{+0.14} \times 10^{33}$ W and $L_{CIE}^{2014} = 4.04_{-0.07}^{+0.11} \times 10^{33}$ W, respectively, which are significantly larger than the X-ray luminosities inferred from L_{FIR} . To double check this, I used the relation $L_X = L_{FIR} 10^{-3.70}$ (Eq. 8 from [Ranalli et al., 2003](#)) and obtained soft X-ray luminosities of $L_X = 1.78 \times 10^{32} - 3.19 \times 10^{32}$ W, but these are still an order of magnitude less than L_{CIE} .

With the CIE luminosity in both epochs being larger than the soft X-ray luminosity limit inferred from the FIR luminosity, I conclude that something else is contributing to the CIE X-ray luminosity. The SFR values estimated from L_{CIE} in both epochs, using the relation $SFR = 2.2 \times 10^{-33} L_{CIE} M_{\odot} yr^{-1}$ (modified Eq. 14 from [Ranalli et al., 2003](#)), are $SFR_{2000} = 11 M_{\odot} yr^{-1}$ and $SFR_{2014} = 9 M_{\odot} yr^{-1}$. These values are significantly larger compared to the SFR from the FIR ([García-Burillo et al., 2014](#)), again suggesting that the CIE plasma is unlikely to come from the SBR.

Alternatively, the CIE emission could originate from the secondary region, north-east of the central black hole ([Brinkman et al., 2002](#)), assuming CIE plasma is the cause of the Fe XVII lines. The secondary region is bright in both radio and X-rays, possibly due to old jet material ([Wilson & Ulvestad, 1987](#)). Due to the field of view and spatial resolution of RGS, I cannot resolve the SBR and the primary and secondary regions with XMM-Newton, and therefore all the emission from these three regions are seen combined. Therefore, the ionisation and outflow velocities I obtain from the PION modelling may also apply to emission from the secondary region, harbouring a similar plasma to the primary region; however, I do not expect the location of this plasma to be as far out as the secondary region (from our distance estimates in [Section 5.6.1.5](#)). It is possible, therefore, that CIE plasma may be located in the secondary region if there are shocks generated in the gas at times when the nuclear jet was particularly strong.

Figure 5.16: *Top panel:* Total heating rate as a function of ionisation parameter (ξ) for NGC 1068 (black solid line). The contributions from the different heating processes are also shown: Compton scattering (CS; green dot-dashed line), photoelectrons (PE; purple dotted line), and Auger electrons (AE; orange dashed line). *Bottom panel:* Total cooling rate as a function of ξ for NGC 1068 (black solid line). The contributions from the individual cooling processes are also displayed: inverse-Compton scattering (ICS; orange dot-dashed line), Bremsstrahlung (FF; green dashed line), collisional excitation (CE; purple dot-dashed line), and recombination (RE; magenta dotted line). *Both panels:* The labelled circles correspond to the four PION components in each epoch, shown as red for 2000 and blue for 2014, at their respective ionisation parameters from Table 5.10.

5.7 Conclusions

In this analysis, I have investigated the type 2 AGN NGC 1068, comparing XMM-Newton observations in 2000 and 2014, modelling the RGS and EPIC-PN spectra separately and simultaneously. I find that the majority of the emission lines are explained by photoionised plasma, while at least two spectral features require a collisionally ionised component. The main conclusions from this investigation are detailed below.

From the preliminary analysis carried out on RGS and EPIC-PN spectra separately (Section 5.4), two emission components in each spectrum were required. In the RGS spectra, the best fit statistics were $C = 5100$ (1541 d.o.f) and $C = 8273$ (1537 d.o.f) for 2000 and 2014, respectively. For the EPIC-PN results, $C = 726$ (517 d.o.f) and $C = 1400$ (514 d.o.f) for 2000 and 2014, respectively. The ionisation parameters of these emission components range between $\log \xi = 0.1$ and 1.4 in the RGS spectrum and between $\log \xi = 2$ and 4 in the EPIC-PN spectrum. Both the turbulent velocities and column densities of the RGS components are, at least, an order of magnitude smaller than the values found in the EPIC-PN spectrum; the covering factors differ between the two instruments by a factor of 10 to 100. This is not surprising if I assume that the highly ionised components seen in the EPIC-PN spectrum are found closer to the central black hole. I also find the outflow velocities of the RGS spectrum components to be smaller ($v_{out}^{RGS} = -230$ to -420 km s⁻¹) compared to the EPIC-PN components ($v_{out}^{PN} = -100$ to -2100 km s⁻¹). The lower values for the 2014 EPIC-PN velocities are due to the PION components being coupled to the same REDS component as REFL.

In the simultaneous fitting (Sections 5.5) and 5.6), four PION components were required to fit the majority of the emission lines in both epochs, across the full X-ray band. The final best fit statistics were $C = 3790$ (1037 d.o.f) and $C = 7252$ (1027 d.o.f) for 2000 and 2014, respectively. I find that there is very little change in the ionisation states ($\log \xi = 1 - 4$) of these components between 2000 and 2014, implying the four plasma regions have remained unchanged.

I compared distance derivation methods to get an insight into the possible locations of the emitting plasma regions within NGC 1068. Although I cannot constrain the estimates, these methods are useful in obtaining rough locations for the outflowing wind, even if there are no spectral changes between observations. See Figure 5.13 and Table 5.14 for details.

I investigated the thermal properties of emitting plasma regions, studying their thermal stability and heating and cooling processes. Using the thermal stability curve (Figure 5.14) I find that the highest ionisation state plasmas in each epoch are thermally unstable. I also conclude that the highest and lowest ionisation phases cannot be part of the same regions in the outflowing wind.

From the photoionisation modelling (Table 5.10), the distances (Figure 5.13), and the thermal stability properties (Figure 5.14), the results suggests that EM1 and EMA, and EM4 and EMD are very close to the central SMBH, compared to the other components. This indicates that these components could be part of the BLR. However, I cannot conclude this with certainty as the BLR is obscured by the dusty torus.

I find evidence for emission from collisionally ionised plasma in NGC 1068, as photoionised plasma (PION) is unable to account for the Fe XVII lines at 15 and 17 Å. However, photoexcitation would be a more natural way to produce these lines in the outflowing gas surrounding the central black hole (Kinkhabwala et al., 2002), and the lack of PION emission in this region may be due to incomplete information regarding photoexcitation in SPEX. If CIE emission was the cause of these Fe-L lines, I found no conclusive evidence for it to originate from the SBR or the secondary region. This suggests that CIE may not be the underlying emission component to produce these lines, but instead only statistically accounts for the lines PION cannot produce, where photoexcitation is not accounted for.

Finally, I calculated the mass outflow rate and kinetic luminosity of the outflowing wind from each epoch, which increased by $\Delta\dot{M}_{out} = 0.372M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and $\Delta\log L_K = 33.70 \text{ W}$ between 2000 and 2014. These changes are not sig-

nificant and the values all have large uncertainties. Furthermore, the outflow wind only accounts for 0.004 % and 0.006 % of the bolometric luminosity, suggesting that the wind has insignificant energies to impact the host galaxy, at least on short timescales relative to the lifetime of the AGN.

In conclusion, NGC 1068 has changed very little, if at all, in the 14 year period between XMM-Newton observations. Future monitoring of NGC 1068 would be important in assessing if this ionisation state of the plasma is maintained, or if this AGN is dynamic in a similar way to type 1 AGN.

Chapter 6

A deeper look at the Seyfert 2 AGN, NGC 5643: a candidate for outflow-induced star formation

This Chapter is based on the work carried out in preparation of submitting an XMM-Newton proposal accepted for the implementation in AO20

Abstract

The motivation for this Chapter follows on from the study by [Cresci et al. \(2015\)](#), who, for the first time, found evidence of outflow-induced star formation in a Seyfert AGN. The type 2 AGN, NGC 5643, was discovered to contain an outflowing wind travelling towards two star forming clumps located 1.2 kpc from the central black hole. The star formation in these clumps was proposed, by [Cresci et al.](#), to be initiated and driven by positive feedback, caused by the interaction between the wind and clumps. As a result of this, I wanted to explore the outflowing wind of NGC 5643 in the X-ray band, to determine whether the X-ray wind can impact the surrounding material, and therefore determine if the X-ray wind has significant energetics to initiate star formation

through the feedback process.

In this Chapter, to investigate the X-ray outflowing wind, I modelled the 55 ks XMM-Newton/RGS spectrum from the 2009 observation of NGC 5643. After fitting the data with a simple model, made up of single photoionisation and collisionally ionised components, I simulated a spectrum equivalent to 240 ks of exposure with XMM-Newton/RGS. I found that 240 ks of observation time would significantly improve the signal-to-noise ratio of the spectrum, reduce the uncertainties on both the flux and energies, as well as the errors on the model parameters, and finally would resolve all the emission lines of interest. This work was used for an XMM-Newton proposal, which was accepted, and can be implemented to estimate the mass outflow rate and kinetic luminosity of the X-ray outflowing wind, in order to determine the impact on the host galaxy through feedback.

6.1 Introduction

NGC 5643 is a low X-ray luminosity ($L_{0.5-10keV} \sim 2 \times 10^{33}$ W; [Annuar et al., 2015](#)) type 2 Seyfert AGN within an intermediate spiral galaxy, at a redshift of $z = 0.004$. Figure 6.1 shows the EPIC-MOS, where the AGN is the bottom bright source identified by the yellow arrow, and OM UVW1 images of NGC 5643. Although it is a bright infrared galaxy ($L_{IR} = 6.89 \times 10^{37}$ W; [Genzel et al., 1998](#)) where star formation occurs in the galaxy's spiral arms, there is evidence that AGN dominates the IR energy budget, suggesting NGC 5643 is a Seyfert 2 and starburst hybrid (see [Matt et al., 2013](#), and references within).

NGC 5643 has been found to have a compact radio core with a two sided kiloparsec scale lobes in the direction of east to west ([Morris et al., 1985](#)). The mapping of the [S III] flux emission shows an elongated structure in the same direction, with kinematics dominated by the outflow of ionised gas ($\dot{M}_{out} \sim 0.3 M_{\odot} yr^{-1}$; [Riffel et al., 2018](#)). [SIII] is distributed in the same spatial region as [O III], parallel to the galaxy bar within a double sided ionisation cone (see left side of Figure 6.2), with an outflow velocity of $v_{[OIII]} = -450$ km s⁻¹ ([Cresci](#)

Figure 6.1: Images of NGC 5643. *Left:* 0.15 - 10 keV MOS image - the AGN nucleus is the bottom bright point in the middle CCD (yellow arrow) and the ULX, NGC 5643 X-1, is the top bright point (green arrow). Also visible is diffuse X-ray emission, seen in the 0.15 - 2 keV energy range. *Right:* OM image using the UVW1 filter; up is north and left is east. As the OM image was in full-frame mode, each edge is 17 arcminutes, meaning the galaxy is approximately 3 arcminutes in size.

et al., 2015). The ionised outflowing material, as seen in the optical band, is moving in the direction of two clumps near the edge of the bar with prominent H II line emission, a signature for star formation (right side of Figure 6.2). Cresci et al. (2015) proposed that the star formation in these clumps is due to positive feedback from gas compression between the outflowing material and the high density clumps. The star formation rate (SFR) in clump A (see right side of Figure 6.2) is $SFR \sim 0.03 M_{\odot} yr^{-1}$ (Cresci et al., 2015); 10% of the mass outflow rate found by Riffel et al. (2018). This is the first time possible outflow-induced star formation has been observed in a Seyfert AGN and is the motivation for this work. The optical data suggest that feedback can be present even in low luminosity type 2 AGN (Cresci et al., 2015).

NGC 5643 has been observed in the X-ray band by ASCA and BeppoSAX (Guainazzi et al., 2004), XMM-Newton (Guainazzi et al., 2004; Matt et al., 2013), Chandra (Bianchi et al., 2006), and NuSTAR (Annuar et al., 2015).

Figure 6.2: *Left:* H α maps of the outflowing gas with the contours from (a) [O III] flux, (b) 8.4 GHz radio emission, and (c) Chandra X-ray emission (0.3 - 0.5 keV in green and 0.5 - 8 keV in blue) plotted on top. The high energy X-ray emission is located within the nucleus, but the lower X-ray energies are extended, consistent with the outflowing material, which is moving towards the star formation clumps on the left side of each panel. This shows a connection between the star formation clumps and the outflowing cone, seen in both optical and X-ray emission. *Right:* Schematic of NGC 5643 with the plane of the host galaxy disk in the left-right direction and the plane of the obscuring torus in the up-down direction. The two sided ionisation cone is bordered by the red lines along the east to west direction, with the outflowing wind moving towards the two star formation clumps (A and B), shown by the solid blue circles. The nuclear dusty torus is shown in brown, collimating the ionising cone. The dashed blue line shows the radius of the star formation ring. (Both figures taken from Cresci et al., 2015).

However, the exposure times from these observations are very small. [Guainazzi et al. \(2004\)](#) analysed the ~ 40 ks ASCA and < 10 ks BeppoSAX observations from 1996 and 1997, respectively. Possible evidence of variability in NGC 5643 (compared to the 2003 XMM-Newton observation) was later dismissed because of the presence in the telescopes large point spread function (PSF) of the bright and variable ultraluminous X-ray (ULX) source (NGC 5643 X-1), located $0.8'$ from the AGN (identified with the green arrow in [Figure 6.1](#)). The ULX has a peak luminosity of $L > 10^{33}$ W and has been found to fluctuate by a factor of 3 to 4 between observations ([Pintore et al., 2016](#)). [Figure 6.3](#) shows the ULX spectra observed by NuSTAR between 2014 and 2020, where we see a flux increase below 10 keV indicating significant flux variability.

The analysis on the 10 ks XMM-Newton observation in 2003 ([Guainazzi et al., 2004](#)) left some questions open: was the flat hard X-ray spectrum a result of Compton-thin (CT) absorption or reflection off Compton-thick material; and what was the dominating process to produce the soft X-ray emission features? This was later, somewhat, answered by [Matt et al. \(2013\)](#), who analysed the ~ 55 ks XMM-Newton observation from 2009, and found that the source is CT, and photoionisation was the dominating emitting process; however, a contribution from collisionally ionised material could not be ruled out.

Chandra images show that the soft X-ray emission and the Hubble Space Telescope (HST) [O III] emission are spatially correlated (top and bottom panels of [Figure 6.2](#), left), which is seen in many type 2 AGN ([Bianchi et al., 2006](#)). Furthermore, Chandra ACIS images of NGC 5643 show an elongated, clumpy feature of the Fe $K\alpha$ line emission, extending 65 pc from north to south ([Fabbiano et al., 2018](#)), which is spatially consistent with the CO(2-1) high resolution imaging from Atacama Large Millimeter/submillimeter Array (ALMA; [Alonso-Herrero et al., 2018](#)). This suggests that the neutral Fe $K\alpha$ and CO emission originate in the torus, which is perpendicular to the ionisation cone (see right side of [Figure 6.2](#)). The molecular gas seen with ALMA has a gas mass of $M(H_2) \sim 10^7 M_\odot$ and a column density of $N(H_2) \sim 5 \times 10^{27} \text{ m}^{-2}$

(Alonso-Herrero et al., 2018).

Finally, Annuar et al. (2015) were the first to analyse NGC 5643 with the addition of ~ 42 ks of NuSTAR data for energies greater than 10 keV. This not only allowed them to resolve NGC 5643 X-1 from the AGN nucleus separately at hard X-ray energies, but they could directly measure the column density $N_H > 5 \times 10^{28} \text{ m}^{-2}$ of the absorbing material in NGC 5643. This column density is above the threshold for a CT source, and is 10 times larger than N_H found by Alonso-Herrero et al. (2018).

The size of NGC 5643 is roughly $3' \times 3'$ as shown in Figure 6.1. Therefore, like NGC 7469 (Chapter 4) and NGC 1068 (Chapter 5), the whole host galaxy will also be observed with RGS (which has a viewing aperture of $30'$ by $5'$). However, because of the presence of the ULX in the galaxy, XMM-Newton has observed NGC 5643 with the orientation such that NGC 5643 X-1 was placed along the direction perpendicular to the RGS dispersion direction with respect to the AGN (Matt et al., 2013). In other words, the RGS dispersion direction is orientated from left-to-right in Figure 6.1, rather than top-to-bottom. This means that the photons from the AGN and ULX produce two separate spectral traces on the RGS CCDs separated in the cross-dispersion direction with little overlap between the two sources. I also implemented this orientation into the XMM-Newton proposal (Section 6.6).

6.2 Aims and Motivation

NGC 5643 is a starburst/Seyfert 2 galaxy for which there is very little high resolution X-ray data, none of which have been studied in detail before. The RGS spectrum shows the same emission features as other well studied type 2 AGN, yet, due to the short exposure times, the soft X-ray band has only been investigated with the EPIC-PN data (Matt et al., 2013). The EPIC-PN data, however, are unable to resolve the details of the emission lines, and therefore the properties of the emitting plasma cannot be fully established. Further to this, RGS can spectrally resolve collisionally ionised equilibrium (CIE) plasma

Figure 6.3: NuSTAR spectra (and background) of the ULX taken in 2014 (blue) and 2020 (red), showing significant variability of this source below 10 keV. Image Credit: P. Boorman (private communication).

from photoionised equilibrium (PIE) plasma emission lines, allowing us to study the different plasma components. For example, the Fe XVII (L) lines found at around 15 and 17 Å in NGC 1068 were accounted for with a CIE component (Chapter 5; as well as in NGC 7469, Chapter 4); this can be seen in top panel of Figure 6.5 for NGC 5643. NGC 5643 is the first AGN to show possible outflow-induced star formation within a Seyfert galaxy, as seen in the optical band. This strengthens the motivation to study the RGS spectrum of this AGN so that we can analyse separately the PIE and CIE plasmas, and therefore the outflowing X-ray wind; NGC 5643 is an interesting and complex galaxy that requires more attention.

Within some AGN both radio emission and ionisation cones are present, meaning that it is possible for the soft X-ray emission plasma to be collisionally ionised by the outflowing material. The main aim here is to understand whether the soft X-ray emission in Seyfert 2 nuclei with radio outflows is fundamentally different (or not) from that in Seyfert 2 AGN without such radio

Figure 6.4: RGS light curve for the summation of RGS 1 and RGS 2 (blue line); the red area shows the count rate error. The light curve was binned up into 500 second bins, therefore the y-axis shows the number of counts per 500 seconds.

structures. By discriminating whether the material is CIE or PIE dominated will allow these questions to be answered and to further examine the mechanisms driving these outflows and their effects on the host galaxy. Although this is not answered in this Chapter, it is still an open question and discussed in Chapter 8.

In this Chapter, I report the analysis of the 55 ks RGS spectrum of NGC 5643, observed in 2009. After modelling the data, I simulated 120 and 240 ks spectra, comparing the models for each scenario in view of proposing observations with XMM-Newton. The parameters of interest in the X-ray outflowing wind were the ionisation parameter (ξ) and column density (N_H), while I assumed an outflow velocity of $v_{out} = -450 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (Cresci et al., 2015), in order to estimate the mass outflow rate and energetics of the outflowing X-ray wind, for each spectrum. In addition, I modelled the EPIC-PN data with the emission lines accounted for from the RGS model, whereby I also simulated a 240 ks spectrum and compared the results.

6.3 RGS Analysis

6.3.1 Method

I reduced the 2009 XMM-Newton data with `SAS v17.0.0`, with `RGSPROC` to obtain the RGS1 and RGS2 spectra, before combining them together with the `RGSCOMBINE` command. There were no background flares in CCD 9, so the total exposure time for both RGS 1 and RGS 2 was 54500 s. Figure 6.4 shows the light curve for RGS 1 + RGS 2 (blue line), with the count rate errors shown in red. Although there appears to be some variability over the course of the observation, and a strong count increase between 10 and 20 ks, the errors suggest that there is little short term change. The average RGS count rate for NGC 5643, observed in 2009, is 0.0094 counts s⁻¹, and therefore the total number of counts in the spectrum is 1025 photons.

The observed RGS spectrum, shown in the top panel of Figure 6.5, displays significantly higher noise at longer wavelengths due to a low count rate and therefore flux; the sensitivity of RGS is lower at the edges of the waveband. However, an exposure time significantly greater than 55 ks will decrease the flux uncertainties, meaning better statistics at longer wavelengths will be achieved.

For the RGS spectrum, I modelled the continuum with a simple power-law, fitting the normalisation (N_{pow}) and photon index (Γ). The initial values were taken from [Matt et al. \(2013\)](#), where the normalisation $N_{pow} = 3.26 \times 10^{48}$ ph s⁻¹ keV⁻¹ was set such that the observed 2 - 10 keV luminosity was $L_{2-10} = 2.7 \times 10^{33}$ W. The initial photon index was $\Gamma = 1.26$. These two parameters were fitted to yield an initial C-statistic of 679 for 380 degrees of freedom (d.o.f, hereafter).

Next, I fitted the emission features present in the RGS spectrum. Unfortunately, as NGC 5643 is a type 2 Seyfert galaxy, I did not have an intrinsic SED. So instead, I used the SED from NGC 7469 ([Mehdipour et al., 2018](#)), similarly to what I did for NGC 1068 ([Grafton-Waters et al., 2021b](#), see Chapter 5, Section 5.3). Here, the SED is fed through the `PION` compo-

nents, ionising the plasma, before being turned off, such that we only see the X-rays that are generated in the photoionised plasma; we do not see the intrinsic SED flux. Fitting one PION component improved the fit by $\Delta C = 89$ ($C = 590$), however a second component did not statistically improve the fit or account for any other features. [Matt et al. \(2013\)](#) found three photoionised emission components, but they fitted their soft X-ray model to the EPIC-PN spectrum. Furthermore, they used a phenomenological model to fit the full EPIC-PN data and a `Cloudy` model for the soft X-ray band, whereas here I used a self-consistent model that uses the ionising SED and does not require a pre-calculated ionisation grid (see Section 2.3.2 for details).

In addition to PIE plasma, [Matt et al. \(2013\)](#) suggested CIE plasma was also present, as a pure photoionised model was not able to reproduce the data well. As NGC 5643 has an active star forming region ([Cresci et al., 2015](#)), CIE plasma should be considered anyway. Adding a CIE component improved the fit by $\Delta C = 6$, fitting the emission measure (EM) and the electron temperature (T_e). This is not significant compared to the PION component, but it did fit the lines at 15 and 17 Å, as well as a few other emission features. As a comparison, the CIE component in NGC 7469 only yielded $\Delta C = 9$ (see Chapter 4). A second CIE component made no statistical difference to the fit.

After fitting the two emission components and the power-law together, a final best fit of $C = 583$ for 375 d.o.f was achieved. This fit is acceptable, but not great ($C/\text{d.o.f} = 1.6$). Here, v_{out} and v_{turb} are fixed at 0 and 100 km s⁻¹, respectively, and I have assumed all the abundances are at their solar values ([Lodders et al., 2009](#)). Although, fitting these parameters would further improve the C-statistic, as I have shown in NGC 7469 (Chapter 5) and NGC 1068 (Chapter 5), the small signal-to-noise ratio of this low exposure spectrum is not enough to accurately measure these parameters - so I kept them fixed.

The best fit parameter values for the 2009 observation (Obs.) are shown in Table 6.1: the PION parameters are the column density (N_H), the ionisation parameter (ξ), and the covering fraction (Ω); the CIE parameters are the

normalisation (N_{cie}) and electron temperature (T_e).

6.3.2 Results of fitting the 2009 spectrum

The ionisation parameter from the observed PION model is $\log \xi = 1.31$ (Table 6.1) which is consistent with $\log U_1 = 0.30$ from Model B, Table 2 in Matt et al. (2013) - the comparison was made using Figure 1 from George et al. (1998a). The column density found here is 10 times larger than the value for the same component in Matt et al. (2013), possibly a consequence of the fact that I only fit one PIE component, compared to three. From the CIE component, the electron temperature is much lower compared to the value from Matt et al. (2013) ($T_e = 0.53 keV$). The top panel in Figure 6.5 shows the observed 55 ks RGS spectrum (grey crosses) and best fit model (red), along with the PION (green) and CIE (blue) components, clearly showing which features they fit.

Using this model, I then simulated spectra of NGC 5643 for observation times of 120 and 240 ks. The middle panel of Figure 6.5 displays the two simulated and the observed spectra, where it is clear that the longer the exposure time, the smaller the flux uncertainties. Within each simulated spectrum I also fitted the model parameters (Table 6.1) in order to compare the simulated data to the observation results. The bottom panel of Figure 6.5 shows the 240 ks simulated spectrum only with the best fit model (red line) and the two emission components plotted on top (green for PIE and blue for CIE). An exposure time of 240 ks is sufficient to separate and resolve these emission lines (compared with the top panel), and allows for better constraints on the parameters (see Table 6.1). The parameter values from Table 6.1 are compared in Figure 6.6 - the errors for each parameter are reduced for an increase in exposure time. Overall, the parameters do not differ too much between the three scenarios and are all within the errors.

I also compared the O VII triplet from my analysis (left) to the results from Matt et al. (2013) (right) in Figure 6.7; both are plotted in the rest frame. The left side of Figure 6.7 shows the observed spectrum (blue crosses) and the simulated 240 ks spectrum (black crosses), with the best fit model, from Table

Table 6.1: Best fit parameter values for the RGS spectrum. The best fit models from the observed (Obs.) and 240 ks simulated spectrum data are shown in Figure 6.5 as the red line (top and bottom, respectively).

Comp.	Parameter	Units	Obs. (2009)	Sim 120 ks	Sim 240 ks
POW	N_{pow}	$(10^{48} \text{ ph s}^{-1} \text{ keV}^{-1})$	$5.16^{+0.48}_{-0.50}$	4.72 ± 0.33	$4.97^{+0.25}_{-0.26}$
	Γ	-	2.68 ± 0.22	2.88 ± 0.15	2.84 ± 0.11
PION	N_H	(10^{25} m^{-2})	$2.49^{+2.40}_{-1.11}$	$3.31^{+4.68}_{-1.55}$	$1.64^{+0.61}_{-0.41}$
	ξ	(10^{-9} Wm)	$1.31^{+0.10}_{-0.12}$	$1.34^{+0.11}_{-0.12}$	1.35 ± 0.05
	Ω	(10^{-3})	$1.98^{+1.62}_{-1.06}$	$1.37^{+1.10}_{-0.85}$	$3.17^{+1.07}_{-0.91}$
CIE	N_{cie}	(10^{68} m^{-3})	$1.78^{+1.18}_{-1.12}$	$2.27^{+0.86}_{-0.77}$	$1.22^{+0.62}_{-0.58}$
	T_e	(keV)	$0.21^{+0.11}_{-0.03}$	$0.20^{+0.03}_{-0.02}$	$0.24^{+0.09}_{-0.03}$
C-stat (d.o.f)			583 (375)	384 (375)	361 (375)

Table 6.2: Best fit parameter values for the EPIC-PN spectrum. The best fit model from the observed data is shown in Figure 6.8.

Comp.	Parameter	Units	Obs.	Sim 240 ks
POW	N_{pow}	$(10^{48} \text{ ph s}^{-1} \text{ keV}^{-1})$	2.89 ± 0.07	2.89 ± 0.03
	Γ	-	3.03 ± 0.05	3.05 ± 0.02
REFL	N_{refl}	$(10^{50} \text{ ph s}^{-1} \text{ keV}^{-1})$	< 1.57	< 1.40
GAUS	Norm	$(10^{46} \text{ ph s}^{-1} \text{ keV}^{-1})$	$6.66^{+1.73}_{-1.62}$	5.76 ± 0.72
	Energy	(keV)	7.41 ± 0.04	7.38 ± 0.02
	Norm	$(10^{46} \text{ ph s}^{-1} \text{ keV}^{-1})$	$3.95^{+1.40}_{-1.30}$	3.53 ± 0.60
	Energy	(keV)	1.85 ± 0.03	1.87 ± 0.01
C-stat (d.o.f)			176 (119)	125 (119)

6.1, shown as the red line. Clearly, there is a difference between the two panels, but this is due to the way the spectra were binned.

6.4 PN Modelling

The EPIC-PN spectrum was obtained using the EPPROC command, after removing the background flares. The source and background spectra were extracted using radii of 25 arcseconds (similar to Matt et al., 2013). Once I had obtained the 0.3 - 10 keV spectrum I initially fitted the continuum, made from a power-law (POW) and a reflection component (REFL). The POW parameters

Figure 6.5: RGS spectra. *Top:* 2009 observed spectrum (Obs.; grey crosses) fitted with the best fit model (red line). Also plotted are the model components, PION in green and CIE in blue, to show which emission lines they account for. *Middle:* Comparing the observed spectrum (purple crosses) with the 120 ks (blue) and 240 ks (green) simulated spectra; the red line is the best fit model to the observed data. *Bottom:* Same as *Top*, but this time for the 240 ks simulated spectrum (between 13 and 26 Å) with the best fit model (red line) and the two emission components plotted on top (green for PION and blue for CIE). An exposure time of 240 ks is sufficient to separate and resolve the emission lines (compared with the top panel).

Figure 6.6: Comparing the parameter values, and more importantly the error bars, from each RGS scenario fit: red for the observed RGS data, blue for the 120 ks simulated data, and green for the 240 ks simulated spectrum.

were initially set at the values from [Matt et al. \(2013\)](#) (same as Section 6.3.1), while the photon index in the REFL component was fixed at $\Gamma_H = 1.3$ ([Matt et al., 2013](#)). This was to reduce the number of free parameters as much as possible. I then fitted the normalisation and photon index of the power-law (N_{pow} and Γ) and the normalisation (N_{refl}) of the REFL component. This yielded an initial best fit of $C = 655$ for 123 d.o.f.

Next, I added and fixed the emission feature components that were fitted to the observed RGS spectrum: PION and CIE (Table 6.1). I then refitted the continuum parameters to the EPIC-PN data, which gave a new fit of $C = 535$ for 123 d.o.f. However, there were residuals in the soft X-ray band

Figure 6.7: Comparing the O VII triplet lines between my SAS reduction and SPEX binning (left), and the reduction and binning done by [Matt et al. \(2013\)](#) (right). Both plots are shown in the rest frame energy. The left panel displays the observed data (blue crosses), 240 ks simulated data (black crosses), and best fit model in red. The two plots differ slightly, but this is due to binning, rather than the counts being different.

which could be attributed to the known cross calibration issue between RGS and PN. In SPEX this is taken into account with the KNAK model (see Section 2.3.3 for the model details). In this case, and similarly to the analysis of NGC 3227 (Chapter 7), I took the ratio between the model and EPIC-PN data and used this as the correction factor for preselected segments in the spectrum. This KNAK correction is done instead of fitting the emission line components to the EPIC-PN data, where I am only interested in the harder X-rays (above 1.8 keV). This correction improved the C-statistic from $C = 535$ to $C = 324$. I refitted the continuum parameters (after fixing KNAK) and obtained a new C-statistic of $C = 207$ for 123 d.o.f. Finally, I added a Gaussian to fit the Ni $K\alpha$ line at around 7.4 keV (similarly to [Semena et al., 2019](#)), and the emission feature at 1.8 keV (similarly to [Matt et al., 2013](#), as no additional PION or CIE component accounted for this line). The GAUS components improved the fit further by $\Delta C = 21$ and $\Delta C = 8$, respectively. The final best fit C-statistic, with all parameters freed together (except KNAK) was $C = 176$ for 119 d.o.f ($C/\text{d.o.f} = 1.48$).

From this model, I simulated a 240 ks EPIC-PN spectrum. The best fit parameter results for the observed data (Obs.) and simulated spectrum are

shown in Table 6.2. Between the two scenarios, the power-law parameters do not change, but the reflection normalisation (N_{refl}) was not constrained, even in the 240 ks simulated data. The use of, for example, NuSTAR or EPIC-MOS data may help with this. There are slight differences in the Gaussian lines, but they are within the uncertainties, with the simulated spectra having significantly smaller errors. Figure 6.8 (top panel) shows the EPIC-PN spectrum with the best fit model overplotted in purple - also shown are the different steps taken to fit the model, described above. The bottom panel of Figure 6.8 shows the 240 ks simulated spectrum with best fit model in red.

6.5 Mass Outflow Rate

Riffel et al. (2018) found the mass outflow rate of the outflowing wind in NGC 5643 to be $\dot{M}_{out} \sim 0.3 M_{\odot} yr^{-1}$, from optical observations. However, [O III] emission traces the low density gas, meaning it underestimates the real nuclear mass outflow rate. X-ray emission, on the other hand, traces gas over a larger ionisation and density range and is more sensitive than the optical [O III] lines. Therefore, I aim to estimate the X-ray mass outflow rate (\dot{M}_{out} ; see Section 1.4.2 and Appendix B.1 for details) using the equation (Blustin et al., 2005)

$$\dot{M}_{out} \sim \frac{1.23 m_p L_{ion} f_v v \omega}{\xi}, \quad (6.1)$$

where m_p is the proton mass, L_{ion} is the ionising radiation between 13.6 eV and 13.6 keV, f_v is the volume filling fraction, v is the outflow velocity ($v_{out} = -450$ km s⁻¹; fixed from Cresci et al., 2015), ω is the solid angle, and ξ is the ionisation parameter. Here, I assume a volume filling factor of $f_v = 0.1$ (Chapter 4) and a solid angle of $\omega = 1.6$ sr (assuming 25% of the AGN population are Compton-thick, with an average 50% covering fraction; see references within Blustin et al., 2005; Annuar et al., 2015). For the ionising luminosity, I used and compared two values, from the following methods.

- A.) As NGC 5643 is a Compton-thick AGN we do not know the intrinsic SED. So instead, I assumed the SED model of NGC 7469 (Section 6.3.1),

Figure 6.8: *Top:* EPIC-PN spectrum of NGC 5643 from 2009 (grey crosses), with the different model steps applied, before getting to the final best fit. *Red line:* The initial continuum fit, made up from a power-law (POW) and a reflection component (REFL). *Blue line:* Adding the PION and CIE components to the continuum, with the values fixed from the RGS fit (Table 6.1). *Green line:* Accounting for the cross-calibration difference between RGS and EPIC-PN at low energies using the KNAK component, keeping the emission and continuum component parameters fixed. *Purple line:* Final best fit model with the continuum parameters refitted and with two additional GAUS components to model the 1.8 keV line, and the NiK α line at 7.4 keV. The best fit parameters are shown in Table 6.2. *Bottom:* 240 ks simulated EPIC-PN spectrum (black crosses) with the observed best fit model on top (red line).

a typical Seyfert nucleus (Mehdipour et al., 2018). From Section 5.3.1 in Chapter 5, I argued that the SED from NGC 7469 can be used in the analysis of NGC 1068 - Mehdipour et al. (2016b) compared photoionisation results based on different SEDs and found no significant changes between SEDs within the type 1 AGN studied. Therefore NGC 7469 is a reasonable SED to use for NGC 5643 as well. The derived ionising luminosity from the SED model is $L_{ion,SED} = 1.72 \times 10^{37}$ W.

B.) Alternatively, I used the ionising luminosity derived by Annuar et al. (2015), who were able to estimate the intrinsic 0.5 - 2 keV luminosity, $L_{0.5-2,int} = 0.3 - 0.6 \times 10^{35}$ W, after accounting for the Compton-thick absorption. To find the ionising luminosity, I set the power-law normalisation to a value such that the luminosity (in the 0.5 - 2 keV range) was equal to $L_{0.5-2,int} = 0.3 - 0.6 \times 10^{35}$ W. I then recalculated this for the ionising range of 13.6 eV to 13.6 keV, and obtained an intrinsic ionising luminosity of $L_{ion,int} \sim 8.65 \times 10^{35}$ W.

After inserting these numbers into Eq. 6.1, the X-ray mass outflow rate results to be $1.97 \pm 0.40 M_{\odot}yr^{-1}$ for the observed spectrum, when using the NGC 7469 SED (method A), which is an order of magnitude larger than the value found from Cresci et al. (2015) ($\dot{M}_{out} \sim 0.3 M_{\odot}yr^{-1}$). Similarly, for the simulated data, the mass outflow rates are 1.84 ± 0.42 and $1.80 \pm 0.20 M_{\odot}yr^{-1}$, for 120 ks and 240 ks, respectively. Alternatively, using the ionising luminosity derived from Annuar et al. (2015) (method B), the mass outflow rate is $0.10 \pm 0.02 M_{\odot}yr^{-1}$ for all three data sets, a third of the value found by Cresci et al. (2015) in the optical band.

From estimating the X-ray mass outflow rate, I then estimated how much energy is being carried by the X-ray wind. This gives us insight into whether the wind significantly influences the starburst clumps and host galaxy through feedback processes. The kinetic luminosities (L_K ; Section 1.4.2) is given by

$$L_K = \frac{\dot{M}_{out}v^2}{2}. \quad (6.2)$$

Using the observed mass outflow rate values of 1.97 and $0.10 M_{\odot}yr^{-1}$, and assuming $v = -450 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (Cresci et al., 2015), I estimated the kinetic luminosities to be $L_K = 1.26 \pm 0.26 \times 10^{34}$ and $L_K = 6.14 \pm 0.93 \times 10^{32}$ W using method A and method B, respectively.

In order to gauge anything useful from these values, I needed to find the ratio between L_K and the bolometric luminosity (L_{bol} ; similar to the WA analysis by Blustin et al. 2005 and in Chapter 4). In other words, what fraction of the total AGN luminosity comes from the X-ray band. There are a few values for the bolometric luminosity of NGC 5643 in the literature. From the radio luminosity ($L_{\nu}[8.4GHz] = 5.5 \times 10^{15}$ W) a kinetic luminosity of $L_K \sim 2 \times 10^{32}$ W is required, which is around 1% of the bolometric luminosity ($L_{bol} = 2 \times 10^{34}$ W; Cresci et al., 2015). However, this is too small compared to the ionising luminosities above. Alternatively, Brightman et al. (2017) obtained a bolometric luminosity of $L_{bol} = 1 \times 10^{36}$ W, while Guainazzi et al. (2004) estimated a value of $L_{bol} = 7.5 \times 10^{36}$ W (assuming Model 3 from their Table 3, and a typical AGN SED; see references within Guainazzi et al., 2004). These luminosities are larger compared to the intrinsic ionising luminosity (Annuar et al., 2015) (method B), but are still smaller compared to L_{ion} from the SED (method A). Therefore, I can only determine the L_K/L_{bol} ratio with the intrinsic value (method B).

For the intrinsic luminosity, L_K/L_{bol} is between 0.01 and 3.2 %, depending on which bolometric luminosity is used. This fraction is significantly larger than the L_K/L_{bol} ratios for NGC 7469 (< 0.003 %; Chapter 4) and for NGC 1068 (between 0.004 and 0.006 %; Chapter 5). As a comparison, the kinetic luminosity for the optical outflowing wind is $L_K = 1.92 \times 10^{33}$ W, which corresponds to 9.6% of the bolometric luminosity (assuming L_{bol} from Cresci et al., 2015). Although the X-ray energetics are smaller compared to the optical value, if the ionisation and bolometric luminosities used in the X-ray calculations are correct, then the X-ray wind could have some impact on the host galaxy, at least on long timescales, e.g. the lifetime of the AGN (Blustin

et al., 2005). This is evidence that the X-ray outflowing wind can induce star formation in the star forming clumps, as seen in the optical band (Figure 6.2).

6.6 Proposal

From this study, I wanted to put forward an XMM-Newton proposal at the twentieth announcement of opportunity (AO20), to observe NGC 5643 with a 240 ks exposure time. The aims of this proposal are similar to the above analysis. I want a long exposure to obtain a high signal-to-noise RGS spectrum in order to analyse the PIE and CIE plasma components in great detail; 240 ks is enough to resolve and separate the contributions from these emission line regions. Previous studies have analysed the soft X-rays ($E < 2$ keV) from NGC 5643 with EPIC-PN data (e.g. Matt et al., 2013), which does not have the line resolving power like RGS does. Therefore, I would be able to understand the origin of the PIE and CIE plasmas, and determine which is more dominating through RGS.

The overall impact of this proposal will come from establishing whether the soft X-ray emission in Seyfert 2 nuclei with radio outflows is fundamentally different (or not) from that in Seyfert 2 AGN without such radio structures, by discriminating whether the material is CIE or PIE dominated. We know that it is possible for the soft X-ray emission to be collisionally ionised by the outflowing material, just as the star formation is supposedly driven by it, but is this related to the radio emission in some AGN, or the ionised cones?

Furthermore, there is possible evidence for outflow-induced star formation in NGC 5643 (Cresci et al., 2015), which had never been seen in any AGN before. Therefore, I want to study the mass outflow rate and energetics (kinematic luminosity) of the X-ray wind: how much will the outflowing wind affect the host-galaxy and contribute to the galaxy/black hole co-evolution? Unfortunately, the analysis above is not conclusive, giving very low values for \dot{M}_{out} , inconsistent ionising luminosities, and no measured outflow velocity. However, a new RGS spectrum will allow N_H , ξ and v_{out} values to be accu-

rately measured, which are fundamental in understanding the properties of the outflowing wind. From this, estimates of the mass outflow rate and wind energetics will be achieved.

The proposal is shown in Appendix D.

6.7 Conclusion

NGC 5643 is an example of a Compton-thick AGN that is bright and close enough to be studied with RGS. However, although we can model the RGS spectrum, the exposure times are too short to separate PIE and CIE plasmas conclusively. In the past, only the EPIC-PN data have been studied in great depth, including the soft X-rays (e.g. [Matt et al., 2013](#)).

Despite this, I have modelled the 2009, 55ks RGS spectrum with a PIE component, and an additional CIE component. I have also simulated data for 120 ks and a 240 ks exposures, and compared the results together. Overall, there is very little difference in the parameter values (they are all within uncertainties; see Figure 6.6), but the error bars, for most parameters, decrease for an increase in exposure time.

I then modelled the EPIC-PN spectrum from the same observation, and a simulated 240 ks spectrum. Again, there is very little difference in parameter values, except in both cases the high energy reflection component could not be constrained. This could be solved by stacking the old and new observations (assuming no variability), or by adding additional NuSTAR data for energies > 10 keV. In comparison with previous analysis of the hard X-rays, I find a photon index ($\Gamma = 3.04$) lower than the values found from [Annuar et al. \(2015\)](#), but significantly softer than the model values from [Guainazzi et al. \(2004\)](#). This may be because I fixed the hard photon index of $\Gamma_H = 1.3$ from [Matt et al. \(2013\)](#), which is lower than that found in [Annuar et al. \(2015\)](#).

From this modelling, I tried to measure the X-ray mass outflow rate and wind energetics. The mass outflow rate was found to be $1.97M_{\odot}yr^{-1}$ for the SED luminosity (method A), or $0.1 M_{\odot}yr^{-1}$ for the intrinsic ionising luminos-

ity (method B), both from the observed data. In comparison, the mass outflow rate from the optical analysis was $0.3 M_{\odot} \text{yr}^{-1}$. Regarding the ratio between the kinetic and bolometric luminosities, I was unable to use the results from the SED luminosity (method A) as L_{ion} was larger than all L_{bol} values. However, using the intrinsic luminosity (method B), L_K/L_{bol} is between 0.01 and 3.2 %, suggesting that this wind could impact the host galaxy. As a comparison, the ratio of L_k/L_{bol} for the optical wind is $\sim 10\%$, which is significant enough to impact the galaxy (e.g. [Blustin et al., 2005](#)).

There are, however, a number of significant caveats with this analysis of the outflowing wind. (i) I do not know the intrinsic SED shape and therefore have assumed the ionising SED of NGC 7469. (ii) I directly estimated an ionising luminosity based on the intrinsic 0.5 - 2 keV luminosity from [Annuar et al. \(2015\)](#), which may not be applicable to the full X-ray energy range - I only used the power-law component to obtain this value, and did not include the reflection component. (iii) These results depend highly on L_{ion} , whereby the two values I used (method A or method B) differ by a factor of ~ 20 . (iv) Finally, I have assumed that the X-ray outflowing wind is travelling at the same velocity as the optical gas ($v_{out} = -450 \text{ km s}^{-1}$; [Riffel et al., 2018](#)), as the low exposure time of the 2009 RGS spectrum did not allow me to fit the outflow velocity of the PIE component.

NGC 5643 is an excellent target, similar to NGC 1068, for further observations and analysis of outflowing winds and the emission line region in CT AGN. In particular, optical analysis provides evidence that NGC 5643 is the first AGN to show possible outflow-induced star formation. Furthermore, NGC 5643 has been found to have a compact radio core ([Morris et al., 1985](#)). This opens up questions as to whether these outflowing winds initiate or quench star formation, and whether radio emission has an impact on the emitting plasma that we observe. Studying this Compton-thick AGN will allow us to understand whether the outflowing wind is driven by this radio outflow, or if the collisional emission is a result of the outflowing wind interacting with

the star forming region. Unfortunately, the analysis in this Chapter does not answer these questions. However, with a significantly longer exposure time and a high signal-to-noise soft X-ray spectrum, some progress in solving these paradigms can be made, in addition to over-coming some of the caveats.

Chapter 7

Examining the Variability during an Obscuration Event Captured in NGC 3227

The work carried out in this Chapter follows on from a series of papers,
studying NGC 3227 during an obscuration event:

M. Mehdipour, ... S. Grafton-Waters, et al., 2021,
A&A, **652**, **A150** (Paper I);

Y. Wang, ... S. Grafton-Waters, et al., 2022,
A&A, **657**, **A77** (Paper II);

J. Mao, ... S. Grafton-Waters, et al., Submitted, A&A (Paper III);
S. Grafton-Waters, et al., in Prep, A&A (Paper IV).

Abstract

Recently obscuration events in type 1 AGN, where there is a significant drop in soft X-ray flux between two observations, have been observed frequently. They are thought to be caused by clouds with large column densities transiting our line-of-sight to the central black hole. Unfortunately, little is known about these events, such as, for example, where do they originate from; why do the event durations differ between AGN; what are their physical properties; and how do they differ from UFOs and WAs?

In this Chapter, I explore the obscuration event seen in the type 1 AGN, NGC 3227, at the end of 2019. By studying the EPIC-PN spectra, the aim is to determine the properties of the obscurer and origin of the observed variability. The two 2019 observations show strong differences in flux and spectral shape between each other, and compared to archival data from 2016 when NGC 3227 was in an unobscured state. I initially fit the time-averaged 0.35 - 10 keV EPIC-PN spectra of each observation, using the model from [Mao et al.](#) (who fitted the RGS, EPIC-PN and NuSTAR data from both observations), before splitting each observation into ten timing bins (TBs) of equal length. I then fit the EPIC-PN spectrum of each TB to see how the parameters of the continuum and obscurer varied over the course of each observation. In the first observation, there is an anti-correlation between the continuum parameters and the column density of the obscurer. Through further testing, I find evidence that the continuum drives the observed variability, but I cannot rule out some contribution from the obscurer. The parameters in the second observation stay consistent throughout.

7.1 Introduction

Obscuration events in active galactic nuclei (AGN) have started being detected more readily in recent years. The first major event was seen in NGC 5548 ([Kaastra et al., 2014](#)) where the XMM-Newton soft X-ray flux in 2013 was 25 times weaker compared to the 2002 Chandra data. Other obscuring events include, NGC 3783 ([Mehdipour et al., 2017](#); [Kriss et al., 2019](#)), Mrk 335 ([Longinotti et al., 2013](#)), NGC 985 ([Ebrero et al., 2016](#)), and NGC 3227 ([Turner et al., 2018](#)). It is possible that many AGN have undergone obscuration at some point in their lifetime and these events are more common than first thought ([Kaastra et al., 2018](#)). For example, multiple occultation events were seen in NGC 3783 between 1993 and 2016 ([Kaastra et al., 2018](#)), including the December 2016 event lasting 32 days ([Mehdipour et al., 2017](#)); while NGC 3227 has undergone many obscuring events lasting days, weeks

and months (Lamer et al., 2003; Markowitz et al., 2014; Beuchert et al., 2015; Turner et al., 2018). Obscuring winds (Section 1.3.5) have different properties compared to the warm absorbers (WAs, Section 1.3.2; e.g. Kaastra et al., 2002; Grafton-Waters et al., 2020), ultra-fast outflows (UFOs, Section 1.3.4; e.g. Risaliti et al., 2005; Tombesi et al., 2013) and the emission line regions (Section 1.3.1; e.g. Kinkhabwala et al., 2002; Grafton-Waters et al., 2021b), such as column densities and outflow velocities. For further details regarding the properties of the obscurers found in NGC 5548 and NGC 3783, see Section 1.3.5.

The type 1.5 AGN¹, NGC 3227 ($z = 0.003859$; de Vaucouleurs et al., 1991), has shown strong variability in both X-ray and UV bands, particularly during periods of high flux (Markowitz et al., 2009; Arévalo & Markowitz, 2014), with a steeper X-ray slope when brighter trend consistent with other AGN (Lobban et al., 2020). A good correlation between the soft and hard X-ray variability has been seen (e.g. Komossa & Fink, 1997; Markowitz et al., 2009), although other analysis has found the soft band to lag behind the hard X-ray flux (Lobban et al., 2020). Changes on short timescales (within a few days) were due to continuum variations, and on longer timescales (weeks or months) variations were due to changes in the absorber properties (e.g. George et al., 1998b; Gondoin et al., 2003; Lobban et al., 2020). This is similar to the explanations for the variability in NGC 4151 (e.g. Keck et al., 2015; Beuchert et al., 2017).

Two (Markowitz et al., 2009, 2014) and three (Crenshaw et al., 2001; Beuchert et al., 2015) ionised absorbers have been found in NGC 3227. The variable absorption event in NGC 3227 during 2008 was caused by a medium ionised component ($\log \xi \sim 1.2 - 1.4$) increasing in covering fraction (f_{cov} ; from 0.7 to 0.9) and column density (N_H ; from 5 to $18 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}^{-2}$), possibly located within the BLR or inner torus (Beuchert et al., 2015). Furthermore, an XMM-Newton and NuSTAR campaign in 2016 found a rapid variability event lasting

¹A type 1.5 AGN is one where the line strengths and broadness of the H α and H β spectral are the same.

Figure 7.1: EPIC-PN and NuSTAR spectra for 2016 (blue data) and 2019 (November - red data; December - purple data). There is strong soft X-ray absorption between 2016 and 2019, which also becomes prominent in the hard X-ray band during December 2019. (Image taken from [Mehdipour et al., 2021](#)).

a day ([Turner et al., 2018](#)). To explain the observed spectral hardening and a depth change of the unresolved transition array (UTA) in the RGS data, in addition to the soft band curvature in the EPIC-PN data, a fourth component (covering 60% of the X-ray continuum) was required (with $N_H = 5 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}^{-2}$; $\log \xi = 2$; $v_{out} \sim -800 \text{ km s}^{-1}$). This obscurer was also associated with clouds within the BLR.

During a Swift ToO (target of opportunity) monitoring programme, an obscuration event in NGC 3227 was captured at the end of 2019 (November and December), triggering observations with XMM-Newton, NuSTAR and HST. Strong spectral hardening and intrinsic X-ray variability were found between the two 2019 observations taken three weeks apart, along with strong soft X-ray absorption compared to the 2016 observations; this is shown in the right

Figure 7.2: Softness ratio against the 0.3 - 10 keV count rate. Grey data points show the 2016 data that did not undergo obscuration. Red and orange data points show the obscuration events in 2016 analysed by Wang et al. (2022). The green and blue data points show the November and December 2019 observations, respectively, that are analysed in this Chapter. (This figure is an extension from Figure 2 in Wang et al., 2022).

side of Figure 7.1 (Mehdipour et al., 2021). Figure 7.2 expresses the strong flux decrease in an alternative way, showing the softness ratio of the 2016 NGC 3227 data during the unobscured states (grey data points) and obscured states (orange and red for 2016, and green and blue for 2019). In 2019, the softness ratio is lower compared to 2016, showing stronger X-ray absorption, corresponding to the spectral changes in the right side of Figure 7.1.

Studies of the 2019 occultation event were started with the derivation of the broadband continuum, giving rise to the spectral energy distribution (SED) of NGC 3227 (Mehdipour et al., 2021). Mehdipour et al. (2021) modelled and compared two spectra from different epochs: December 2016 (unobscured) and December 2019 (obscured). The former date was used to better constrain the intrinsic soft X-ray continuum and the latter epoch showed the greater difference compared to 2016 (see Figure 7.1). This SED model was used to probe the properties and location of the obscuring material in the sequential papers reporting the study of the obscuration event.

Analysis of the archival 2006 and 2016 data is presented in Wang et al. (2022), using the broadband SED to model the WA wind. Four WA components were found with ionisation parameters ranging from $\log \xi = -1$ to 3, and outflow velocities in the range $v_{out} = -100$ to -1300 km s⁻¹, located between the BLR and NLR. The column density of the highest ionised component was $N_H \sim 10^{26}$ m⁻², while the other three components had columns of $N_H \sim 10^{25}$ m⁻². A missed obscuring event in 2006 was found for the first time in Wang et al. (2022), while the event in 2016 (Turner et al., 2018) was re-evaluated. The 2006 obscurer was explained with one component, but two were required in 2016: $\log \xi = 1 - 1.9$ and $N_H = 10^{26}$ m⁻² for both epochs, and $\log \xi = 2.8$ and $N_H = 10^{27}$ m⁻² for 2016 only. The obscurers were located within the BLR. Finally, Mao et al. (Submitted) has studied the 2019 data and obscuring event in detail, focusing on the time-averaged spectra. One photoionisation absorber component (PI0N) was required in each observation, with the estimated location comparable to the BLR and inner torus.

Table 7.1: Observation log for NGC 3227.

Obs	Obs ID	Start Date	Duration (ks)
1	0844341301	2019/11/15	103
2	0844341401	2019/12/05	50

In this Chapter, I analyse the variability in the obscuring wind within NGC 3227 during 2019, by implementing the initial model from (Mao et al., Submitted) and fitting it to the EPIC-PN data. The aim is to understand what drives the variability in this obscuration event by measuring how the model parameters change over the course of each observation.

7.2 Data Reduction

XMM-Newton observed NGC 3227 twice during an X-ray obscured state at the end of 2019. The two observations (Obs 1 and Obs 2, hereafter) lasted 103 and 50 ks, respectively, with the details shown in the observation log (Table 7.1). Here I report on the analysis of the European Photon Imaging Camera pn-CCD (EPIC-PN, Section 3.1.2; Strüder et al., 2001) spectra, taken in small-window mode, modelled between 0.35 - 10 keV. The EPIC-PN data were reduced using the `EPPROC` command in the `SAS` (v18.0.0) pipeline, where I removed background flaring with counts greater than 0.4 counts s⁻¹ within the energy range (`PI IN [10000:12000]`) using the `#XMMEA_EP` filter. I extracted the source spectrum using a circle of radius 40 arcseconds and the background spectra were extracted with two circular regions of 30 arcseconds from a source free region on the same CCD; both with quality photons only (`FLAG == 0`). I included both single and double events (`PATTERN <= 4`). Finally, the instrumental response matrices were generated with the `rmfgen` and `arfgen` commands. The data were binned using the Kaastra & Bleeker (2016) optimal binning method and I fitted the spectra using `SPEX` (v3.05.00; Kaastra et al., 1996).

7.3 Light Curves

The light curves for each observation are displayed in Figure 7.3, shown through five different energy bands: 0.3 - 10 keV (red), 0.3 - 2 keV (green), 2 - 10 keV (blue), 2 - 6 keV (magenta), and 6 - 10 keV (cyan). The left side of Figure 7.3 shows large variability over the course of Obs 1, whereas Obs 2 (right side) has far fewer counts and is less variable, although there is an apparent repetitive pattern. To determine how each energy band varied with respect to each other, I took the count rate ratios between each energy band and the full 0.3 - 10 keV range (shown in Figure 7.4). For Obs 1 (left), the 0.3 - 2 keV (green) ratio decreases between 35 and 55 ks and again, albeit weakly, at 65 - 70 ks, whereas the 2 - 10 keV (blue) and 2 - 6 keV (magenta) ratios increase. These features occur during the deep minima of the total flux (Figure 7.3), likely a result of natural variations of the underlying continuum. On the other hand, Obs 2 shows little change between the energy ratios.

I also obtained the hardness ratio (HR) for each observation (Figure 7.5), which is defined as $(H - S)/(H + S)$, where H is the 2 - 10 keV hard and S is the 0.3 - 2 keV soft energy band fluxes. For Obs 2 (right side of Figure 7.5), the ratio stays constant over the observing window, with slight fluctuations, similar to Figure 7.3. However, for Obs 1 (left side of Figure 7.5), there is strong spectral hardening between 30 and 50 ks, corresponding to the changes in soft (0.3 - 2 keV) and hard (2 - 10 keV) light curve ratios over this period (see left panel of Figure 7.4). This suggests changes in the underlying continuum or the possible variability of the obscurer, which is what I am investigating in this Chapter.

7.4 Timing Bins

To measure any spectral changes over the duration of the observations, I split each observation into ten timing bins (TBs). The TBs in Obs 1 and Obs 2 were 10.3 ks and 5 ks in duration, respectively, as shown in Figure 7.3.

For each TB, I obtained the averaged 0.3 - 2 keV and 2 - 10 keV count rates

Figure 7.3: Light curves for Obs 1 (left) and Obs 2 (right). Each colour represents a different energy band: 0.3 - 10 keV (red), 0.3 - 2 keV (green), 2 - 10 keV (blue), 2 - 6 keV (magenta), 6 - 10 keV (cyan). Also displayed are the timing bins (TB) from which I extracted EPIC-PN spectra for the analysis. The light curves were binned at 100 s.

Figure 7.4: Ratio light curves between each energy band in Figure 7.3 divided by the full 0.3 - 10 keV light curve (red line, top panels). The Obs 1 ratios are on the left hand side and the Obs 2 ratios are on the right.

from the light curves, displayed in the left side Figure 7.6 in both observations; exhibiting a clear correlation between each energy band. For Obs 2 (diamonds), there is no correlation between the two energy ranges; not surprising as there is very little change in the full light curve (Figure 7.3). For Obs 1 (circles), on the other hand, there is a correlation between the two energy ranges, and there are TB groups. For TB1 - TB5, the count rates in both energy bands are low, compared to TB7 - TB10.

The right side of Figure 7.6 shows the average hardness ratios for Obs 1 and Obs 2 as a function of the 0.3 - 10 keV count rate. Obs 2 has a larger hardness ratio and smaller count rates, while Obs 1 is softer than Obs 2, but

fluctuates in HR over the course of the observation, similar to Figure 7.5. In Obs 1, TB1 and TB2 have the smallest hardness ratios, which increase for TB3 - TB5, before decreasing again for TB6 - TB10. This increased hardening (TB3 - TB5) is related to the Figures 7.4 and 7.5 where the hard X-ray flux increased between 35 and 55 ks. A decrease in the HR comes about when the total count rate increases during the second half of the observation (left side of Figure 7.3). Figure 7.6 implies that NGC 3227 shows a ‘softer-when-brighter’ correlation (Lobban et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2022).

From each TB, I extracted the 0.35 - 10 keV EPIC-PN spectrum², in addition to the time-averaged spectrum from each observation (i.e. the EPIC-PN spectrum from the full observation). Figure 7.7 shows each TB spectrum for Obs 1 (left) and Obs 2 (right); the time-averaged spectrum is shown in red as a comparison. The spectra from Obs 2 are significantly noisier compared to Obs 1 because of the lower count rate and shorter observation time (half that of Obs 1). A clear gap between the spectra of TB1 - TB5, and TB7 - TB10, with TB6 somewhere in between, and very similar to the average spectrum, can be seen in Obs 1, relating to the flux increase half way through (see Figure 7.3).

I initially modelled the time-averaged spectrum from each observation (separately), corresponding to the base model, before fitting each TB spectrum. This allowed me to study what caused the variability in the light curves and changes in the spectra, in order to explain the nature of the X-ray variability within this AGN.

7.5 Spectral fitting

In order to analyse the spectral variations over the course of the two observations, I required the models from the previous papers in this campaign. The intrinsic (unobscured) SED (Mehdipour et al., 2021) consisted of a power-law

²All the light curves were obtained with the energy range of 0.3 - 10 keV, however the spectra were modelled between 0.35 - 10 keV to remove some data points that dropped significantly in flux below 0.35 keV.

Figure 7.5: Hardness ratios $\left(\frac{H-S}{H+S}\right)$, where $S = 0.3 - 2$ keV and $H = 2 - 10$ keV, for Obs 1 (left) and Obs 2 (right). The red dashed lines show the average hardness ratio (HR_{avg}) across each observation. For Obs 1 $HR_{avg} = -0.115$, and for Obs 2 $HR_{avg} = -0.033$.

Figure 7.6: *Left:* Correlation between the averaged 0.3 - 2 keV (soft) and 2 - 10 keV (hard) count rates for each timing bin (TB). Obs 1 (hollow circles) and Obs 2 (diamonds) are compared with the time-averaged values shown in red. *Right:* Hardness ratio $\left(\frac{H-S}{H+S}\right)$ as a function of the average 0.3 - 10 keV count rates. NGC 3227 shows a ‘softer-when-brighter’ trend as Obs 1 has a larger flux but lower hardness ratio compared to Obs 2.

(POW), a neutral reflection component (REFL; Magdziarz & Zdziarski, 1995), a Comptonisation component (COMT; Titarchuk, 1994) for the soft excess, and a disk blackbody component (DBB) for the optical to UV band. (Details of these components are discussed in Section 2.3.1.) In the model, the intrinsic continuum was absorbed by the obscuring wind, and therefore the SED parameters were fixed to the values from (Mehdipour et al., 2021); this is the obscured SED. However, the initial values for the normalisations of the DBB, POW and COMT components (N_{dbb} , N_{pow} , N_{comt} , respectively), the reflection scaling parameter (s), and photon index (Γ_{pow}) were taken from Table 2 in Mao et al. (Submitted) - shown in the top half of Figure 7.2, as these were

Table 7.2: Continuum parameter values for NGC 3227. Values in the top half were initial values taken from [Mao et al. \(Submitted\)](#) and modelled in this Chapter. Values in the bottom half were fixed to the 2016 values from [Mehdipour et al. \(2021\)](#). Parameters followed by an (f) were fixed throughout, all other values were fitted.

Comp.	Parameter	Value		Reference
		Obs 1	Obs 2	
POW	N_{pow} (10^{50} ph s $^{-1}$ keV $^{-1}$)	2.86	0.76	Mao et al. (Submitted)
	Γ_{pow}	1.70	1.83	
COMT	N_{comt} (10^{53} ph s $^{-1}$ keV $^{-1}$)	2.20	0.53	
REFL	s	0.43	0.26	
DBB	N_{dbb} (10^{30} m $^{-2}$)	4.9 (f)	4.0 (f)	
REFL	N_{refl} (10^{50} ph s $^{-1}$ keV $^{-1}$)	3.87 (f)		Mehdipour et al. (2021)
	Γ_{refl}	1.38 (f)		
	E_{cut} (keV)	309 (f)		
COMT	T_{seed} (eV)	10.2 (f)		
	T_e (keV)	0.06 (f)		
	τ	30 (f)		
DBB	T (eV)	10.2 (f)		

measured during the obscured state. Furthermore, the normalisation (N_{refl}) and photon index (Γ_{refl}) of the reflection component were coupled and fixed to the power-law values in 2016 (unobscured state; [Mehdipour et al., 2021](#)). These are displayed, along with the other fixed SED parameters from the 2016 observations, in the bottom half of [Table 7.2](#). Here it was assumed that the reflection occurs from neutral material far from the ionising continuum. However, this may not be the case and is discussed later in [Section 7.6.4](#). To the power-law, I applied upper (309 keV; [Turner et al., 2018](#)) and lower energy (equal to the disk energy) cutoffs. The high energy cutoff was also applied to the reflection component, fixed at 309 keV. I modelled the neutral gas in our Galaxy using the H0T model in SPEX; I fixed the column density and temperature at $N_H^{HOT} = 2.07 \times 10^{24}$ m $^{-2}$ ([Murphy et al., 1996](#)) and $T_{Gal} = 0.5$ eV, respectively.

I also included the four WA components from [Wang et al. \(2022\)](#) ([Table](#)

7.3), modelled with PION components (Mehdipour et al., 2016b), but accounted for their deionised nature due to the obscurer (similar to NGC 5548; Kaastra et al. 2014, and NGC 3783; Mehdipour et al. 2017). One PION component was used to model the obscurer in both observations with the initial parameters from Table 7.3 (Mao et al., Submitted). Finally, I accounted for the emission lines with PION components (one in Obs 1 and two in Obs 2). However, the ionising continuum was different to the one used for the obscurer and WA (see Mao et al., Submitted, for details). Here I applied the intrinsic SED derived from 2016 (Mehdipour et al., 2021) and the warm emitter values were fixed to those from Table 7.3 (Mao et al., Submitted).

I then folded the initial model described above to the time-averaged 0.35 - 10 keV EPIC-PN spectrum for each observation. The initial C-statistics were $C = 3691$ (123 degrees of freedom, d.o.f hereafter) and $C = 582$ (113 d.o.f), for Obs 1 and Obs 2, respectively. However, I found that there were strong residuals between the data and model at softer energies in both observations, as shown in Figure 7.8. This is most likely due to the cross calibration issue between the Reflection Grating Spectrometer (RGS, Section 3.1.1; den Herder et al., 2001) and EPIC-PN instruments as Mao et al. (Submitted) modelled both - the RGS for the soft X-rays and EPIC-PN data for the hard X-rays - and here I only model the EPIC-PN data.

Therefore, to correct for the cross calibration issue I forced the EPIC-PN data to agree with RGS. To do this, I first obtained the ratio between the data (D_{PN}) and the initial model (M_{PN}) for the EPIC-PN spectra ($R_{PN} = \frac{D_{PN}}{M_{PN}}$; with D_{PN} and M_{PN} from Figure 7.8), between 6 and 37 Å (as this corresponds to the RGS band, shown in Figure 7.9). Here I assumed that the model from Mao et al. (Submitted) fitted the RGS data very well, such that the ratio between the data (D_{RGS}) and model (M_{RGS}) was approximately one ($R_{RGS} = \frac{D_{RGS}}{M_{RGS}} \sim 1$). Next, I applied a KNAK component to the model (similar to Porquet et al., 2004; Detmers et al., 2010), which is a piecewise broken power-law. KNAK splits the model into continuous segments, multiplying the

Table 7.3: Obscurer, warm emitter and warm absorber parameter values for NGC 3227. Two emitting components were used in Obs 2 and four WA components were found in the 2016 data. All values followed by a (f) are fixed throughout the fitting.

Parameter	Value		Reference
	Obs 1	Obs 2	
Obscurer			
N_H (10^{26} m $^{-2}$)	3.5	7.3	Mao et al. (Submitted)
$\log \xi$ (10^{-9} W m)	0.4 (f)	1.8 (f)	
f_{cov}	0.61	0.67	
Warm Emitter			
N_H (10^{24} m $^{-2}$)	7.9 (f)	3.8, 2.8 (f)	Mao et al. (Submitted)
$\log \xi$ (10^{-9} W m)	1.28 (f)	2.6, 0.7 (f)	
v_{turb} (km s $^{-1}$)	1790 (f)	840 (f)	
C_{cov}	0.1 (f)		
Warm Absorbers			
N_H (10^{26} m $^{-2}$)	2.27, 0.25, 0.12, 0.16 (f)		Wang et al. (2022)
$\log \xi$ (10^{-9} W m)	3.29, 2.59, 1.89, -1.06 (f)		
v_{turb} (km s $^{-1}$)	20, 140, 50, 260 (f)		
v_{out} (km s $^{-1}$)	-1270, -500, -440, -110 (f)		

model by a factor T_N , set to R_{PN} taken from Figure 7.9 (top panel), for a given wavelength (λ_N), where N is the segment number (the maximum is nine per KNAK component; see Section 2.3.3 and the SPEX manual for more details³). The KNAK model takes into account the instrumental effects and not the physics of NGC 3227, therefore when applying the KNAK component I kept the initial model parameters fixed. In order to be consistent outside the selected range (6 - 37 Å), the lowest wavelength (λ_1) was fixed to 0.1 Å and T_1 was coupled to T_2 . For the opposite end, λ_9 was fixed at 100 Å and T_9 was coupled to T_8 . For the remaining seven wavelengths, I chose R_{PN} , and its respective wavelength, by eye from Figure 7.9. This gave an improved R_{PN} across the wavelength range, but the parameters $T_2 - T_8$ and $\lambda_2 - \lambda_8$ were fitted to achieve a more reasonable fit between the model and the data. This can be seen as the blue

³<https://www.sron.nl/astrophysics-splex/manual>

Figure 7.7: EPIC-PN spectra for Obs 1 (left) and Obs 2 (right). The time-averaged spectra are shown in red and the TB colours are presented in the legends.

and purple data points in Figure 7.9 for Obs 1 and Obs 2, respectively. Once the KNAK parameters were fitted, I kept them fixed throughout the rest of the EPIC-PN modelling. I repeated the above for Obs 2, as shown in the right side of Figures 7.8 and 7.9. The corrected C-statistics were $C = 336$ (123 d.o.f) and $C = 209$ (113 d.o.f) for Obs 1 and Obs2, respectively (see Figure 7.8).

For the time-averaged spectrum of each observation, I then fitted N_{pow} , Γ , N_{comt} , and s of the obscured SED from 2019; the column density (N_H) and covering fraction (C_f) of the obscurer component; and the velocity broadening of the Fe $K\alpha$ 6.4 keV line by coupling a VGAU component to REFL. I initially tried fitting the ionisation parameter (ξ) of the obscurer (PION component) but could not constrain it. Therefore I kept the ξ values for each observation fixed from Mao et al. (Submitted) (see Table 7.3). Fitting these parameters improved the best fit to $C = 224$ (116 d.o.f) in Obs 1, and $C = 103$ (106 d.o.f) for Obs 2. The final best fit models are displayed in Figure 7.10. Now that I obtained a good fit to the time-averaged EPIC-PN data only, I used this as the baseline model to fit the spectra of each TB. The best fit parameter results are displayed in Tables 7.4 and 7.5 for Obs 1 and Obs 2, respectively.

7.6 Results and discussion

Figure 7.10 shows the time-averaged spectra of the two observations with the final best fit models. In this Section, I compare the parameter results from each TB for the two observations before studying the cause of the observed

Figure 7.8: Initial and KNAK corrected models for Obs 1 (left) and Obs 2 (right). The initial models were from Tables 7.2 and 7.3 (green and pink, respectively), while the corrected models are in blue and purple, respectively. The C-statistic values are displayed, along with their respective degrees of freedom in the parentheses. The bottom panels show the residuals between the data and model. Section 7.5 explains the steps required to correct the models, shown in Figure 7.9.

variability, and the decrease in flux between archive data and the 2019 observations. To check that my modelling was consistent with the SED from Mehdipour et al. (2021), I obtained the SED from the time-averaged results in both observations. Figure 7.11 shows that the SEDs shapes of the two 2019 observations are similar with the December 2019 SED from Mehdipour et al. (2021), the difference in normalisation is a result of the observed continuum variations.

7.6.1 Timing Bins Comparison

Tables 7.4 and 7.5 display the best fit parameter values for each TB in Obs 1 and Obs 2, respectively, along with the time-averaged spectrum results (All). Figure 7.12 displays how these parameters change over the course of each observation. For each panel in Figure 7.12, the time averaged values are shown by the red dashed and solid horizontal lines for Obs 1 and Obs 2, respectively, and the shaded areas show the uncertainties.

The top two panels in Figure 7.12 display how the power-law normalisation (N_{pow} ; left) and photon index (Γ_{pow} ; right) change over time. For Obs 1, N_{pow} increases during the observation, between TB5 and TB7, consistent with the count rate increase in the light curve of Figure 7.3. For Obs 2, on

the other hand, N_{pow} fluctuates around the time-averaged value, similar to the light curves in Figure 7.3. The photon index in both observations varied between TBs, whereby for Obs 2, the values correlate well with N_{pow} . For both observations, Γ_{pow} is consistent with the typical slope in the hard part of the spectrum, similar to previous observations ($\Gamma = 1.5 - 1.8$; e.g. Gondoin et al., 2003; Cappi et al., 2006; Rivers et al., 2011; Arévalo & Markowitz, 2014), although this parameter is overall slightly lower in Obs 1.

The top-middle panels in Figure 7.12 show the Comptonisation normalisation (N_{comt} ; left) and reflection scaling parameter (s ; right). For Obs 1, N_{comt} has the same, but more significant, trend as N_{pow} , which is to be expected from the light curves (Figure 7.3). For Obs 2, similarly to N_{pow} , N_{comt} just varies slightly between TBs. The reflection scaling parameter is consistent over each observation within error bars (except for TB2 in Obs 1). With no changes with respect to N_{pow} and N_{comt} , this could suggest that the reflecting material is located further from the black hole than the source of the continuum radiation. This result was also found by Lobban et al. (2020).

The bottom-middle panels in Figure 7.12 present the column density (N_H ; left) and covering fraction (f_{cov} ; right) of the obscurer component. In Obs 1, N_H decreases through each TB, which follows the inverse trend compared to N_{pow} and N_{comt} . I discuss the possible causes of this observed variability in Section 7.6.3. For Obs 2 on the other hand, the f_{cov} and N_H values are both larger compared to Obs 1; N_H is fairly consistent, while f_{cov} varies within the uncertainties. This could explain the observed low soft X-ray flux in Obs 2.

Comparatively, Beuchert et al. (2015) found that the variability of NGC 3227 in 2008 was caused by an increase in covering fraction (0.7 to 0.9) and column density (5 to $18 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}^{-2}$) in an absorption component. Between Obs 1 and Obs 2 (Tables 7.4 and 7.5), the time-averaged results indicate that f_{cov} increased from 0.57 to 0.63 ($\Delta f_{cov} = 0.06$) and N_H altered from $3.74 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}^{-2}$ to $6.52 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}^{-2}$ ($\Delta N_H = 2.78 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}^{-2}$); which are not as large compared to Beuchert et al. (2015). Conversely, N_{pow} and N_{comp}

decreased from 2.59 to 0.67×10^{50} ph s⁻¹ keV⁻¹ and from 2.10 to 0.54×10^{53} ph s⁻¹ keV⁻¹ ($\Delta N_{pow} = 1.92 \times 10^{50}$ and $\Delta N_{comt} = 1.56 \times 10^{53}$ ph s⁻¹ keV⁻¹), respectively, for the time-averaged results. As a comparison, in NGC 5548, the short-term variability (days to weeks) was driven by changes in both the column density and covering fraction of the obscurer (Cappi et al., 2016), whereas for the long-term variability (weeks to months), the covering fraction of the obscurer changed over time (Mehdipour et al., 2016a). The difference between f_{cov} is not very significant here, but a large difference is seen in the other three parameters.

Finally, the bottom panel in Figure 7.12 shows the Fe K α 6.4 keV line broadening velocity (σ). This parameter was very difficult to constrain, where in most cases only the upper limit was achieved. This is because the instrumental line resolution of EPIC-PN at 6.4 keV is roughly 7×10^3 km s⁻¹ (150 eV), such that the line velocity broadening may not be obtained if too narrow. The fluctuations in σ are not correlated to the other parameters, but could help explain why s in TB2 is so large compared to the others. The broadening velocity for TB2 is 9680 km s⁻¹, while $s = 1.09$; both of which have very large uncertainties, suggesting that there could be a degeneracy between s and σ of the reflection component. In addition, TB3 has a very large σ with large uncertainties, but the s value is consistent with the other TBs in Obs 1, which do not have such high broadening velocities.

7.6.2 Parameter Comparison

After fitting the data for each TB, I examined whether there were any correlations between the parameters. In doing so, I find that there are trends between N_{pow} and N_{comt} , as well as with N_H . These are displayed in the left side of Figure 7.13. By comparing both observations, N_{pow} and N_{comt} correlate well with each other, while an inverse trend is seen between them and N_H (Figure 7.13). In addition to Figure 7.13, I found some, albeit less conclusive, trends between parameters: N_{pow} and Γ , and f_{cov} and Γ , but these were only seen in Obs 2; N_H against s , and f_{cov} against s , but there were some outliers.

Figure 7.9: Steps taken to correct for the poor initial model fit caused by the RGS and PN cross calibration issue (see Section 7.5 for details). In Obs 1 (left) green is the initial model and blue is the corrected model; in Obs 2 (right) pink and purple are the initial and corrected models, respectively. *Top:* The ratio between the data and model. These ratio values (R_{PN}) were then used in the KNAK model (λ_N and T_N) for the correction. *Bottom:* The PN spectrum between 6 - 37 Å with the two models on top.

Therefore, for these reasons, I do not include them in Figure 7.13.

The right side of Figure 7.13 shows the relation between N_{pow} , N_{comt} , and N_H with the averaged 0.3 - 10 keV count rates of each TB, taken from the right panel of Figure 7.6. Both normalisations are correlated with the 0.3 - 10 keV count rates, shown in the top right and middle right panels in Figure 7.13, but an inverse correlation between N_H and the count rate in Obs 1 is observed (bottom right panel in Figure 7.13). This is anti-correlation between N_H and the continuum parameters is also seen in Figure 7.12. For Obs 2, the count rates are consistently low, which could be a result of a high N_H , and large f_{cov} , especially for the low X-ray energies; no significant change over the observation is seen.

Figure 7.10: Final best fit models fitted to the time-averaged spectra: Obs 1 grey crosses and blue model; Obs 2 black crosses and purple model. Also shown are the C-statistics and degrees of freedom. The best fit parameter values are displayed in Tables 7.4 and 7.5. The bottom panel shows the residuals between the data and model for Obs 1 (blue) and Obs 2 (purple).

Figure 7.11: Comparing the December 2019 SED from Mehdipour et al. (2016a) (red line) to the time-averaged SEDs from this work (blue for Obs 1 and purple for Obs 2). The shapes of all three SEDs are similar and the changes in normalisations are related to the continuum fluctuations modelled here.

Figure 7.12: Model parameter comparisons for each TB in Obs 1 (hollow circles) and Obs 2 (diamonds). The red horizontal dashed and solid lines represent the time-averaged parameter values for Obs 1 and Obs 2, respectively, and the shaded areas show the uncertainties. The TB colours are consistent with their respective spectra in Figure 7.7. The model parameter is shown on the y-axis of each panel.

Figure 7.13: *Left:* Correlations between model parameters. The normalisations of the power-law (N_{pow}) and Comptonisation component (N_{comt}) over the two observations (top); N_{pow} against the column density of the obscurer (N_H ; middle); and N_{comt} against N_H (bottom). *Right:* Correlations between N_{pow} , N_{comt} and N_H against the 0.3 - 10 keV count rate for top, middle and bottom panels, respectively.

7.6.3 Cause of the Observed Variability

From Figures 7.12 and 7.13, and the discussion in Section 7.6.1, there is a clear inverse correlation between the continuum (N_{pow} and N_{comt}) and the column density of the obscurer (N_H) in Obs 1. However, in the model here, ξ is fixed as I was unable to constrain it, and as a consequence N_H changes to account for the variable absorption. Therefore, I want to carry out some tests to see whether the observed changes could be caused by the continuum, ionisation parameter, the column density.

Figure 7.14: Ionisation parameter (red squares) and covering fraction (blue triangles) for each TB in Obs 1 during one of the tests to determine the cause of the observed variability (Section 7.6.3). The blue dashed and red dot-dashed lines are the time-averaged covering fraction and ionisation parameter values, respectively.

As the S/N of each TB was too low to fit ξ , I used the *lixi* parameter in PION, which is defined as L_{ion}/ξ . The *lixi* parameter is useful when ξ has been determined in another spectrum or model (in this case from Mao et al., Submitted) while the changes of the plasma caused by different ionising continua need to be determined. This assumes that $n_H r^2$ of the obscurer is constant (which is equal to *lixi* by definition), where n_H is the hydrogen number density and r is the distance from the SMBH. In order to use *lixi* only, in PION the *type* parameter is set to 1 (meaning ξ is not used⁴). Therefore, by fixing *lixi* to the value from the time-averaged model of Obs 1 in Mao et al. (Submitted), the ionisation parameter can be measured, using L_{ion} calculated from the SED components for each TB. In this test, N_H is fixed, while f_{cov} of the obscurer, and N_{pow} and N_{comt} are free to vary. From here, I plotted ξ (from L_{ion} and *lixi*) over each TB and found that it increased over time, consistent with changing as a result of the continuum variations. However, I also found that f_{cov} increased in the same way. This is displayed in Figure 7.14. A reason for the change in f_{cov} could be a result of an increase in the

⁴For ξ to be the main parameter, the *type* parameter is set to 0 (default) in PION, and *type* = 1 is for *lixi* only. See the SPEX manual for further details: <https://www.sron.nl/astrophysics-spex/manual>.

ionising luminosity, and therefore ξ , causing the gas to expand.

Following on from this result, I did another test. Here I freed and fitted ξ ($type = 0$ in PION) in the time-averaged spectrum of Obs 1. The l_{ixi} value was then calculated for Obs 1 ($type = 1$), which was then fixed in all the TBs. From there, in each TB I fitted f_{cov} and found that it again increased over time. Finally, I then fitted N_H for each TB and found that with the column density free, the model parameters would behave like in Figure 7.12: N_H would decrease (bottom-middle left panel), while f_{cov} became less variable (bottom-middle right panel).

From these tests, therefore, it seems that regardless of ξ there needs to be changes in N_H and f_{cov} of the obscurer in order to obtain a good fit. However, this is still not fully conclusive to explain the variability given that the continuum changes significantly during Obs 1. One final test I implemented was to determine what contributions the changes in both N_H and the continuum had on the overall variability. To do this, I firstly fixed the N_H values in all the TBs to the time-averaged value of $N_H = 3.74 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}^{-2}$ (see Table 7.4), and fitted the normalisations of POW and COMT. The results of this can be seen in the left side of Figure 7.15. I then fixed the continuum normalisations to their time-averaged values in each TB, $N_{pow} = 2.59 \times 10^{50} \text{ ph s}^{-1} \text{ keV}^{-1}$ and $N_{comt} = 2.10 \times 10^{53} \text{ ph s}^{-1} \text{ keV}^{-1}$, and fitted N_H and f_{cov} . The results can be seen in the right side of Figure 7.15. The remaining parameters, in both scenarios, were fixed at their best fit values from each TB (see Table 7.4).

From the left side of Figure 7.15, with N_H fixed, both N_{pow} and N_{comt} increase over the course of Obs 1. This strong variability suggests that the most of the variability is driven by continuum changes. However, from the right side of Figure 7.15, when the two continuum normalisations are fixed, both N_H and f_{cov} decrease, which could also suggest that the obscurer parameters drive the variability. However, given the error bars on f_{cov} (Figure 7.12 and Figure 7.15) it seems that the covering fraction is less dominant compared to the column density.

Figure 7.15: Further tests to determine the cause of the observed variability. *Left:* Fixing the column density to the time-averaged value in Obs 1, and fitting N_{pow} (red circles) and N_{comt} (blue triangles) in each TB. *Right:* Fixing N_{pow} and N_{comt} to their time-averaged values and fitting N_H (magenta diamonds) and f_{cov} (orange triangles). In both scenarios the changes in the parameters suggest that they could contribute to the observed variability.

So, what is the cause of the observed variability? There are two scenarios here: 1) the continuum varies and as a consequence, so does the obscurer; 2) the obscurer varies independently of the continuum changes. For scenario 1), the ionisation parameter ξ varies with the continuum, which is supported within the first test (Figure 7.14). However, I also find that N_H and f_{cov} (Figures 7.12 and 7.14) have to change as well in order to obtain a good fit, which means that not all of the obscurer variability is explained by the effect of ξ . In addition, for scenario 1, we see changes in both the continuum and obscurer, but N_H variations are independent on the continuum. Therefore, the obscurer cannot change to variations in the obscurer if ξ is fixed, meaning this scenario must be ruled out. However, from the left side of Figure 7.15, it is clear that the continuum itself can drive the variability we observe, regardless of if the obscurer changes with it, as seen through ξ . For scenario 2), the obscurer varies independently of the continuum, which can be seen in the right side of Figure 7.15, whereby N_H and f_{cov} vary independently of the continuum. However, what causes the changes in column density in the obscurer over the course of Obs 1?

One way in which the column density can change is by moving transversely out of our LOS to the X-ray source. If the obscurer was clumpy, by crossing

our LOS it would produce variations in N_H . The other two possible scenarios are that the obscurer expands, causing the column density to decrease, for an increase in covering fraction (but this requires a large expansion velocity), or alternatively, the material condenses to become visible dust (very unlikely as the ionising flux increases over the course of Obs 1). As the latter two explanations are less likely, or at least harder to prove, I determined whether the obscurer could cross our LOS, and thus cause changes in N_H .

The location of the obscurer in Obs 1 was estimated to be between 0.014 and 0.063 pc (Mao et al., Submitted). Using $v_{cross} = \sqrt{\frac{GM_{BH}}{r}}$, where G is the gravitational constant, $M_{BH} = 5.96 \times 10^6 M_\odot$ is the black hole mass, and r is the distance of the obscurer from the SMBH, the velocity of the obscurer, assuming it follows a Keplerian orbit (Mao et al., Submitted), comes out to be 640 or 1360 km s⁻¹, depending on which distance is used. For the largest velocity, the obscurer would travel a distance of 1.36×10^{11} m in the length of Obs 1 (~ 100 ks). Assuming that the radius of the X-ray corona is 15 R_g (Chainakun et al., 2019), then the diameter of the X-ray source would be 2.65×10^{11} m, which is larger than the crossing distance. Therefore, changes in N_H cannot be caused by the obscurer moving transversely out of our LOS towards the X-ray corona.

However, what about the changes seen between Obs 1 and Obs 2? The length of time between observations was 1810 ks (three weeks), such that the distance travelled by the obscurer, assuming $v_{cross} = 1360$ km s⁻¹, is 2.35×10^{12} m. This is larger than the size of the ionising source, suggesting that the increase in N_H between Obs 1 and Obs 2 could be a result of the obscurer moving transversely out of our LOS. This would explain the large drop in flux in the spectra and light curves (Figure 7.1) between Obs 2 and Obs 1.

Therefore, from these arguments and different tests, I conclude that the continuum (N_{pow} and N_{comt}) drives the observed variability. However, given the strong changes in N_H (Figure 7.12), I cannot fully rule out its contribution to the observed variability, even if it is not known why N_H varies with N_{pow}

and N_{comt} .

7.6.4 Future Exploration

In the model above (Section 7.5), I coupled the reflection parameters, N_{refl} and Γ_{refl} , to the 2016 values from Mehdipour et al. (2021) (Table 7.2). This was also done initially in Mao et al. (Submitted), as it was assumed that the neutral reflector was located far from the SMBH (several parsecs; J. Mao - private communication) and therefore there were no changes in the reflected continuum between 2016 and 2019. However, Gandhi et al. (2015) found that the narrow Fe K α emission is consistent with originating from within the dust sublimation radius, from the AGN in their sample, rather than from the torus. Furthermore, Markowitz et al. (2009) argued that the iron emission lines arose from the BLR in NGC 3227 specifically, measuring the distance to be $r_{BLR} = 7_{-5}^{+13}$ light days⁵. This distance is close enough such that any changes in the intrinsic continuum will be visible in the reflected continuum within the 3 years between 2016 and 2019.

From this argument, therefore, the model in Section 7.5 needed to be updated. In the above fit, the 2019 reflection component was coupled to the 2016 power-law continuum. However, the model from Mao et al. (Submitted) is now updated such that the N_{refl} and Γ_{refl} parameters are coupled to the values of the 2019 power-law values (this was done in the modelling by Mehdipour et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2022, in their respective epochs). After updating the initial parameter values of the model described in Section 7.5 (from Mao et al., Submitted), I fitted the time-averaged EPIC-PN spectrum from each observation. Comparing the two models, I found that the C-statistic is slightly larger in the updated model, but the obscurer parameters are consistent with each other in both epochs. The same results were found when comparing the models in Mao et al. (Submitted). Therefore, there is insignificant consequence on the obscurer parameters when coupling either the 2016 or 2019 power-law

⁵The black hole mass used for this distance is over twice as larger as the mass used in this Chapter (Bentz & Katz, 2015).

to the reflection component; there is a slight change in the model C-statistics, however. In conclusion, the results from this Chapter explain the observed variability and properties of the continuum and obscurer of NGC 3227 in 2019.

7.7 Summary and Conclusions

NGC 3227 has undergone many obscuration events (Lamer et al., 2003; Markowitz et al., 2014; Beuchert et al., 2015; Turner et al., 2018) lasting a variety of time scales. At the end of 2019, this AGN was observed to undergo obscuration again, detected by a *Swift* monitoring programme, and follow-up observations from XMM-Newton, NuSTAR and HST were obtained. Mehdipour et al. (2021) studied the unobscured and obscured SEDs from 2016 and 2019, respectively, which was used to probe the properties and location of the obscuring material in the sequential papers in the series. Wang et al. (2022) analysed the WAs and past occultation periods using the broadband continuum model, and the 2019 observations were studied in great detail in Mao et al. (Submitted).

In this Chapter, using the initial model from Mao et al. (Submitted), I investigated the cause of the variability during the two 2019 observations. In Obs 1, I found an anti-correlation between N_H and the continuum normalisations, N_{pow} and N_{comt} . Between Obs 1 and Obs 2, time-averaged results for f_{cov} and N_H increased from 0.57 to 0.63, and from $3.74 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}^{-2}$ to $6.52 \times 10^{26} \text{ m}^{-2}$, respectively. Comparatively, N_{pow} and N_{comp} decreased from 2.59 to $0.67 \times 10^{50} \text{ ph s}^{-1} \text{ keV}^{-1}$, and 2.10 to $0.54 \times 10^{53} \text{ ph s}^{-1} \text{ keV}^{-1}$, respectively, for the time-averaged results.

From multiple tests in Section 7.6.3, I argued that the continuum is the most likely driver for the observed variability Obs 1. However, a contribution from the column density of the obscurer cannot be ruled out. For Obs 2, the count rate was significantly lower compared to Obs 1, and the lack of variability was due to the combination of a high column density and covering fraction in the obscurer. There is no evidence for the obscurer to transversely

cross our LOS to the X-ray source during Obs 1, and hence I cannot explain why N_H varies with N_{pow} and N_{comt} . However, the difference in N_H between observations could be explained by the obscurer travelling transversely across our LOS in the time taken between Obs 1 and Obs 2, as the distance travelled is larger than the size of the X-ray source.

In conclusion, I attribute the observed variability in NGC 3227 during Obs 1 to be driven by the continuum, as seen via the normalisations of POW and COMT. However, some contribution from the column density of the obscurer cannot be ruled out.

Table 7.4: Best fit parameter results for the 0.35 - 10 keV EPIC-PN time-averaged ('All') and TB spectra of Obs 1.

Obs 1 (d.o.f = 116)								
Time Bin	N_{pow} (1)	Γ	N_{comt} (2)	s	σ (3)	N_H (4)	f_{cov}	C-stat
All	2.59 ± 0.05	1.65 ± 0.01	2.10 ± 0.04	0.60 ± 0.04	2910^{+700}_{-880}	3.74 ± 0.06	0.57 ± 0.01	224
1	2.27 ± 0.17	1.75 ± 0.04	1.18 ± 0.10	0.59 ± 0.10	< 5240	5.68 ± 0.36	0.57 ± 0.03	155
2	2.28 ± 0.20	1.78 ± 0.05	1.02 ± 0.11	1.09 ± 0.14	9680^{+2610}_{-2030}	4.64 ± 0.30	0.56 ± 0.04	162
3	1.94 ± 0.15	1.66 ± 0.05	1.22 ± 0.09	0.71 ± 0.14	7770^{+4600}_{-2300}	5.44 ± 0.39	0.57 ± 0.03	167
4	2.14 ± 0.15	1.62 ± 0.04	1.57 ± 0.10	0.64 ± 0.10	< 4040	4.67 ± 0.25	0.56 ± 0.03	124
5	2.11 ± 0.16	1.61 ± 0.05	1.56 ± 0.10	0.50 ± 0.12	< 8370	4.47 ± 0.25	0.62 ± 0.03	161
6	2.58 ± 0.17	1.65 ± 0.04	1.99 ± 0.11	0.66 ± 0.12	4480^{+2780}_{-2410}	3.38 ± 0.19	0.56 ± 0.03	151
7	3.39 ± 0.18	1.69 ± 0.03	2.97 ± 0.14	0.63 ± 0.11	< 3720	2.87 ± 0.15	0.59 ± 0.02	103
8	3.76 ± 0.19	1.73 ± 0.03	3.47 ± 0.16	0.72 ± 0.10	< 2140	2.70 ± 0.14	0.63 ± 0.02	113
9	3.22 ± 0.17	1.66 ± 0.04	3.56 ± 0.17	0.56 ± 0.13	5160^{+3270}_{-2330}	2.42 ± 0.14	0.61 ± 0.02	141
10	3.44 ± 0.18	1.69 ± 0.03	3.35 ± 0.15	0.45 ± 0.12	< 7370	2.58 ± 0.14	0.61 ± 0.02	140

(1) 10^{50} ph s $^{-1}$ keV $^{-1}$ at 1 keV; (2) 10^{53} ph s $^{-1}$ keV $^{-1}$ at 1 keV; (3) km s $^{-1}$; (4) 10^{26} m $^{-2}$.

Table 7.5: Best fit parameter results for the 0.35 - 10 keV EPIC-PN time-averaged ('All') and TB spectra of Obs 2.

Obs 2 (d.o.f = 106)									
Time Bin	N_{pow} (1)	Γ	N_{comt} (2)	s	σ (3)	N_H (4)	f_{cov}	C-stat	
All	6.67 ± 0.45	1.73 ± 0.04	5.36 ± 0.26	0.37 ± 0.03	< 2150	6.52 ± 0.30	0.63 ± 0.02	103	
1	5.30 ± 1.27	1.65 ± 0.14	4.79 ± 0.73	0.40 ± 0.08	< 3880	6.10 ± 1.30	0.54 ± 0.11	94	
2	6.63 ± 1.36	1.65 ± 0.12	4.08 ± 0.72	0.31 ± 0.07	< 6300	6.58 ± 0.95	0.58 ± 0.08	118	
3	7.39 ± 1.61	1.84 ± 0.05	5.47 ± 0.98	0.43 ± 0.08	< 4500	6.00 ± 0.86	0.66 ± 0.07	122	
4	8.50 ± 1.78	1.86 ± 0.13	4.79 ± 1.12	0.45 ± 0.07	< 2100	6.07 ± 0.78	0.67 ± 0.07	102	
5	6.42 ± 1.34	1.65 ± 0.13	5.67 ± 0.78	0.37 ± 0.09	< 7370	6.30 ± 0.10	0.58 ± 0.08	103	
6	5.20 ± 1.23	1.62 ± 0.12	7.04 ± 0.96	0.29 ± 0.06	< 1710	6.35 ± 0.89	0.62 ± 0.08	103	
7	7.92 ± 1.66	1.76 ± 0.12	5.34 ± 0.95	0.37 ± 0.07	< 3000	7.10 ± 0.88	0.67 ± 0.07	100	
8	5.04 ± 1.15	1.60 ± 0.13	4.87 ± 0.72	0.33 ± 0.09	4260^{+3280}_{-3440}	7.43 ± 1.57	0.56 ± 0.09	115	
9	10.34 ± 2.18	1.97 ± 0.13	5.14 ± 1.72	0.34 ± 0.08	< 6400	7.89 ± 0.79	0.78 ± 0.05	106	
10	6.37 ± 1.58	1.86 ± 0.16	5.63 ± 0.97	0.54 ± 0.08	< 4490	6.07 ± 0.98	0.68 ± 0.08	92	

(1) 10^{49} ph s $^{-1}$ keV $^{-1}$ at 1 keV; (2) 10^{52} ph s $^{-1}$ keV $^{-1}$ at 1 keV; (3) km s $^{-1}$; (4) 10^{26} m $^{-2}$.

Chapter 8

Conclusions

In this Thesis I studied the ionised outflowing winds of four individual AGN with high resolution X-ray spectroscopy and photoionisation modelling. In each Chapter, I concluded with the main results of each AGN study on its own. Here I compare and discuss the properties of many AGN together, before looking ahead to the future.

8.1 Unification of the WA and ELR

The overall aim of this Thesis is to establish whether the plasma regions seen in different types of AGN are the same. After studying the physical properties of the winds in the individual AGN, I compare the photoionisation properties and locations to obtain some insight into the whether the emitting and absorbing plasma regions are part of the same outflowing wind.

8.1.1 Comparing the Outflowing Winds in this Thesis

The first AGN that I studied in this Thesis was the type 1 Seyfert, NGC 7469 (Chapter 4). Three warm absorber (WA) components, with three kinematic phases ($v_{out} = -630, -930$ and -1960 km s⁻¹) and a total equivalent column density of $N_H = 64 \times 10^{25}$ m⁻², were required to explain the absorption features in the RGS spectrum. These WA components had ionisation parameters of $\log \xi = 2.3, 3.0$ and 1.6 , respectively. I also modelled the emission features and found two narrow emission line region (NELR) components with ionisation parameters of $\log \xi = 0.35$ and 1.6 for EM1 and EM2, respectively. Evidence for

a broad emission component (EM3; $\log \xi = 0.18$), with an outflow velocity of $v_{out} = -4460_{-110}^{+200}$ km s⁻¹, consistent with the optical BLR ($v_{BLR} = -4521$ km s⁻¹; Suganuma et al., 2006), was also found. However, EM3 was an unreliable identification with an apparent intercombination line; the outflow velocity suggests that it was a highly blueshifted O VII forbidden line. In Chapter 4, this uncertainty was attributed to the fact that PION models photoionised plasma as a thin shell that is optically thin; this is true for the NLR, whereas the BLR is dense and optically thick. Therefore, I shall not compare EM3 with the other components in the rest of this Chapter.

NGC 1068 was the second AGN I investigated (Chapter 5). In this archetypal Seyfert type 2 galaxy, I found from the RGS spectrum that the emission line region (ELR) components, had ionisation parameters of $\log \xi = 0.63$ and 1.84 in the 2000 epoch, and $\log \xi = 0.67$ and 1.91 in 2014. This shows a similar trend of low and high ionisation components present in the soft X-ray gas, like with EM1 and EM2, and the WA components in NGC 7469; this could be expected within a distribution of gas around the AGN. The outflow velocities for these two components fitted to the RGS data were -110 and -260 km s⁻¹, and -230 and -300 km s⁻¹, for the 2000 and 2014 epochs, respectively. These are lower compared to the kinematics of the WA and ELR components in NGC 7469. A further two ELR components were fitted to the EPIC-PN data in NGC 1068, with ionisation parameters $\log \xi = 3$ and 4 in both epochs; the outflow velocities were -200 and -610 km s⁻¹ (2000), and -530 and -230 km s⁻¹ (2014), respectively.

The third AGN I studied in this Thesis was the Seyfert type 2 galaxy NGC 5643 (Chapter 6). The ionisation state of the emission line component in NGC 5643 ($\log \xi = 1.3$) is similar to WA component 3 and EM2 in NGC 7469, and in between the values of the two low- ξ components in NGC 1068. However, the outflow velocities were not reported in Chapter 6 as the total observation length of the RGS spectrum was too low, causing a poor signal-to-noise ratio. This meant that accurate measurements of the line shifts could

Figure 8.1: Comparing the parameters of the WA (solid shapes) and ELR (empty shapes) in NGC 7469 (purple; values taken from Chapter 4, Behar et al. 2017, Mehdipour et al. 2018, and Blustin et al. 2007) and NGC 1068 (magenta; from Chapter 5). *Top:* Column density against the ionisation parameter; *Bottom:* Turbulent velocity (v_{turb}) against outflow velocity (v_{out}).

not be made. With a new and longer observation, which I have been granted with XMM-Newton (see Appendix D for the proposal), the velocity can be measured and a study of the kinematics can be made. As a result of this, I do not compare NGC 5643 to the other AGN in this Chapter.

The PION model parameter ranges for the WA and ELR components in NGC 7469 and NGC 1068 (Chapters 4 and 5) are displayed in Table 8.1 (along with three other AGN - see Section 8.1.2). Also included in Table 8.1 are the number of components found from each analysis (see the reference column). From here, I have plotted and compared the parameters together in Figure 8.1. For NGC 7469 (purple data points), the parameter values were taken from Chapter 4, Behar et al. (2017) and Mehdipour et al. (2018), as well as from Blustin et al. (2007) for a further comparison, while the parameters for NGC 1068 (magenta data points) were from Chapter 5. The top panel of Figure 8.1 displays the column density (N_H) against ionisation parameter ($\log \xi$), and the bottom panel shows the turbulent velocity (v_{turb}) against the outflow velocity (v_{out}). The solid data points are for the WA components and the empty data points show the results for the ELR components. The legends in each panel show the data point shapes and respective references, also shown in Table 8.1.

For both AGN, the ionisation parameters of the WA and ELR are within the same range, $\log \xi = 0$ to 4 (top panel of Figure 8.1). On the other hand, there is a large difference between column densities seen in the WA compared to the ELR. This is because for the WA, N_H refers to the total column density in our line of sight (LOS). However, for the ELR, line emission can come from any region such that in PION N_H quantifies the total amount of gas in all regions that cause line emission. Overall, the amount of emitting cloud is larger compared to the absorbing plasma as it is not confined to our LOS, so the column densities are larger in the ELR compared to the WA. However, for the WAs, the column density increases for an increase in the ionisation parameter. This is an observation bias whereby more column is needed to

Figure 8.2: Direction of the outflowing wind kinematics based on the line of sight (LOS). In both scenarios, the wind is travelling radially away from the central SMBH, in the form of an ionisation cone. *Left:* LOS is side on, i.e. viewing a type 2 AGN. The direction of the outflowing wind motion is mostly perpendicular to our LOS (red and blue arrows; both labelled v_{\perp}). So we measure a component of the true outflow velocity, parallel to our LOS, depicted by the blue \ominus or red \oplus , depending if we are measuring the wind coming towards or away from us, respectively (both labelled v_{\parallel}). However, as v_{\perp} is mostly perpendicular to our LOS, a range of radially outflowing velocities are seen, contributing to the observed broadening; hence v_{turb} is large in NGC 1068. *Right:* LOS is front on, i.e. viewing a type 1 AGN. The outflowing wind is moving parallel to our LOS towards the observer with a velocity depicted by the blue \ominus (v_{\parallel}), while the radial velocities perpendicular to the LOS (blue arrows; v_{\perp}) are smaller, and therefore the overall turbulence is not as large compared to the scenario on the left. *Both:* The purple arrows (v_t) show the natural motion of the ions and electrons within the plasma, giving rise to the bulk of the observed turbulence.

observe the highly ionised lines; at large ξ , the N_H of the WA tends towards the values of the ELRs for NGC 7469 and NGC 1068.

From the results in the top panel of Figure 8.1, it appears that our LOS to the nucleus passes through less material in the WA compared to the ELR. Therefore, what fraction of these regions cover the central engine? In Chapter 4, the covering fractions (f_{cov}) of the WA components were fixed at 100%, i.e. they cover the total X-ray source along our LOS. Comparatively, the covering fractions (C_{cov}) of the ELR components were fitted in both NGC 7469 and NGC 1068. In NGC 7469, $C_{cov} < 0.001$, meaning the ELR components cover a very small fraction of our LOS, possibly confined to the edge of the ionisation cone; the WA would be in the middle. This would however suggest that these two regions are separate. For NGC 1068, $C_{cov} = 0.01 - 0.30$, which implies that the ELR components, viewed from side on, are more likely to be seen as the WA if seen face on, as they intercept a large fraction of the ionising source. Given this comparison between the covering fractions of the ELRs in these two AGN, it appears that they cover a relatively small fraction of the central source, but have higher column densities, compared to the low- N_H WA components in our LOS. On the other hand, a degeneracy has been found between N_H and C_{cov} in PION (Di Gesu et al., 2017), in addition to v_{turb} (Chapter 5). Both C_{cov} and N_H act as normalisation parameters, scaling the spectral features up or down, except that N_H is calculated from line ratios while C_{cov} is not. SPEX finds the best combination of the two parameters to fit the spectrum. Furthermore, the slab geometry in PION is too simple, especially when we view the ionisation cone from side on in type 2 AGN (e.g. NGC 1068; Chapter 5). This means that an accurate geometry for the ELR and WA components cannot currently be obtained from the modelling in this Thesis, especially when the outflowing wind is seen side on.

Furthermore, in NGC 7469 (Section 4.3.5.2; Figures 4.13 and 4.14) there was no evidence that the WA and ELR components were located together in the ionisation cone. Some similarities in the distances were seen, but these

depended on the method and data analysed. However, EM2 (Chapter 4) and component F (Mehdipour et al., 2018) both had outflow velocities that were zero. This suggests that there is no radial velocity in our LOS, possibly placing it at the edge of the ionisation cone. In addition to the C_{cov} and N_H results above, this suggests that the WA is in the centre of the ionisation cone, while the ELR is located at the edges. However, this is likely to be an observation bias whereby the plasma directly over the X-ray source in our LOS will always produce absorption lines, whereas if we were to observe the ionisation cone from a different angle, we would not observe the same result. Therefore, the ELR and WA are not from different parts in the cone, but rather the observed features are dependent on our LOS view, however we look at the AGN. The major difference is when we observe the cone directly from side on, like in NGC 1068, such that we only observe emission lines.

The bottom panel of Figure 8.1 shows that the WA components in NGC 7469 have larger outflow velocities, spanning a wide range in values, compared to the ELR in both NGC 7469 and NGC 1068. In NGC 1068, although the ELR components have similar velocities to the ELR in NGC 7469, the turbulent velocities are $v_{turb} > 400 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, larger than the WA values and most of the ELR components in NGC 7469 ($v_{turb} < 100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$).

I interpret the difference in v_{out} and v_{turb} in the following way (see Figure 8.2). In both AGN, the wind is travelling radially away from the central SMBH, in the form of a cone (e.g. Figure 1.6). With this, therefore, a range in velocities will be measured based on the different radial velocities. As we see NGC 1068 from side on, the direction of the outflowing wind motion is mostly perpendicular to our LOS (red and blue arrows in the left side of Figure 8.2), so the outflow velocity I measured was only a component of the true outflow velocity: the part of the cone that radially travels towards us in our LOS (left side of Figure 8.2). This is shown as the blue \odot for the component travelling towards us, or the red \oplus for component travelling away. In comparison, for NGC 7469, the outflowing wind is travelling parallel to our line of sight, so

I measured the radial velocities that are directly coming towards us (blue \odot in the right side of Figure 8.2). Hence, the outflow velocity values are larger for the WA in NGC 7469 compared to the ELR in NGC 1068. Similarly, the large difference in t_{turb} between NGC 1068 and NGC 7469 in Figure 8.1 is based on our LOS view of the plasma wind. From side on, as in NGC 1068, a range of outflow velocities travelling radially along different directions, and perpendicular to our LOS (blue and red arrows), contribute to the observed broadening. In other words, if there are multiple clouds with a range of radial velocities, then the combined velocities of each component will contribute to the line broadening. As a comparison, the radial velocities perpendicular to our LOS in a type 1 AGN (blue arrows in right side of Figure 8.2) are smaller and therefore the line broadening is weaker for NGC 7469; the radial outflow velocity parallel to our LOS is larger than the velocities in the perpendicular direction. In addition, in both the WA and ELR for NGC 7469 and NGC 1068, there is a natural motion of the ions and electrons in all directions within the plasma clouds (see the purple arrows in Figure 8.2); this is expected to be the same in both cases causing a natural broadening to the observed lines. However, in NGC 1068, due to the large range in radial velocities, this broadening is larger than the natural motion, so therefore dominates the line widths.

8.1.2 Comparison with other AGN

In addition to the plasma components of the AGN studied in this Thesis, here I also compare the properties of the WA and ELR from three other type 1 AGN: NGC 5548, NGC 3783 and NGC 3227¹. Their parameter ranges are displayed in Table 8.1, in addition to NGC 7469 and NGC 1068, along with the number of components and the references from the literature where the values were obtained. This gives a further comparison for the plasma properties and locations of the WAs and ELR, and helps investigate whether they are

¹I studied the variability in the EPIC-PN spectra of NGC 3227 (Chapter 7), whereas my colleagues analysed the WA (Wang et al., 2022) and ELR (Mao et al., Submitted).

Table 8.1: Range of parameter values for all the WA (top) and ELR (bottom) components in each AGN discussed in this Chapter.

AGN	$\log \xi$ (10^{-9} W m)	N_H (10^{25} m $^{-2}$)	v_{turb} (km s $^{-1}$)	v_{out} (km s $^{-1}$)	No. of Comps.	Ref.
Warm Absorbers						
NGC 7469	1.6 - 3.0	1.0 - 5.2	11 - 35	(-630) - (-1960)	3	(1)
	1.9 - 3.3	0.7 - 2.3	42	(-370) - (-1830)	4	(2)
	(-0.6) - 2.7	0.01 - 2.2	35 - 70	(-650) - (-2050)	6	(3)
	0.8 - 3.6	0.03 - 2.9	—	(-580) - (-2300)	3	(4)
NGC 3783	(-0.7) - 3.0	0.1 - 12	50 - 800	(-460) - (-1600)	9	(5)
	0.3 - 2.4	0.5 - 28	300	-800	2	(6)
NGC 5548	0.3 - 2.7	0.2 - 6	20 - 210	(-250) - (-1150)	6	(7)
NGC 3227	(-1.1) - 3.3	1 - 23	20 - 260	(-110) - (-1270)	4	(8)
Emission Line Regions						
NGC 7469	0.2 - 1.6	42 - 780	50	(-660) - 0	2	(1)
	0.9 - 2.2	26 - 120	35 - 590	(-220) - 0	2	(2)
NGC 3783	1.0 - 2.6	3 - 60	140 - 600	—	3	(5)
NGC 5548	0.1 - 1.3	10	250 - 520	(-50) - (-420)	2 - 3	(9)
	1.45	79	180	—	1	(10)
NGC 3227	0.8 - 2.5	0.3 - 0.8	840 - 1790	—	1 - 3	(11)
NGC 1068	0.6 - 4.0	18 - 51	410 - 2910	(-110) - (-610)	4	(12)

References: (1) Chapter 4; (2) [Mehdipour et al. \(2018\)](#); (3) [Behar et al. \(2017\)](#); (4) [Blustin et al. \(2007\)](#); (5) [Mao et al. \(2019\)](#); (6) [Blustin et al. \(2002\)](#); (7) [Kaastra et al. \(2014\)](#); (8) [Wang et al. \(2022\)](#); (9) [Mao et al. \(2018\)](#); (10) [Whewell et al. \(2015\)](#); (11) [Mao et al. \(Submitted\)](#); (12) Chapter 5

part of the same plasma clouds. These three AGN were chosen for further comparison because they had all been studied with PION. The ELR components were analysed during obscuration events in each AGN, which meant that they could be studied in greater detail than before. The WA parameters used here are from the epochs when these AGN were not obscured. As both wind types were studied with PION, direct comparisons with the parameters can be made.

Figure 8.3 displays the parameter values for NGC 5548 (top, blue), NGC 3783, (middle, red), and NGC 3227 (bottom, green). The left panels compare the column density against the ionisation parameter, and the right panels show

the turbulent velocity against the outflow velocity. For all three of these AGN, there is a large range in the ionisation parameter for the WA components, that overlap with the ELR components, similar to NGC 7469 and NGC 1068 (Figure 8.1). Comparatively, the column densities of the ELR components in NGC 5548 and NGC 3783 are larger compared to the WA components (left side of Figure 8.3). The WA components also show the observation bias where more column is needed to see the high- ξ lines. Interestingly for NGC 3227 (bottom left of Figure 8.3), the column density of the WA components are equal to or larger than the N_H values for the ELRs. This is likely to be a result of the model fitting only a few emission features in the RGS spectrum of NGC 3227 during an obscuration event (Chapter 7; Mao et al., Submitted). The spectrum also had a low signal-to-noise ratio meaning an exact representation of the ELR was hard to model.

Similarly to NGC 7469, the WA components in these three AGN (Figure 8.3) have a wide range of outflow velocities (right side of Figure 8.1). For NGC 5548, some of these velocities coincide with the values of the ELR. However, for NGC 3783 and NGC 3227, the outflow velocities of the ELR components were not measured; instead I plot them above the blue arrows in Figure 8.3 so that their turbulent velocities can be compared. Interestingly, all the ELR components in these three AGN have a wide range in v_{turb} , significantly larger than the WA values; however, they are all smaller than the turbulent velocities from NGC 1068 (Figure 8.1).

Figures 8.4a and 8.4b display the WA (solid data points; top panels) and ELR (empty data points; bottom panels) parameter values for the five AGN in Table 8.1. Figure 8.4a compares the column densities and the ionisation parameters of each component, while Figure 8.4b compares the turbulent and outflow velocities. I have also included parameter values of the WA components found in the AGN studied by Blustin et al. (2005), shown as the black upside-down triangles in the top panels of both Figure 8.4a and Figure 8.4b. The colours represent each AGN discussed in this Chapter, and the data point

Figure 8.3: Parameter values from NGC 5548 (top panels; blue), NGC 3783 (middle panels; red), and NGC 3227 (bottom panels; green). *Left:* column density against ionisation parameter; *Right:* turbulent velocity against outflow velocity. In all panels, the WA components are the solid data points and the ELR components are the empty data points.

shapes correspond to the references in Table 8.1; both are shown in the legends of each panel.

In the top panel of Figure 8.4a, the WAs show an increasing trend for both the column density and ionisation parameter, caused by the observation bias, spanning a wide range of ξ . However, the ELR components (bottom panel) show a fairly flat relation between the two parameters - i.e. there is no correlation between N_H and ξ , even for the same range of ξ . In the top panel of Figure 8.4b, the WA components span a wide range in outflow velocity compared to the ELR components (bottom panel), which has already been

Figure 8.4a: Scatter plots of the column density (N_H) and ionisation parameter (ξ) values for the WA (solid data points; top) and ELR (empty data points; bottom) components. Also included are the WA parameter values from Blustin et al. (2005) (black upside-down triangles in the top panel).

discussed. The turbulent velocities from Blustin et al. (2005) were all fixed at 100 km s^{-1} and hence the line of values (top panel of Figure 8.4b). The WA turbulent velocities in the type 1 AGN are all fairly similar $v_{turb} < 500 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, with a few exceptions, while the ELR span a range of values. There is a small overlap ($v_{turb} \sim 500 - 1000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) where some of the ELR components in the four type 1 AGN have similar velocity broadening values as NGC 1068 ($v_{turb} > 500 \text{ km s}^{-1}$).

Figure 8.4b: Scatter plots of the turbulent and outflow velocity parameters of the WA (solid data points; top) and ELR (empty data points; bottom) components for all the AGN discussed in this Chapter (Table 8.1). Also included are the WA parameter values from Blustin et al. (2005) (black upside-down triangles in the top panel). The light blue arrow in the bottom panel shows the components for which the outflow velocities were not measured - NGC 3227 (green) and NGC 3783 (red).

Figure 8.5 shows all components together, combining the panels from Figures 8.4a and 8.4b. As with all the other Figures, the solid data points are for the WA and the empty data points are for the ELR. I have also added the results from Blustin et al. (2005) for further comparisons. The top panel of Figure 8.5 combines both panels from Figure 8.4a, comparing the column density and ionisation parameter of all components. Although the range in ionisation parameter is large for both WA and ELR components in all the AGN, the N_H values of the ELR components are overall larger than those seen in the WAs (top panel of Figure 8.5). However, in some cases, like the WA components in NGC 3783 (red) and some of the WA components from Blustin et al. (2005), the column densities are similar compared to the ELR, even for relatively low ionisation parameter values, e.g. $\log \xi = 1 - 3$. This shows that in some cases, both the column densities and ionisation parameters between the WA and ELR are similar.

The bottom panel of Figure 8.5 compares the turbulent and outflow velocities for all WA and ELR components in these five AGN, combining the two panels from Figure 8.4b. Overall, the WA components in each AGN have a large range in outflow velocities, extending down to -2500 km s^{-1} , but the turbulent velocities do not go above a few hundred km s^{-1} , with a few exceptions (this is shown more clearly in the top panel of Figure 8.4b). As discussed for the bottom panel of Figure 8.4b, there is some overlap in terms of outflow and turbulent velocities in the ELRs (as well as with the WA components) of these five AGN. The ELR components in NGC 3783, NGC 5548, and NGC 3227 have fairly large broadening velocities ($v_{turb} > 200 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) compared to the WA components, some of which are similar to those found in NGC 1068. Interestingly, there appears to be a trend of an increase in v_{turb} for a decrease in v_{out} , with most of the WA components falling below the orange dashed line in Figure 8.5.

Figure 8.5: Combining panels from Figures 8.4a and 8.4b. Presented here are the WA (solid shapes) and ELR (empty shapes) components in their respective AGN (colours are shown in the legends). Also included are the parameter values for the WAs from Blustin et al. (2005) (black upside-down triangles). *Top:* Column density against ionisation parameter; *Bottom:* Turbulent velocity against outflow velocity. The outflow velocities of the data points above the light blue arrow were not obtained in NGC 3227 (green) and NGC 3783 (red), so are grouped together here to compare the turbulent velocities. The dashed orange line illustrates a possible trend between v_{turb} and v_{out} , with most of the WA components falling below it.

8.1.3 Distances

The distances (R) for the WA and ELR components in the five AGN were obtained through three different methods using the parameters from Table 8.1. The three methods are: volume filling factor (Eq. 8.1); outflow velocity (Eq. 8.2); and recombination timescale (Eq. 8.3). The three equations used in each method are:

$$R = \frac{L_{ion} f_v}{\xi N_H}; \quad (8.1)$$

where f_v is the volume filling factor, L_{ion} is the ionising luminosity, N_H is the column density, and ξ is the ionisation parameter;

$$R = \frac{2GM_{BH}}{v_{out}^2}, \quad (8.2)$$

where M_{BH} is the SMBH mass and G is the gravitational constant; and

$$t_{rec} n_H = n_H^* \tau, \quad (8.3)$$

where t_{rec} is recombination time, n_H is the hydrogen number density in the plasma, τ is the time between observation changes, and n_H^* is the density of the plasma needed for the changes to happen in time τ . Therefore, by using the ionisation parameter equation ($\xi = L_{ion}/nr^2$), the upper limit of the distance can be found (n_H^* here is the lower density limit). See Section 1.4.1.2 for the derivations of Eqs. 8.1 and 8.2, and Section 1.4.1.1 for details on Eq. 8.3. From these relations, one would expect larger distances for more luminous AGN (Eqs. 8.1 and 8.3), or with more massive black hole masses (Eq. 8.2). Therefore, the distances measured depend on the intrinsic properties of the AGN, too.

For NGC 7469 (Chapter 4) the WA distances were determined using Eqs. 8.1 and 8.2 (see Section 4.3.4), while I used Eq. 8.1 for the ELR, assuming $f_v = 0.1$. For NGC 1068 (Chapter 5) Eqs. 8.1 and 8.2 were both used to measure the distances of the ELR components (see Sections 5.6.1.3 and 5.6.1.4). I

calculated the distances of the ELR within NGC 5548 (Mao et al., 2018), NGC 3783 (Mao et al., 2019) and NGC 3227 (Mao et al., Submitted), which were all analysed with PION, using Eqs. 8.1 and 8.2. For the narrow emission components $f_v = 0.1$, and for the broad components $f_v = 0.001$ (similar to Chapter 4); L_{ion} was taken from the SED models of each AGN. The distances of the WA components were from the literature or estimated using Eq 8.2. The distances using Eq. 8.3 were taken from Mehdipour et al. (2018) for NGC 7469, Ebrero et al. (2016) for NGC 5548, and Wang et al. (2022) for NGC 3227. This method is more physically motivated compared to using an arbitrary value for f_v to obtain a distance, but relies on there being observed changes in the SED and plasma regions, which is not always seen.

The distances of the ELRs and WA components in each AGN are shown in Figure 8.6. I have also included the distances for the WA components found in the AGN studied by Blustin et al. (2005), who obtained the values using Eqs. 8.1 and 8.2. The top left panel of Figure 8.6 displays the distances from the recombination timescale method (Eq. 8.3). For NGC 7469 (purple), NGC 5548 (blue) and NGC 3227 (green) the distances decrease for an increase in ionisation parameter. This is because, for a constant ionising luminosity (L_{ion} will be the same for each WA component in the AGN), $R \propto \xi^{-1/2}$, and n_H is the lower density limit, so R will decrease for an increase in ξ .

In the top right panel of Figure 8.6, the distances obtained from the volume filling factor method (Eq. 8.1) are shown. Here, there is a similar trend to the top left panel, whereby the distance decreases for an increase in ξ ($R \propto \xi^{-1}$; Eq. 8.1). This plot shows that for a given range in ionisation parameter, both the WA and ELR have a similar range in distance from the black hole. Although this distance range is fairly large, there is no clear difference in the locations between the WA and ELR.

The bottom panels of Figure 8.6 show the distances when the outflow velocity method is used (Eq. 8.2). Unlike the panels above, the bottom left panel of distance against ionisation parameter does not show any trends. However,

if I plot the distance as a function of outflow velocity, then it is clear that the smaller the outflow velocity, the further away the component is from the SMBH ($R \propto v^{-2}$). The WA components show a larger range in outflow velocity, but focusing on the range $v_{out} > -750 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, i.e. where the outflow velocities of the ELR and WA are similar, it is clear that the range in distances are similar between the two wind types.

From Figure 8.6, the three distance methods (Eqs. 8.1 - 8.3) show that there is a wide range of locations for the plasma components in all AGN. This means that the distances of the NELR seen in NGC 1068 span a similar range to those of the WA and ELR plasma regions in the four type 1 AGN. This suggests that these wind components could be located at similar distances from the SMBH. However, I am unable to constrain the locations of the plasma regions well from these methods, such that the evidence the WA and ELR are part of the same regions in the outflow wind, based on the distances, is inconclusive.

8.1.4 Summary

The ionisation cone model (e.g. Kinkhabwala et al., 2002), is used to explain the observed spectral differences between type 1 and type 2 AGN. The outflowing wind that absorbs the X-ray radiation, seen in type 1 AGN, scatters and re-emits the X-rays observed in type 2 AGN (see Figure 1.6). Kinkhabwala et al. (2002) argued that because the ionic column densities of the ELR in NGC 1068 were similar to the values from WAs in type 1 AGN, then the plasma regions could be the same in both AGN types. In this Section, I compared the properties of five AGN, allowing for the ionisation cone model to be tested further.

For all five of these AGN discussed in this Chapter, the ELR components have been found to have larger column densities compared to the WA components. This is because the line emitting regions are not just confined to our LOS, like the WA. However, this does not tell us what fraction of the central region is covered by the ELR components to try and obtain a possible geome-

Figure 8.6: Distances of the WA (solid data points) and ELR (empty data points) components for all AGN discussed in this Chapter, separated by method. *Top left:* Distances obtained from the recombination timescale method (Eq. 8.3). Up-facing triangles are the upper limits and down-facing triangles are the lower limits; solid lines between upper and lower limits are for the same WA component. *Top Right:* Distances obtained from the volume filling factor method (f_v ; Eq. 8.1). Black diamonds are the values obtained from the AGN survey in Blustin et al. (2005). *Bottom Left:* Distances obtained by assuming the outflow velocity is equal to the escape velocity (Eq. 8.2). Black diamonds are the values obtained from the AGN survey in Blustin et al. (2005). *Bottom Right:* Same as bottom left but the distances are a function of outflow velocity - now a correlation can be seen, like in the top two panels.

try. For NGC 7469, C_{cov} was found to be < 0.001 , while for NGC 1068 it was < 0.30 . This suggests that in NGC 7469, the ELR covers a very small region of the X-ray source in our LOS, possibly inferring that it is located at the edge of the ionisation cone. The ELR in NGC 1068, on the other hand, intercepts a larger area of the ionising source in our LOS, suggesting that the ELR plasmas seen from side on could be the same as the WA in type 1 AGN. For NGC 5548, $C_{cov} \sim 0.006 - 0.02$ (Mao et al., 2018) and for NGC 3783, $C_{cov} \sim 0.003 - 0.07$ (Mao et al., 2018); the covering fraction for NGC 3227 was fixed at 0.1. These

results follow on from NGC 7469, whereby the ELRs in type 1 AGN cover a small fraction of the ionising source.

Furthermore, the kinematics of both the WA and ELR could give insight into the geometry of the ionisation cone, in addition to N_H and C_{cov} . From the bottom panel of Figure 8.5, there is a trend of increasing v_{turb} for a decrease in v_{out} , depicted by the dashed orange line. The ELRs in the type 1 AGN show a low outflow velocity, but large turbulent velocities, similar to the ELR in NGC 1068. This suggests that the ELRs are travelling radially away from the black hole at angles greater than the outflow direction for the WA components; hence we measure smaller outflow velocities for the ELRs in type 1 AGN. As a result, the turbulent velocity of the ELR components are larger compared to the WA because a range of radial velocities are seen, interpreted as v_{turb} (Figure 8.2); they are not directly travelling in our LOS (v_{out}). However, a problem here is that we do not know the outflow velocities of the ELRs in NGC 3227 and NGC 3783.

From these arguments (Figures 8.2 and 8.5), it is possible that the ELRs in NGC 7469, NGC 3783, NGC 5548, and NGC 3227 are located at larger angles in the ionisation cone relative to our direct LOS view to the central X-ray source; the WA is located in the centre of the cone. This would mean that the direction of outflow for the ELR is not directly towards us and hence the measured outflow velocities are smaller compared to the WA kinematics. However, it is more likely that the difference between the observed emission and absorption properties is due to our LOS viewing angle. This observation bias would also mean that if we were to see through the cone at a larger angle from the central axis, then we would still observe absorption in our LOS. Hence, for side on views (e.g. NGC 1068) only emission is seen from the ionisation cone.

For both the WA and ELR, in all AGN, there are overlaps between parameters, whereby a wide range of distances across the ionisations states from $\log \xi = -1$ to 4, and outflow velocities $v_{out} > -750 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ are seen. The differences between the locations (Figure 8.6) are a result of the different method

assumptions, as well as the parameter values used. Although, overall, the distances cover a similar range, they are not constrained. The inconsistencies from Eq. 8.1 are due to the large uncertainties associated with f_v . Currently, for the NELR components in all the AGN, I have used the arbitrary value of $f_v = 0.1$. However, the actual f_v values for the NELR need to be measured, in a similar way to the values obtained for the WA components (Section 4.3.4.2 in Chapter 4). Some other caveats from this Chapter are that Eqs. 8.1 and 8.2 are upper and lower distance limits (for the WA), respectively (see Section 1.4.1.2). In addition, Eq. 8.3 requires changes in the SED, which in itself can only produce upper distance limits. Furthermore, the simple geometry of PION breaks down for type 2 AGN where the ionisation cone is seen from side on and different LOS make it difficult to compare all of the parameters, e.g. N_H and v_{out} . This means that the exact locations of the components are currently unknown.

In all the AGN discussed in this Chapter (Table 8.1), the NELR and WA components have similar plasma properties measured from photoionisation modelling (see Table 8.1, and Figures 8.5 and 8.6). The similarities in terms of the range in distances and ionisation parameter values between the WAs and ELRs suggest that the properties of the outflowing winds seen in a handful of AGN are similar. However, the main problem is obtaining the actual locations of the plasma regions, which are unconstrained over large distances (1 - 500 pc), as shown in Figure 8.6. This is most likely a result of the method assumptions, assumed model geometries, and large uncertainties associated with the volume filling factor f_v . The difference in N_H can be attributed to the amount of absorbing gas within our LOS, which is smaller compared to the amount that emits. However, to get a better comprehension of the cone geometry, the C_{cov} values for the ELR need to be compared. Here, it suggests that for type 1 AGN, the ELR covers a small fraction of the ionising source in our LOS, whereas for type 2 AGN, it covers a larger amount of the X-ray source. However, this is an observation bias based on our LOS through the ionisation cone, such that it

is how we observe these objects that leads to us seeing the ELR at the edge of the cone in Type 1. In addition, differences in the measured outflow velocities depend on the LOS viewing angle, such that the kinematics of type 1 AGN cannot currently be properly compared to the values seen in type 2 AGN.

From this work, I conclude that the ELR and WA components can be part of the same regions in the outflowing wind, but to achieve a better understanding, a larger study of both wind types is required, in addition to an examination of both type 1 and 2 AGN. Overall, the work done in this Thesis, and using AGN from other studies, suggests that the WA and ELRs in type 1 and type 2 AGN *could* be part of the same regions in the outflowing wind, seen through different LOS. This supports the unification theory of AGN.

8.2 Evidence for Kinematically Important Feedback Signatures

For the four AGN studied in this Thesis, I estimated the kinetic luminosity and energetics of the outflowing winds in NGC 7469, NGC 1068, NGC 5643; for NGC 3227 (Chapter 7) I studied the obscurer and not the outflowing wind. For NGC 7469 and NGC 1068 (Chapters 4 and 5, respectively) the wind energetics were insignificant compared to the energy budget of the AGN, and therefore the winds were unlikely to impact the host galaxy. This is because the winds in NGC 1068 and NGC 7469 are related to the WA and NLR, which have weaker kinematics compared to UFOs and therefore less impact on the host galaxy (consistent with the findings by [Blustin et al. 2005](#) for WAs and [Tombesi et al. 2013](#) for UFOs). For NGC 5643 (Chapter 6), on the other hand, I found that the kinetic luminosity was between 0.1 and 3.2 % of the bolometric luminosity, in agreement with the findings of the outflow induced star formation in the optical band ([Cresci et al., 2015](#)). This is consistent with the range of 0.5 - 5 % required to explain the $M - \sigma$ relation for feedback processes (e.g. [Hopkins & Elvis, 2010](#)).

From the UFO study by [Tombesi et al. \(2013\)](#), 34 % of Seyferts contain

UFOs, with a further 67 % of these also containing WAs. In their sample, the AGN are located at redshifts of $z < 0.1$, and hence the UFO percentage in these AGN is relatively low, compared to WAs that are found in half of nearby Seyferts (e.g. Reynolds & Fabian, 1995). However, in a sample of fourteen quasars, with redshifts of $z = 1.4 - 3.91$ ², Chartas et al. (2021) found all to contain UFO winds, with 92 % of the sources also containing UV narrow absorption lines (NAL³). This shows that a significantly larger fraction of UFO winds are present in higher redshifted quasars (for a relatively small sample size of 14). In addition, a significant fraction are also within quasars that contain other outflowing wind components, similar to low- z Seyfert AGN. This evidence can explain why no UFO signatures were found in the AGN studied in this Thesis - the fraction of nearby Seyferts that contain UFOs is relatively small (Tombesi et al., 2013). Therefore, I argue that there are no biases in the source selection nor in the detection methods implemented here.

Some, UFO winds have been found in the grating spectra of AGN. However, these observations are significantly rarer compared to the signatures in the hard X-ray band (e.g. Tombesi et al., 2013). From the literature, I found two AGN that contain a UFO wind, where the signatures have also been observed in their soft X-ray spectra: PDS 456 ($z = 0.184$; e.g. Reeves et al., 2003, 2016, 2020) and PG1211+143 ($z = 0.081$; e.g. Pounds et al., 2003; Pounds, 2014). In addition, UFO winds have also been observed in the outflows of ULXs within the RGS band, with velocities of around $0.2 c$ (Pinto et al., 2016).

In PG1211+143, the outflow velocity of the UFO wind was found to be just less than $0.1 c$, consistent between RGS and EPIC-PN/MOS analysis (Pounds et al., 2003; Pounds, 2014). PDS 456, on the other hand, is a little more complicated. In the 2001 RGS spectrum studied by Reeves et al. (2003), the outflowing wind signatures were absorption lines of Fe XVII - Fe XXIV in

²This is near the peak of AGN and star formation activity ($z = 3$), suggesting that there was a strong feedback between the host galaxy and AGN during this time.

³UV NALs are analogous to WAs in powerful quasars.

Figure 8.7: UFO winds seen in the RGS spectrum of the AGN, PDS 456, from the 2019 XMM-Newton observations. (Figure adapted from [Reeves et al. \(2020\)](#).) *Top:* Observed RGS spectrum of PDS 456 in the AGN rest frame (blue histogram) with the best fit absorption model overlaid (black line). *Bottom:* Transmission model for the same absorber but in the rest wavelength frame. The lines of interest in the top panel are the Ne X (9.3Å; purple arrow), Ne IX (10.3 Å; magenta arrow), and O VIII (14.5 Å; green arrow). These lines are heavily blueshifted when compared to the expected lab-frame wavelengths in the bottom panel; the three lines of interest are also identified by the coloured arrows. The outflow velocity for the wind in PDS 456, derived from the blueshifts between the top and bottom panels of all three lines, is 0.258 c, which is consistent with an UFO wind.

the 12 - 15 Å range indicating the presence of a wind with an outflow velocity of 0.16 c. In addition, during the five XMM-Newton observations in 2013/14, the H- and He-like Ne lines, as well as the Fe L lines, were found to be shifted by 0.1 - 0.2 c (Reeves et al., 2016). More recently, PDS 456 was observed in 2019, showing strong absorption features of O VIII Ly α , Ne IX, and Ne X Ly α , in the RGS spectrum, with broadening velocities of around 3000 km s⁻¹ and a common outflow velocity of 0.258 c. This was consistent with the Fe K absorption lines in the hard X-ray energy band observed at the same time in EPIC-PN data ($v_{FeK} = 0.261$ c; Reeves et al., 2020). Figure 8.7 shows the velocity shifts of the three absorption lines in the RGS spectrum during the 2019 observation of PDS 456. It is clear that these lines are strong and broad, suggesting that they are relatively easy to detect in grating spectra, and are easily deconvolved from the underlying continuum.

In summary, UFO winds are less frequent in nearby AGN compared to quasars at $z > 1$, which can explain why none of the AGN studied in this Thesis contain this type of wind. In addition, UFO signatures have been found in the soft X-ray grating spectra of some AGN, with strong and broad absorption lines. This means that we can examine UFO winds across the full X-ray energy range, assuming the target is bright enough.

8.3 Future Work

This Thesis has focused on the data from XMM-Newton which, along with Chandra, has revolutionised the X-ray analysis of AGN, with high resolution spectra, for the last 21 years. Now we are looking ahead to new X-ray missions that will further expand our understanding of these powerful objects. One such mission is Athena (see Chapter 3), set to launch in the early 2030s. Athena will have an outstanding effective area (e.g. Barret et al., 2016), due to the silicon pore optic technology (see Figure 3.8 in Chapter 3; Willingale et al., 2013); and will also have a resolving power similar to that of RGS extending to EPIC-PN energies (e.g. den Herder et al., 2012), provided by the X-ray

microcalorimeter, a non-dispersive spectrometer, X-IFU (X-ray Integral Field Unit; Barret et al., 2013, 2016). In terms of AGN analysis, Athena will help answer questions about UFO winds, characterised by the narrow absorption lines above 6 keV (Risaliti et al., 2005); the origins of the Fe K emission lines; and put constraints on abundances, ionisation states and column densities of the emission and absorption features in the outflowing wind - paramount in understanding their locations. In addition, Athena will answer questions on accretion physics; energy release through ionised gas and molecular outflows; how black holes grow and via what mechanism; and the feedback process between black holes and their host galaxy (Nandra et al., 2013; Barcons et al., 2015).

8.3.1 Bridging the gap between AGN winds

In this Chapter (Section 8.1.1), I compared the properties of the WA and ELR in NGC 7469 (type 1) with the ELR components in NGC 1068 (type 2). Similar results were also found when I compared three other AGN (Section 8.1.2), in addition to the locations (Section 8.1.3). The ionisation states (ξ) of each component were similar to each other, but the kinematics and column densities differed, likely due to the LOS viewing angle between the WA and ELR (Figure 8.2). In summary, I conclude that it is possible for the WA and ELR to be part of the same regions in the outflowing wind, but further investigations are required.

Following on from the WA analysis done by Blustin et al. (2005) and the ultra-fast outflow (UFO) studies by Tombesi et al. (2013), further investigations of the NELRs in type 2 AGN would be extremely useful. Analysing type 2 AGN will test different regions of the AGN outflow parameter space as well as the origin and structure of the winds seen through emitting plasma only and through a different LOS. By obtaining the properties of the NELR, such as the ionisation states, column densities and outflow velocities, a larger sample size can be compared to the outflow winds in type 1 AGN.

Currently in type 1 AGN, the outflow winds can be characterised as UFOs

(Section 1.3.2), WAs (Section 1.3.4) and obscurers (Section 1.3.5). However, to fully understand the origins and morphology of the outflowing wind, we need to bridge the gap between UFO and WA winds, and find where the obscurers are located with respect to them. There is evidence to suggest that both the WA and UFO are part of the same outflowing wind as they are found at opposite ends of the parameter space (see Figure 1.7 in Chapter 1; Tombesi et al., 2013). The UFO winds are likely to originate from the accretion disk, driven by magnetic forces (Lorenz force and magnetic pressure gradient; e.g. Proga, 2007; Fukumura et al., 2010a,b, 2015), while the WA is launched from the torus due to thermal driving (Krolik & Kriss 2001; see Section 1.6 for details).

From the studies in NGC 5548 (Kaastra et al., 2014), NGC 3783 (Mehdipour et al., 2017), and NGC 3227 (Mehdipour et al., 2021) the obscurers were located at distances consistent with the BLR, as possibly dense clouds that pass through the LOS of the ionising continuum. The outflow velocity of the obscurer in NGC 5548 was $v_{obs} = -5000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (Kaastra et al., 2014), which puts it in the middle of the velocity space of UFOs ($v_{UFO} < 0.5 c$; e.g. Risaliti et al., 2005; Tombesi et al., 2013) and WAs ($v_{WA} > 100 - 1000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$; e.g. Kaastra et al., 2000, 2002; Grafton-Waters et al., 2020). Although the obscurers in NGC 3783 and NGC 3227 had an ionisation parameter $\log \xi = 1.8$ (Mehdipour et al., 2017) and $\log \xi = 1 - 3$ (Wang et al., 2022), respectively, consistent with the WA wind, the obscurer in NGC 5548 was almost neutral. Furthermore, the column densities in all three AGN were $N_H = 10^{26} - 10^{27} \text{ m}^{-2}$ (Kaastra et al., 2014; Mehdipour et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2022), larger than the values measured in the WA ($N_H = 10^{24} = 10^{26} \text{ m}^{-2}$). Further observations of these relatively rare obscuration events are required to fully understand the different characters of outflowing AGN winds, and to place them with respect to WAs and UFOs.

However, answering these questions may require the next generation of X-ray missions. Athena X-IFU will not only be able to achieve a high spectral

resolution for nearby AGN across a wide X-ray energy range, but will also be able to study in detail more distant galaxies up to a redshift of $z = 4$ (Nandra et al., 2013). This will increase the redshift-luminosity parameter space for a large number of AGN, meaning we can probe the black hole and galaxy evolution in more powerful, distant objects. Not only will this allow us to understand further the processes that drive the most luminous quasars, but will also give insight into whether WAs and UFOs are present in highly luminous and distant AGN, or if there is another type of wind yet to be discovered. This will help unify the different types of absorbing winds discussed here.

8.3.2 AGN Feedback and Star Formation

The main aim for studying NGC 5643 (Chapter 6) is to measure the X-ray mass outflow rate of the ionised wind and to determine whether it can affect star formation; this was the first AGN to show possible outflow-induced star formation within a Seyfert galaxy, as seen in the optical band (Cresci et al., 2015). In addition, both NGC 7469 (Figure 4.1) and NGC 1068 (Figure 5.1) have a starburst ring (SBR). Although the collisionally ionised equilibrium (CIE) plasma observed in the RGS spectrum of NGC 7469 was likely to originate from its SBR (Behar et al., 2017; Mehdipour et al., 2018), I found no evidence of this in NGC 1068 (Chapter 5). Instead, the CIE emission in NGC 1068 was likely to come from the secondary region, if there were shocks generated in the gas at times when the nuclear jet was particularly strong (see Section 5.6.4). Although there is no evidence for the nuclear outflows interacting with the SBR in both these AGN, other regions closer to the SMBH may cause CIE emission if the outflow wind interacts with them. Alternatively, it is possible for jets to influence the galaxy if they are present.

An additional goal of the analysis on NGC 5643 could be to test whether the radio outflow (Morris et al., 1985) within this AGN can influence the outflowing wind and therefore contribute to the collisionally ionised emission, or if the outflow wind is purely photoionisation dominated. One question that has come about from studying NGC 5643 is this: Is the soft X-ray emission in

type 2 AGN, with radio outflows, fundamentally different compared to Seyfert 2 galaxies without these radio structures? The aim is to understand whether the outflowing wind is driven by this radio outflow⁴, and if the collisional emission is a result of the outflowing wind interacting with material further out from the central engine. One way to answer this question would be to study samples of both radio quiet (RQ) and radio loud (RL) type 2 AGN, over different redshifts, to see what effects radio emission has on the outflowing wind and host galaxy. By determining whether collisionally ionised, photoionised, or both emission types were associated with either RL or RQ galaxies would give insight into whether these radio outflows play a significant role in affecting the host galaxy, and by what mechanisms. In addition, studying a large sample of type 2 AGN will answer whether these outflowing winds initiate or quench star formation, and if radio emission has an impact on the emitting plasma that we observe.

Evidence for jet-induced CIE emission has been observed in NGC 4151. A faint and highly collimated jet was found within the central 100 pc of NGC 4151 where a shock feature was associated with an interaction between the jet and clouds (Mundell et al., 2003; Wang et al., 2011). The jet power was found to be $P_{jet} \sim 10^{35}$ W, approximately a few percent of the AGN energy output ($L_{bol} = 7 \times 10^{36}$ W; Wang et al., 2011). Emission line images over a 150 pc radius with Chandra ACIS showed an extended structure spatially correlated with a radio outflow and optical [O III] emission. X-ray emission exceeded the expectation for pure PIE plasma, and the spectral fitting showed strong evidence for a CIE component with $kT = 0.58$ keV, caused by the interaction between the jet and dense material; the thermal energy of the hot gas implies the estimated jet power is related to the host ISM through this interaction

⁴Radio outflows in AGN are usually high-powered jets seen in radio-loud quasars (e.g. Figure 1.1 and Section 1.1.2). However, in the Seyfert AGN studied in this Thesis, the radio outflows are likely to be old jet material, that is still emitting radio emission, but is not bright enough to characterise these AGN as radio loud; hence the radio outflows are different to the outflowing winds studied in this Thesis. This radio emitting, weak jet, can still interact with the surrounding material or photoionised material in these AGN, but how this happens is not fully understood - hence these questions and motivations.

(Wang et al., 2011). Although this result from NGC 4151 suggests that the radio jet's interaction with the ISM caused CIE emission at the shock, further studies are required to fully infer whether radio-emitting outflows do induce CIE emission.

8.3.3 NGC 4151

During the last year of my PhD, I lead a research-for-schools outreach project for some year 10 and 12 students. The outreach goals were to promote science and research, to influence students to follow a career in STEM⁵ subjects, and to show how exciting black hole physics is. Most importantly, this research project has been extremely successful in making black hole physics accessible to young student scientists without the need for complex spectral codes. This is evidence that studies of the ionised plasma properties within the AGN outflowing wind can be successfully carried out outside of an academic environment.

The project aim was to analyse real X-ray data of NGC 4151 (from XMM-Newton observations) using Python, by fitting the emission lines with a simple Gaussian model. From there, the velocity shift for each line could be measured, and in turn the distances of the plasma regions from the black hole were obtained (the results from this project were published in Grafton-Waters et al., 2021a). Finally, by grouping the distances and velocities together, the number of outflowing clouds within the wind were determined. The motivation was to test whether the plasma properties in the wind changed over a 15 year period by comparing the observations. Despite the simplicity of the modelling, it could be established that no change took place over the years NGC 4151 was observed with XMM-Newton, but there are at least 2 to 3 plasma regions. I do have future plans to study this AGN with photoionisation modelling, which I discuss here.

NGC 4151 ($z = 0.003262$) is a type 1.5 Seyfert galaxy with a SMBH mass of $M_{BH} = 3.59 \times 10^7 M_{\odot}$ (Bentz & Katz, 2015). It has one of the brightest AGN, with $L_{bol} = 7.4 \times 10^{36} - 1.4 \times 10^{37}$ W and $\frac{L_{bol}}{L_{Edd}} = 0.016 - 0.031$ (e.g.

⁵STEM stands for Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics

Crenshaw et al., 2015; Miller et al., 2018), and has therefore been studied extensively across many energy bands.

The continuum emission from NGC 4151 is highly variable in the hard X-ray band (e.g. Beuchert et al., 2017), while the soft X-ray spectrum is rich in narrow emission lines and RRC features, with no underlying continuum emission (similar to NGC 1068; Chapter 5), consistent among observations (e.g. Schurch et al., 2004b). Figure 8.8 compares the RGS spectra from each epoch, where clearly there is very little difference in the emission line fluxes and the negligible continuum over time. Contrarily, Figure 8.9 shows that the hard X-rays are very variable within and over different epochs. This observed variability was likely to come from the variations in the corona/disk reflection on short timescales (Keck et al., 2015), whereas Beuchert et al. (2017) argued changes on long timescales were due to possible changes in the absorption components. However, degeneracies were found between the column densities of these components, which meant that they could not tell if either or both of the absorbers were intrinsically variable (Beuchert et al., 2017). On the other hand, Couto et al. (2016) found that the absorbers were stable, and instead the continuum changes were mostly intrinsic, rather than material crossing our LOS causing the observed changes. This extreme contrast between soft and hard X-ray bands makes NGC 4151 an ideal target to study the properties of the emission line region and to try and understand what drives the variability over different energy bands and timescales - an obscurer or changes in the intrinsic continuum - and whether these relate some way to the host galaxy.

My future goals are to **a)** create an optical-UV-X-ray SED of NGC 4151 over the different epochs to try and further answer the questions regarding the variability in this AGN, and **b)** study the emission features in NGC 4151 with the self-consistent PION model (Section 2.3.2 in Chapter 2). The broadband SED, from **a)**, will be used to model the ionising continuum, which would be fed into PION components to model the soft X-ray emission features, similar to my work on NGC 1068 (Chapter 5). In order to model the full optical-UV-X-

Figure 8.8: Comparing the RGS spectra of NGC 4151. *Top:* All RGS spectra combined together. The emission lines are labelled with their respective ions; black means present in all spectra; grey means weak or not present in some. *Bottom:* Separating the spectra for plotting purposes to see the details better; shifted by arbitrary values.

Figure 8.9: PN spectra of NGC 4151 from all XMM-Newton observations plotted together.

ray broadband SED, I will also use data from NuSTAR (three observation from 2012; [Harrison et al., 2013](#)) for the harder X-rays (above 10 keV), and Hubble Space Telescope / Space Telescope Imaging Spectrograph (HST/STIS⁶; with observations spanning from 1997 to 2014) data for the optical/UV band; in addition to XMM-Newton.

Assuming that the variability is caused by intrinsic changes in the ionising continuum, rather than absorption ([Couto et al., 2016](#)), the EPIC-PN data would be used for the SED modelling between 0.3 and 10 keV (Figure 8.9), as the continuum is non-zero and it has an effective area over 10 times larger than RGS. This SED model can then be applied to the RGS spectra in order to model the narrow emission lines with PION. Interestingly, however, from the 2002 Chandra/HETGS data of NGC 4151, [Kraemer et al. \(2005\)](#) were able to simultaneously fit the soft X-ray absorption and underlying power-law (found to have a photon index of $\Gamma = 1.5$ for the 2 - 10 keV band). The SED was made up of a broken power-law ($L_\nu \propto \nu^{-\alpha}$, where $\alpha = \Gamma + 1$ is the energy index),

⁶Sohn, S. T., et al., 2019, “STIS Data Handbook”, Version 7.0, (Baltimore: STScI); https://www.stsci.edu/files/live/sites/www/files/home/hst/instrumentation/stis/documentation/_documents/stis_dhb.pdf

with a few different α values depending on the energy range. This method could be used here initially to get a base for the SED model, before modelling the UV/optical data and the Compton hump, similar to previous AGN SED fits (e.g. [Mehdipour et al., 2015a, 2018](#)). Although I have used the SED of NGC 7469 for the studies of NGC 1068 (Chapter 5) and NGC 5643 (Chapter 6), trying to obtain an intrinsic SED for NGC 4151 will allow me to obtain the true ionisation properties of the outflowing wind, seen in the RGS spectra (Figure 8.8).

The emission lines have been studied in NGC 4151 (Figure 8.8; [Schurch et al., 2004b](#); [Beuchert et al., 2017](#)) either with Gaussian profiles or a simple photoionisation model. Using the PION model will lead to achieving a self-consistent understanding of the ionisation state within the emitting plasma regions. However, a problem with studying the NLR is that it has not changed in 15 years (Figure 8.8). This implies that the ELR is either very large or far from the SMBH, so there is a time lag between the continuum that we observe (Figure 8.9) and the continuum that ionised the plasma regions; hence no change in the NLR lines. However, despite the lack in photoionisation changes for the NLR, photoionisation modelling with PION gives strong motivation in understanding the properties self consistently, as I did for NGC 1068. This has not been done before for NGC 4151.

8.4 Overall Summary

A fundamental question in AGN studies is how do galaxies and SMBHs co-evolve with each other? However, in order to answer this, small scale studies of the AGN winds are required: Are the WA and ELR part of the same outflowing wind regions? Will these winds impact the host galaxy, and can they induce star formation? Where do these winds originate from, how are they launched, and where are they located? Do radio-emitting outflows drive CIE emission, and is it dominant over PIE emission? From these questions can the energetics, kinematics and ionisation states of the winds can be inferred, which can give

insight into the driving mechanism behind the feedback process.

From this Thesis and the conclusions made in Section 8.1, there is evidence to suggest that the ELR and WA in AGN could be part of the same regions in the outflowing wind. The parameters of these wind components have been found to be similar over a wide range of different values, such as ξ , whereas any differences (e.g. N_H and the kinematics) are likely to be a result of our LOS viewing angle and unknown geometry of the wind. Although the winds studied in this Thesis do not have enough energies to impact the host galaxy overall, they can still play a vital role in inducing star formation (e.g. NGC 5643; Chapter 6.)

Unfortunately, there are still many caveats in this research. One is that we are unable to constrain the distances of the plasma regions. Physically motivated distance methods such as the recombination timescale (Eq. 8.3) are dependent on changes in the SED and plasma properties, so in the majority of cases we need to apply Eqs. 8.1 and 8.2, which can have ad hoc assumptions. For the NELR components, $f_v = 0.1$ is assumed, which has a very large uncertainty associated with it. Therefore, a method of determining f_v directly for the NELR, like we can do for the WA, is vital. Alternatively, the differences in locations could be a result of the assumed geometry by PION. The WA is located directly within our LOS, so a simple slab geometry works well. However, when we see the plasma from side on, like for the ELR in type 2 AGN, the modelling becomes more complex, especially if the outflowing wind is emitting in an ionising cone (Kinkhabwala et al., 2002). Therefore, a simple slab model for the ELR is not adequate. In addition, a significant amount of the photoionisation modelling in this Thesis depended on the intrinsic SED, which for type 2 AGN is unknown. This means that obtaining the correct ionisation state and properties of the outflowing wind in type 2 AGN is challenging.

In conclusion, from this Thesis, I have found evidence that the WA and ELR could be part of the same regions in the outflowing wind of AGN. However, further studies of the ELR and WA in different AGN types are required

to determine this with greater certainty. In addition, further investigations are required in obtaining constraints on the parameters (e.g. kinematics, ξ , N_H), in order to measure the distances of the plasma regions without the need of observing changes in the ionising SED. This will require the next generation of X-ray missions, such as Athena, so that we can study these winds with high spectral resolution across the full X-ray band, in addition to high- z AGN, in order to understand the feedback mechanism between SMBHs and their host galaxy.

Appendix A

Constants and Acronyms

List of Constants

Parameter	Value/Unit	Description
c	$3 \times 10^8 \text{ m s}^{-1}$	Speed of light
ξ	$W m$	Ionisation parameter
N_H	m^{-2}	Column density
n_H	m^{-3}	Hydrogen number density
n_e	m^{-3}	Electron number density
v_{out}	$km s^{-1}$	Outflow velocity
v_{turb}	$km s^{-1}$	Turbulent velocity
L_{ion}	W	Ionising luminosity
L_{bol}	W	Bolometric luminosity
f_v	≤ 1	Volume filling factor
f_{cov}	1	Absorption covering fraction
C_{cov}	≤ 1	Emission covering fraction
\dot{M}_{out}	$M_{\odot} yr^{-1}$	Mass outflow rate
L_K	W	Kinetic luminosity
M_{BH}	$10^5 - 10^{10} M_{\odot}$	Black hole mass
M_{\odot}	$2 \times 10^{30} \text{ kg}$	Mass of sun
G	$6.67 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$	Gravitational constant
α	$-1 \leq \alpha \leq 1$	Specific angular momentum

Parameter	Value/Unit	Description
pc	$3.08 \times 10^{16} m$	Parsec
t_{rec}	s	Recombination timescale
σ_T	$6.65 \times 10^{-29} m^2$	Thompson cross-section
k	$1.38 \times 10^{-23} JK^{-1}$	Boltzmann constant
χ	keV	Threshold energy
T	K	Temperature
F_{rad}	$Wm^{-1}s$	Radiation force
F_g	$kgms^{-2}$	Gravitational force
\dot{P}_{scat}	$Wm^{-1}s$	Scattered momentum
\dot{P}_{abs}	$Wm^{-1}s$	Absorbed momentum
m_p	$1.67 \times 10^{-27} kg$	Mass of proton

Parameter	Description
R_{BH}	Black hole radius
R_S	Schwartzchild radius
R_g	Gravitational radius
R_{isco}	Innermost stable circular orbit
R_{sub}	Sublimation radius
Ξ	Pressure form of ionisation parameter
z	Redshift
m_s	Spin magnetic moment
L	Orbital angular momentum
S	Spin angular momentum
J	Total angular momentum
Γ	Photon index
τ	Optical depth
Ω	Solid angle

Acronyms

ACIS	Advanced CCD Imaging Spectrometer
AGN	Active Galactic Nuclei
ASCA	Advanced Satellite for Cosmology and Astrophysics
ATHENA	Advanced Telescope for High ENergy Astrophysics
BBB	Big Blue Bump
BLR	Broad Line Region
CCD	Charged Coupled Device
CIE	Collisionally Ionised Equilibrium
CT	Compton-thick
d.o.f	Degrees of Freedom
EA	Effective Area
EM	Emission Measure
EPIC	European Photon Imaging Camera
ESA	European Space Agency
EUV	Extreme Ultraviolet
FOV	Field of View
FSRQ	Flat Spectrum Radio Quasars
FR	Fanaroff and Riley
HEG	High Energy Gratings
HETGS	High Energy Transmission Grating Spectrometer
HRC	High Resolution Camera
HST	Hubble Space Telescope
ISM	Interstellar Medium
LINER	Low Ionising Nuclear Emission Regions
LOS	Line of Sight
LETGS	Low Energy Transmission Grating Spectrometer
MEG	Medium Energy Gratings
MOS	Metal-oxide semiconductor
NGC	New General Catalogue
NLR	Narrow Line Region

NLS1	Narrow Line Seyfert Type 1
NuSTAR	Nuclear Spectroscopic Telescope Array
OM	Optical Monitor
PIE	Photoionised Equilibrium
QE	Quantum Efficiency
RGS	Reflection Grating Spectrometer
RL	Radio Loud
ROSAT	ROentgen SATellite
RQ	Radio Quiet
RRC	Radiative Recombination Continuum
SAS	Science Analysis Software
SBR	Starburst region
SED	Spectral Energy Distribution
SMBH	Supermassive Black Hole
SPO	Silicon Pore Optics
SQUID	Superconducting Quantum Interference Device
STIS	Space Telescope Imaging Spectrograph
TES	Transition Edge Sensors
UFO	Ultra-fast Outflow
WA	Warm Absorber
WFI	Wide Field Imager
X-IFU	X-ray Integral Field Unit
XMM	X-ray Multi Mirror
XMS	X-ray Microcalorimeter Spectrometer
XRISM	X-ray Imaging and Spectroscopy Mission

Common AGN Values

Parameter	Value	Unit
M_{BH}	$10^5 - 10^{10}$	M_{\odot}
T_{disk}	$10^5 - 10^6$	K
R_{in}	$2 - 18$	R_S
R_{out}	1000	R_S
T_{corona}	10^8	K
R_{corona}	< 1	ld
T_{dust}	$1500 - 2000$	K
R_{torus}	$0.1 - 30$	pc
T_{WA}	$10^4 - 10^6$	K
R_{WA}	$1 - 100$	pc
R_{BLR}	$0.01 - 1$	pc
n_{BLR}	$\geq 10^{15}$	m^3
v_{BLR}	$1000 - 10,000$	kms^{-1}
T_{BLR}	10^4	K
R_{NLR}	$1 - few\ 1000$	pc
n_{NLR}	$10^9 - 10^{12}$	m^{-3}
v_{NLR}	$100 - 1000$	kms^{-1}
T_{NLR}	10^4	K
$L_{Seyfert}$	$10^{34} - 10^{38}$	W
L_{Quasar}	$10^{38} - 10^{41}$	W

Appendix B

Derivations

B.1 Mass Outflow Rate

The mass outflow rate (\dot{M}_{out}) is the measure of how much material is launched in the outflowing wind per year. It is used to assess the energetics of the wind. Here I derive it using an adapted method from [Blustin et al. \(2005\)](#).

If we assume that the outflow is spherical, and we take a thin slab of material with thickness dr , the mass within it will be

$$dM = \rho\Omega r^2 dr, \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where ρ is the density of material, r is the distance from the black hole and Ω is the solid angle. The amount of matter travelling through the shell in time dt , with a velocity $v = dr/dt$, is therefore

$$\dot{M}_{out} = \frac{dM}{dt} = \rho\Omega r^2 v. \quad (\text{B.2})$$

The density of the plasma ρ is approximately equal to $\mu m_p \bar{n}$, where $\mu = 1.23$ ¹, m_p is the proton mass, and \bar{n} is the average number density in the shell seg-

¹ μ is a correction for a 75% and 25% by mass of H and He, respectively, measured as the ratio between the total mass and the total number of ions. Therefore for 100 ions, $\mu = \frac{75/100 + 25/100}{75/100 + 25/(100 \times 4)} = 1.23$.

ment. Substituting $\rho = \mu m_p \bar{n}$ into Eq. B.2 means \dot{M}_{out} becomes

$$\dot{M}_{out} = 1.23 m_p \bar{n} \Omega r^2 v. \quad (\text{B.3})$$

The average number density (\bar{n}) is related to the measurable quantity (n), the density of the gas where absorption is taking place, through $\bar{n} = n f_v$, where f_v is the volume fitting factor of the plasma. Therefore substituting in \bar{n} we get

$$\dot{M}_{out} = 1.23 m_p n f_v \Omega r^2 v, \quad (\text{B.4})$$

which can be further updated using the ionisation parameter equation, $\xi = L_{ion}/nr^2$, such that the final mass outflow rate equation becomes

$$\dot{M}_{out} = \frac{1.23 m_p L_{ion} f_v \Omega r^2 v}{\xi r^2} = \frac{1.23 m_p L_{ion} f_v \Omega v}{\xi}. \quad (\text{B.5})$$

B.2 The Cash Statistic

The Cash statistic (or C-statistic, hereafter; [Cash, 1979](#)) stems from the Poisson distribution, much like the χ^2 test comes from the Gaussian distribution. The Poisson distribution is given by

$$P = \prod_{i=1}^N \frac{\mu_i^{n_i} e^{-\mu_i}}{n_i!}, \quad (\text{B.6})$$

where P is the probability, n_i is the number of counts in each bin, N , and μ is the mean/expected number of counts in a given time. In Poisson statistics, one measurement is taken given mean, whereas in the Cash statistic, many measurements are made given mean or model. We use the product notation (Π) because each photon event is multiplied together to obtain the total distribution, taking into account the full set of observed measurements. From here, we can take the log-likelihood function, which is the probability of the parameters, given the data ([Vaughan, 2013](#)). Here, the log-likelihood function is written as $C = -2 \ln P$. The derivation for the C-statistic, from [Cash \(1979\)](#),

is as follows:

$$C = -2 \ln \left(\prod_{i=1}^N \frac{\mu_i^{n_i} e^{-\mu_i}}{n_i!} \right) = -2 \sum_{i=1}^N [n_i \ln \mu_i - \mu_i - \ln n_i!] \quad (\text{B.7})$$

Cash (1979) removed the factorial term as this is independent of any parameters, however, in SPEX the factorial term is used. Using Sterling's approximation, $\ln x! = x \ln x - x$, the C-stat can be rewritten as

$$C = -2 \sum_{i=1}^N [n_i \ln \mu_i - \mu_i - n_i \ln n_i + n_i] = -2 \sum_{i=1}^N [n_i - \mu_i + n_i \ln \frac{\mu_i}{n_i}]. \quad (\text{B.8})$$

Taking the minus sign inside the brackets, the final C-statistic used in SPEX (Kaastra, 2017) becomes

$$C = 2 \sum_{i=1}^N [\mu_i - n_i - n_i \ln \frac{\mu_i}{n_i}] = 2 \sum_{i=1}^N [\mu_i - n_i + n_i \ln \frac{n_i}{\mu_i}]. \quad (\text{B.9})$$

This shows that the C-statistic can be minimised when the difference between the model and data (expected and observed) decreases. As the number of counts increases, the C-statistic tends towards the χ^2 statistic. Therefore the C-statistic can be used on any data set, whilst χ^2 should only be used when there are a large number of counts per bin.

SPEX also gives the expected C-statistic value, which gives a good indication of the goodness of fit with respect to the model and data fitting (Kaastra, 2017). The expected C-statistic is given by the Poisson distribution with expected number of counts λ and observed counts per bin n . This is then multiplied by the probability, as a weight, such that the expected C-statistic is

$$C_e = 2 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P_n(\lambda) (\lambda - n + n \ln \frac{n}{\lambda}), \quad (\text{B.10})$$

where $P_n(\lambda)$ is the Poisson distribution (Eq. B.6; Kaastra, 2017).

Appendix C

NGC 7469 - The velocity structure of the Galaxy

I modelled the absorbing material of the Galaxy using HOT in SPEX (see model explanation in Section 2.3.3, and application in Section 4.3.1.2), with the sum of HI and HII column densities initially set to $5.5 \times 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-2}$ (Wakker, 2006; Wakker et al., 2011), and a temperature of 0.5 eV to mimic neutral gas. However, the velocity structure of the gas in the Galaxy was unknown, meaning I did not have any information about the turbulent velocity for the HOT component.

To determine the turbulence of the neutral (and mildly ionised) Galaxy absorbing gas in the line of sight towards NGC 7469, I used the 21 cm HI profiles from the EBHIS (Winkel et al., 2016) and LAB (Kalberla et al., 2005b) surveys¹. Figure C.1 shows the data from the LAB survey (black dots), displaying the 21 cm HI profile in terms of brightness temperature (T_B) as a function of velocity at the local standard of rest (V_{LSR}).

In order to obtain the information regarding the velocity, I fitted a Gaussian to the survey data, red line in Figure C.1, given by

$$T_B = A \exp\left(-\frac{(v - \mu)^2}{2\sigma_v^2}\right), \quad (\text{C.1})$$

¹The interface to measure the HI profiles can be found at https://www.astro.uni-bonn.de/hisurvey/AllSky_profiles/index.php

Figure C.1: Galactic 21 cm HI profile in our line of sight towards NGC 7469, of brightness temperature as a function of velocity, from the LAB survey (black dots). The red line is the Gaussian function (Equation C.1) used to determine the velocity dispersion σ_v and the velocity mean μ . Estimates of these two parameters were obtained by averaging the values from the LAB (Kalberla et al., 2005b) and EBHIS (Winkel et al., 2016) surveys. The average velocity dispersion is used as the turbulent velocity for the Galaxy in the HOT components.

where v is the velocity (V_{LSR} data from the two surveys). The standard deviation (σ_v), mean (μ), and normalisation (A) are the three unknown parameters. I did this for both LAB and EBHIS surveys and averaged the three unknown parameters $\bar{\sigma}$, $\bar{\mu}$ and \bar{A} . The average mean and normalisation values were $\bar{\mu} = -2.1 \pm 0.9 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and $\bar{A} = 16.9 \pm 2.3 \text{ K}$ respectively. The average velocity dispersion is found to be $\bar{\sigma} = 5.64 \pm 1.10 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. The HI column density (N_H) is found using the LAB survey (Wakker et al., 2011), which means the $\bar{\sigma}$ value is needed from the HI profile of $N_H(v)$ to get the turbulent velocity in the Galaxy. However, the HI profile for $N_H(v)$ is, in fact, the same as the profile for $T_B(v)$, as the following argument proves (Chengalur et al., 2013):

$$T_B(v) = T_S(v)[1 - e^{-\tau(v)}]; \quad (\text{C.2})$$

$$N_H(v) = K \int T_s(v) \tau(v) dv. \quad (\text{C.3})$$

In these two equations, $T_B(v)$ is the brightness temperature (Figure C.1), $T_S(v)$ is the hydrogen spin temperature, $\tau(v)$ is the optical depth, and $K = 1.8 \times 10^{18}$ is a constant. Here, it is clear $N_H(v) \propto \tau(v)$, meaning the optical depth, measured via absorption measurements, is used to determine the column density (Lee et al., 2015). Substituting Equation C.2 into Equation C.3 to remove T_S gives

$$N_H(v) = K \int \frac{T_B(v) \tau(v)}{1 - e^{-\tau(v)}} dv. \quad (\text{C.4})$$

To estimate $N_H(v)$, I assumed that the gas in the Galaxy is optically thin ($\tau(v) \ll 1$; Lee et al., 2015), which gives the final equation

$$N_H(v) = K \int T_B(v) dv, \quad (\text{C.5})$$

meaning that the column density can be measured by integrating the emission spectrum of the 21 cm line ($T_B(v)$) over the velocity interval dv (V_{LSR}). Equation C.5 implies $N_H(v) \propto T_B(v)$, so the HI profile in Figure C.1 is the same as the HI profile for $N_H(v)$, except with the factor of K being the difference (Chengalur et al., 2013; Lee et al., 2015). Therefore, the $\bar{\sigma}$ found from Figure C.1 can be taken as the velocity dispersion of the HI profile of $N_H(v)$, which I use in the H0T model as the turbulent velocity of the Galaxy.

Appendix D

XMM-Newton AO20 Proposal on NGC 5643

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D.1 Abstract

The Compton-thick AGN, NGC 5643, is the first candidate for outflow-induced star formation in a radio-quiet Seyfert galaxy. Evidence of resolved emission lines in archival RGS data can be modelled with photoionised (PIE) and collisionally ionised (CIE) equilibrium plasma, produced in an outflowing wind and star forming regions, respectively. However, these RGS spectra have never been studied in great detail; instead, the soft X-ray band has been extensively examined with PN data. Our RGS simulations show that an exposure of 240 ks is required to sufficiently separate and resolve the contributions to the emission lines. This will allow us to characterise the components and accurately measure the column density, ionisation state and outflow velocity of the emitting PIE plasma. These parameters are essential for measuring the X-ray mass outflow rate, which can significantly influence the host galaxy and AGN coevolution. This is the first time RGS will study potential outflow-induced star formation within an AGN. Furthermore, studying the CIE plasma emission will give us insight into whether there is a nuclear starburst region. Our

proposal will also allow us to study the ultraluminous X-ray (ULX) source in NGC 5643. Many ULXs are known to pulsate, with some of these pulsations being transient, hence we need more exposure time of this luminous ($L \geq 10^{40}$ erg s⁻¹) source to capture this.

D.2 Description of the proposed programme

D.2.1 Scientific Rationale

X-ray spectra of some type 2 Seyfert active galactic nuclei (AGN) show strong absorption below 10 keV, with spectral properties of a flat hard spectrum ($\Gamma < 1$) and the Fe K α line having an equivalent width greater than 1 keV (Guainazzi et al., 2004). The cause of this strong absorption is optically thick material ($N_H > 10^{24}$ cm⁻²) surrounding the central nucleus, in our line of sight - these types of AGN are classed as ‘Compton-thick’. The amount of obscuration also depends on the covering fraction and line of sight viewing angle (Ramos Almeida & Ricci, 2017; Hönig, 2019).

Despite this X-ray obscuration, narrow emission lines can still be observed in the soft X-ray band. For example, in NGC 1068, the prototype Compton-thick AGN, soft X-ray emission lines, produced by photoionised plasma (Kinkhabwala et al., 2002), are scattered or reflected into our line of sight, without being absorbed by the Compton-thick material.

Given the coincidence of the radio emission and the ionisation cones within some AGN, it is also possible that the soft X-ray emission is collisionally ionised by the outflowing material, just as the star formation is supposedly driven by it. So, by discriminating whether the material is CIE or PIE dominated will inform whether the soft X-ray emission in Seyfert 2 nuclei with radio outflows is fundamentally different (or not) from that in Seyfert 2 AGN without such radio structures.

NGC 5643 is a low luminosity ($L_{0.5-10 \text{ keV}} \sim 2 \times 10^{42}$ erg s⁻¹; Matt et al., 2013; Annuar et al., 2015) type 2 Seyfert AGN within an intermediate spiral galaxy at a redshift of $z = 0.004$. It is classed as an infrared luminous galaxy

Figure D.1: $H\alpha$ maps (centred on the nucleus of NGC 5643) of the outflowing gas with the contours from a) [OIII] flux, b) 8.4 GHz radio emission, and c) Chandra X-ray emission (0.3 - 0.5 keV in green and 0.5 - 8 keV in blue) plotted on top. The hard X-ray emission is located within the nucleus, but the soft X-ray energies are extended, consistent with the outflowing material, which is moving towards star formation clumps on the left side of each panel. Figure taken from (Cresci et al., 2015).

($L_{IR} = 6.89 \times 10^{43}$ erg s^{-1} ; Genzel et al., 1998), where star formation occurs in the galaxy's spiral arms, but the AGN dominates the full IR energy budget, suggesting NGC 5643 is a Seyfert 2 and starburst hybrid (Matt et al., 2013, see references within).

In a study of NGC 5643 by Matt et al. (2013), the soft X-ray spectrum was modelled using EPIC-PN data. The authors analysed the 55 ks XMM-Newton observation, taken in 2009, finding that PIE was the dominating emitting process, but they could not rule out the contribution from CIE material. The emission lines included in the fit could not be studied in detail with RGS because of the short observing time. For this reason, a long exposure, high

resolution X-ray spectrum of NGC 5643 is crucial in studying and resolving the emission line plasma; this will be the first time that the soft X-ray spectrum of NGC 5643 is characterised with RGS data in detail.

Within NGC 5643, the distribution of [SIII] and [OIII] flux emission (Cresci et al., 2015; Riffel et al., 2018) gives evidence for an ionised outflowing wind, travelling in the direction of two star forming clumps near the edge of the galaxy bar (see Figure D.1; Cresci et al., 2015). This ionised outflowing wind has a velocity of $v_{[OIII]} = -450 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (Cresci et al., 2015) and mass outflow rate of $\dot{M}_{out} \sim 0.3 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Riffel et al., 2018). Optical band [OIII] emission traces the low density gas, meaning it underestimates the real nuclear mass outflow rate. X-ray emission, on the other hand, traces gas over a larger ionisation and density range and is more sensitive than the optical [OIII] lines. This [OIII] gas distribution correlates with the soft X-ray emission, seen with Chandra (Figure D.1), which is common in many type 2 AGN (Bianchi et al., 2006).

Cresci et al. (2015) proposed that the star formation in the clumps is due to positive feedback from gas compression between the outflowing material and the high density clumps, with one clump having a star formation rate of $SFR \sim 0.03 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. NGC 5643 is the first AGN to show potential outflow-induced star formation within a Seyfert galaxy, whereby optical data suggest that feedback can be present even in low luminosity type 2 AGN (Cresci et al., 2015). This gives us motivation to obtain the X-ray mass outflow rate, by modelling a long exposure RGS spectrum to accurately measure the outflow velocity and ionisation of the outflowing emitting plasma. Furthermore, evidence for a nuclear starburst region in NGC 5643 is currently controversial (Guainazzi et al., 2004), therefore our new RGS spectrum will help resolve this issue by studying the CIE emission lines.

Possible evidence of variability in NGC 5643, seen in ASCA and BeppoSAX observations (compared to the 2003 XMM-Newton observation; Guainazzi et al., 2004), was dismissed because of the presence in the tele-

scopes large point spread function of the bright and variable ULX source (NGC 5643 X-1), located 0.8' from the AGN. The ULX has peak luminosity of $L \geq 10^{40}$ erg s⁻¹, although it has varied by a factor of 3 - 4 between observations (Pintore et al., 2016). NuSTAR data were able to resolve NGC 5643 X-1 from the AGN nucleus at hard X-ray energies, which meant the column density ($N_H > 5 \times 10^{24}$ cm⁻²) of the absorbing material in the AGN was directly measured (Annuar et al., 2015).

D.2.2 Immediate Objective:

The goal of this proposal is to determine the balance between PIE and CIE in a rare example of a Compton-thick AGN, NGC 5643, that is bright and close enough to be studied with RGS. For the first time, we will study outflow-induced star formation, whereby our extensive simulations show that a 240 ks exposure is required to resolve the Fe XVII L lines which are essential to disentangle CIE from PIE. From here, the energetics and X-ray mass outflow rate of the photoionised wind can be measured, giving insight into the black hole and host galaxy coevolution. The CIE modelling will determine whether there is emission from a nuclear starburst region, as a result of the outflowing wind.

NGC 5643 is a starburst/Seyfert 2 galaxy for which there are very little high resolution X-ray data available, none of which have been analysed in detail before. The RGS spectrum shows emission features as other well studied type 2 AGN (see Figure D.2), yet, because of the short exposure time, the soft X-ray band has only been investigated with the EPIC-PN data, therefore the properties of the emitting plasma have not been fully established. Further to this, RGS spectra can spectrally resolve the contribution from CIE plasma (for example, the Fe XVII (L) lines found at around 15 and 17 Å; see Figure D.2) from PIE plasma emission lines, which will allow us to study the different plasma components in greater detail than before.

We have analysed the RGS spectrum from 2009 and fitted it with a power-law for the continuum and PIE and CIE components to model the emission

Figure D.2: RGS spectra (grey crosses) with best fit model (red line), in addition to the model components, PIE in green and CIE in blue, to show which emission lines they account for. *Top:* Observed spectrum; *Bottom:* 240 ks simulated RGS spectrum.

lines. The top panel in Figure D.2 shows the observed RGS spectrum (grey crosses) between 13 and 26 Å, with the main emission features labelled, as well as the best fit model shown in red. The PIE (green line) and CIE (blue line) model components are also plotted to show clearly which features they fit. The bottom panel of Figure D.2 shows the 240 ks simulated spectrum with

Table D.1: Best fit parameter values to the 2009 RGS spectrum: observed data (Obs.); simulated data (Sim 240 ks). N_{pow} : power-law normalisation (10^{48} ph s $^{-1}$ keV $^{-1}$); Γ : photon index; N_H : PIE plasma column density (10^{21} cm $^{-2}$); $\log \xi$: ionisation parameter (erg cm s $^{-1}$); Ω : covering fraction (10^{-3}); N_{cie} : normalisation of CIE plasma component (10^{62} cm $^{-3}$); and T_e : electron temperature (keV).

Parameter	Obs.	Sim 240 ks
N_{pow}	$5.16^{+0.48}_{-0.50}$	$4.97^{+0.25}_{-0.26}$
Γ	2.68 ± 0.22	2.84 ± 0.11
N_H	$2.49^{+2.40}_{-1.11}$	$1.64^{+0.61}_{-0.41}$
$\log \xi$	$1.31^{+0.10}_{-0.12}$	1.35 ± 0.05
Ω	$1.98^{+1.62}_{-1.06}$	$3.17^{+1.07}_{-0.91}$
N_{cie}	$1.78^{+1.18}_{-1.12}$	$1.22^{+0.62}_{-0.58}$
T_e	$0.21^{+0.11}_{-0.03}$	$0.24^{+0.09}_{-0.03}$
C-stat (d.o.f)	583 (375)	361 (375)

the best fit model (red line) and the two emission components plotted on top (green for PIE and blue for CIE emission). Our extensive simulations show that an exposure of 240 ks is required to sufficiently separate and resolve the contributions to the emission lines.

The best fit parameter values for our RGS analysis of the archival 55 ks observation are shown in Table D.1, along with the simulation modelling results: the fitted PIE parameters are the column density (N_H), the ionisation parameter (ξ) and the covering fraction (Ω); the CIE parameters are the normalisation N_{cie} and electron temperature (T_e). In Table D.1, the simulated results have smaller errors compared to the observed data by up to 60% and 15% for the PIE and CIE components, respectively. The ionisation parameter of the PIE model that best fits the observed data is $\log \xi = 1.31$ (Table D.1) which is consistent with $\log U_1 = 0.30$ from Model B, Table 2 in Matt et al. (2013). The column density found here is 10 times larger than the value for the same component in Matt et al. (2013), possibly a result of these authors finding three components, whereas we only find one.

From the results of the spectral modelling, we will be able to determine

the mass outflow rate of the X-ray wind, given by

$$\dot{M}_{out} \sim \frac{1.23m_p L_{ion} f v \omega}{\xi}, \quad (\text{D.1})$$

where m_p is the proton mass, L_{ion} is the ionising radiation between 13.6 eV and 13.6 keV, f is the volume filling fraction, v is the outflow velocity, ω is the solid angle, and ξ is the ionisation parameter (Blustin et al., 2005). For the sake of an example, we assume an outflow velocity of $v_{out} = -450 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (from the optical analysis; Riffel et al., 2018), a volume filling factor of $f = 0.1$ (Grafton-Waters et al., 2020), a solid angle of $\omega = 1.6 \text{ sr}$ (assuming 25% of the AGN population are Compton-thick, with an average 50% covering fraction (see references within; Blustin et al., 2005; Annuar et al., 2015), and an ionising luminosity derived from the SED model $L_{ion,SED} = 1.72 \times 10^{44} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$. As NGC 5643 is a Compton-thick AGN, we do not know the intrinsic SED. Instead, we assume the SED model of NGC 7469, a typical Seyfert nucleus (Mehdipour et al., 2018). Mehdipour et al. (2016b) compared photoionisation results based on different SEDs and found no significant changes between SEDs of the same type, therefore NGC 7469 is a reasonable SED to use. The X-ray mass outflow rate results to be $1.97 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, which is an order of magnitude larger than the value found from ($\dot{M}_{out} \sim 0.3 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$; Riffel et al., 2018). Given that [OIII] emission traces the low density gas, it underestimates the real nuclear mass outflow rate, so the X-ray mass outflow rate estimated here is consistent with tracing the gas over a larger ionisation and density range.

From establishing the X-ray mass outflow rate, we can estimate how much energy is being carried by the X-ray wind, and therefore see if it significantly influences the starburst clumps and host galaxy through feedback processes. This will also give us insight into the origin, location and launching mechanism of the wind, similar to warm absorbers seen in type 1 AGN (e.g. Blustin et al., 2005).

Our proposed observations will also allow us to investigate the ULX in NGC5643, by combining and/or comparing the spectra taken in previous NGC

Table D.2: Best fit parameter values for the PN spectrum. N_{pow} : power-law normalisation (10^{48} ph s $^{-1}$ keV $^{-1}$); Γ : photon index; N_{refl} : reflection normalisation (10^{50} ph s $^{-1}$ keV $^{-1}$); N: normalisation of Gaussian (10^{46} ph s $^{-1}$ keV $^{-1}$); and E: energy of Gaussian (keV)

Parameter	Obs.	Sim 240 ks
N_{pow}	2.89 ± 0.07	2.89 ± 0.03
Γ	3.03 ± 0.05	3.05 ± 0.02
N_{refl}	< 1.57	< 1.40
s	< 1.23	< 1.44
N	$6.66^{+1.73}_{-1.62}$	5.76 ± 0.72
E	7.41 ± 0.04	7.38 ± 0.02
N	$3.95^{+1.40}_{-1.30}$	3.53 ± 0.60
E	1.85 ± 0.03	1.87 ± 0.01
C-stat (d.o.f)	176 (119)	125 (119)

5643 and X-1 observations. From here, we will carry out in depth spectral and temporal analysis of this ULX source, as it is known that many ULX sources are pulsars, while others only pulsate if they are undergoing transient behaviour (Bachetti et al., 2014). Therefore more observations are required to establish this for NGC5643 X-1.

For a 240 ks observation with EPIC-PN, and assuming the same count rate (0.2 count s $^{-1}$) as the 2014 ULX observation (Pintore et al., 2016), the total number of counts will be > 47000 counts, for a luminosity $> 10^{40}$ erg s $^{-1}$. This will improve the signal-to-noise ratio by 1.5 over the total number of counts for EPIC-PN. The total counts from a 240 ks observation are enough to measure a 1 s pulse period with a fraction of $\sim 10\%$ (Fürst et al., 2016). Observing NGC 5643 X-1 again will give us a chance of potentially discovering a new ULX pulsar if the pulsations are transient between observing epochs. Figure D.3 shows the ULX spectra observed by NuSTAR between 2014 and 2020, where we see a flux increase below 10 keV, indicating significant flux variability.

Figure D.3: NuSTAR observations of the ULX taken in 2014 and 2020.

D.3 Justification of requested observing time, feasibility and visibility

We request 240 ks total observation time, equivalent to two XMM-Newton orbits, which can be back to back, or separate by a few days. In the latter case we will look for possible variability on shorter timescales than those between the epochs of previous observations.

The RGS count rate for NGC 5643, observed in 2009, is $0.0094 \text{ counts s}^{-1}$, and therefore the total number of counts in the spectrum is 1025 photons. From an observation length of 240 ks, the total number of counts would therefore be 4512 photons, which would yield an improvement in the signal-to-noise ratio of 2.1, over the total spectrum.

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